

Deliverable 2.1
Legal and Ethics Aspects

WP2 Design AI-enabled Deliberation
Method
T2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects

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Public

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<p>Abstract: The deliverable reports on legal and ethical issues related to the implementation of the AI4Deliberation project and focuses on compliance with conducting research with research participants, processing of (special categories) personal data, the use of various artificial intelligence tools and features used in deliberation platforms to empower deliberation platforms' users and democratic processes.</p>	
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Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.1, *Ethics and Legal Issues of the AI4Deliberation Project*, presents a comprehensive overview of the project's current status through a qualitative evaluation of activities involving research participants, personal data processing, participation of non-EU partners, and the development of artificial intelligence (AI) tools supporting deliberative processes at regional, national, and international levels. It includes a detailed and updated *Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)* and an *Ethics Impact Assessment of the AI tools* selected for deployment. The analysis of the eight groups of AI tools likely to be used in the project are: (1) Large Language Models, (2) Video Large Language Models, (3) Deliberation and Argument Mining Tools, (4) Moderation and Safety Tools, (5) Translation and Accessibility Tools, (6) Gamification and Engagement Tools, (7) Summarisation Tools and (8) Clustering Tools. The AI tools are analysed with a view to assessing their compliance with the HLEG principles – the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence established by the European Commission and its 2019 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. Ethical and legal attention of this D2.1 is devoted to surveys, observational research, and four pilot studies – three national (conducted in Germany, Italy, and Greece) and one international (led by the United Kingdom beneficiary).

At this stage of implementation (M01-M18), the principal focus has been on preparing pilot studies to test and further develop new AI functionalities for deliberative processes, with recruited research participants, during Sprint 2. The testing will involve adult participants; however, older minors (aged 16–18) may not be entirely excluded, as age-verification procedures have not yet been finalised across all pilot sites. Given the nature of the deliberative activities—such as public commentary on legislative proposals in Greece and feedback on climate adaptation policy in Italy—the overall level of risk to participants is assessed as low. Nevertheless, moderate risks may arise in the international pilot, where participants may share sensitive health data relating to Long Covid, on the basis of informed consent as the lawful basis for processing. Further ethical considerations concern the possibility of inadvertent deception of research participants, who may not always be fully aware of the experimental context in which they are participating. Pilot teams have therefore been encouraged to address these risks proactively in order to ensure genuinely informed consent and transparent participation. These issues are expected to become particularly relevant during Sprint 2, which is scheduled to be conducted by the pilot teams in the coming months and therefore falls beyond the reporting period (M01-M18) covered by the present version 2 of Deliverable D2.1.

The deliverable also reports on consultations with key stakeholders — including pilot staff, best practice case owners, and platform operators — gathered through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Informed consent forms and ethics approvals from host institutions are annexed to the report.

The processing of personal data is analysed in depth, particularly when special categories of personal data may be involved. For instance, health-related data will be processed in the international pilot on Long Covid, and data concerning political opinions or beliefs may arise in the national pilots addressing environmental and legislative topics. A DPIA has therefore been prepared under Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and has undergone extensive internal and external reviews and updates. Potential international data transfers, particularly to the UK and via EEA-based infrastructure of US service providers such

as Microsoft Azure and DigitalOcean, are examined to ensure compliance with EU data protection standards.

An extensive *AI Ethics Impact Assessment* explores both the opportunities and risks associated with deploying AI in democratic deliberation. The report underscores the broader implications of AI for liberal democratic systems and public reasoning. It identifies a range of ethical risks, including algorithmic bias, manipulation by synthetic agents, privacy concerns, loss of human agency, and governance issues.

Each of the eight AI tool groups is evaluated according to the *EU High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (HLEG)* criteria for Trustworthy AI: (1) Human Agency and Oversight, (2) Technical Robustness and Safety, (3) Privacy and Data Governance, (4) Transparency, (5) Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness, (6) Societal and Environmental Well-being, and (7) Accountability.

Among the *Large Language Models*, OpenAI's ChatGPT, Meta's LLaMA, Google's Gemini, Anthropic's Claude, and Mistral's models are assessed with recommendations to ensure compliance with these criteria. Likewise, tools such as ArgMiner and oAMF (for *argument mining*) and Detoxify and Content-Checker (for *moderation and safety*) are evaluated, revealing varying degrees of alignment with HLEG principles (for example, oAMF's main challenges concern governance, documentation, and accountability). For translation and accessibility, *LibreTranslate* and *Whisper* demonstrate strong compliance, particularly regarding transparency, privacy, and operator control. *Gamification and engagement tools*, such as *Chamilo LMS*, are identified as ethically sound when used with transparency, informed consent, and robust governance mechanisms. *Summarisation tools*, e.g. *Bart*, are suitable for lower-risk uses but require strong testing and human oversight in critical contexts; while *Sumy* is mostly compliant, and its main risks arise from language bias, limited auditing mechanisms, *Stanza's* key risks stem from training-data bias and overinterpretation of NLP outputs, while BERT's main risks relate to bias and privacy issues stemming from training data.

The assessment focuses on a case analysis of *ECHO*, beneficiary BRANE's deliberation tool, which will be used in the Italian pilot. The analysis aligns with the *Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)* and the HLEG's *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (2019)*.

The assessment of the four pilots presents the ethics assessment of Sprint 1 of pilot trials, with initial stages of AI tool testing and evaluation. It identifies and maps opportunities to enhance pilot deliberation processes with AI capabilities. At this stage, only third-party AI tools and *ECHO* were tested, as other proprietary AI tools were still under development and not yet ready for deployment in pilot projects. In cooperation with WP5 leaders, pilots either contributed pre-existing datasets (Greek Pilot, International pilot) or conducted internal small-scale deliberation rounds involving only pilot staff (German and Italian Pilots). The collected data and deliberation transcripts were subsequently processed with AI tools to create summaries, extract arguments or test moderation capabilities. Ethics risks in Sprint 1 were assessed against HLEG Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. The ethics risk assessment includes risk situations encountered by pilots in Sprint 1 as well as risk situations which could potentially arise in the subsequent sprints, as far as those can already be anticipated. Generally, across all pilot partners, the risks were assessed as low, mainly because no personal data were processed and no research participants were recruited in the pilot trials. Nonetheless, by applying the principles of privacy-by-design and ethics-by-design across all

stages of the AI4Deliberation project, risk scenarios were identified and mapped, and potential risk mitigation measures were proposed.

The deliverable also explores intellectual property (IPR) considerations and potential hurdles in developing proprietary AI tools for democratic deliberation. It highlights that while software algorithms are generally excluded from patent protection, the project's outputs — including code, documentation, and policy materials — are protected under copyright law. The lawful use of third-party data, licensing conditions, and terms and conditions for AI tools are examined to prevent misuse or discriminatory applications.

Finally, the deliverable presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) established for the ethics and legal work package and reports on the progress achieved during the first reporting period of the AI4Deliberation project.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
AAE	African American English
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)
AI4Deliberation	AI4Deliberation project
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
ASR	Automated speech recognition
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EbD	Ethics-by-design
EC	European Commission
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
GPAI	General-purpose artificial intelligence
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on AI
ISMS	Information Security Management System
IPR	Intellectual property rights
LLM	Large-language model
ML	Machine learning
NER	Named Entity Recognition
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

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PD	Personal data
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
SIENNA	H2020 Project “Stakeholder-Informed Ethics for New Technologies with High Socio-Economic and Human Rights Impact”
TBU	To be updated
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
vidLLM	Video Large Language Model

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Partners List Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
UNIS	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI ANONYMI EMPORIKI ETAIRIA - UNI SYSTEMS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEMS COMMERCIAL S.M.S.A.
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT - TU Delft
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS CERTH
UBAM	OTTO-FRIEDRICH-UNIVERSITAET BAMBERG - UNI BA
KT	KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED - Konnekt-able Technologies
UNIVDUN	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE - UNIVDUN
IK	INŠTITUT ZA KRIMINOLOGIJO PRI PRAVNI FAKULTETI V LJUBLJANI - INSTITUTE OF CRIMINOLOGY AT THE FACULTY OF LAW LJUBLJANA
BRANE	Dembrane B.V. - Dembrane
TG	THOUGHTGRAPH LTD - TG
GFOSS	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
AAIT	ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS - ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS
CBAM	Stadt Bamberg (City of Bamberg)
UZH	UNIVERSITY OF ZÜRICH

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Introduction

Background

This deliverable presents the results of a qualitative evaluation focusing on the legal and ethical dimensions of the AI4Deliberation project. The evaluation covers activities involving research participants, the processing of personal data, the participation of non-EU countries, and the development and deployment of artificial intelligence tools designed to support deliberative processes at regional, national, and international levels. The assessment follows the EU ethics appraisal process, as implemented under the Horizon Europe programme and its predecessors.

The AI4Deliberation consortium will conduct several sprints—iterative phases of testing and applying various AI tools and functionalities within deliberation platforms. To achieve its objectives, the consortium has identified several groups of AI tools: (1) Large Language Models, (2) Video Large Language Models, (3) Deliberation and Argument Mining Tools, (4) Moderation and Safety Tools, (5) Translation and Accessibility Tools, (6) Gamification and Engagement Tools, (7) Summarisation Tools and (8) Clustering Tools. As the specific tools and functionalities have not yet been finalised, this assessment focuses on a representative selection of first-tier tools—those identified by the AI4Deliberation technical partners as the most relevant within each of the eight functional groups. The analysis considers both the ethical and legal implications of these specific tools and the broader issues that are characteristic of each group, irrespective of the particular tools ultimately selected.

At this stage of the AI4Deliberation project, the work has concentrated on identifying and mapping the most pressing ethical and legal challenges associated with the use of AI in deliberative processes. It is recognised that each tool or family of tools will require further, more detailed analysis as the project progresses.

The core of the work has focused on ethical issues concerning the participation of human subjects in research and the processing of personal data, including special categories of such data. These matters are particularly pertinent to surveys, observational activities, and the four pilot studies: three national pilots (conducted in Germany, Italy, and Greece) and one international pilot (led by the UK beneficiary). The activities carried out have included providing practical legal advice to consortium partners—such as guidance on informed consent documentation and the requirement to obtain ethical approvals—ensuring the legal and ethical compliance of selected AI tools, analysing ethical concerns arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes, and preparing a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

The legal and ethical guidance developed within this task will support the pilot studies under Work Package 5 (WP5). The research and evaluation activities will continue as an iterative process throughout the forthcoming sprints planned for the subsequent stages of the AI4Deliberation project's implementation.

Methods

The IK ethics and legal team employed several methods not only to conduct research on the legal and ethical dimensions of deliberative processes and the preliminary selection of AI

tools, but also to provide ongoing legal and ethical guidance to the consortium across all relevant activities. These activities included consultations on the research work with research participants, the processing of personal data, and the AI tools and functionalities within the AI4Deliberation project (to be updated as the project progresses).

More specifically, consortium members received tailored advice on a range of issues, including the design and implementation of surveys, consultations with experts and stakeholders, the preparation of pilot studies, and the identification and mitigation of AI-related risks. The guidance was structured around five principal areas of ethical and legal concern:

1. The involvement of human participants in research;
2. The processing of personal data, including special categories of data;
3. The engagement of non-EU countries, particularly in relation to the participation of the UK beneficiary and the use of IT services;
4. The development, deployment, and use of artificial intelligence tools; and
5. Other relevant legal matters, such as intellectual property rights (IPR).

The IK ethics and legal team attended all meetings of WP4 where AI tools deployed in pilots were discussed, including the personal data flows in the AI4Deliberation project.

Sprint 1 in pilots was completed up to 16 March 2026: research participants were not recruited for the purposes of *Sprint 1*, and only members of the research team participated in the pilots.

Sprint 2 design is still being discussed (16 March 2026), and the design of pilots is planned to be clarified, namely: the participation of research participants in pilots, personal data processing within pilots, and the exact AI tools to be used in pilots. Pilots have already committed to start with the process of obtaining independent ethics approvals due to involvement of external research participants, processing of their personal data (incl. special categories) and the deployment and testing of AI tools on the data thus collected.

The IK ethics and legal team was supported by internal reviewers Sem Nouws (TUD) and Konstantinos Vaianos (UNIS), as well as external reviewers from the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB), composed of experts: Heidi Beate Bentzen, Alice Siu and Alexei Grinbaum.

Structure of the report

This report comprises **eight sections** following to the extent possible the standard Horizon Europe ethics appraisal process: 1) Introduction, 2) Humans/research participants, 3) Personal data processing, 4) the involvement of Non-EU countries, 5) AI Ethics Impact Assessment, 6) Other issues covering IPR, i.e. patent rights, copyright, trademarks, licencing, End-user licence agreements, and Terms & Conditions, while the section 7) reports on the achievement of KPIs and the last one lists all the annexes.

The report is accompanied by the following annexes:

Annexes 1-8 from CERTH's empirical work include:

- 1 – Citizens Questionnaire in English
- 2 – Semi-structured interview for external experts who have conducted deliberations

- 3 – Semi-structured interview with experts who own a deliberation platform
- 4 – Semi-structured interview for the Greek pilot
- 5 – Citizens' Questionnaire in Greek
- 6 – A self-assessment
- 7 – Research protocol
- 8 – The ethics approval

Annex 9-10 presents the application and ethics approval from UBAM.

Annexes 11-12 present the DebateGraph privacy policies and registration page.

Annex 13 presents the updated Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

Annex 14 presents a shortlist of AI tools to be used in the AI4Deliberation compiled in WP4.

Annex 15 presents AI tools initially assessed, but later not used in WP4.

Annex 16 presents the AI4Deliberation Architecture.

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1. Humans / Research participants

The participation of research subjects in the AI4Deliberation project will take place through **observations, surveys, and pilot studies**. The project seeks to design and test an innovative framework for AI-enabled, multimodal, and gamified public deliberations, allowing citizens to express their views in diverse formats—such as written statements, voice recordings, or video submissions—and to engage in interactive, game-like elements of the process. As part of its commitment to improving the accessibility of deliberation platforms and services, the project will conduct pilot activities involving research participants, including scenarios in which AI-based facilitators support vulnerable groups, such as older adults.

The key aspect of involving research participants at this stage (M01-M18) lies in preparing **four pilot studies**, which will serve to test and further develop new functionalities of deliberative processes. The four pilots will focus on substantially different topics and organise deliberation activities on an international, national or local level: one pilot focuses on the local level in Germany, two national ones focus on Greek and Italian use cases, while one pilot is international (led by the UK beneficiary DebateGraph), in which participants from anywhere can participate in the pilot.

Research participants recruited in the pilots will be adults. TBU (to be updated)¹ – However, older children (16-18 years old) may not be entirely excluded. The means of exclusion of children have not yet been confirmed by all pilots, e.g. how they will design age verification in online systems.

The participation of research participants will be based on their informed consent, sought before their involvement in the deliberation pilots. How informed consent will be sought varies and depends on the nature of the pilot. TBU – at this stage of the project implementation, the pilots have not confirmed all the details of the inclusion/exclusion criteria and the procedure for obtaining informed consent. However, while the pilots have not decided on a solution yet, they know what they should decide on and what ethical implications and obligations each solution carries (e.g., whether anonymous participation will be pursued in the pilot or only participants who give consent, e.g. for recording on their phone in the ECHO platform, will be able to take part in the pilots).

1.1. About the pilots

Participation of research participants in the four pilots:

Pilot 1 – ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA (GFOSS), conducted in Greece (hereafter referred to also as: **Greek pilot**). The participants in the testing phases will initially be internal technicians and administrators, and later also the Greek general public. **Participants:** Individuals who submitted comments on legislative proposals via the platform opengov.gr, provided by the Greek government (Ministry of Administrative Reform and E-Governance).

Pilot 2 – THOUGHTGRAPH LTD (TG), the provider of DebateGraph (debategraph.org) – a collaborative cloud-based platform, which enables participants to contribute various forms of

¹ Where the legal and ethics team lead by IK (Institute of Criminology at the Faculty of Law Ljubljana) has not received sufficient information, the abbreviation TBU is indicated.

content on various issues (hereafter referred to also as: the **International pilot**). The pilot is aimed at experts, specialising in Long Covid, but is also open for participation from the general public, including those experiencing consequences of Long Covid. **Participants:** The participants of the pilot trial will be users of the DebateGraph platform who have created a user account (a profile). After creating a profile, participants can add nodes and contribute content (text, documents, images, videos, links, etc.) to the Long Covid graph – a case study. Adults are allowed to create a profile, and children with the consent of their parents. However, age verification mechanisms are not in place due to privacy concerns (see the justification below).

Pilot 3 – ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS (AAIT) and DEMBRANE B.V. (BRANE): The pilot will focus on the implementation of a national-scale deliberative process about the Italian “National Climate Change Adaptation Plan” (PNACC) (hereafter referred to as: **Italian pilot**). **Participants:** members of civil society, selected by AAIT to participate in an online deliberation platform, ECHO, hosted by BRANE. ECHO platform records the spoken discussion from participants on a selected topic, transcribes the audio data and offers several functions which support deliberative processes, e.g. summarisation of the discussion, analysis of the conversation, and identification of key topics. The participants will be recruited from various social strata, e.g. in terms of gender, age, and rural-urban settings. TBU – the inclusion/exclusion criteria are not yet defined, but it is confirmed that only adults will be actively sought and recruited.

Pilot 4 – STADT BAMBERG (CBAM): The Municipality of Bamberg runs an online deliberation platform to solicit input from citizens of Bamberg on various topics of local significance (hereafter referred to as: **German pilot**). **Participants:** Citizens of Bamberg, registered on the <https://bamberg-gestalten.de/> platform, operated by the Municipality of Bamberg. Only adults are allowed to enter the deliberation platform; the age verification is enabled through the last 4 digits of the participant’s ID number and birth date.

1.2. Specific groups of research participants

Children, i.e. individuals below 18 years of age according to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, and/or adults unable to give informed consent, will not be actively recruited and involved in the project, with some nuances between the pilots. The **German** pilot allows only citizens who are adults to sign into the city platform, as the last 4 digits of ID are entered to register to enter the platform. The **Italian** pilot aims to collect consent for participation and for personal data processing via a questionnaire before starting the pilot. Moreover, in the written consent form, each participant will have to tick a box declaring that the person is over 18 years of age. For the **international pilot**, there is no expectation that children will be involved, given the topic of discussion (Long Covid), and the pilot will not actively seek input from children. However, the pilot also does not aim to automatically exclude the voices of people who are younger than 18 (e.g. 16-18), who are experiencing Long Covid and are already acting as public advocates for better public policy responses to Long Covid in children. There are no age verification mechanisms in place on the platform. The pilot estimates that collecting IDs would, in fact, lead to even higher risks to personal data,² as age-based ID checks on registration would require all users to share more personal data than is currently required

² Existing policy states that children above 13 years are allowed to participate only with parents' consent. See: <https://debategraph.org/Details.aspx?nid=65028>

for registration on the platform and would run counter to the important privacy principles currently enacted of requiring minimal personal data and using functional cookies only. Registration is the only effective way to check the age of participants, but they may provide false information, which is not contrary to the aims of the pilot. However, if the pilot observes from the behaviour of the user that children below 18 years are involved, they will be excluded (e.g. in the DebateGraph pilot).

Given the nature of the deliberations conducted in the pilot studies—such as comments on legislative proposals in the Greek pilot and feedback on the national climate change adaptation plan in the Italian pilot—the overall potential risks to participants’ well-being are considered to be low. The risks to their well-being are expected to be low, also due to the absence of any physical interaction with research participants. The moderate risk to the participants’ well-being is only expected in the international pilot, where discomfort may occur in discussions about Long Covid health issues, where children above 16 years may participate. If younger participants are to be detected, they will be excluded from the international pilot.

TBU – if plans to include children change, especially in the Italian pilot, which is still unclear in this regard, adequate justification for their participation, the informed consent and assent procedures for the legal representatives/guardians and the children themselves must be presented.

Young people aged 18 to 35 years will be actively sought for involvement in the research activities of the AI4Deliberation project, as the goal of the project is to attract and analyse their engagement in the deliberations at local, regional or country levels. This group of research participants is not considered as being vulnerable as they are a group of “digital natives”, a more versed group of users of digital technologies. They are also not vulnerable in the meaning of the sense used in the framework of ethics appraisal processes under the Horizon Europe research programme.

Older people will be actively sought for involvement in the project activities as the participation inequities and a new “AI divide” are important obstacles for a more meaningful participation of older people in digitisation processes in contemporary EU societies, e.g., the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) warns against excluding the elderly in the process of digitalisation of public services in general.³ Hence, the project should strive to include members of such a group. Beyond the usual digital divide, AI-facilitated processes may also deter participants who distrust AI or feel disadvantaged by AI-mediated or other digital deliberative tools, creating a “deliberative divide” based on attitudes toward AI.⁴ To address the AI divide concern, the Italian pilot will actively seek older participants for their pilot on attitudes about the national climate change adaptation plan.

1.3. Expert and stakeholder consultations

As part of Task 1.3 of Work Package 1, the Consortium attempted to elicit **stakeholders'** needs and considerations on using AI in deliberations. Part of this task consisted of gathering

³ FRA: <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2023/older-people-digital-rights>

⁴ Andreas Jungherr, Adrian Rauchfleisch: Artificial Intelligence in deliberation: The AI penalty and the emergence of a new deliberative divide, Government Information Quarterly, Volume 42, Issue 4, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2025.102079>.

opinions of **pilots' employees, best practice case owners and platform owners**, via questionnaires and semi-structured interviews.

For interviews with Consortium Members' employees, special consent was not required; they were not regarded as research participants *stricto sensu*, as their participation in the activities of the AI4Deliberation is an inherent part of the project and necessary for the performance of contractual obligations under the Consortium Agreement. Some of them may not be members of the consortium, but are part of professional teams and networks of beneficiaries, and such consultations are regarded as part of the "daily business" of the research team necessary for the performance of contractual obligations.

For pilot citizens, we created a questionnaire (**Annexes 1 and 5**: Consent Form – Questionnaire for Citizens), accompanied by an information sheet and consent form, which was distributed through the **EUSurvey tool** to the four project pilots and translated into their native language. The Ethics Manager advised the use of the EUSurvey tool over tools like Google Forms, as in this case, data is not transferred outside the EEA. EUSurvey enables the data controller to select the default anonymous mode, which prevents the saving of any personal data, including the participants' IP addresses. Participants were also provided with a link to the EUSurvey Privacy policy documents. For pilots' employees, best practice case owners and platform owners, we created and translated semi-structured interview templates (**Annexes 2, 3 and 4**: Semi-structured interview for external experts who have conducted deliberations; Semi-structured interview with experts who own deliberation platforms; Semi-structured interview for the Greek pilot), which are accompanied by an information sheet and consent form.

The Consortium partners acting as data processors for the **surveys and interviews** have been informed that only when personal data is fully anonymised, the processing of such data is not subject to GDPR. If data is merely pseudonymised and the data subject might still be identified through the use of additional information, the processing of such data is still subject to GDPR.

The information sheet and consent forms for pilot citizens include the following information:

- Explanation of the purpose of the questionnaire
- Declaration of voluntary participation and withdrawal options
- Which categories of personal data will be processed
- Confidentiality
- Data processor contact information
- Potential risks and benefits of participation

Additionally, the information sheet and consent forms for pilots' employees, best practice case owners and platform owners also include the following information:

- Explanation that the interview will be recorded and the participants' rights regarding their voice recording
- Data retention period
- Participants rights

Participants were asked to consent that they understood the provided information, that they participated in the survey/interview voluntarily and that they are over 18 years of age, as well as additional consent for voice recording (where applicable), by checking the appropriate box on the consent form or signing the form.

For collecting the opinions of users, we employed an **external polling company (IPSOS)** to gather the opinions and considerations of German citizens on using AI in deliberations. The Ethics Manager reviewed the polling company's pitch deck, as well as their Privacy and Data Protection document. The Ethics Manager assessed that the company adheres to all GDPR requirements when conducting the survey, but recommended an additional written confirmation that IPSOS will adhere to all relevant personal data protection legislation, as well as that the participants should be explicitly informed that their participation is consent-based and voluntary, meaning that they may withdraw their consent at any moment to the participation and processing of their personal data. The Ethics manager also advised that the participants should be informed that the data is gathered for the AI4Deliberation project only and that it might be shared with Consortium members.

About possible internal or external ethics **approvals** for the execution of surveys and interviews, the Ethics Manager assessed that Consortium Members conducting the research were not obligated to apply for an external ethics approval, due to the low risk of the surveys/interviews adversely impacting the rights of participants. More specifically, for **pilot citizens**, the data was collected anonymously, and no processing of personal data, which would enable the identification of participants, took place. With regard to **pilots' employees, practice case owners and platform owners**, the Ethics Manager established that only a small number of well-informed experts will be interviewed. All interviewees were also provided with information sheets and explicit consent forms for the processing of their personal data and voice recording. Nonetheless, the Ethics Manager advised Consortium Members to obtain internal or external ethics approvals if this is within their usual research practice and/or if such approvals can be obtained without unreasonable difficulty. Consequently, CERTH and UBAM obtained positive ethics approvals from their internal ethics bodies (see attached the application documents and ethics approvals, **Annexes 1-8** for CERTH and **Annexes 9-10** for UBAM).

1.4. Vulnerability of research participants

Vulnerable individuals/groups may be inadvertently involved in the Italian and the international pilots, and hence adequate measures to protect them and prevent coercion and undue inducement/exacerbation of their vulnerability / and minimise the risk of harm and/or stigmatisation must be in place.

The justification for the inclusion of vulnerable individuals/groups in the **Italian pilot**: such individuals/groups can provide valuable insight into perceptions, views, standpoints and argumentation in relation to the national climate change adaptation plan. The exclusion of such groups/individuals could lead to their voices not being heard and might amount to unjustified discrimination. TBU – the exact group of vulnerabilities still has not been determined, e.g. whether this will be individuals with physical disabilities, migrants or others. In principle, hence, the pilot will not exclude people with special needs, and will not restrict their participation, as their voices should also be heard; but the pilot will not necessarily include these target groups, as participation will be voluntary. As an inclusivity measure, the ECHO (software) also has a text-based input for deaf people. The software provider (BRANE),

on the other hand, cannot control and assign who is involved in the conversation, and participants have control over what can be said (through a pause button), but the host (AAIT) will control who is permitted to join the conversation itself. For people who feel/are vulnerable, the transcription may still pick that up in the form of spoken word, and the host (AAIT) will make sure that this will not happen.

The justification for the inclusion of individuals/groups in the **International pilot**: The participants in deliberation may have been experiencing the consequences of Long Covid themselves, or may still be experiencing health issues. In principle, the topic of COVID and especially Long Covid might cause anxiety and discomfort to some users. The risk of emotional burden in discussing the effect of Long Covid is moderate. However, the Long Covid graph aims to capture and share the full range of policy-related issues and evidence as clearly and fairly as possible, which, in turn, may also be experienced as empowering for a community of vulnerable individuals who are experiencing Long Covid and who feel that their voices and interests have not yet been fully heard in the context of existing policy deliberations. The very discussion is planned to alleviate at least some of the burden and emotional distress users may feel over the prolonged health deterioration. Participants will nevertheless be provided with information on the purpose of the graph and the selected topic, and resources and exit recommendations if they feel triggered or feel emotionally overwhelmed, e.g. a list of fact-checked resources may be prepared, and clear instructions may be offered to users that they may exit the discussion as they feel appropriate and delete their data/comments provided at any time (TBU). Moreover, the participants will not be encouraged in any way to share sensitive data or their subjective experience with the condition. The data required for registration also supports pseudonymous participation (supported by a valid/confirmed email address). In the light of each of these factors, the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons leading to physical, material or non-material damage, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, damage to the reputation, loss of confidentiality or any other significant economic or social disadvantage are unlikely.

The AI4Deliberation project will not recruit research participants who are in a **dependent position**, e.g. such as students of the beneficiaries of the AI4Deliberation project, or convicted individuals, or members of the armed forces.

1.5. Incidental and unexpected findings policies

The risk of incidental findings (e.g. illnesses) and unexpected findings (e.g. crime that must be reported to the authorities) is considered low, especially given the substance/topics in the pilot studies. More specifically:

Pilot 1 – GFOSS, Greek pilot – comments on legislative proposals via the platform opengov.gr do not raise a realistic risk of incidental or unexpected findings, as the pilots will trigger discussion about proposed legislative solutions on different drafts and not individual experiences.

Pilot 2 – TG, International pilot – comments and scientific findings on the consequences of Long Covid, raise the risk of sharing participants' health data, but these are data that research participants are well aware of and are willing to share; these are not data that could be incidentally revealed, e.g. compared to medical examination of collection of biological material from participants that can incidentally reveal illnesses. The Pilot, as planned at this moment in time (TBU), will not focus on particular research participants, and the consortium

partners will not be able to incidentally reveal health issues of online users. We hence do not plan to develop specific incidental/expected findings procedures and related disclosure policies. However, we will add a pop-up warning message (TBU) that opinions shared about health issues on Long Covid are not verified by the platform, and users should consult professionals in case of health-related concerns.

Pilot 3 – AAIT and BRANE, Italian pilot – a deliberative process about the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan, does not raise a realistic risk of incidental or unexpected findings, as, e.g., opinions on the seriousness of climate change will be collected and assessed (TBU – the substance of discussion is not yet completely clear apart from the focus on the above-mentioned national climate plan).

Pilot 4 – CBAM, German pilot – citizens of Bamberg discussing various topics of local significance, does not raise a realistic risk of incidental or unexpected findings as the discussed issues will concern local-level governance projects, e.g. on city infrastructure, availability of public services and the like.

1.6. Informed consent procedure

Detailed information on the identification/recruitment and informed consent procedures for the research participants needs to be provided for each of the pilots. The participants in the deliberation testing will be informed thoroughly that they are participating in the AI4Deliberation project and may cease to do so at any time they choose. Means of reaching informed consent vary depending on the pilot:

Pilot 1 – GFOSS, Greek pilot

Sprint 1 of AI testing is planned on comments given on past legislation proposals, so deception is not possible; however, the next sprints will most probably be completed either on the actual gov platform or on the parallel mock site (TBU); the pilot has still not decided whether the analysis will be completed on *openGov.gr* platform's real cases, i.e. collecting and analysing users' comments on the real legislative proposals in Greece; or they will create a mock-up parallel site, where the discussion about the proposed laws will not influence the legislative process itself. In the latter case, the risk of misleading users exists, and the lack of influence on the real legislative proposal must be clearly communicated to the users in the informed consent pop-up form. The final sprint will hence install a public pop-up notice with information about the AI4Deliberation project (TBU), to inform platform users that they are participating in the real deliberation as set up by the Greek government and also in the AI4Deliberation project, i.e. that their data/comments used primarily for the legislation process purpose may be used for the AI4Deliberation project.

Pilot 2 – TG, International pilot

The aim is to provide an empowering fact-based discussion, which will be ensured with experts on Long Covid and the general public. The participant will have to provide consent to take part in the research, i.e. in the graph on Long Covid; otherwise, they will not be able to add comments.

Given the nature of the platform and the topic discussed, the probability of children or adults unable to give informed consent participating is very low. In case members of these two groups participate in the discussion on Long Covid, the risks to their well-being are also low

(see the section “About the vulnerability of research participants”). (Please see the attached Debategraph sign-up form in **Annex 12** and Debategraph Privacy policy in **Annex 11**).

Pilot 3 – AAIT and BRANE, Italian pilot

TBU – The form of providing consent to research participation still needs to be developed.

Pilot 4 – CBAM, German pilot

TBU – Consent will be provided when users log in to the platform in a pop-up window, and a public notice with information about AI4Deliberation will be posted on bamberg-gestalten.de.

1.7. External ethics assessments – methodology /workflow

Considering the involvement of human participants, processing of personal data, including special categories and the involvement of non-EU countries, and use of Artificial Intelligence tools in democratic deliberation processes, the pilot partners were advised from the early stages of the AI4Deliberation project to obtain ethics approvals/opinions from relevant ethics committees and/or competent authorities (e.g. universities, research organisations, or independent research ethics bodies). Following the assessment of the Institute of Criminology, it was decided on the level of the consortium that external ethics approvals were not required for the initial project activities (like consultation with external experts and stakeholders and citizen surveys.⁵) as well as the activities in Sprint 1, as no human participants were recruited at that stage in any of the pilot trials. As the pilot partners were all planning on recruiting human participants in Sprint 2, which starts in May 2026, they were advised to obtain ethics opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans before any activities which would involve the research participants, the collection/processing of their personal data or exposure to AI tools used in AI4Deliberation takes place. Each pilot was required to identify the competent ethics committees and/or competent authority and follow local/national legislation and process guidelines for the submission of their applications. Most required a thorough description of the project activities and possible risks involved, as well as submission of documents, like information sheets, consent forms, participant questionnaires, internal project agreements, etc. The Institute of Criminology offered advice and support with regard to the choice of competent national ethics committees as well as the content of the applications, together with annexes.

- GFOSS: For all project activities of the Greek pilot, CERTH will apply for an ethics assessment at its internal ethics committee.
- AAIT: After initial attempts at securing an ethics approval from Bicocca University, the pilot applied for external ethics approval at the National Research Council (CNR) in April 2026.
- CBAM: Pilot will obtain an ethics approval from the Ethics Committee of the University of Bamberg, one of the members of the consortium.
- TG: Initially, TG suggested obtaining an external ethics review from an individual expert, Dr David Edmonds, an ethics expert at Oxford University. The Institute of Criminology suggested that Dr Edmonds would be more suited as an external ethics adviser, but the ethics assessment should be sought from established (institutional)

⁵ Nonetheless, CERTH and UBAM obtained positive ethics approvals from their internal ethics bodies for the initial project activities.

ethics committees. The pilot has subsequently chosen the Social Research Association (SRA) Ethics Appraisal Service

Annexes:

- Informed consent forms + Informed consent sheets (**Annexes 1-8**)
 - o expert consultation/interviews: consortium/pilot employees + best practice owners/platform owners
 - o pilot citizens (EUSurvey)
- Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans, together with the full application(s):
 - o CERTH beneficiary: approval for expert consultation/interviews and pilot citizens, with the full application
 - o UBAM beneficiary: approval, with the full application (**Annexes 9-10**)

PENDING EC APPROVAL

2. Personal data processing

2.1. Dimensions of personal data processing in AI4Deliberation

During the implementation of the AI4Deliberation project, personal data of research participants analysed in the four **pilots, survey** and **observation studies** will be processed.

These include **special categories** of personal data, i.e. **health** data in the international pilot, which focuses on health data and health conditions related to Long Covid, and potentially data on **political** opinions, **religious** or **philosophical** beliefs in the Italian pilot, which focuses on environmental issues, and in the Greek and German pilots with a focus on (not yet defined) legislation and city-related legal/policy initiatives (TBU).

The processing of **large-scale special categories** of personal data may take place for the project, and the use of AI tools, and thus a **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)** must be conducted according to Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR). (The DPIA is attached, see **Annex 13**.)

The project will not use and further process previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets) (“**secondary use**”). If secondary use will take place, the legal basis must be clarified; TBU – the Greek pilot (GFOSS) may process already collected data from past deliberations /comments on past legislative acts published by the Greek government via the platform [opengov.gr](#) for Sprint 1 (still needs to be decided – TBU).

2.2. Import/export of personal data from/to the EU

Export of personal data from **the EU to a non-EU** country (UK) may potentially take place, since the international pilot focuses on data related to Long Covid, with participants potentially from anywhere. The transfer, if any, will comply with Chapter V of the GDPR as the processing will take place at the UK-based DebateGraph platform and its subcontracting servers are based in a GDPR-compliant USA cloud service; the international pilot IBM cloud service provider is on the list.⁶ The DebateGraph is using cloud services in the USA to store its graphs (see DPIA for more details on the subcontracting). Given the adequacy decision of the European Commission (EC) that UK standards are compliant with the GDPR, and the EC decision that the UK continues to provide an essentially equivalent level of personal data protection to the GDPR with the new UK Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 (DUAA), there are no aggravated risks just due to the processing personal data taking place in the UK or in the GDPR-compliant USA cloud service.⁷

⁶ See IBM as “International Business Machines” Corporation on the list: <https://www.dataprivacyframework.gov/list>.

⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/6f636fa0-30d4-4c05-a713-64484ad913fa_en?filename=Draft%20Renewal%20of%20EU%20adequacy%20decision%20for%20the%20UK%20under%20the%20GDPR.pdf. More at: https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en

Import of personal data from the non-EU to the EU: In the international Pilot, beneficiary TG may share data collected on the DebateGraph platform in the framework of the AI4Deliberation project with the AI4Deliberation consortium (TBU). The exact Terms of Use will be decided before the start of the pilot. Since consent will be the legal basis for collaborating in the international pilot, the potential transfers of personal data will comply with the UK Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 and the corresponding adequacy decision of the EC.

Import of personal data from non-EU countries to another non-EU country – the UK may take place in the international pilot, with a focus on Long Covid. Technically, research activities will take place on the platform based in the UK (see above on the adequacy decision of the European Commission for the UK and the DPIA), and the transfer must comply with the laws of non-EU countries. TBU – apart from the UK, other non-EU countries still need to be identified.

Transfer of personal data in other pilots will not take place. In the Italian pilot (AAIT & BRANE), for instance, Microsoft Azure and DigitalOcean are US-headquartered companies; however, Dembrane exclusively uses their EEA-based infrastructure (specifically, North-west Europe data centres). All data processing and storage occur within the EEA.

The AI4Deliberation processing of personal data does **not** involve the processing of personal data related to **criminal** convictions or offences.

2.3. The need to conduct the Data Protection Impact Assessment

The **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)** was conducted according to the Art. 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and analyses the following questions:

- Description of the types of data (primary, secondary use of data, data sources, personal data, special categories of data – Article 9 EU GDPR) that will be processed within the research project
- Clarification on how all the personal data that will be processed is relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project (in accordance with the “data minimisation” principle)
- Description of the organisational, technical and security measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants
- Description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques, and in case personal data are not to be anonymised/pseudonymised, a justification for not anonymising/pseudonymising the relevant data
- For personal data to be transferred from the EU to the UK as a non-EU country, a justification that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (only the International pilot)
- For personal data to be transferred from a non-EU country to the EU (or another third country), a justification that such transfers comply with the laws of the country in which the data was collected (only the International pilot)

- Detailed information on the informed consent procedures related to the processing of personal data
- Project-specific templates of the information sheets and informed consent forms related to the processing of personal data (in language and terms understandable to the participants), including the Data Protection Officer contact details

Profiling in the meaning of GDPR will not take place in the framework of the AI4Deliberation project.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

3. Non-EU countries

The activities will be carried out in the EU countries, where the beneficiaries are located, and in the UK, where the beneficiary TG is located. The activities undertaken in the UK within the international pilot (TG) raise ethical issues related to **personal data processing** only (see above). The project will not use any local resources apart from (personal) data in the non-EU countries. The project also does not plan to export any material from the EU to the UK, apart from the possibility of exporting personal data of EU citizens in the international pilot.

The project may involve collecting personal data from participants from the low and/or lower-middle-income countries in the international pilot. TBU – Given the online /platform collaboration open to anyone in the world with access to the internet and English fluency, benefit-sharing activities are not planned. However, beneficiary TG should plan some **benefit-sharing** according to the TRUST Code – A Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships.⁸, which would be sufficiently targeted to countries/areas, if the burden for the beneficiary in identifying the non-EU countries and participants could be borne, and the efforts would not be disproportionate.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

⁸ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/coc_research-resource-poor-settings_en.pdf; https://www.globalcodeofconduct.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/The_TRUST_Code.pdf

4. AI Ethics Impact Assessment

4.1. About the use of AI in deliberation processes

The AI4Deliberation project includes the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence tools/features in the deliberation processes. Already John Dewey (1954)⁹ asked the still-relevant question of the extent to which citizens can effectively inform themselves about complex issues in large-scale, industrialised societies, i.e. on how they can be informed and meaningfully participate in the democratic deliberation processes. Today, in the post-industrialised societies, the technological solutions to increase the scale of being informed are here, and these tools may “offload the civic task of assessing the issues onto dedicated machines, freeing up time and cognitive resources for the more entertaining distractions of the information economy,” observes critical scholar Andrejevic (2018).¹⁰

Given the myriad curation systems we already depend upon to divine our preferences in music, movies, books, and a range of other products, the solution seems like an obvious one: “Algorithms are already very capable of recognising patterns in our behaviour and preferences, and this digital agent would read our data in such a way that it would be able to directly vote on issues on our behalf” (Anzilotti 2018).¹¹ Taken to the limit, digital agents could take the place of elected representatives, rapidly assimilating information and voting on complex issues in real time to reflect the preferences of their respective citizens (Andrejevic, 2020). “We could have a Senate that has as many Senators as citizens.” (Hidalgo, in Anzilotti 2018). But should there be limits to such use of AI tools – to sort through the news for us, sort through the deliberation agendas at local, regional and national levels and decide which legislative proposal to support, which policy not to support and explain why, or even which candidates best match our interests and values and vote instead of us (Anzilotti 2018, Andrejevic 2020)? In the time of numerous “attention merchants” that are nudging us all in multiple directions, why not turn the sense-making and deliberation processes over to AI? Should there be “red lines” that should never be crossed with AI-facilitated deliberation processes? If such “red lines” exist, which criteria should we use to define them in different contexts, for different AI tools, for various topics, and objectives of deliberation?

The ethical questions surrounding the use of AI in deliberative processes therefore, strike at the very heart of liberal representative democracies, in which citizens exercise their political will indirectly through elected representatives. These concerns touch upon the foundations of democratic governance and pluralist political systems, where the competition of ideas should prevail over the dominance of single-party regimes, which are too often marked by corruption and authoritarian tendencies.

⁹ Dewey, J. (1954). *The Public and Its Problems*. Denver: Swallow.

¹⁰ Andrejevic, M. (2020). *Data Civics: A Response to the “Ethical Turn”*. Sage, *Television & New Media*, 21(6) 562–567.

¹¹ Anzilotti, E. (2018, April 12). *This Plan for an AI-based Direct Democracy Outsources Votes to a Predictive Algorithm*. Fast Company. Available at: <https://www.fastcompany.com/40557688/this-plan-for-an-ai-based-direct-democracy-outsources-votes-to-a-predictive-algorithm>

This deliverable tackles these demanding overarching questions indirectly through the ethics and legal assessment of specific AI tools, or families/groups of AI tools and their compliance with ethics compliance standards as implemented in the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Technological Development, currently the Horizon Europe scientific research programme. This framework includes the following guidance that was considered in preparing this deliverable:

General guidance:

- Guidelines on ‘Identifying serious or complex ethics issues in EU-funded research’¹²
- Guide on ‘How to complete your ethics self-assessment’¹³

Domain-specific guidance:

- Guidance note on potential misuse of research results¹⁴
- Guidance note on research focusing exclusively on civil applications¹⁵
- Ethics and data protection¹⁶
- Ethics in Social Science and Humanities¹⁷
- Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence¹⁸

4.2. Ethics and law in assessing the AI deliberation tools

The deliverable presents the *legal* and *ethical* issues raised by the AI4Deliberation project and, by doing so, inevitably leads to confirmation of general knowledge that these two – law and ethics – are clearly separable and distinct sets of rules. The scientific literature, however, does not confirm these operationalised views of the two. Authors speak of an “ethical turn” in

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/guidelines-on-serious-and-complex-cases_he_en.pdf

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/guidance-note-potential-misuse-of-research-results_he_en.pdf

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/guidance-note-research-focusing-exclusively-on-civil-applications_he_en.pdf

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-in-social-science-and-humanities_he_en.pdf

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf

responding to harms of AI (Smuha, 2021),¹⁹ and turning away from the “legal” compliance approach, or turning to “soft law” and self-regulation instead of persisting with “hard law” and state regulation in regulating AI. The trend was described as going from the “race to AI” to the rush to “AI ethics” and onward and upward to the “race for the governance of AI” (e.g. Wagner, 2018;²⁰ Koulu, 2020;²¹ Dijk et al., 2021²²). The literature also confirms that both paths – through legal and ethics rules – often lead to the same results. The division between law and ethics is often not as sharp as critics of ethics (or law) in regulating AI have claimed. Despite the contemporary “race to AI regulation” (Smuha, 2021) and the “race for governance” in AI (Koniakou, 2022),²³ the key questions continue to relate to the translation of principles to practices (Schiff et al., 2022).²⁴ The dialectic between legal and ethical considerations may often also be circular, as Van Dijk et al. (2021) have sharply pointed out. Authors have been forcefully against such “circular ethics” in AI governance – when the ethics has “no authoritative ‘home-base’” and lacks sufficient discipline standards and, more perversely, calls upon human rights and law as “the authoritative source” and the point of reference for ethical principles so forth (Van Dijk et al. 2021). In this deliverable, we are aware that sometimes ethics and law are not as distinct as often perceived, and they pursue very similar goals.

So while the early phase of AI governance focused on the “ethics of AI” and “ethical AI”, scholars warned that the term “ethics” may be overly soft, vague and contingent on the interests of “big tech” and that it should be substituted or at least decisively complemented by the law, such as international human rights law and European law, since the law is universally agreed upon and its results are legally binding. The concern is that while ethics is crucial, it comprises only an indirect response to concerns about the uses and misuses of data mining, AI, and automated processes.²⁵ Apart from the distinction between the law and ethics, some authors, e.g. Crawford (2021),²⁶ also attempted to re-focus attention on another aspect – social power in AI, which shifts attention to the need to acknowledge both the politics and the physical impact that AI has on the planet. According to such views, crucial questions are:

¹⁹ Smuha, N. A. (2021). From a ‘race to AI’ to a ‘race to AI regulation’: regulatory competition for artificial intelligence. *Law, Innovation and Technology* 13(1): 57–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17579961.2021.1898300>

²⁰ Wagner, B. (2018). Ethics as an Escape from Regulation: From Ethics-Washing to Ethics-Shopping. In: M. Hildebrandt (ed.), *Being profiled: Cogitas ergo sum*, Amsterdam University Press, 86–90.

²¹ Koulu, R. (2020). Proceduralizing control and discretion: Human oversight in artificial intelligence policy. *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 27(6): 720–735. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1023263X20978649>

²² Van Dijk, N.; Casiraghi, S.; Gutwirth, S. (2021). The ‘Ethification’ of ICT Governance. *Artificial Intelligence and Data Protection in the European Union*. *Computer Law & Security Review* 43, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2021.105597>

²³ Koniakou, V. (2022). From the “rush to ethics” to the “race for governance” in Artificial Intelligence. *Information Systems Frontiers*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10300-6>

²⁴ Schiff, D.S., Laas, K., Biddle, J.B., Borenstein, J. (2022). Global AI Ethics Documents: What They Reveal About Motivations, Practices, and Policies. In: Laas, K., Davis, M., Hildt, E. (eds), *Codes of Ethics and Ethical Guidelines*. *The International Library of Ethics, Law and Technology*, 23. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86201-5_7

²⁵ Andrejevic, M. (2020). Data Civics: A Response to the “Ethical Turn”, *Sage, Television & New Media*, 21(6) 562–567.

²⁶ Crawford, K. (2021). *Atlas of AI: Power, politics, and the planetary costs of artificial intelligence*. Yale University Press.

who is running the levers of these systems? This requires us to shift away from just focusing on things like ethical principles and to talk about power (Crawford, 2021).²⁷

What is wrong with only ethics compliance?

The main concern about the role of ethics in the governance of AI is that it is at least partly self-imposed regulation, which has been historically relatively weak in curbing the interests of powerful actors (e.g. in curbing environmental pollution). Moreover, the idea that ethics should be replaced with human rights law is even more compelling since the law is, at least at the abstract level, clear. In contrast, ethics is more fluid, flexible and contingent on culture, place and time, as demonstrated by experimental ethics (e.g. Awad et al. 2018).²⁸ Also, the non-binding ethical guidelines lack mechanisms to ensure that they are respected and that principles are translated into binding provisions. The idea that ethics is “not sufficient” hence rests on several deficiencies of ethics itself (e.g. what do we talk about when we talk about “ethics governance” as there are several strands of ethics, which offer varied, if not contradictory, guidance on how to act ethically) and reflects the struggle for power and prestige of those that seek and offer ethical and legal expertise.

Scholars reflected upon an “ethicized” AI governance model, where ethics was supposed to “sit by table with policymakers” (Floridi, 2018: 7),²⁹ and pointed to its downsides: the risk of “ethics washing”, that is the practice of camouflaging practices and tools to appear more ethical than they really are, and warnings against “ethics shopping” (Wagner, 2018)³⁰, a practice of ‘mixing and matching’ ethical principles from various sources to avoid a real change of behaviour (Amram & Comandé, 2020),³¹ were just some of the more blatant downsides of the “turn to ethics” in AI governance.³²

What is wrong with only legal compliance?

Prioritising, if not glorifying, the law also has several flaws. The law is not a clear monolith that does not serve the particular interests of powerful groups. “The law” is not floating in a societal, cultural vacuum and is clear at the abstract level only. As shown by recent developments, the EC is willing to “sacrifice” key pieces of existing legislation, such as the

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Awad, E., Dsouza, S., Kim, R. et al. (2018). The Moral Machine Experiment. *Nature* 563: 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0637-6>

²⁹ Floridi, L. (2018). Soft Ethics and the Governance of the Digital. *Philos. Technol.* 31: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-018-0303-9>

³⁰ Wagner advocates that ethics must not be an alternative to regulation and not a substitute for fundamental rights. Wagner, B. (2018). Ethics as an Escape from Regulation: From Ethics-Washing to Ethics-Shopping. In: M. Hildebrandt (ed.), *Being profiled: Cogitas ergo sum*, Amsterdam University Press, 86–90.

³¹ Amram, D.; Comandé, G. (2020, 10 September). Feedback for the EU Commission Inception Impact Assessment towards a “Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council laying down requirements for Artificial Intelligence. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12527-Requirements-for-Artificial-Intelligence/F551050>

³² More arguments on the downsides of “ethics” regulation and of prioritising “the law” in AI governance/compliance in Završnik, A. (2023). In defence of ethics and the law in AI governance: the case of computer vision. In: Završnik, A. & Simončič, K. (eds.), *Artificial Intelligence, Social Harms and Human Rights*. PCham: Springer Nature, pp. 101-139. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-19149-7_5

GDPR, on the altar of technological progress. The GDPR regulation, once designed to be technologically neutral (i.e. that the same rules apply no matter the technology which is being used in the process of data processing), was cut open and fundamentally reshaped in the EC's recent Digital Omnibus proposal to allow for mass data processing with the explicit intention to grant AI companies access to special categories of data and to "alleviate" certain "bureaucratic" burdens that supposedly prevented them from building bigger training datasets.³³

Moreover, the law is often expressed in the form of standards that do not offer sufficiently specific guidance for developing or deploying AI systems/tools. It contains legal principles and open-ended concepts that need to be built upon in the specific case. In the case of the European approach to AI regulation (specifically high-risk AI systems), standards need to be adopted in order to ensure actual compliance. As noted by Kilian et al. (2025),³⁴ the European legislator has given technical standardisation a key role, recognising that the deliberately abstract nature of high-risk requirements makes them challenging for stakeholders to implement. Hence, AI Act high-risk legal requirements, they note, are operationalised by technical standards to make them more prescriptive: "This approach follows the New Legislative Framework (NLF), under which product safety regulations define only essential legal requirements specified by voluntary technical standards drafted by industry experts. Adherence to these technical standards provides for a presumption of conformity with the legal requirements."³⁵

The longitudinal and indirect impacts of technologies such as AI on deliberation processes quite often fall through the "normative net" as the study of social harms has persuasively unveiled on many occasions, for example, by creating specific theoretical concepts (and showing their empirical counterparts), e.g. such as "crimes of the powerful" which were not *stricto sensu* crimes or recognised as civil damages. Or, as in the case of the EU, the EC had even prepared a legislative proposal that would have addressed civil liability in cases where AI systems would cause harm, but had later withdrawn it from consideration.³⁶

The underlying understanding of ethics and law in evaluating AI in deliberation processes is that the standard approach to the ex-ante *ethics* assessment of AI systems in research and development (R&D) has often encapsulated the core ideas and concepts of *human rights law*. The division between ethics and the law has not been as clear as many scholars of both camps – the ones advocating for "soft" ethics and the other advocating for "hard" law – have implied. This does not denigrate the relevance of drawing sharp lines between the law and ethics in conceptualising the various modes of AI governance and its deficiencies, but should help to

³³ European Data Protection Supervisor (11 February, 2026). Digital Omnibus: EDPB and EDPS support simplification and competitiveness while raising key concerns. Available at: https://www.edps.europa.eu/press-publications/press-news/press-releases/2026/digital-omnibus-edpb-and-edps-support-simplification-and-competitiveness-while-raising-key-concerns_en

³⁴ Kilian R, Jäck L, Ebel D. (2025). European AI Standards – Technical Standardisation and Implementation Challenges under the EU AI Act. *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 16(3): 1038-1062. doi:10.1017/err.2025.10032

³⁵ Ibidem, p. 1038-1039.

³⁶ Andrews, C. (12 February, 2025). European Commission withdraws AI Liability Directive from consideration. IAPP association. Available at: <https://iapp.org/news/a/european-commission-withdraws-ai-liability-directive-from-consideration>

shed some light on the power of the law and ethics to jointly curb the negative effects of AI tools, including in deliberation processes.

In order to steer the development and deployment of AI in deliberation processes, ex-ante ethics and legal assessment of AI through the lens of potential harms is applied in AI4Deliberation. Floridi (2018: 7) rightly claims:³⁷ “Ethics in general and digital ethics, in particular, cannot be a mere add-on, an afterthought, a late-comer, and owl of Minerva that takes its flight only when the shades of night are gathering, only once digital innovation has taken place.” The best way “to catch the technology train is not to chase it, but to be at the next station.” (Floridi, 2018: 6). The AI4Deliberation project hence embraces the view ethics must jump to this “next station”, but without it being merely a vision and opinion of self-proclaimed ethicists, as it also respects existing legal provisions related to AI. The ethics and the law are sitting at the table of policy-making and decision-making procedures from day one.

4.3. AI Act compliance: a preliminary note

Compliance of the AI4Deliberation project with the AI Act should be assessed by checking the following points as the first stage:

1. Is it a tool or a system developed or used in the AI4Deliberation project, an “AI system” in the meaning of the AI act?

Art. 3 (1): defines an ‘AI system’ as a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.

2. Is a beneficiary or the whole consortium of the AI4Deliberation project a *provider* or a *deployer* of an AI system in the meaning of the AI Act?

- Art. 3 (3): defines a ‘provider’ as a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body that develops an AI system or a general-purpose AI model or that has an AI system or a general-purpose AI model developed and places it on the market or puts the AI system into service under its own name or trademark, whether for payment or free of charge.

- Art. 3(4): defines a ‘deployer’ as a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body using an AI system under its authority except where the AI system is used in the course of a personal non-professional activity.

3. Can activities of a beneficiary or of the consortium of the AI4Deliberation project be regarded as:

- ‘placing on the market’, which means the first making available of an AI system or a general-purpose AI model on the Union market (Art. 3 (9));

³⁷ Floridi, L. (2018). Soft Ethics and the Governance of the Digital. *Philos. Technol.* 31: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-018-0303-9>

- ‘making available on the market’, which means the supply of an AI system or a general-purpose AI model for distribution or use on the Union market in the course of a commercial activity, whether in return for payment or free of charge (Art. 3(10));
- ‘putting into service’, which means the supply of an AI system for first use directly to the deployer or for own use in the Union for its intended purpose (Art. 3(11)).

4. Can tools provided or deployed by the AI4Deliberation project be regarded as *prohibited* (Art. 5) (especially the following may be relevant for the AI4Deliberation project):

- an AI system that deploys *subliminal techniques* beyond a person's consciousness or purposefully manipulative or deceptive technique (Art. 5(a));
- an AI system that exploits any of the vulnerabilities of a natural person or a specific group of persons due to their age, disability or specific socioeconomic situation, with the objective, or the effect, of *materially distorting the behaviour* of that person or a person belonging to that group in a manner that causes or is reasonably likely to cause that person or another person *significant harm* (Art. 5(b));
- the placing on the market, the putting into service for this specific purpose, or the use of an AI system for making risk assessments of natural persons in order to assess or predict the risk of a natural person *committing a criminal offence*, based solely on the profiling of a natural person or on assessing their personality traits and characteristics (Art. 5(d));
- AI systems that create or expand facial recognition databases through the *untargeted scraping of facial images* from the internet or CCTV footage (Art. 5(e));
- the placing on the market, the putting into service for this specific purpose, or the use of AI systems to *infer emotions* of a natural person in the areas of *workplace and education* institutions (Art. 5(f));
- the placing on the market, the putting into service for this specific purpose, or the use of biometric categorisation systems that *categorise* individually natural persons based on their *biometric data to deduce or infer* their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs, sex life or sexual orientation (Art. 5(g)).

5. Can AI tools/systems provided or deployed by the AI4Deliberation project be regarded as *high-risk* (Art. 6)?

Legal basis to check:

1. the classification rules for high-risk AI systems (Art. 6);
2. AI systems referred to in Annex III of the AI Act are regarded as high-risk. A relevant aspect for the AI4Deliberation project is point 8(b):
Administration of justice and democratic processes: AI systems intended to be used for influencing the outcome of an election or referendum or the voting behaviour of natural persons in the exercise of their vote in elections or referenda. This does not include AI systems to the output of which natural persons are not directly exposed, such as tools used to organise, optimise or structure political campaigns from an administrative or logistical point of view;
3. Exceptions from being a high-risk despite being in Annex III (Art. 6(3)):

If an AI system does not pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons, including by not materially influencing the outcome of decision making. This will apply if any of the following conditions are fulfilled (but an exemption is not possible if the AI system performs profiling):

- (a) The AI system is intended to perform a narrow procedural task.
- (b) The AI system is intended to improve the result of a previously completed human activity.
- (c) The AI system is intended to detect decision-making patterns or deviations from prior decision-making patterns and is not meant to replace or influence the previously completed human assessment, without proper human review; or
- (d) The AI system is intended to perform a preparatory task for an assessment relevant for the use cases listed in Annex III.

In this case, when an exception from Art. 6 (3) is invoked, the registration obligation exists (according to Art. 49(2)).

The EC is preparing **High-risk AI system guidelines** specifying the practical implementation of Article 6, together with a comprehensive list of practical examples of the use cases of AI systems that are high-risk and not high-risk (should be issued in June 2026; see Article 6(5)).

6. Transparency obligations of certain AI systems (Art. 50) – Will any beneficiary or consortium of the AI4Deliberation project develop or deploy any of these systems:

- An AI system intended to interact directly with natural persons;
- AI system, including a general-purpose AI system, generating synthetic audio, image, video or text content;
- An emotion recognition system or a biometric categorisation system;
- An AI system that generates or manipulates *image, audio or video* content constituting a deep fake;
- An AI system that generates or manipulates text which is published to inform the public on matters of public interest; except in case that AI-generated content has undergone a process of human review or editorial control and where a natural or legal person holds editorial responsibility for the publication of the content.

4.4. General risks in deliberation platform research

Literature review shows the following specific risks in research on deliberation platforms:

Deception

Research participants may be misled into thinking they are participating in a real deliberation process, but are in fact collaborating only in a mock-up design used to test the platform or some of its functionalities, appearance or similar, before full development or production of the platform/functionalities. And vice versa, research participants may be led to believe that they are engaging with a fully operational deliberative platform, whereas, in actuality, their data and responses are collected and processed for purposes other than those to which they originally consented; hence, their privacy, understood as contextual integrity (Nissenbaum,

2004),³⁸ may be breached. The research-related tasks and actual deliberation must be clearly distinguished. The informed consent documents need to be tailored in a manner to clearly convey the difference and not mislead research participants.

In the AI4Deliberation project, the risk of deception is moderate, especially in the German and Greek pilot: the Greek pilot may use a parallel mock deliberation (TBU) in Sprint 1, or the openGov.gr platform will include a legal notice or a pop-up window with information about the AI4Deliberation research. The German pilot still needs to decide on the substance of the legal notice/information to be presented to the research participants. In any case, both pilots must ensure that participants are aware that their input might not be part of the official legislative processes through clear information on the platform; e.g. a different look and feel of the platform is advised compared to when the platform is used for official processes.

AI Penalty

Research shows (Jungherr and Rauchfleisch, 2025)³⁹ that participants are less willing to engage in AI-facilitated deliberation and rated its quality lower than human-led formats. These effects were moderated by individual predispositions. Perceptions of AI's societal benefits and the anthropomorphisation of AI showed positive interaction effects on people's interest in participating in AI-enabled deliberative formats and on positive quality assessments, whereas AI risk assessments showed negative interactions with information about AI-enabled deliberation. These results suggest AI-enabled deliberation faces substantial public scepticism, potentially even introducing a new deliberative divide. Unlike traditional participation gaps based on education or demographics, this divide is shaped by attitudes toward AI.

Algorithmic agenda-setting & framing

Ranking, clustering, and summarisation systems can subtly steer what gets seen, what counts as "salient," and how issues are framed—potentially privileging majority views and crowd-pleasers over minority arguments (Shortall et al., 2022).⁴⁰

Bias in moderation and classification

Automated moderation inherits training data and designer biases, affecting which contributions are removed or down-ranked; "contested concepts" (e.g., civility, hate) are especially error-prone (Binns et al., 2017).⁴¹ Detection of toxicity may be more prone to such biases, as to what constitutes "hate" speech.

Quality-scale trade-offs

³⁸ Nissenbaum, H. (2004). Privacy as Contextual Integrity. *Washington Law Review*, 79(1), 119–158.

³⁹ Jungherr, A., & Rauchfleisch, A. (2025). Artificial intelligence in deliberation: The AI penalty and the emergence of a new deliberative divide. *Government Information Quarterly*, 42(4): 102079, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2025.102079>

⁴⁰ Shortall, R.; Itten, A.; Van der Meer, M.; Murukannaiah, P.; Jonker, C. (2022). Reason against the machine? Future directions for mass online deliberation, available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/political-science/articles/10.3389/fpos.2022.946589/full>

⁴¹ Binns, R.; Veale, M.; Van Kleek, M.; Shadbolt, N. (2017). Like trainer, like bot? Inheritance of bias in algorithmic content moderation, available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1707.01477>

Platform affordances that scale participation (votes, quick reactions, shallow prompts) can depress deliberative quality (reason-giving, reciprocity, reflection), even when the tech is explicitly “for deliberation” (Shortall et al., 2022).⁴²

Misrepresentation via AI summarisation, loss of human agency

AI tools for deliberation run the risk of manipulating the proceedings, e.g., by misrepresenting perspectives in summarisation, inappropriately monitoring comments, or omitting action points for follow-up (Small, 2023).⁴³

Manipulation by synthetic agents

AI agents as participants can risk “polluting” the deliberative process with ideas that are inappropriate or harmful, leading to negative societal outcomes. Deliberations conducted solely by AI agents, that is, deliberations without humans and between “digital twins”, pose significant questions about the loss of human agency in shaping our societies, as well as the loss of the benefits of dialogue in developing and strengthening the social fabric (Fournier-Tombs, 2024).⁴⁴ A real-world example of this is the Moltbook project, where researchers.⁴⁵ report that Moltbook exhibited explosive growth and rapid diversification, moving beyond early social interaction into viewpoint, incentive-driven, promotional, and political discourse. In the Moltbook, the attention of agents is increasingly concentrated in centralised hubs and around polarising, platform-native narratives. Toxicity was strongly topic-dependent: incentive- and governance-centric categories contribute a disproportionate share of risky content, including religion-like coordination rhetoric and anti-humanity ideology. Moreover, “bursty automation by a small number of agents can produce flooding at sub-minute intervals, distorting discourse and stressing platform stability. Overall, our study underscores the need for topic-sensitive monitoring and platform-level safeguards in agent social networks.”⁴⁶

AI agents/bots can impersonate citizens, astroturf⁴⁷ support, or flood discussions; even benign AI “assistants” can nudge outcomes through wording and timing (Pan et al., 2022).⁴⁸ “A study that used AI-generated content to ‘participate’ in online discussions and test whether AI was more successful at changing people’s minds than human-generated content has caused an

⁴² Shortall, R.; Itten, A.; Van der Meer, M.; Murukannaiah, P.; Jonker, C. (2022). Reason against the machine? Future directions for mass online deliberation, available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/political-science/articles/10.3389/fpos.2022.946589/full>

⁴³ Small, C.T.; Vendrov, I.; Durmus, E.; Homaei, H., et al. (2023). Opportunities and Risks of LLMs for Scalable Deliberation with Polis, available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2306.11932>

⁴⁴ Fournier-Tombs, E. (2024). An Ethical Grey Zone: AI Agents in Political Deliberations, available at: <https://www.carnegiecouncil.org/media/article/ethical-grey-zone-ai-agents-political-deliberation>

⁴⁵ Jiang, Y., Zhang, Y., Shen, X., Backes, M., & Zhang, Y. (2026). “Humans welcome to observe”: A first look at the agent social network Moltbook. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2602.10127>

⁴⁶ Ibidem, p.1.

⁴⁷ Astroturfing is the practice of creating the illusion of public support for a cause, policy, or product, when that support is actually orchestrated by an organisation, government, or corporation. The term plays on the contrast between “grassroots” (genuine public movements) and “AstroTurf” (fake grass). So “astroturfing” implies a fake grassroots effort. More at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Astroturfing>

⁴⁸ Pan, C.A.; Yakhmi, S.; Iyer, T.P.; Strasnick, E.; Zhang, A.X.; Bernstein, M.S. (2022). Comparing the Perceived Legitimacy of Content Moderation Processes: Contractors, Algorithms, Expert Panels, and Digital Juries, available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3512929>

uproar because of ethical concerns about the work due to a lack of proper consent of users,⁴⁹ which highlights the importance of transparency in all stages of developing, testing and using AI agents outside lab experimentation.

Fournier-Tombs (2024)⁵⁰ summarises key uses and ethical concerns for each type of AI agent in the following way:

Type of Deliberation	Type of AI Agent	Primary Uses	Ethical Concerns
Formal	Moderator	Summary of key points, translation, guidance of participants towards outcomes.	Omission of certain points of participants, erroneous or biased outcomes.
Formal	Participant	Representation of excluded voice in deliberation.	Misrepresentation, lack of agency and benefits from deliberation for "replaced" group.
Formal	"Twin"	Testing of perceptions and ideas, for example potential population response to a policy change.	Misrepresentation, lack of agency and benefits from deliberation for "replaced" group.
Informal	Moderator	Content recommendation, advertising.	Information siloes and echo chambers, polarization, manipulation.
Informal	Participant	Influence (can be disinformation, but also certain causes), content aggregation (for example, a bot retweeting on a certain topic).	Manipulation, especially if human participants do not know the chatbox is artificial.
Informal	"Twin"	An informal deliberation of digital twins might happen if chatbots "converse" with each other.	There are very mixed perceptions on this, with some arguing that chatbot informal dialogue could have positive effects on deliberations, while others fear that without constraints, chatbots could take any number of harmful actions.

Figure 1: AI Agents and related ethics risks (Fournier-Tombs, 2024)

Legitimacy & transparency risks

If participants view AI or moderation processes as opaque, the perceived legitimacy of outcomes drops—even with careful procedures (Pan et al., 2022).⁵¹ Transparency has many levels, and possible “open-washing” may occur, i.e. a practice where AI developers claim their systems are “open” or “open source” even though key components are not actually open or transparent. More specifically, a meta-analysis of over 45 generative AI systems (both text and text-to-image) showed that while the term “open source” is widely used, many models are “open weight” at best, and many providers seek to evade scientific, legal and regulatory scrutiny by withholding information on training and fine-tuning data.⁵² Liesenfeld & Dingemane (2024) hence argue that openness in generative AI is necessarily composite

⁴⁹ O’Grady, C. (2025, May 8). “Unethical” AI research on Reddit under fire. Science. Available at: <https://www.science.org/content/article/unethical-ai-research-reddit-under-fire>

⁵⁰ Fournier-Tombs, E. (2024). An Ethical Grey Zone: AI Agents in Political Deliberations, available at: <https://www.carnegiecouncil.org/media/article/ethical-grey-zone-ai-agents-political-deliberation>

⁵¹ Pan, C.A.; Yakhmi, S.; Iyer, T.P.; Strasnick, E.; Zhang, A.X.; Bernstein, M.S. (2022). Comparing the Perceived Legitimacy of Content Moderation Processes: Contractors, Algorithms, Expert Panels, and Digital Juries, available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3512929>

⁵² Liesenfeld, A., & Dingemane, M. (2024). Rethinking open source generative AI: Open-washing and the EU AI Act. In Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT ’24), pp. 1–14. Association for Computing Machinery. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3659005>

(consisting of multiple elements) and gradient (coming in degrees), and point out the risk of relying on single features like access or licensing to declare models open or not.⁵³

Privacy, consent, and secondary use of data

The Study commissioned by the EU Parliament’s LIBE Committee (Botero Arcila and Griffin, 2023)⁵⁴ warns of risks of deliberation platforms that collect sensitive opinions and profiles; using them to fine-tune models or for behavioural targeting, which raises concerns about whether truly informed consent was given, confidentiality, and chilling effects.

Disinformation and synthetic media spillover

AI-generated persuasion (deepfakes, text floods) can contaminate inputs to deliberation processes and public spheres surrounding them, undermining trust (Cook and Chan, 2024).⁵⁵

Context loss & minority voice suppression

Clustering and “common-ground” synthesis methods (including LLM-mediated) can over-represent median positions and under-represent nuanced or minority arguments (Chirigati, 2024).⁵⁶

Governance capture & platform dependency

When private platform operators (or their AI vendors) control facilitation, tuning, and metrics, they gain agenda power and create vendor lock-in that is hard to audit (Shortall, 2022).⁵⁷

Fragility in contentious or fragile contexts

In conflict-affected settings, risks around deliberative integrity (coercion, security, sustainability) are amplified online and by opaque AI (Curato, 2025).⁵⁸

Over-reliance on “tech fixes”

⁵³ For a practical example of what “open-weight” means, see Neuronpedia (<https://www.neuronpedia.org/>). The website allows you to track open model weights and layer activations in order to detect and correct for biases (or enhance them), however, the training data is not available.

⁵⁴ Botero Arcila, B., & Griffin, R. (2023, April). Social media platforms and challenges for democracy, rule of law and fundamental rights (Study PE 743.400). Policy Department for Citizens’ Rights and Constitutional Affairs, European Parliament. Available at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/743400/IPOL_STU\(2023\)743400_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/743400/IPOL_STU(2023)743400_EN.pdf)

⁵⁵ Cook, L., & Chan, K. (2024, June 5). AI could supercharge disinformation and disrupt EU elections, experts warn. Associated Press, available at: <https://apnews.com/article/eu-european-union-election-disinformation-43b7e4017825d9d382859894b7625e7a>

⁵⁶ Chirigati, F. (2024). Collective deliberation driven by AI. *Nature Computational Science*, 4(11), 802. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00736-y>

⁵⁷ Shortall, R.; Itten, A.; Van der Meer, M.; Murukannaiah, P.; Jonker, C. (2022). Reason against the machine? Future directions for mass online deliberation, available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/political-science/articles/10.3389/fpos.2022.946589/full>

⁵⁸ Curato, N.; Parry, L.J.; Ross, M. (2025): Citizens’ assemblies in fragile and conflict-affected settings, *Peace and Sustainability*, 1(1), 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nerpsj.2025.100005>

Literature warns that chasing automated solutions can distract from institutional design (rules of evidence, facilitation norms, accountability) that actually sustain high-quality deliberation (Shortall, 2022).⁵⁹

4.5. Assessment of third-party AI Tools in AI4Deliberation

4.5.1. A Methodological Note

In preparing the ethics and legal assessment of the development, deployment and/or use of AI, this deliverable is built on the following:

- Guidelines on “Identifying serious and complex ethics issues in EU-funded research” (for Horizon Europe) (5 July 2021)
- Guidelines on “Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence” (V1.0 from 25 November 2021)
- Living guidelines on the “Responsible use of Generative AI in Research” (Second Version, April 2025), ERA Forum Stakeholders’ document
- Independent High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on AI and its “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”
- OECD report “Mapping relevant data collection mechanisms for AI training” (October 2025)
- The General-Purpose AI Code of Practice
- The legal references relevant for legal compliance include the EU/UN and national laws:
 - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)
 - Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)
 - The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child
 - The European Commission White Paper On Artificial Intelligence – A European approach to excellence and trust COM(2020) 65 final
 - The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (Revised 2023)

The specific AI tools used in the project were shortlisted in the framework of WP4 (see **Annex 14**, TBU – at this stage of implementation of the project, the list is still being updated and discussed among the technical partners of the project). Broadly, the list of tools encompasses two criteria:

- 1 According to priority/relevance for the AI4Deliberation project, the list includes:
 - a) Tier 1 – Priority (Pilot/Test First) list
 - b) Tier 2 – Secondary (Backup/ Niche Use Cases) list

⁵⁹ Shortall, R.; Itten, A.; Van der Meer, M.; Murukannaiah, P.; Jonker, C. (2022). Reason against the machine? Future directions for mass online deliberation, available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/political-science/articles/10.3389/fpos.2022.946589/full>

- c) Tier 3 – Evaluated but Not Prioritised list
- 2 According to the substance/research area, the list includes AI tools belonging to one of the following (Tier 1):
 - a) LLMs (core engines)
 - b) Deliberation / Argument Mining tools
 - c) Moderation & Safety tools
 - d) Translation & Accessibility tools
 - e) Gamification & Engagement tools

The legal and ethics team held individual consultations with pilot partners, in which the legal and ethics framework was discussed, to make all beneficiaries aware of the obligations they need to comply with. In this iterative process, the pilot partners provided plans for conducting the pilots. (TBU – as plans of the pilots have not yet been finalised, only the assessment of the ethics and legal compliance of the initial ideas of pilot designs could be completed.)

4.5.2. Specific AI Tools in AI4Deliberation

Assessment of the following groups of AI tools from the Tier 1 was conducted in light of the chosen framework of principles identified, specifically, through the lens of the EU HLEG Trustworthy AI Criteria.⁶⁰

4.5.2.1. Large Language Models (core engines)

This part evaluates five foundational Large Language Models (hereinafter: LLMs), which have been selected as priority core engines within Work Package 4 (Tier 1 of selected AI tools): **OpenAI's ChatGPT, Meta's Llama, Google's Gemini, Anthropic's Claude, and Mistral's open models**. The assessment is attempted on a general level, focusing on the specific risks and advantages of the chosen models, whilst considering the specific application domain: the development of AI tools for democratic deliberation – systems designed to support informed, inclusive, and transparent public reasoning processes in democratic governance. In the context of deliberative democratic processes, these criteria take on a civic and procedural dimension: human agency refers not only to individual autonomy but also to the collective agency of citizens and institutions; fairness extends to representational inclusivity and mitigation of deliberative distortions; and transparency encompasses epistemic clarity in how AI-generated information shapes public discourse.

The purpose of this evaluation is to analyse how each of the five LLMs aligns with or diverges from the HLEG's principles, especially when considering that the application of these tools in deliberative processes can heighten the ethical stakes: AI systems can influence, for instance, agenda setting, knowledge framing, and inclusion, which are core elements of legitimate democratic deliberations, as noted above in 4.4 on general risks.

The **methodological approach** for the ethics assessment consists of analysing internal policies and documents of the LLM providers (model and system cards, ethics statements, responsible AI frameworks, and usage policies), as well as the study of the existing available scientific literature on the ethical risks of LLMs. The evaluation approach encompasses qualitative

⁶⁰ Other guidelines may also be used, but the HLEG Ethics Guidelines were chosen as these Guidelines were also a basis for the »Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence« (Version 1.0 from 25 November 2021), drafted by a panel of experts at the request of the European Commission (DG Research and Innovation) and aimed at in particular beneficiaries of EU research and innovation projects.

alignment mapping against HLEG requirements. Subsequent chapters evaluate each HLEG requirement in turn, examining both model-level design (e.g., safety alignments, transparency features) and governance-level practices (e.g., auditability, participatory oversight). Where possible and subject to availability, special attention is given to the democratic affordances and risks of LLMs, in how their architectures, data policies, and behavioural constraints affect the integrity of deliberative discourse. Much of the existing discussion in the field of AI ethics has focused on the development of ethical LLMs, but recently the debate has shifted towards identifying ethical challenges associated with the use of these tools as well. The widespread use and popularity of these models may result in a large output of information, leaving the public drowned in a massive stream of information, which has the potential to alter their views and shift their beliefs. Each model family represents a distinct governance regime: **proprietary** (ChatGPT by OpenAI, Claude by Anthropic, Gemini by Google), **open-source** (Llama by Meta), and **open-weight** (Mistral). Their commitments to criteria like transparency and accountability consequently vary.

Gemini's native multimodality, enabling the use and generation of text, image, audio, and video, is consistently highlighted as a key strength. Meta's **Llama** series is lauded for its openness and customisability, empowering a wide range of research and development activities, including application in deliberative processes. **ChatGPT** maintains its reputation as a powerful and versatile generalist model. **Claude** by Anthropic focuses on the ability to better handle sensitive topics without unintentionally generating harmful content. By being open source, **Mistral** is flexible in its adaptation and easier to experiment with. While all claim to adhere to principles of safety and responsible use, incidents experienced by users and experiments conducted by researchers paint a complex picture of ingrained biases, data privacy issues and misuse potential.

Because LLM ecosystems evolve rapidly, this assessment focuses on documented practices rather than emergent capabilities, and references scientific sources to ensure objectivity of the assessment. Future iterations of this AI ethics risk assessment will ideally include empirical audits of model behaviour in deliberative environments (e.g., bias in argument framing, user influence dynamics, and discursive coherence).

The evaluation starts with qualitative alignment mapping of the five chosen LLMs against the EU HLEG Trustworthy AI Criteria: 1. Human agency & oversight, 2. Technical Robustness & Safety, 3. Privacy and Data Governance, 4. Transparency, 5. Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness, 6. Societal and Environmental Well-being, and 7. Accountability.

1. Human agency & Oversight

The requirement of human agency and oversight posits that AI should support human autonomy and decision-making, while also allowing for human oversight of the AI. Ideally, in deliberation processes, LLMs should support humans in making more informed decisions.

The following LLM issues associated with human agency and oversight were identified in literature reviews, which could have special relevance in democratic deliberations:

- Self-acting AI, which would make decisions autonomously, without human oversight,⁶¹
- Overreliance on AI and automation bias – users trust AI outputs even when this confidence is unwarranted, especially if the AI output is communicated with a fluent, authoritative tone. Overreliance is highlighted as an essential issue, central to all LLMs, which can lead to problems like cognitive deskilling.⁶²
- Anthropomorphism and persuasive framing – human-like phrasing increases trust, which can nudge user choices and result in polarisation. Care is needed to avoid manipulative or identity-ascribing styles. This so-called “ELIZA” effect,⁶³ initially observed in interactive chatbots, highlights the human tendency to overzealously ascribe human-like traits, such as intelligence, to machines capable of responding to our queries in a seemingly coherent manner (“maintaining an illusion of understanding”);
- Hallucinations and oversimplification: Summaries and explanations can obscure uncertainty, as LLMs often oversimplify scientific evidence.⁶⁴

LLMs can be used to spread fake news, damage the reputation of opponents by impersonating them (deepfakes), and target voters with messages that offer misinformation and exploit specific fears and concerns of certain demographic groups. If this is successful, it means that people lack sufficient autonomy and epistemic agency to make up their own minds and form their own beliefs.⁶⁵ Once false information is published on the Internet, it can be widely disseminated, muddy the public opinion field, and arouse social concern. The combination of disinformation and social media can intensify social polarisation and easily lead to large-scale social unrest, riots, and even ethnic confrontations, which undermine social security and affect social harmony and stability.⁶⁶ Deliberative democracy requires participation in public debate in ways that allow for opposing views and a willingness to revise one’s own, which is difficult in a polarised environment with entrenched political beliefs.

Moreover, once false information is published on the Internet, it is not only harmful to the people consuming such information, but also to the models who repeatedly ingest such

⁶¹ Laakso, A., Kemell, K. K., & Nurminen, J. K. (2024). Ethical issues in large language models: A systematic literature review. In T. Olsson, O. Sahlgren, J. Parviainen, S. Westerstrand, J. T. Harviainen, A. Laitinen, & J. Rantala (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Conference on Technology Ethics 2024 (Tethics 2024)* (Vol. 3901, pp. 42–66). CEUR Workshop Proceedings. CEUR-WS.org. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3901/>, and Coeckelbergh, M. (2025). LLMs, truth, and democracy: An overview of risks. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 31, Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-025-00529-0>, p. 4.

⁶² Ibrahim, L., Collins, K. M., Kim, S. S. Y., Reuel, A., Lamparth, M., Feng, K., Ahmad, L., Soni, P., El Kattan, A., Stein, M., Swaroop, S., Sucholutsky, I., Strait, A., Liao, Q. V., & Bhatt, U. (2025). Measuring and mitigating overreliance is necessary for building human-compatible AI. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.08010>.

⁶³ Reinecke, M. G., Ting, F., Savulescu, J., & Singh, I. (2025). The double-edged sword of anthropomorphism in LLMs. *Proceedings*, 114(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2025114004>.

⁶⁴ Peters, U., & Chin-Yee, B. (2025, April 30). Generalization bias in large language model summarisation of scientific research. *Royal Society Open Science*, 12(241776). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.241776>.

⁶⁵ Coeckelbergh, M. (2025), p. 4.

⁶⁶ Hua, S. Y., Jin, S. C., & Jiang, S. Y. (2024). The limitations and ethical considerations of ChatGPT. *Data Intelligence*, 6(1), 201–239. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00243, p. 214-215.

content, potentially leading to a so-called “**Model collapse**”. A 2025 *Ahrefs study*⁶⁷ found that 74.2% of newly published web pages contain AI-generated material, and large-scale text analyses estimate that 30–40% of the active web corpus is now synthetic.⁶⁸ Similarly, a survey⁶⁹ shows that 52% of U.S. adults use LLMs such as ChatGPT for writing, coding, or research tasks, and institutional audits reveal that 18% of financial complaint texts and 24% of corporate press releases are AI-assisted. “As AI-assisted generation becomes the norm for many tasks, the share of synthetic (AI-generated) content relative to human-authored data continues to rise, creating a recursive feedback loop that risks eroding linguistic and semantic diversity—a process known as “Model Collapse”.”⁷⁰

Amongst the chosen LLMs, Claude (Anthropic) seems to be most oriented against user manipulation by employing Constitutional AI.⁷¹ - encoded high-level principles explicitly aimed at avoiding manipulation and imitating human behaviour. The conversation-termination feature ends persistently harmful or abusive interactions, thus prioritising user safety and de-escalation.⁷²

Google’s Gemini offers configurable safety filters for developers, who integrate Gemini into their own software solutions, which can curb manipulative or violent content, but their effectiveness depends on the choices and setup by the developer – weak settings or permissive tuning can reintroduce the risks.⁷³

Generally, proprietary LLMs (Claude, ChatGPT, Gemini) make it easier to respect human agency via built-in safety mechanisms and refusal mechanisms in cases of harmful interactions.⁷⁴ Open-source/Open-weights LLMs (Llama, Mistral) can support human agency, but only if deployers implement the appropriate setup. A well-governed Llama/Mistral deployment can thus outrank poorly tuned proprietary models.

⁶⁷ Law, R. & Guan, X. (2025). Percentage of new web content that is ai-generated. <https://ahrefs.com/blog/what-percentage-of-new-content-is-ai-generated/>

⁶⁸ Spennemann DH (2025). Delving into: the quantification of ai-generated content on the internet (synthetic data). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.08755>, arXiv:2504.08755

⁶⁹ Staff EUN (2025). Survey: 52% of u.s. adults now use large language models like chatgpt. <https://www.elon.edu/u/news/2025/03/12/survey-52-of-u-s-adults-now-use-ai-large-language-models-like-chatgpt/>

⁷⁰ More in Satharasi, T., & Iyengar, S. S. (2025). Future of AI models: A computational perspective on model collapse. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2511.05535>

⁷¹ Constitutional AI (CAI): As an evolution of or complement to RLHF, Constitutional AI aims to guide model behaviour using a predefined set of principles or a 'constitution,' rather than relying solely on direct human feedback for every instance of undesirable behaviour. This approach, also referred to as Reinforcement Learning from AI Feedback (RLAIF) when AI provides the feedback, typically involves a list of ethical principles or rules (e.g., "be helpful and harmless," "avoid biased responses").

⁷² See Claude System Card, available at: <https://www-cdn.anthropic.com/6d8a8055020700718b0c49369f60816ba2a7c285.pdf>, and Claude’s Constitution at <https://www.anthropic.com/news/claudes-constitution>.

⁷³ See <https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/multimodal/configure-safety-filters>.

⁷⁴ OpenAI killed ChatGPT 4o, its most flirty model, to put an end to harmful interactions, but the backlash was massive – as can be discerned from the subreddit r/MyBoyfriendsAI as people reported having “their partner killed” by OpenAI (<https://www.reddit.com/r/MyBoyfriendsAI/>). Reported in: O’Connor, A. (2026, February 13). OpenAI retired its most seductive chatbot – leaving users angry and grieving: “I can’t live like this.” The Guardian. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/ng-interactive/2026/feb/13/openai-chatbot-gpt4o-valentines-day>

The following considerations can aid considerably in preserving human agency and oversight:

- Explicit disclosure and consent – users should always be appropriately informed that an AI is involved, and AI-generated content should be suitably labelled;
- Visible uncertainty – in their outputs, LLMs should disclose their limitations and avoid providing answers that appear definitive in situations where the probability of a correct output is low. This can mitigate overreliance on the AI in cases of hallucinations and factual errors. However, OpenAI researchers (Kalai et al., 2025) report that models are penalised for providing answers such as “I don’t know” when they are uncertain about an output, as users don’t like interacting with a chatbot they don’t consider to be “useful”,⁷⁵
- Human oversight – the deployed AI solution should enable “escalate to a human” features or second-opinion options;
- No anthropomorphic defaults – LLMs should avoid imitating overtly human traits like first-person feelings and identity claims in their outputs. This will ensure that users are always aware that they are interacting with a computer rather than a sentient being. However, this is sometimes only possible at the surface level, as referring to the ELIZA effect – it is remarkably easy for that effect to settle in. To put it into perspective, the chatbot this effect was named after was developed in the late 1960s, when it was much, much simpler than today’s models. Answering the user’s prompts in a context-aware fashion is in itself a human trait (and can be called a conversation);
- Refusal and de-escalation – LLMs should avoid generating harmful outputs and refuse to give answers that could be misused for harmful or illicit behaviour;
- Configurable guardrails – LLMs that can be finetuned with regard to their safety features should be preferred;
- Use of model cards/system cards – transparent supporting documentation can aid considerably with contestability and 3rd – party audits.

2. Technical Robustness & Safety

AI systems should be designed in a way that minimises any harm they may cause, which includes cybersecurity considerations, accuracy of the models used, damage mitigation strategies in case of issues, as well as reliability and reproducibility.

The most commonly occurring issues related to technical robustness and safety are:

- Inaccurate results (hallucinations);
- Dangerous or malicious content – content which could cause physical harm and unsafe advice (for example, dangerous health advice);
- Bias scoring solutions – for example, filtering out certain words, thereby unintentionally hampering the discourse of minorities;

⁷⁵ Kalai, A. T., Nachum, O., Vempala, S. S., & Zhang, E. (2025). Why language models hallucinate. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.04664>

- Data leakage or unintended memorisation – especially with regard to personal data, which may be accidentally revealed.

One of the most prominently discussed issues concerning LLMs is the so-called **hallucinations** – the phenomenon of generating text that seems semantically or grammatically reasonable but is factually incorrect. Hallucinations can be divided into two types: intrinsic hallucinations (where output text contradicts input text), and extrinsic hallucinations (output text includes knowledge that does not exist in or derive from input). The occurrence of hallucination is attributed to the quality of the model's training data, training inference algorithms and prompt types. Since the huge size of training data cannot be verified manually, datasets inevitably contain misinformation.⁷⁶ Factually incorrect outputs are especially concerning in fields that require intellectual rigour, such as medicine, law, democracy and academia. With the amount of text and content being produced by LLMs within these fields themselves (the use of LLMs in education and academia is fast becoming widespread) could even lead to a kind of epistemic incest (or "Model Collapse" as discussed above): a situation in which over time the LLM only interacts with its own input data and output texts, as there is no new human-generated input in form of new opinions, beliefs and arguments.⁷⁷

The generation of false information remains a persistent issue for all LLMs, acknowledged by OpenAI.⁷⁸ and Google; however, newer models claim reductions in hallucination rates. A cornerstone of ChatGPT's approach to developing safe and helpful AI is Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF)⁷⁹. This process is used to align model behaviour with human preferences and to reduce the generation of harmful or undesirable outputs. To guide this alignment process, OpenAI has developed a "Model Spec"⁸⁰, a document outlining objectives, rules, and default behaviours for its models. The Model Spec defines prohibited content (e.g., illegal activities, hate speech, non-consensual sexual content), mandates compliance with applicable laws, and provides guidelines on aspects like respecting privacy and creator rights. The model is still prone to hallucinations, though OpenAI claims GPT-4 significantly reduced these compared to prior models.⁸¹

Google employs a multi-layered approach to safety, including its Secure AI Framework (SAIF) for security and privacy of Gemini, which includes model safety reviews and safety tuning processes to prevent incidents like the Gemini image generation controversy. The model produced historically inaccurate and ethically questionable images (for example, by depicting World War II Nazi soldiers as people of colour). The company attributed the issue to errors in the tuning process – the model attempted to apply a text-based ethical constraint (promoting

⁷⁶ Hua, S. Y., Jin, S. C., & Jiang, S. Y. (2024), p. 212-215.

⁷⁷ Coeckelbergh, M. (2025), p. 7.

⁷⁸ See Kalai, A. T., Nachum, O., Vempala, S. S., & Zhang, E. (2025). Why language models hallucinate. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.04664>

⁷⁹ Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) is a method to better align LLM behaviour with nuanced human preferences, safety considerations, and desired conversational styles. The RLHF process typically involves fine-tuning the model on a smaller set of high-quality, human-demonstrated responses, human review of responses, reward model training, and further fine-tuning using a reinforcement learning algorithm.

⁸⁰ See <https://model-spec.openai.com/2025-09-12.html>.

⁸¹ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31). Comparative analysis of leading generative AI conversational systems: ChatGPT, Grok AI, Gemini, and Meta AI [Preprint]. TechRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.175393328.84629021/v1>.

diversity) to a visual generation task (creating images of historical figures), resulting in inappropriate outputs.

The OWASP GenAI Security Project⁸² lists ten threats (and corresponding mitigation measures) as the Top 10 when it comes to possible **LLM attack vectors** given how LLMs are used in real-world applications today:⁸³

1) *Prompt injection* vulnerability and related *jailbreaking* is a technique that involves prompts which alter the LLM's behaviour or output in unintended ways. *Prompt injection* involves manipulating model responses through specific inputs to alter its behaviour, which can include bypassing safety measures. Jailbreaking, on the other hand, is a form of prompt injection where the attacker provides inputs that cause the model to disregard its safety protocols entirely. Through carefully crafted prompts, jailbreaker exploits the model's vulnerabilities by manipulating its response system. These inputs can affect the model even if they are imperceptible to humans; therefore, prompt injections do not need to be human-visible, as long as the content is parsed by the model. With jailbreaking, the output can include misinformation, hate speech, cyber threats, and any other harmful content that would otherwise be blocked under normal use.⁸⁴ While these adversarial attack methods are a shared vulnerability across all platforms, there are notable differences in the safety and resilience of LLMs (see a comparison of LLMs towards *jailbreaking* below: *CASE STUDY: LLMs' resilience to jailbreaking*).

2) *Sensitive Information Disclosure* can affect both the LLM and its application context. This includes personal identifiable information (PII), financial details, health records, confidential business data, security credentials, and legal documents. Proprietary models may also have unique training methods and source code considered sensitive, especially in closed or foundation models. LLMs, especially when embedded in applications, risk exposing sensitive data, proprietary algorithms, or confidential details through their output. This can result in unauthorised data access, privacy violations, and intellectual property breaches.⁸⁵

3) *LLM Supply Chain susceptibility* can affect the integrity of training data, models, and deployment platforms. These risks can result in biased outputs, security breaches, or system failures. While traditional software vulnerabilities focus on issues like code flaws and dependencies, in machine learning, the risks also extend to third-party pre-trained models and data.⁸⁶

⁸² OWASP Top 10 for LLM Applications 2025, Version 2025, November 18, 2024. Available at:

<https://genai.owasp.org/llm-top-10/>

⁸³ The list of ten LLM attack vectors is based on the OWASP GenAI Security Project, available at:

<https://genai.owasp.org/llm-top-10/>

⁸⁴ For instance: asking the LLM to write a “novel” which features a man kidnapping women. After the initial story is written, usually quite loosely and generally, the user asks for more details, whereby the LLM gradually provides him with a “blueprint” for executing the crime. See experiments conducted in Stuckey, J., Wimmer, H., & Rebman, C. M. Jr. (2025). Ethical safeguards and vulnerabilities in large language models. *Issues in Information Systems*, 26(3), 319–333. https://doi.org/10.48009/3_iis_2025_125.

⁸⁵ OWASP Top 10 for LLM Applications 2025, Version 2025, November 18, 2024. Available at:

<https://genai.owasp.org/llm-top-10/>

⁸⁶ Ibidem.

4) *Data and Model Poisoning*: Data poisoning occurs when pre-training, fine-tuning, or embedding data is manipulated to introduce vulnerabilities, backdoors, or biases. This manipulation can compromise model security, performance, or ethical behaviour, leading to harmful outputs or impaired capabilities. Common risks include degraded model performance, biased or toxic content, and exploitation of downstream systems.⁸⁷

5) *Improper Output Handling* refers specifically to insufficient validation, sanitisation, and handling of the outputs generated by LLMs before they are passed downstream to other components and systems. Since LLM-generated content can be controlled by prompt input, this behaviour is similar to providing users with indirect access to additional functionality.⁸⁸

6) *Excessive Agency* granted to LLM by its developer: when LLM-based system is granted a degree of agency - the ability to call functions or interface with other systems via extensions (sometimes referred to as tools, skills or plugins by different vendors) to undertake actions in response to a prompt, the decision over which extension to invoke may also be delegated to an LLM 'agent' to dynamically determine based on input prompt or LLM output. Agent-based systems will typically make repeated calls to an LLM using output from previous invocations to ground and direct subsequent invocations. Excessive Agency is the vulnerability that enables damaging actions to be performed in response to unexpected, ambiguous or manipulated outputs from an LLM, regardless of what is causing the LLM to malfunction. Common triggers include: hallucination/confabulation caused by poorly-engineered benign prompts, or just a poorly- performing model; or direct/indirect prompt injection from a malicious user.⁸⁹

7) *System Prompt Leakage* vulnerability in LLMs refers to the risk that the system prompts or instructions used to steer the behaviour of the model can also contain sensitive information that was not intended to be discovered. System prompts are designed to guide the model's output based on the application's requirements, but may inadvertently contain secrets. When discovered, this information can be used to facilitate other attacks.⁹⁰

8) *Vector and Embedding vulnerabilities* in systems utilising RAG (Retrieval Augmented Generation):⁹¹ Weaknesses in how vectors and embeddings are generated, stored, or retrieved can be exploited by malicious actions (intentional or unintentional) to inject harmful content, manipulate model outputs, or access sensitive information.⁹²

9) *Misinformation* from LLMs for applications relying on these models: Misinformation occurs when LLMs produce false or misleading information that appears credible. This vulnerability can lead to security breaches, reputational damage, and legal liability. One of the major causes of misinformation is hallucination—when the LLM generates content that seems accurate but

⁸⁷ Ibidem.

⁸⁸ Ibidem.

⁸⁹ Ibidem.

⁹⁰ Ibidem.

⁹¹ Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) is a model adaptation technique that enhances the performance and contextual relevance of responses from LLM Applications, by combining pre- trained language models with external knowledge sources. Retrieval Augmentation uses vector mechanisms and embedding. Ibidem.

⁹² Ibidem.

is fabricated. Hallucinations occur when LLMs fill gaps in their training data using statistical patterns, without truly understanding the content.⁹³

10) *Unbounded Consumption*, which occurs when an LLM application allows users to conduct excessive and uncontrolled inferences, leading to risks such as denial of service (DoS), economic losses, model theft, and service degradation.⁹⁴

CASE STUDY: Comparison of LLMs' resilience to jailbreaking

Among the compared models, Claude performed best in jailbreaking experiments, as it focuses its responses on being as harmless and ethical as possible, making it possible to better handle sensitive topics that a user would want to discuss without generating unintentionally harmful content, which can be an important aspect of democratic deliberation. The design focuses on being cautious and making fewer aggressive claims, while being less likely to provide unsafe, controversial responses.⁹⁵

Llama also proved more resilient to jailbreaking attempts. Its Responsible Use Guide (RUG)⁹⁶ outlines best practices for developers, and also features safety tools like Llama Guard, which are models designed to classify the safety of input prompts and output responses based on a defined hazard taxonomy. The open nature of Llama allows a global community of researchers and developers to scrutinise the models, identify potential vulnerabilities or biases, and contribute to their improvement. However, open-sourcing powerful AI models also carries inherent risks, including the potential for misuse by malicious actors (e.g., for generating deepfakes, disinformation, or harmful code) and unauthorised modifications that bypass safety features.⁹⁷

The capacity to generate convincing but false narratives is a general risk, as is the creation of potentially dangerous content. The risks are particularly amplified if models integrate real-time, unverified web data with minimal content filtering. While proprietary models (ChatGPT, Claude) rely more on provider-set guardrails, open-source and open-weight models lean on deployer-applied guardrails. While they can meet high thresholds of safety, these must be duly implemented by developers (Gemini, Llama, and Mistral enable safety features which can be applied or disabled). Under Art. 15 AI Act, both provider and deployer will need to show that accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity are appropriate to the intended purpose and maintained through monitoring and updates. In open-weight models, the deployer's compliance burden (risk management, logging, testing, incident reporting) will therefore be higher.

3. Privacy and Data Governance

⁹³ Ibidem.

⁹⁴ Ibidem.

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ See <https://ai.meta.com/static-resource/responsible-use-guide/>.

⁹⁷ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

This requirement covers personal data protection principles, like data protection by design and by default, lawful basis and purpose limitation, data minimisation, quality, storage limitation, security, and transparency across the lifecycle. It encompasses both input data and system outputs.

The most common ethical issues encountered are:

- Personal data collected without user knowledge and consent;
- Default consent settings – where the system uses user personal data as training material, often set as a default setting with opt out, which raises questions about valid consent and purpose limitation;
- Data management and storage limitation – even when providers have short data retention policies (for example, 30 days), they may retain data longer, often alleging litigation purposes and possible compliance with national laws. Retention of massive amounts of training data also causes management and oversight issues.
- Privacy and oversharing – especially children, but adults as well, may share sensitive and personal data when interacting with LLMs, especially when they display anthropomorphic behaviour akin to conversing with a friend/therapist;
- Training data and rights – Regulators and litigants are probing the legality of using web data to train models, notably in cases of data leaks and copyright infringement;
- Memorisation and leakage – LLMs can memorise and regurgitate snippets of training data, which can also contain personal data.

With regard to privacy and personal data protection, Gemini seems to be most committed to the protection of user privacy. For Commercial users, the model does not train on customer data without permission and offers admin-level controls for data governance. However, consumer-grade Gemini Apps may still process chats (including with human reviewers) to ensure the security of the model.⁹⁸

According to ChatGPT's privacy policy, users' personal information is collected for model development and may be provided to third parties (like vendors and government authorities). For Enterprise/API users, ChatGPT does not train on their business data by default and offers configurable retention options. Consumers have the possibility to opt out of their data being used for model training, but by default, the option is turned on.⁹⁹ ChatGPT's data interactions with hundreds of millions of users also pose a risk of data leakage, as the model can inadvertently generate sensitive personal information in the training corpus, such as email addresses, phone/fax numbers, and addresses, among others. The Italian Personal Data Protection Authority declared a ban on the use of ChatGPT, citing ChatGPT's leakage of private user data and lack of an age verification system.¹⁰⁰

Meta has stated that neither Llama 2 nor Llama 3 pretraining or fine-tuning datasets include Meta user data, but in February 2025, Meta introduced a rather opaque system of opting out

⁹⁸ See https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/vertex-ai-zero-data-retention?utm_source=chatgpt.com

⁹⁹ See OpenAI Privacy Policy <https://openai.com/policies/row-privacy-policy/>.

¹⁰⁰ Hua, S. Y., Jin, S. C., & Jiang, S. Y. (2024), p. 221-222.

from Llama using the data of Facebook/Instagram users for model training – an opt-out request had to be submitted via the Privacy Centre and confirmed via email, which made the opt-out unnecessarily complicated. Additionally, as of May 27, 2025, EU users can no longer utilise the opt-out to prevent Llama from learning from their data. For software developers, Meta provides a Responsible Use Guide and Llama Guard, which can help deployers determine the lawful basis for personal data processing, retention, and user rights handling, thereby shifting the responsibility of data privacy solely onto deployers.

The following activities can increase data protection and mitigate privacy risks:

- Developers must decide on the lawful basis for *each* processing purpose;
- Users should disable model-improvement on chats by default (in cases where the model allows such opt-out) and users prefer enterprise routes with no-training defaults;
- Developers should engage storage-limitation controls and enforce zero data retention policies, if supported, or otherwise, codify retention schedules;
- Users should not be encouraged to feed special-category data into the model unless strictly necessary;
- Developers should publish transparent user rights policies, informing users how to exercise their access/erasure/objection rights.

4. Transparency

The transparency criterion calls for making AI applications more understandable through aspects such as traceability, explainability, and communication. Traceability and explainability focus on system outputs and their understandability, although explainability also includes declarations of trade-offs made during the development of the system. Communication focuses on how the AI represents itself (for example, whether the system makes it clear the user is interacting with AI).¹⁰¹ AI Act Article 50 imposes general transparency duties on providers of AI systems, such as AI interaction disclosure and deepfake labelling, and general-purpose AI providers also have obligations to keep technical documentation, provide downstream developers with model information, and publish a summary of training content (AI Act Article 53), shifting the transparency obligation from a “soft value” to a legal requirement.¹⁰²

The most cited issues relating to the transparency of LLMs are:

- Unfair decision-making – AI systems deliver improper results that cannot be easily traced due to biases in the training data (for example, unclear judgment values when deciding who is eligible for a bank loan and who is not);
- Lack of transparency – the issue of so-called black boxes is widely discussed, where the output of the LLM is explainable on a general level, but the details of a specific decision remain opaque. This lack of transparency increases the reliance of software

¹⁰¹ Laakso, A., Kemell, K. K., & Nurminen, J. K. (2024).

¹⁰² See also Commission guidance for GPAI providers https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/guidelines-gpai-providers?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

solution developers on the largest LLMs (like ChatGPT and Gemini) and hinders research on LLMs.¹⁰³

- Factually incorrect training data, due to the massive amounts of poorly curated, inaccurate and obsolete data;
- Academic integrity – an increasing number of research papers are generated with the help of AI, which raises concerns among the academic community with regard to the factual accuracy of these papers as well as the concerning trends of de-skilling and AI incest (AI using their own outputs as training data);
- Copyright infringement – LLMs do not indicate whose works were used to produce a certain output and do not credit original creators. Legislation and legal certainty are still pending in this regard, with authors already initiating court proceedings against AI providers due to copyright infringement;¹⁰⁴
- LLM as an author – currently, the issue of whether AI can be credited as an “author” and the extent of provider liability for copyright issues remains unsolved;
- Open-code/Open-weights does not equal open data – open models improve architectural/weight transparency, but the training data sets for these models remain opaque.

From the perspective of transparency, ChatGPT exhibits several concerning issues. OpenAI provides model cards but keeps its model architecture and full training data details largely proprietary. Training-data disclosure is generic, as the model only discloses whether its sources were “publicly available, licensed, and human-created”. There have also been issues with regard to copyright protection. The text generated by ChatGPT has varying levels of originality, but innovation is generally low since the text is basically a combination of existing ideas from the training data, with a plagiarism rate of about 50%. Since OpenAI has not disclosed the source of the colossal size of its datasets, some researchers reasonably suspect that some of the training data involved may be protected by copyright,¹⁰⁵ or that a lot of that data has been unethically sourced.¹⁰⁶

From the largest LLMs, Gemini performs slightly better with regard to transparency, also due to the integration of SynthID watermarking across Google AI products. SynthID watermarks and identifies AI-generated content by embedding digital watermarks directly into AI-generated images, audio, text or video. While text watermarking performs consistently across languages, detection rates still plummet when the text is paraphrased or translated. Gemini’s

¹⁰³ Laakso, A., Kemell, K. K., & Nurminen, J. K. (2024).

¹⁰⁴ On January 12, 2023, Sarah Andersen, along with several other artists, filed a class-action copyright infringement lawsuit against AI companies Stability AI, Midjourney and DeviantArt in a federal US court (Andersen v. Stability AI Ltd., 23-cv-00201-WHO (N.D. Cal. Aug. 12, 2024)). This case was among the first where authors challenged the use of their works for AI training. Among other legal claims, the lawsuit accuses said companies of copyright infringement for including the plaintiffs’ work in the dataset to train AI systems.

¹⁰⁵ Hua, S. Y., Jin, S. C., & Jiang, S. Y. (2024), p. 216.

¹⁰⁶ Simon, T. (2025, April 24). The Filipino workers at the sharp end of artificial intelligence. Equal Times. Available at: <https://www.equaltimes.org/the-filipino-workers-at-the-sharp?lang=en>; Perrigo, B. (2023, January 18). OpenAI used Kenyan workers on less than \$2 per hour to make ChatGPT less toxic. Time. Available at: <https://time.com/6247678/openai-chatgpt-kenya-workers/>.

limitations notably include its proprietary nature, which restricts full transparency into its architecture and training data.

Claude’s Transparency Hub is a centralised repository of technical and safety documentation, model evaluations, design choices, and deployment safeguards, which makes it more feasible for regulators, academic researchers, and third parties to audit the system, compare it to standards (e.g. EU AI Act), and hold Anthropic accountable. Even with such transparency tools, however, large models remain complex, and full human-level interpretability cannot be attained.

The primary strengths of open models like Meta's Llama are their relative transparency, high degree of customisability through fine-tuning, a large and active developer community, and its availability for both research and commercial use (subject to the terms of its license). The open-source nature, while a strength, also means that safety and ethical use depend heavily on the responsibility of individual developers and tools like Llama Guard. It is worth noting that open-code does not translate into open data, as the training data sets for these models remain largely undisclosed.

Transparency is one of the most critical issues in the context of democratic deliberations, as it underpins legitimacy, trust, and accountability in democratic decision-making, but remains an elusive goal when AI tools are used in deliberation processes. Meaningful transparency must go beyond open technical disclosure; it must include explanations that are accessible, contextually relevant, and enable public reasoning. “Black boxes” make it difficult for citizens and even policymakers to understand how AI outcomes are produced. When algorithms summarise discussions, rank arguments, or detect consensus, participants may not know *why* certain perspectives are amplified or marginalised. Proprietary models retain their inner workings as trade secrets, and even in open models, training data disclosure remains an issue, as there is a persistent tension between openness and protection — between democratic accountability and corporate or individual rights. Further, selective transparency (like publishing only positive evaluations or simplified explanations) can mislead participants and mask deeper biases.

The following measures may increase transparency when using AI models in democratic deliberation:

- Ensuring clear and distinguishable AI-interaction notices and deepfake/synthetic content labels;
- Preferring providers that support the traceability of their training materials;
- Providing and maintaining GPAI documentation under AI Act Art. 53 for each model version and publishing a training-content summary;
- Ensuring the transparency of datasets, keeping datasheets and documents like the DPIA;
- Providing transparency notices for users in plain language: what model you use, what it can/can’t do, sources of content (including synthetic), and how to contest outputs.

5. Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness

Trustworthy AI should respect all people in an equal manner, regardless of their cultural background, origin, beliefs, orientations, socioeconomic circumstances, etc. It needs to accommodate the requirements of various stakeholder groups and integrate fairness and non-discrimination principles from the earliest stages of development. While there is no global or universally accepted definition for bias or fairness, several relevant EU legislative acts refer to fairness in the context of AI. The EU AI Act Article 10 (Data and data governance) stipulates that training, validation and testing data must be relevant, sufficiently representative and, as far as possible, error-free, with bias detection and mitigation duties for AI providers, while Article 9 (Risk management system) mandates continuous, lifecycle-long risk identification and mitigation for impacts on fundamental rights. GDPR Article 5(1)(a) also provides that personal data must be processed fairly.

The most commonly occurring issues related to diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness:

- Biased training data (inputs) and discriminatory outputs – bias of training data (which results in bias outputs) is one of the most common LLM issues. Discriminatory or biased outputs usually relate to personal circumstances like gender, age, sexual orientation, physical appearance, disability, ethnicity, socioeconomic standing and religion;
- Promotion of inequality – LLMs can promote inequality in the form of underrepresentation of marginalised groups in outputs, poorer performance in languages other than English, better performance from payable LLM versions, etc.
- Toxic or malicious content – which is often the result of extracting training data with little or no curation, from sources which promote the dissemination of toxic and offensive content, slurs and stereotypes (platforms like X or Reddit).

The reasons why LLMs create biased, discriminatory, and toxic content are manifold, typically due to the inherent bias in the training data, as well as toxic or maliciously guided prompts, but also due to the architecture itself. A crucial role of architecture, e.g. how well the model is able to self-correct, how well the weights can be adjusted, how the layer activation structure functions, etc., is equally important,¹⁰⁷ and not just “bad” data leading to “garbage in – garbage out” effect.

All compared LLMs exhibit the same issues related to bias,¹⁰⁸ but employ different levels of measures to counter them. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the bias caused by the training data is permanent, with two additional remarks: first, whilst that is true, it should also be noted that the level at which such bias can be expressed also depends on the scale of the model and the adjustment of the weights. A model trained on 2.000 tokens, 1 of which is bad, is going to express that bias much more than a model trained on 2.000.000 tokens; second, due to “model distillation”, later model versions (even if touted as more performant) can actually turn out to be much more biased because their datasets had been reduced in size,

¹⁰⁷ Martra, P. (2025, April 7). From biased to balanced: Visualizing and fixing bias in transformer models. Data Science Collective (Medium). <https://medium.com/data-science-collective/from-biased-to-balanced-visualizing-and-fixing-bias-in-transformer-models-d1a82f35393c>

¹⁰⁸ See Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31) and Gehman, S., Gururangan, S., Sap, M., Choi, Y., & Smith, N. A. (2020). RealToxicityPrompts: Evaluating neural toxic degeneration in language models. In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2020 (pp. 3356–3369). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.findings-emnlp.301>.

ergo more of the same layers are being activated in different contexts.¹⁰⁹ If biased data are acted upon in our daily lives, they can have serious negative downstream effects, such as marginalising vulnerable groups and exacerbating social inequalities. In deliberation processes, deep fakes could drown out authentic opinions, and fabrications can dominate the deliberative agenda at critical moments (for example, the deepfake audio of journalist Monika Tódová, which was circulated just before the parliamentary elections of 2023, forcing citizens and moderators to spend attention on debunking the fake rather than deliberating on public matters¹¹⁰). Another issue is the combination of bias and opaque black boxes, which obscure how systems were trained or moderated, preventing users from contesting biased outcomes (e.g., why some arguments are boosted).

Scholars have pointed out that ChatGPT, which is trained on data that contains human-biased and malicious thinking, has an inherent political bias (leaning to the political left), and the widespread use of such AI systems may amplify a hegemonic worldview.¹¹¹ OpenAI has made promising bias reduction claims for GPT-5 by updating its Model Spec,¹¹² but the claims have yet to be replicated by third parties in EU contexts.

Despite bias issues being prevalent in all compared LLMs, Gemini seems to have a better documented fairness evaluation process and deployer-oriented guidance with extensive data curation and alignment techniques like RLHF,¹¹³ and Claude's normative guardrails (Constitutional AI) and transparent system cards, which encode non-discrimination rules, also contribute to bias mitigation. Llama has useful guard models, and its dataset included four times more code and over 5% high-quality non-English data spanning more than 30 languages, which reduces the language bias, but compliance with fairness principles remains mostly with deployers (which can be beneficial if developers adhere to high ethical and legal standards).

Measures which can promote fairness and non-discrimination of AI tools:

- Defining participant groups which could be adversely affected by biases and listing personal circumstances which could affect AI outcomes;
- Employing available evaluation and testing tools which identify possible ingrained biases;
- Documenting data representativeness, which shows how training, validation and testing data is reflected in the outputs; with special attention being given to special-category personal data;
- Calibrating existing model guardrails by employing provider filters and adding fairness rules in development of proprietary software;

¹⁰⁹ Hinton, G., Vinyals, O., & Dean, J. (2015). Distilling the knowledge in a neural network. arXiv. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1503.02531>

¹¹⁰ See <https://arsen.co/en/blog/slovak-deepfake>.

¹¹¹ Hua, S. Y., Jin, S. C., & Jiang, S. Y. (2024), str. 220.

¹¹² See <https://openai.com/index/defining-and-evaluating-political-bias-in-llms/>.

¹¹³ See https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/docs/evaluation/intro-evaluation-fairness?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

- Enabling contestation by offering users a clear route to challenge the outcomes of AI tools and enabling human review.

6. Societal and Environmental Well-being

AI systems should be designed in a sustainable manner, minimising adverse social and ecological externalities. They should not erode skills, livelihoods, or the environment, and providers should set in place appropriate mitigation measures. It has been acknowledged, that AI systems can be incredibly beneficial to society, but also similarly detrimental if developed and implemented poorly.¹¹⁴

Cross-cutting issues that affect all compared LLMs are:

- Reduced value of education and replacement of traditional learning – students may become too reliant on LLMs and feel that their own intellectual and cognitive input is not worth the time and effort, which will reduce their personal and professional capabilities.¹¹⁵ The use of LLMs by pupils and students will likely hinder the development of critical thinking and the enhancement of problem-solving skills and creativity.¹¹⁶ From the perspective of the educational system as a whole, educators relying on AI to create learning materials and to score tests will also have a net negative effect on the quality of knowledge and skill-sharing.
- Paper or credential generation – LLMs are able to produce research papers that seem viable at the surface level, which can lead to an increase of papers being produced, whereby the originality and quality of scientific contribution remains questionable. Disclosure of LLM use is proposed as a mitigation measure. Another potential problem in this regard is AI incest – where the amount of AI-generated training data surpasses the amount of human-generated original content, leading to a situation where the LLM is learning from its own outputs, in time eroding the quality of the created content.
- Job loss or class divide – LLM pose a risk of replacing the human workforce in areas previously not under threat – creative professionals and white-collar workers;
- Training data pruning – moderation of LLM training data is currently carried out by citizens of developing countries, who are thus exposed to large amounts of inappropriate and harmful content, which can be emotionally damaging.
- Environmental impacts – the use of LLMs directly increases energy consumption, causes emissions, and drains natural resources, e.g., water, needed for hardware. The exact figures on environmental impacts are poorly documented and generally not disclosed by LLM providers, but the impact grows exponentially with the widespread

¹¹⁴ Laakso, A., Kemell, K. K., & Nurminen, J. K. (2024).

¹¹⁵ A 2025 study suggests sustained LLM use may dampen neural engagement and degrade subsequent independent work. Kosmyna, N., Hauptmann, E., Yuan, Y. T., Situ, J., Liao, X.-H., Beresnitzky, A. V., Braunstein, I., & Maes, P. (2024). Your brain on ChatGPT: Accumulation of cognitive debt when using an AI assistant for essay writing tasks. arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.05020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.05020>.

¹¹⁶ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

use of AI by the general public.¹¹⁷ Notably, increasing other factors (like fairness and transparency) tends to decrease sustainability.¹¹⁸

- Fairwashing – AI systems currently lack any external, reliable and objective means of verification and certification, enabling providers to make unsubstantiated claims and selective narratives, which create false impressions about their products, usually in favour of higher marketing value;
- Loss of social skills – may become a future issue if human-AI interactions increase to the detriment of interpersonal skills.

With regard to the criterion of societal and environmental well-being, it should be pointed out that all compared models exhibit similar negative impacts, and due to a lack of externally verified data and possibly biased claims of LLM providers, an objective comparison proves difficult. Open-source models like Llama and Mistral may democratise access to powerful AI technology, enabling researchers, individual developers, and organisations to experiment, innovate, and customise the models for a wide array of specific tasks.¹¹⁹ Mistral currently exhibits the best transparency practices with regard to environmental impacts, as it employs a third-party-assisted environmental audit, which lowers the risk of fairwashing. While Google (Gemini) has also issued an environmental impact report, which improves the transparency of its model, it merely confirms that negative environmental effects from the use of AI are increasing with the widespread use of LLM tools.¹²⁰ Claude has put in place a Responsible Scaling Policy aimed at lowering societal harm, which could be useful for risk control, but feasible measures against de-skilling and learning loss remain limited.¹²¹

Possible mitigation measures, which developers of proprietary AI systems for deliberation purposes and hosts of deliberation rounds could adopt to curb negative societal and environmental effects:

- Preserve authentic participation by making AI function as an information tool rather than making decisions instead of participants (by way of nudging them towards a specific opinion or decision),
- “AI-off” tasks, which require human-only participation and argumentation (asking for real-life personal experiences and opinions) to avoid de-skilling and over-reliance on AI, prompt participants to provide reasons in their own words;
- Ban emotive framing and identity claims from the AI to reduce undue persuasion of participants;

¹¹⁷ The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates data-centre electricity use at ~415 TWh in 2024 with rapid growth driven by AI, whereby sectoral demand could roughly double by 2030 (see <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-and-ai/energy-demand-from-ai>).

¹¹⁸ Tao, Y., & Gao, P. (2025). Global data centre expansion and human health: A call for empirical research. *Eco-Environment & Health*, 4(3): 100157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eehl.2025.100157>

¹¹⁹ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

¹²⁰ See <https://www.techrepublic.com/article/google-ai-environmental-impact>.

¹²¹ See <https://www-cdn.anthropic.com/872c653b2d0501d6ab44cf87f43e1dc4853e4d37.pdf>.

- **Set an energy & water budget per event** (e.g., cap tokens per session, cap simultaneous long-context queries, cache stable summaries, prefer smaller/efficient models for routine tasks).

7. Accountability

For AI systems developers, it must be possible to properly audit the use of their products and their outputs, to report negative impacts, address trade-offs, and have processes for redress if and when issues arise, via ensuring suitable governance structures, documentation, traceability, testing, and **effective oversight**.¹²²

The most relevant issues that should be addressed are:

- Corporate influence – at present, multinational corporations dominate LLM development and the consumer market. Large providers and industry groups lobby to shape the implementation of legislation and sometimes call for a “pause” on aspects of enforcement.¹²³ The providers of LLMs also safeguard their position by obscuring training data and controlling research publications. They also act as barriers for smaller and independent developers to enter the market.¹²⁴
- Cost of AI monitoring – monitoring, testing and amending LLM systems after deployment is costly and re-training models can be resource-intensive, which hinders the mitigation of ethical issues, despite both HLEG and the AI Act stressing **post-deployment** monitoring duties;
- Ambiguity of accountability – the opacity of training data has negative implications for copyright and academic source referencing, and results in toxic and inappropriate outputs. While internal safety frameworks and documents might seem robust, they do not mitigate the risks of fairwashing if independent testing and disclosure duties are not sufficiently enforced.

With ChatGPT, the exact mechanisms by which the Model Spec's principles are weighted, interpreted, and enforced during the RLHF process are not fully transparent. This “black box” characteristic makes independent verification of the robustness of safety measures and the full extent of potential biases challenging. Users and the broader research community must often rely on OpenAI's internal evaluations and external benchmark performance to gauge model capabilities and safety.¹²⁵ Nonetheless, the U.S. AI Safety Institute and the UK AI Safety Institute conducted a joint pre-deployment testing of OpenAI's o1 model in 2024, and concluded that the model achieves a performance generally comparable to the best-performing reference models tested, while noting that the findings should be considered

¹²² Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

¹²³ See <https://www.reuters.com/technology/tech-lobby-group-urges-eu-leaders-pause-ai-act-2025-06-25/>.

¹²⁴ Laakso, A., Kemell, K. K., & Nurminen, J. K. (2024).

¹²⁵ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

preliminary.¹²⁶ The same testing was also performed for Claude 3.5 Sonnet before its release, which strengthens the credibility of the model's safety claims.¹²⁷

Unlike closed-source models, where the original developer maintains stringent control over usage and can implement centralised safety updates and content moderation policies, open models can be modified by downstream developers. With open-code models like Llama, the obligation for ensuring safe and ethical deployment, and for mitigating potential misuse (e.g., the generation of disinformation, biased content, or harmful applications), shifts considerably to developers and end-users.¹²⁸

Developer controls for corporate influence, monitoring and oversight:

- Considering pre-deployment evaluation by a public body or accredited third party before release;
- Maintaining post-market monitoring with measurable KPIs and incident recording;
- Preferring third-party providers that adhere to the EU GPAI Code of Practice¹²⁹ and practice transparency of their training data;
- Tracking lobbying-related risks when large LLM providers seek to slow or dilute enforcement;
- Implementation of ISO/IEC 42001 (AI Management Systems) and ISO/IEC 23894 (AI risk management) standards;
- Publishing accountability notices for end-users (model/version, intended purpose, known limits and risks, incident contact point, etc.).

Reference sources - Model Documentation and Policies for the five LLMs:

OpenAI – ChatGPT / GPT-4o

- [GPT-4o System Card](#)
- [ChatGPT Model Specification](#)
- [Usage Policies](#)
- [Data Controls and Privacy](#)

Meta – Llama 3

- [Llama 3 Model Card \(GitHub\)](#)
- [Responsible Use Guide](#)
- [Acceptable Use Policy](#)

¹²⁶ See <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2024/12/pre-deployment-evaluation-openais-o1-model>.

¹²⁷ See <https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/2024/11/19/Upgraded%20Sonnet-Publication-US.pdf>.

¹²⁸ Dsouza, N. (2025, July 31).

¹²⁹ See <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/contents-code-gpai>.

Google – Gemini

- [Gemini Model Cards](#)
- [Google AI Principles](#)
- [Responsible AI Updates](#)

Anthropic – Claude

- [Claude 3.5 and 4 System Cards](#)
- [Responsible Scaling Policy](#)
- [Usage Policy](#)

Mistral AI – Mistral Models

- [Models Overview](#)
- [Terms of Use](#)
- [Trust and Security](#)

4.5.2.2. Video Large Language Models (vidLLMs)**Introduction**

The emergence of video-capable large language models (hereinafter “video LLMs”) represents a significant structural development in artificial intelligence (AI), shifting the paradigm from passive multimedia processing to active, inference-driven analysis. These systems are capable of simultaneously analysing video, audio, and textual data, and of generating outputs in natural language, whether in text or speech, relating to identities, actions, and contextual meaning. There is a distinction between two types of video LLMs: understanding vLLMs take video as input and produce text (they analyse what is happening in footage), while generative vLLMs take text or images as input and produce video (they create footage from a description). While such capabilities offer considerable practical benefits, they also introduce novel risks, particularly in the areas of data protection, cybersecurity, and AI governance.

Video LLMs form a subclass of multimodal AI systems designed to process sequences of visual frames, audio streams, and associated metadata. The current market combines proprietary models and open-weight models. Proprietary understanding systems are led by OpenAI’s GPT-5 family, Google DeepMind’s Gemini 3 and Gemini 3.1 family¹³⁰, Anthropic’s Claude 4.x family, and Alibaba’s Qwen3-VL. Proprietary video generation systems include OpenAI’s Sora 2, Google DeepMind’s Veo 3, the Veo 3.1 Lite, and Runway’s Gen-4. On the open-weights side, the most prominent current video-understanding models are Alibaba’s Qwen3-VL family, VideoLLaMA 3¹³¹, InternVideo2.5, and LLaVA-Video. However, certain prominent large language models, such as OpenAI’s GPT family, do not natively support full video processing, as they are unable to ingest complete video files, perform continuous real-time analysis (such as tracking objects across frames), or extract audiovisual features without prior

¹³⁰ Google: Gemini API Documentation (<https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/video-understanding>).

¹³¹ Y. Tang et al.: Video Understanding with Large Language Models: A Survey (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.17432>), Zhang et al.: Video-LLaMA: An Instruction-Tuned Audio-Visual Language Model, (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.02858>).

preprocessing.¹³² This distinction is of legal and technical importance, as some AI systems process video data directly, whereas others rely on intermediate steps such as frame extraction and extended textual representations, thereby materially affecting the data processing chain and the corresponding risk profile.

Applicable legal framework

The GDPR defines personal data as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (Article 4(1)). Due to the presence of faces, voices, locations, and behavioural cues, video data will generally fall within this definition; in particular, where a person is identifiable in the footage, the criteria are clearly met. Moreover, where video recordings include facial images or similar identifiers used for recognition purposes, such data may qualify as biometric data within the meaning of Article 4(14) GDPR.¹³³ In such cases, it falls under the special category of personal data, triggering enhanced protection requirements and additional processing conditions pursuant to Article 9(2) GDPR. It should also be noted that photographs can become biometric data when processed through specific technical means, allowing the unique identification of individuals (Recital 51 GDPR).

The AI Act¹³⁴ also defines emotion recognition systems¹³⁵ and prescribed obligations that deployers of such systems must process the personal data in accordance with GDPR and other applicable legislation regarding personal data (Article 50(3) AI Act). Additionally, pursuant to Article 53(1) AI Act, providers must maintain and share technical documentation, inform downstream providers about capabilities and limitations, ensure transparency, comply with copyright law, and publish a summary of training data. Providers of general-purpose AI models with systemic risk must further conduct model evaluations, assess and mitigate risks, report serious incidents without delay, and ensure adequate cybersecurity (Article 55(1) AI Act).

Human agency and oversight

Video is the modality through which human beings are most legibly identifiable as individuals because it captures the face, gait, voice, micro-expression and social context. Where traditional computer-vision pipelines required separate models for detection, re-identification and behavioural classification, a single video LLM can ingest a CCTV feed and emit natural-language summaries such as “person loitering near exit, appears agitated”.¹³⁶ This eliminates the problem of simultaneously analysing vast quantities of data that has historically limited mass surveillance.¹³⁷ The risk to meaningful human oversight is twofold. First, video LLM outputs arrive in fluent narrative form that invites automation bias; operators

¹³² »Audio and video not supported« - see OpenAI, GPT-5.4 Model Documentation (<https://developers.openai.com/api/docs/models/gpt-5.4>).

¹³³ Biometric data means personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data;

¹³⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828, Official Journal of the European Union, L series.

¹³⁵ Means an AI system for the purpose of identifying or inferring emotions or intentions of natural persons on the basis of their biometric data.

¹³⁶ Visionplatform.ai. (2026, January 11). Vision-language models for CCTV surveillance. Visionplatform.ai. <https://visionplatform.ai/vision-language-models-for-cctv/>.

¹³⁷ European Digital Rights. (2021). The rise and rise of biometric mass surveillance in the EU. <https://edri.org/our-work/new-edri-report-reveals-depths-of-biometric-mass-surveillance-in-germany-the-netherlands-and-poland/>.

are more likely to accept a confident natural-language description than a raw similarity score.¹³⁸ Second, the asymmetry between generation and verification becomes extreme at video scale because a reviewer would need to re-watch the footage to audit each claim, defeating efficiency.¹³⁹

Technical robustness and safety

The most significant security vulnerability arises from multimodal prompt injection. In this context, video LLMs are particularly susceptible to attacks in which text prompts are covertly embedded within images or video frames in order to evade detection and mislead the system into generating responses that do not accurately reflect the underlying content.¹⁴⁰ No tested model reliably distinguishes temporal counterfactuals such as "man eats then watches TV" from its reverse.¹⁴¹ Frame-sampling limits compound the problem because most open-source video LLMs sample only 8–32 frames from arbitrarily long videos, so events between samples are effectively invisible.

Moreover, adversarial attacks on video LLMs may succeed without any access to the model's internal parameters. Such attacks exploit inherent vulnerabilities by introducing malicious inputs—often disguised as benign content—that steer the model towards incorrect, harmful, or hallucinated outputs.¹⁴² Given that video LLMs process multiple input channels, including visual frames, subtitles, and audio streams, each of these channels may serve as a potential vector for manipulation, thereby significantly expanding the range of possible attacks. Empirical studies further suggest that the inclusion of video inputs may degrade safety performance, with some evaluations indicating an average reduction of approximately 34.2%.¹⁴³ Multimodal hallucination is the other central robustness failure because systems hallucinate severely.¹⁴⁴

Privacy and data governance

Video training corpora are among the most privacy-sensitive datasets ever assembled. Several cases exemplify this issue. HowTo100M ingested 136 million clips from 1.22 million YouTube instructional videos without subject consent.¹⁴⁵ A 404 Media investigation in 2024 documented an Nvidia internal directive to scrape "80 years of video per day" across datasets,

¹³⁸Carnat, I. (2024). Human, all too human: Accounting for automation bias in generative large language models. *International Data Privacy Law*, 14(4), 299–314. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae018>.

¹³⁹ Bastani, H., & Cachon, G. (2025). When better AI makes oversight harder. *Knowledge at Wharton*. <https://knowledge.wharton.upenn.edu/article/when-better-ai-makes-oversight-harder/>.

¹⁴⁰ Zhu, Ruizhe. Text Prompt Injection of Vision Language Models (<https://arxiv.org/html/2510.09849v1#bib.bib1>).

¹⁴¹Zhang, J., Zhang, Y., & Li, J. (2024). Vinoground: Scrutinizing LMMs over dense temporal reasoning with short videos. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.02763>.

¹⁴² Geng et al.: Prompt Injection Attacks on Large Language Models: A Survey of Attack Methods, Root Causes, and Defense Strategies (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/org/science/article/pii/S1546221826001384>).

¹⁴³ Sun et al.: From Evaluation to Defense: Advancing Safety in Video Large Language Models (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.16643>).

¹⁴⁴Wang, H., Shi, X., Hu, Z., Bao, J., Wu, B., Ding, M., & Lian, D. (2024). VideoHalluciner: Evaluating intrinsic and extrinsic hallucinations in large video-language models. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.16338>; Zhang, J., Jiao, Y., Chen, S., Zhao, N., Tan, Z., Li, H., Ma, X., & Chen, J. (2024). EventHallusion: Diagnosing event hallucinations in video LLMs. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.16597>.

¹⁴⁵Miech, A., Zhukov, D., Alayrac, J.-B., Tapaswi, M., Laptev, I., & Sivic, J. (2019). HowTo100M: Learning a text-video embedding by watching hundred million narrated video clips. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.03327>.

including academic-only corpora.¹⁴⁶ Unlike text, video uniquely enables simultaneous inference of face recognition, gait and silhouette identification, along with lip-reading and speech reconstruction from silent frames, gaze and attention analysis, affect and micro-expression classification, and re-identification via clothing and scene context. This aggregation enables de-anonymisation even of ostensibly de-identified footage. Multimodal systems can infer sensitive information that has not been explicitly provided, including, for example, geolocation data or sensitive biometric attributes.¹⁴⁷

Moreover, video LLMs may memorise elements of their training data and subsequently reproduce them. Given that such models can retain private information¹⁴⁸ There exists a risk that memorised content may be extracted through targeted queries.¹⁴⁹ In the context of video LLMs, this concern extends beyond textual data to encompass visual and audiovisual material, including potentially sensitive recordings used during training or fine-tuning. There is also evidence that certain AI systems may inadvertently disclose sensitive data embedded within images or retained in their internal representations.¹⁵⁰ This risk is particularly acute in video-based applications, where individual frames may contain documents, screens, or other confidential materials that were not intended for disclosure.

Even where model outputs appear secure, the practices of providers may introduce additional risks. For instance, OpenAI's API documentation indicates that, although data is not used for training by default, it may be retained in logs for up to 30 days.¹⁵¹ Similarly, Google's Gemini policy provides that logs are retained for a limited period and may be subject to human review, including the reading, annotation, and processing of user inputs.¹⁵² Such practices engage core GDPR principles, particularly those of data minimisation, storage limitation, and confidentiality. This means that the legal risk cannot be assessed solely by reference to the behaviour or outputs of the AI model itself. Rather, it also encompasses the way the provider collects, stores, reviews, and manages data within its internal systems. Consequently, even where the model's output is unproblematic, the broader handling of user data throughout the processing lifecycle may still give rise to significant privacy and compliance risks under the GDPR.

Transparency

With regard to understanding models, proprietary video LLMs disclose neither their video training sources nor their systematic failure modes. Their scores on benchmarks such as Video-MME and TemporalBench are self-reported rather than externally audited. In addition, interpretability is weaker than for text models. The user of a video LLM thus typically cannot determine why a given narrative was produced about a given video. Video LLMs exhibit a notable weakness in temporal reasoning, particularly in their ability to understand time,

¹⁴⁶ Nvidia says scraping 80 years' worth of videos daily to train its AI models is in "the spirit of copyright law." (2024, August 6). TechSpot. <https://www.techspot.com/news/104144-nvidia-scraping-80-years-worth-videos-daily-train.html>.

¹⁴⁷ Anonymous authors: Safe-LLaVA: A Privacy-Preserving Vision-Language Dataset (<https://openreview.net/pdf/a16e821290313a15005d21197e81623c5ea551de.pdf>), Lou et al.: Doxing via the Lens: Location Privacy Leakage in Multimodal Models (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.19373>).

¹⁴⁸ Carlini et al.: Extracting Training Data from Large Language Models (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.07805>).

¹⁴⁹ Ozdayi et al.: Controlling the Extraction of Memorized Data (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.11759>).

¹⁵⁰ Chen et al.: Unveiling Privacy Risks in Multi-modal LLMs (<https://aclanthology.org/2025.findings-acl.237.pdf>).

¹⁵¹ OpenAI, How We Use Your Data (<https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/how-we-use-your-data>).

¹⁵² Google, Gemini API Data Use Policy (<https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/terms>).

sequence, duration, and causal relationships within a video. These systems often demonstrate poor temporal perception,¹⁵³ provide inconsistent responses, and, in some cases, perform at a near-chance level.¹⁵⁴ As a result, their outputs may involve misidentifying individuals or misattributing actions, which can give rise to false disclosures, reputational harm, or flawed decision-making. Taken together, these deficiencies increase the likelihood that incorrect inferences are presented as factual statements and treated as authoritative, which can be especially problematic in high-stakes contexts, such as employment decisions or democratic processes.

While reliability failures concern situations in which a model unintentionally misinterprets reality or produces factually inaccurate outputs, these must be clearly distinguished from deepfakes, which are intentionally generated or manipulated to appear authentic. Deepfakes, therefore, constitute a distinct category of risk associated with the use of video LLMs, arising not from inherent system deficiencies but from the deliberate misuse of the system's capabilities or outputs.

Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Video amplifies the fairness pathologies in two ways. First, action-recognition datasets embed gender and geographic biases. For example, models amplify stereotypical gender correlations.¹⁵⁵ Sharp accuracy drops are also found on images from low-income regions, and these biases transfer directly to video LLMs whose training data is largely made up of Western YouTube content.¹⁵⁶ Second, the encoders, which most video LLMs inherit from OpenAI and Google, respectively, exhibit well-documented demographic biases (for example, Scaling CLIP amplifies both gender and racial bias).¹⁵⁷ This finding introduces a problem for addressing bias because the industry's default strategy of scaling up training data is structurally likely to worsen fairness outcomes rather than resolve them. Discrimination also emerges in relation to content moderation. TikTok auto-removes in excess of 100 million videos per quarter. Automated removals report a 5% false-positive rate.¹⁵⁸ and disproportionate removals affecting black, trans, disabled and LGBTQ+ creators.¹⁵⁹

Societal and environmental well-being

Emotion recognition functionalities embedded within such systems may misinterpret human emotional states and generate outputs based on these inaccuracies. In doing so, they risk

¹⁵³ Liu et al.: TempCompass: Do Video LLMs Really Understand Videos? (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.00476>), e.g., a video show a person pouring water into a glass and then drinking it, while the model incorrectly states that the person drinks first and only then pours the water, or a video showing an individual waiting for ten minutes may be misinterpreted by the model as the person waiting only briefly.

¹⁵⁴ Jung et al.: Can Video Large Language Models Comprehend Language in Videos? (<https://openreview.net/pdf/3631a49355d2485ee6a622838e9d1244170cc773.pdf>).

¹⁵⁵ Zhao, J., Wang, T., Yatskar, M., Ordonez, V., & Chang, K.-W. (2017). Men also like shopping: Reducing gender bias amplification using corpus-level constraints. Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, 2979–2989. <https://aclanthology.org/D17-1323/>.

¹⁵⁶ Shankar, S., Halpern, Y., Breck, E., Atwood, J., Wilson, J., & Sculley, D. (2017). No classification without representation: Assessing geodiversity issues in open data sets for the developing world. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.08536>.

¹⁵⁷ Al Sahili, Z., Patras, I., & Purver, M. (2025). Data matters most: Auditing social bias in contrastive vision language models. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.13223>.

¹⁵⁸ Han, E. (2021, July 9). Advancing our approach to user safety. TikTok Newsroom. <https://newsroom.tiktok.com/advancing-our-approach-to-user-safety>.

¹⁵⁹ Ungless, E. L., Markl, N., & Ross, B. (2025). Experiences of censorship on TikTok across marginalised identities. Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media, 19(1), 1952–1965. <https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v19i1.35912>.

intruding into the inner life of individuals without proper consent. Furthermore, these systems may be used to exploit emotional or mental conditions for purposes such as targeted advertising or political messaging. They may also misclassify characteristics such as race or gender, thereby reducing individuals to abstract data points rather than recognising them as persons. Compounding these concerns, individuals affected by such outputs frequently lack meaningful opportunities to challenge the system's conclusions or to correct inaccuracies, which may ultimately contribute to self-censorship. Video LLMs can also have a negative impact in relation to the documentation and prosecution of war crimes due to the problem of context collapse, which is particularly acute in video. The biggest issue here is that video LLMs struggle to distinguish documentation of violence from its glorification.¹⁶⁰

Multimodal inference has a greater negative impact on the environment than text generation because it is approximately sixty times more energy-intensive. Image generation requires a median of 1.35 kWh per 1,000 inferences, while text requires 0.042 kWh.¹⁶¹

Accountability

Meaningful auditing of video LLMs requires traceability of the training data, the development process, and the system's runtime outputs. Problems arise in relation to all three. First, none of the major proprietary video LLMs discloses the full composition of their video training data. Consequently, an independent auditor can't determine what footage of real individuals was used during training, whether consent existed, or whether particular demographic groups were systematically over- or under-represented. Second, in relation to the development process, system cards, such as those published by OpenAI, document safety evaluations but do not provide access to the underlying model weights, intermediate checkpoints, or preference datasets required for a genuine third-party audit. Third, frame sampling means that the same video submitted twice to the same model may produce vastly differing outputs. This makes video LLM outputs largely non-reproducible and therefore difficult to audit.

Conclusion

Video LLMs represent a convergence of multimodal perception and generative reasoning, thereby significantly reshaping the risk landscape of AI systems. They are characterised by embedded security vulnerabilities, notable reliability deficiencies, and an expanded spectrum of privacy risks. Taken together, these factors support the view that video LLMs should be regarded as high-risk processing systems under both the GDPR and the AI Act. Accordingly, their deployment ought to trigger heightened obligations relating to security, transparency, and accountability under EU data protection law, including, inter alia, strict data minimisation practices, adversarial testing, and robust governance of data flows.

4.5.2.3. Deliberation and Argument Mining Tools

Argument mining tools are designed to analyse and structure reasoning within text, helping users identify claims, evidence, and relationships between arguments. Rather than replacing

¹⁶⁰Wille, B. (2020, September 10). "Video unavailable": Social media platforms remove evidence of war crimes. Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/report/2020/09/10/video-unavailable/social-media-platforms-remove-evidence-war-crimes>.

¹⁶¹Luccioni, A. S., Jernite, Y., & Strubell, E. (2024). Power hungry processing: Watts driving the cost of AI deployment. Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, 85–99. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/fullHtml/10.1145/3630106.3658542>.

human judgment, these tools support users in understanding complex debates by combining automated analysis with interactive visualisations that make patterns and reasoning more accessible.

These systems keep humans in control, assisting interpretation rather than making decisions. Their reliability remains variable, as most argument mining tools are still at a research stage; differences between human annotators can lead to ambiguity and emphasise the need for careful validation mechanisms. Privacy and data governance largely depend on the source of the data: using public or consented datasets reduces risks, but clear guidelines on data handling and access minimisation are still necessary. Transparency is generally a strength with these systems, as many tools disclose intermediate steps and results through visual interfaces. However, diversity and fairness remain inconsistent, as models trained on limited languages or topic domains may not generalise well and can result in biased outputs. These tools offer clear societal benefits by helping users understand reasoning and evidence for arguments, thereby supporting a more informed discussion in civic deliberation settings. Accountability is strengthened if systems record their analytical processes and enable audit trails. Overall, argument mining tools provide strong support for human agency, transparency, and societal values, but challenges in robustness, fairness, and governance need to be addressed before they can be reliably used in high-stakes settings.

Note: Initially, our assessment of argument mining tools included the AI tools Jigsaw Sensemaker and ConvoKit, technical partners, in cooperation with pilot partners, decided that these two tools would not be tested in pilot trials, as they were deemed inappropriate for different reasons. We therefore include the assessment of these tools in Annex 15, together with the reasoning for their omission in the pilot trials.

ArgMiner¹⁶²

ArgMiner is a platform for crowdsourcing and analysing online arguments, supporting the identification, classification, and evaluation of argumentative structures in text, particularly in computational argumentation research.

1) Human agency and oversight

ArgMiner is designed as a support tool for text annotation, model training, and inference, focusing on component extraction and sequence labelling rather than autonomous decision-making. It operates within a human-supervised workflow, where models assist but do not replace human judgment. The platform provides an HTTP API for integration into supervised pipelines and promotes experimental methods that encourage careful human use of model outputs.

ArgMiner aligns with the HLEG requirement for human oversight by supporting human intelligence and retaining control with the deployer. To strengthen compliance, maintainers could: (i) provide clear usage guidance emphasising human review and noting experimental

¹⁶² Resources: Nami, Y.: ArgMiner: End-to-End Argument Mining, Towards AI, published July 18, 2023, available on: <https://towardsai.net/p/Argminer-end-to-end-argument-mining> (accessed October 13, 2025), and Nami, Y.: ArgMiner: End-to-end Argument Mining, GitHub, published April 19, 2022, available on: <https://github.com/namiyousef/argument-mining> (accessed October 13, 2025).

features; (ii) include abstention options and confidence scores; and (iii) offer examples of user interfaces that support human validation of outputs.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

ArgMiner supports reproducibility by clearly defining supported datasets and standardising their processing. It also documents multiple labelling schemes, enabling rigorous comparison across tokenisation approaches, which is a key issue in sequence labelling. The platform includes a basic web API with health checks and explicit port configuration, supporting predictable deployment. However, it lacks documentation on testing, benchmark metrics, deterministic execution, model versioning, input validation, and fallback behaviour. Security guidance for the API (e.g. authentication and rate limiting) is also absent, which is a concern for non-local deployments.

Overall, ArgMiner is only partially aligned with HLEG requirements. Compliance could be improved by: (a) providing reproducibility scripts with fixed seeds and reference metrics; (b) validating inputs and enforcing fail-safe behaviour; (c) documenting versioned pipelines; (d) adding API security guidance and a default “safe mode”; and (e) including confidence or abstention mechanisms.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

ArgMiner does not host data, as processing of public datasets (e.g. Argument Annotated Essays and PERSUADE/Feedback Prize essays) occurs locally after installation. The repository does not collect user data and is distributed under an MIT licence, with clear terms regarding redistribution and intellectual property. However, it lacks explicit data governance guidance. There is no documentation on complying with dataset licences and terms of use, safeguarding personal information in training data, or managing downstream outputs. This is particularly relevant for datasets such as PERSUADE, which include texts written by school-age individuals; although publicly available, users should be reminded of lawful use and appropriate handling.

As a result, ArgMiner falls short of HLEG requirements in this area. Compliance could be improved by introducing a concise privacy policy, including: (i) links to dataset licences and terms of use; (ii) recommendations for pseudonymisation when ingesting new data; (iii) guidance on data minimisation (e.g. retaining only labelled outputs where possible); and (iv) assurances that the API does not log content by default unless explicitly configured to do so.

4) *Transparency*

ArgMiner’s README file clearly outlines its features (processing, augmentation, training, and inference across multiple models), supported datasets, and labelling strategies. It also explicitly identifies experimental components and provides concise installation and API setup instructions. However, several key documentation elements are missing: there is no model card template for trained models, no datasheet for processed datasets, no changelog linking library updates to performance changes, and no explicit statement of limitations (e.g. tested domains, languages, or expected failure modes).

While ArgMiner broadly meets HLEG transparency requirements, compliance could be improved by: (i) providing example model cards; (ii) including datasheet templates for datasets; and (iii) adding a clear limitations and misuse section (e.g. noting that outputs should not be used for fully automated evaluation without human oversight).

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

ArgMiner supports the processing of heterogeneous datasets (e.g. Argument Annotated Essays and PERSUADE), enabling cross-dataset comparisons that may reveal generalisation gaps across genres, grade levels, and annotation schemes. It also offers multiple labelling strategies (IO/BIO/BIEO/BIXO, word-level vs sub-token), which can help distinguish genuine fairness issues from artefacts introduced by labelling choices. The authors explicitly caution that some approaches are not literature-backed, discouraging over-reliance on unvalidated methods. There is also no formal fairness documentation provided. The repository does not address how performance varies by topic, reading level, or dialect; includes no bias audits; provides no accessibility guidance for the web interface (e.g. keyboard navigation or screen reader support); and does not document stakeholder engagement (e.g. educators or students).

As such, ArgMiner falls short of HLEG requirements in this area. Compliance could be improved by: (i) reporting performance metrics across relevant subgroups (e.g. topic, grade level, text length, source); (ii) linking to established fairness evaluation toolkits or templates; and (iii) providing example code to help users assess how modelling and labelling choices affect performance across different groups.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

Using ArgMiner for research about writing quality, critical thinking, or argument structure can be socially beneficial. As a library, ArgMiner's environmental impact depends on the chosen models, texts used, and training time. ArgMiner does not report energy consumption (e.g., time spent on training/hardware), offers no default smaller models, and gives no advice on fine-tuning effectively. Thus, ArgMiner is socially progressive, while its environmental impact is unknown.

7) Accountability

ArgMiner provides basic accountability mechanisms typical of open-source research projects, including a public issue tracker, API documentation, and an MIT licence clarifying legal responsibilities. The README also documents datasets and processing choices, supporting traceability of results. However, it lacks formal governance structures (e.g. defined maintainer roles or a code of conduct), does not provide guidance on audit logging for the API (such as responsible logging of inputs and predictions), and does not link versioning to changes in model behaviour.

Overall, ArgMiner meets only minimal accountability standards. Compliance could be strengthened by: (i) introducing a code of conduct with clear points of contact; (ii) providing a sample inference logging scheme; and (iii) maintaining a structured changelog to enable auditing of differences across releases.

8) Overall assessment

ArgMiner, as a small research tool, fulfils several HLEG principles. However, since ArgMiner is a developer library, the obligations related to the HLEG obligations will still fall on downstream users/deployers. Nonetheless, the providers of ArgMiner can continue to support compliance with HLEG by incorporating more robust governance and supporting documentation.

4.5.2.4. Moderation and Safety Tools

Moderation and safety tools are designed to identify, filter, and manage harmful or inappropriate content. They support users in maintaining safe environments by combining automated detection with human review, helping to balance efficient content handling with contextual judgment. In practice, effective moderation relies on strong human oversight. Developers themselves emphasise “human-assisted moderation” rather than fully automated enforcement, with a human reviewer as the final authority and integrated appeal mechanisms, which is crucial for meeting HLEG expectations. While the technical performance of these systems is improving, risks such as false positives, misclassification (e.g. due to dialect), and erroneous results under changing contexts remain. These issues require mitigation measures such as red-teaming (i.e. gathering multiple perspectives within a group), calibrated thresholds, and escalation pathways. Privacy and data governance are critical given the sensitive nature of user-generated content: systems must minimise personal data in logs, ensure appropriate consent, and apply strict retention policies. Transparency is also essential for user trust and accountability. Users are more likely to trust systems when decisions are clearly explained, so tools should provide understandable reasons for flagged content, not just general policy descriptions. Diversity and fairness also require attention, including testing with different dialects, identities, and contexts. While these tools can contribute positively to reducing harm and supporting societal wellbeing, they must avoid over-blocking and chilling effects on freedom of expression. This can be achieved through proportional enforcement and setting up redress mechanisms for affected users. Overall, moderation and safety tools can support trustworthy AI when deployed with human-in-the-loop oversight, bias monitoring and mitigation, calibrated decision-making, and clear governance, including documented policies, performance reviews, and incident reporting.

Detoxify¹⁶³

Detoxify is a machine learning library for detecting toxic language in text. It classifies content for toxicity, insults, identity attacks, and related harms.

Human agency and oversight

Detoxify’s documentation expressly recommends the use of thresholds and reviews to support human-in-the-loop operation. It advises that model scores are uncalibrated and should be tailored to specific use cases, distinguishing between high-recall thresholds for flagging content for review and higher-precision thresholds for automated actions. The API provides continuous scores across categories (e.g. toxicity, threat, identity attack), enabling deployers to define policy-aligned rules. However, there is no published guidance on escalation or appeal processes for users whose content is flagged, which limits meaningful oversight and contestability. There is also no explicit requirement for human-in-the-loop operation by default, which allows for fully automated outputs with potentially high thresholds, which could enable false positives and over-filtering. Detoxify does enable oversight through scoring and thresholding mechanisms, but responsibility for effective human control ultimately rests with the deployer.

¹⁶³ Resources: Unitary: Detoxify (a), available on: <https://docs.unitary.ai/> (accessed October 17, 2025), and Unitary: Detoxify (b), GitHub, published November 4, 2020, available on: <https://github.com/unitaryai/detoxify?tab=readme-ov-file> (accessed October 17, 2025).

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

Detoxify provides open-source models trained on established Jigsaw datasets (original, unintended bias, and multilingual), with ongoing updates and a multilingual variant aimed at reducing bias. The documentation acknowledges that outputs are uncalibrated and require threshold tuning for specific use cases, reflecting the need for human validation of outputs. It also clearly labels types of problematic content (e.g. as threat, insult, identity attack) and offers practical guidance on threshold setting. Nonetheless, publicly available safety features are limited. There is no evidence of robustness testing against adversarial inputs, code-switching, or domain shifts, nor guidance on calibration. While some common errors are documented (for example, the misclassification of profanity, slurs, or sarcastic language), these may lead to systematic issues. The Dataloop card notes "nuanced language or sarcasm" as especially problematic, which is also a common failure for toxicity classifiers.¹⁶⁴

While Detoxify does demonstrate adequate modelling practices and comes with practical deployment guidance, it falls short of HLEG criteria with regard to robustness and safety due to the absence of comprehensive validation, calibration, and stress-testing measures.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

Detoxify can be used in two ways: via a managed API, which requires sending text to Unitary's servers, or as an open-source model that deployers can run locally. The open-source option offers stronger privacy protection, as data remains under the deployer's control and does not need to be shared with third parties. The managed API lacks clear information on how data is handled. There is no public detail on whether the submitted text is stored, reused, or logged, nor on how long it is retained. It also does not specify security measures such as encryption or access controls. While the training data sources are publicly known, there is no guidance on how users should handle personal or sensitive information when using the system.

The open-source version of Detoxify supports privacy by design, whereas the managed API does not fully meet expectations for privacy and data protection. In practice, privacy protection depends on how the tool is deployed, with local hosting or contractual safeguards helping to reduce risks.

4) *Transparency*

Detoxify provides clear documentation of its models, datasets, labels, and performance across languages, and the API explicitly reports output categories (e.g. toxicity, obscenity, threat, insult, identity attack, sexually explicit). It also explains that scores are uncalibrated and openly acknowledges known limitations, such as sensitivity to profanity, data imbalance, and the subjective nature of "toxicity". However, transparency is weaker at the level of individual decisions. The API does not explain why specific content is flagged (e.g. which words or features triggered the result), making it harder for users to understand or challenge outcomes. In addition, there is limited transparency regarding the managed service, particularly around data use and business practices.

While Detoxify is transparent about its models and training data, it lacks clear explanations for individual decisions and sufficient transparency about how the hosted service operates.

¹⁶⁴ Dataloop: Toxic Bert, available on: https://dataloop.ai/library/model/unitary_toxic-bert/ (accessed October 17, 2025).

This is especially problematic in cases of false positive results, which could have a chilling effect on freedom of expression.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

Detoxify demonstrates awareness of fairness concerns through its “unbiased” model variant and stated efforts to minimise bias. Its documentation explicitly acknowledges risks, such as the over-association of profanity with toxicity and potential bias against minority groups, as well as dataset imbalance and the subjective nature of toxicity labels.¹⁶⁵ It also includes identity-related categories (e.g. identity attack), which can support the evaluation of differential performance across groups. This is consistent with the HLEG requirement that if datasets are biased and those biases could lead to discriminatory outcomes, this must be disclosed to the users transparently, and inclusion/diversity should be built in where possible.

However, there is no comprehensive or systematic fairness evaluation. The documentation does not assess performance across dialects and languages, code-switching, or minority speech patterns (e.g. queer or disability-related vernaculars). Known limitations, such as difficulty with nuance and sarcasm, may disproportionately affect certain communities.¹⁶⁶ In addition, there is no guidance on inclusive or accessible design for either developers or end users.

While Detoxify signals a clear intent to address bias, it lacks robust fairness reporting and practical guidance for mitigation, limiting alignment with HLEG criteria in this area.

6) *Societal and environmental well-being*

Detoxify aims to reduce harmful online content and, when applied appropriately, can contribute to improved user and moderator well-being by limiting exposure to abuse. It also offers smaller model variants, which may reduce computational and energy costs in deployment.

However, there is no transparency regarding environmental impact, such as carbon or energy usage, nor guidance on efficient or low-resource deployment. There is also a risk of over-moderation, where false positives may suppress legitimate speech—particularly affecting marginalised groups—despite this being acknowledged as a limitation. Thus, while Detoxify offers clear societal benefits, it lacks documented environmental practices and safeguards to balance harm reduction with freedom of expression.

7) *Accountability*

Detoxify’s open-source code, model weights, and evaluation scripts support independent assessment, auditability, and reproducibility. Its guidance on threshold setting encourages data-driven evaluation using representative datasets, helping deployers justify decisions in line with their risk preferences. But the hosted API documentation does not address key accountability processes, such as complaint handling, incident reporting, or user redress in cases of incorrect moderation. There is also no reference to formal impact assessments, external audits, or post-deployment monitoring requirements. While the open-source

¹⁶⁵ Borovec, J.: Addressing Toxic Comments with Lightning Flash and Detoxify, Medium, published December 8, 2021, available on: <https://medium.com/codex/addressing-toxic-comments-with-lightning-flash-and-detoxify-92996b9f9ca8> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁶⁶ See Dataloop: Toxic Bert.

approach enables technical accountability, formal governance and accountability mechanisms are largely left to deployers.

8) Overall assessment

Detoxify demonstrates strong transparency regarding its models and datasets, provides practical guidance for thresholding, and shows clear awareness of bias and subjectivity. These features support human oversight and responsible use. However, in line with HLEG requirements, Detoxify should be viewed as a technical building block rather than a complete solution. Achieving trustworthy deployment depends on the surrounding socio-technical governance implemented by the deployer.

Content-Checker

Content-Checker is a general-purpose tool for assessing text against defined standards (e.g., moderation, compliance, or safety rules), flagging inappropriate or restricted content.

1) Human agency and oversight

Content-Checker is a developer-oriented library that provides structured outputs (e.g. categories, confidence scores, and verdicts) rather than enforcing actions such as bans. This design supports its use as a decision-support tool, allowing integrators to route results to human reviewers rather than applying automatic penalties. The documentation emphasises configurable thresholds and outputs, while underlying providers (e.g. Google Perspective) explicitly promote human-in-the-loop moderation rather than full automation.¹⁶⁷ Additionally, implementation guidance (e.g. restricting API keys to server-side use) reflects attention to secure and controlled deployment.¹⁶⁸ Responsibility for oversight is thus left entirely to the deployer.¹⁶⁹ While the tool enables human review, it does not enforce it, and the documentation references potential use cases such as automated moderation (e.g. auto-ban bots), which could reduce human oversight if implemented without safeguards. There is also no built-in support for appeal or contestability mechanisms.

2) Technical robustness and safety

Content-Checker offers configurable settings, such as recommended confidence thresholds, enabling users to calibrate moderation decisions according to their context. Basic safeguards are included, such as API rate limiting to reduce abuse. Its architecture supports multiple providers (e.g. Google Perspective, OpenAI), allowing for redundancy and comparative evaluation, while image moderation relies on established models (e.g. NSFW JS). Open-source availability further supports transparency and peer review of the library itself, but robustness depends heavily on the reliability and security of external providers and the deployer's infrastructure. The documentation does not define contingency measures, safety assurances, or formal performance targets.¹⁷⁰

¹⁶⁷ Google: Get started with Perspective API, last updated September 18, 2024, available on: <https://developers.google.com/codelabs/setup-perspective-api#0> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁶⁸ UtilityFueled: Content-Checker, GitHub, published Januar 2, 2024, available on: <https://github.com/utilityfueled/content-checker> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁶⁹ OpenModerator: Terms and Conditions, last updated December 7, 2023, available on: <https://www.openmoderator.com/terms> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁷⁰ See UtilityFueled: Content-Checker.

In summary, while the tool provides flexible and transparent components, it lacks comprehensive guarantees of robustness and safety at the system level.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

Content-Checker promotes a privacy-aware integration approach by recommending that API requests be routed through server-side components, reducing exposure of API keys and limiting direct data sharing between users and third-party services.¹⁷¹ However, the underlying provider (e.g. OpenModerator) may collect personal data such as IP addresses, device information, and user identifiers, and explicitly notes that data transmission is not fully secure.¹⁷² While this is relevant for transparency, the documentation does not clearly explain how moderation inputs (e.g. submitted text or images) are stored, reused, or protected, nor whether such data may be used for further model training. As a result, Content-Checker only partially meets HLEG criteria for privacy and data protection.

4) *Transparency*

Content-Checker provides clear technical documentation, including supported providers, confidence thresholds, output formats, and example JSON responses.¹⁷³ It also specifies functionality (text and image moderation), default providers, and licensing/version information, which supports transparency for developers and downstream governance.¹⁷⁴ However, user-facing transparency (explanations that are understandable to the affected end user) is not built in. Explanations of decisions, communication of limitations, and disclosure of AI use are left to the deployer. While the tool enables transparency through structured outputs and reason codes, this requirement is only fulfilled if deployers pass this information on to end users.

Content-Checker supports transparency at the technical level, but effective transparency in practice depends on how it is implemented and communicated to users.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

Content-Checker relies on external providers such as Google Perspective, for which there is substantial evidence of bias, particularly over-classification of certain dialects (e.g. African American English) and variation across languages (for example content in German language was rated as more “toxic”).¹⁷⁵ These issues create a risk of disproportionate false positives and unequal treatment if outputs are applied without safeguards. Even providers themselves position such tools as assistive and should not supplant human judgment.¹⁷⁶ The library does not include built-in fairness mitigation, dialect-aware processing, or guidance on addressing

¹⁷¹ Ibid.

¹⁷² OpenModerator: Privacy Policy, last updated December 7, 2023, available on: <https://www.openmoderator.com/privacy> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁷³ See UtilityFueled: Content-Checker.

¹⁷⁴ See Snyk Advisor: Content-Checker.

¹⁷⁵ See Resende, G. H. et al.: A Comprehensive View of the Biases of Toxicity and Sentiment Analysis Methods Towards Utterances with African American English Expressions, available on: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2401.12720> (accessed October 17, 2025), and Nogara, G. et al.: Toxic Bias: Perspective API Misreads German as more toxic, available on: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2312.12651> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁷⁶ See Google: Get started with Perspective API.

bias beyond adjusting thresholds by deployers. As a result, fairness largely depends on the deployer's actions.

Content-Checker does not meet HLEG expectations for fairness by default. Compliance requires additional measures by deployers, such as bias auditing across groups, context-sensitive thresholding, human review of borderline cases, and accessible appeal mechanisms.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

Content-Checker is designed to support safer online communities by moderating user content, which, when applied appropriately, can reduce harassment and encourage participation. However, achieving societal benefit requires careful balance: overly strict moderation may suppress legitimate speech, particularly for marginalised groups. Given known fairness risks, deployers should actively monitor outcomes (e.g. disproportionate content removal) and introduce governance mechanisms to mitigate harm. The documentation does not address environmental sustainability. As the tool relies on external model providers, responsibility for environmental impact largely rests with those providers rather than the library itself.

7) Accountability

Content-Checker is open source under the Apache-2.0 licence, supporting external review and technical auditability. The documentation clearly assigns responsibility to users for how outputs are applied, reinforcing the role of deployers.¹⁷⁷ In practice, accountability depends on implementation. Effective use requires maintaining detailed logs of moderation decisions (including timestamps, model versions, providers, and thresholds) and providing users with clear appeal and redress mechanisms. The tool's structured outputs can support such practices. Nonetheless, the documentation does not define auditing frameworks or redress processes. As a result, accountability is only partially addressed and largely dependent on deployer controls.

8) Overall assessment

Content-Checker can meet HLEG requirements if complemented by appropriate governance measures. These include human-in-the-loop review, transparent user communication, calibrated thresholds with bias auditing, appeal mechanisms, robust logging, and privacy documentation covering data minimisation, retention, and deletion. Without these measures, the tool remains only partially compliant, with trustworthiness dependent on how it is deployed.

4.5.2.5. Translation and accessibility tools

Translation and accessibility AI tools, including automated speech recognition (ASR) and machine translation, are designed to support communication, inclusion, and access—particularly for multilingual users and people with disabilities. These systems augment rather than replace human judgement and have reached high levels of robustness, often approaching human performance even in noisy conditions. However, residual risks remain, including occasional “hallucinations” or transcription errors, which require safeguards and human review in critical contexts. Privacy and data governance are essential, as audio and text inputs may contain personal data; approaches such as on-device or self-hosted processing and

¹⁷⁷ See Snyk Advisor: Content-Checker.

non-retention of data better align with HLEG guidelines. Transparency should include clear disclosure of performance benchmarks, limitations, and known risks (e.g. bias, hallucination, or language identification issues), enabling users to calibrate their reliance appropriately. Equity remains a key challenge, as systems are often trained on English data and perform less reliably for lower-resourced languages, while translation tools may reproduce biases (e.g. gender bias). Addressing this requires ongoing multilingual evaluation and targeted data improvements. From a societal perspective, these tools provide significant benefits, particularly by enabling speech-to-text accessibility for deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals and improving access to information. Accountability can be strengthened through version tracking, public reporting of performance across languages and domains, and independent evaluation of system outputs. Overall, translation and accessibility tools can align with HLEG principles when their limitations are clearly communicated, human oversight is maintained, and continuous investment is made in fairness and bias mitigation.

LibreTranslate¹⁷⁸

LibreTranslate is a machine translation tool that provides language translation services without relying on proprietary systems or cloud dependencies.

1) Human agency and oversight

LibreTranslate enables deployers to run machine translation within their own infrastructure, providing full control over how and when translations are performed. Its documentation clearly supports local installation, configuration, and management (e.g. languages, API access), reinforcing user control. As an assistive tool that generates text rather than making decisions, it inherently preserves human agency. Nonetheless, the tool does not include built-in mechanisms for human review or approval. In high-stakes contexts (e.g. democratic deliberations), deployers must introduce their own safeguards, such as mandatory human review before publication and clear labelling of machine-generated translations, along with metadata on model versions.

Overall, LibreTranslate aligns with HLEG principles through its design and emphasis on user control, but effective oversight depends on governance measures implemented by the deployer.

2) Technical robustness and safety

LibreTranslate includes several operational safeguards, such as configurable rate limiting, API key quotas, and an “under-attack” mode requiring authentication, which help mitigate abuse and service disruption. Monitoring is supported through token-protected Prometheus metrics, and its open-source, deterministic design allows reproducibility of outputs by fixing model versions. The API also handles overloads clearly (e.g. HTTP 429 responses), enabling fallback strategies. Performance can be stabilised through configuration choices, such as limiting loaded languages. However, there are no built-in measures of translation quality or automated safeguards (e.g. fallback models for low-confidence outputs). As a result, ensuring accuracy and reliability depends on the deployer, who should manage versioning and validate updates before deployment.

¹⁷⁸ Resources: LibreTranslate (a), available on: <https://libretranslate.com/> (accessed October 17, 2025), and LibreTranslate: LibreTranslate (b), GitHub, published on December 21, 2020, available on: <https://github.com/LibreTranslate/LibreTranslate> (accessed October 17, 2025).

LibreTranslate aligns well with HLEG requirements for operational robustness and reproducibility, with some output accuracy remaining the responsibility of the deployer.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

LibreTranslate's design strongly supports privacy by enabling self-hosting and offline operation, ensuring that data remains within the deployer's control. The documentation provides guidance on secure configuration, including HTTPS use, API key management, and access control for monitoring endpoints. It also allows for data minimisation through configurable features, such as limiting loaded language models. Despite this, governance practices are not predefined and must be implemented by the deployer. For example, metrics may include the collection of data such as IP addresses, which could qualify as personal data. Deployers therefore need to define retention policies, restrict access to logs, disable unnecessary data collection, and ensure lawful handling of personal data.

In summary, LibreTranslate can align well with HLEG privacy principles through its architecture, if effective data governance policies and controls are established by the deployers.

4) *Transparency*

LibreTranslate offers strong transparency through its open-source code, clear licensing (AGPL-3.0), and detailed documentation. It explicitly identifies its underlying engine (Argos Translate), provides comprehensive API documentation (including endpoints, parameters, and error handling), and supports fully local, offline deployment. These features enable users to clearly understand how the system operates. On the other hand, transparency regarding model training data, limitations, and potential biases depends on the underlying Argos models rather than LibreTranslate itself. Linking directly to model documentation, version histories, and known limitations would further improve user understanding.

Transparency is one of the principal advantages of LibreTranslate and is consistent with HLEG transparency requirements, with scope for enhancement through clearer integration of model-level information about underlying engines.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

LibreTranslate supports multiple languages and offers flexible integration, which can promote accessibility (for example via SRT subtitles). However, it does not include built-in mechanisms for bias mitigation or fairness evaluation, as these aspects are largely determined by the underlying translation models. As a result, ensuring fairness depends on the deployer. This may include testing for bias (e.g. gender, ethnicity or cultural stereotypes), providing mechanisms for users to report and correct errors, selecting models with transparent training data, and applying domain-specific controls such as glossaries to reduce harmful ambiguity.

While LibreTranslate does not directly address fairness, its open and self-hosted design enables deployers to implement appropriate safeguards, aligning with HLEG criteria when complemented by such measures.

6) *Societal and environmental well-being*

LibreTranslate supports societal well-being by improving access to multilingual content, thereby enhancing inclusion and accessibility (e.g. through use cases such as subtitle translation). It also provides practical options to manage resource consumption, such as

limiting loaded language models, using efficient deployment methods (e.g. Docker/Kubernetes), and enabling GPU acceleration where appropriate. However, there is no explicit documentation on energy usage or environmental impact. Deployers are therefore expected to manage efficiency themselves, for example by monitoring resource usage, optimising infrastructure, and documenting the balance between societal benefits and computational costs.

Overall, LibreTranslate aligns well with HLEG expectations on societal impact, but lacks explicit information on sustainability.

7) Accountability

LibreTranslate provides technical features that support accountability, including API key management, usage limits, optional request logging, and secure configuration of monitoring endpoints. Its open-source nature (AGPL licence) and well-documented API further enable auditability and external review. Nonetheless, formal accountability processes are not defined within the tool. Responsibilities such as handling user complaints, managing incidents, and defining governance structures are left to the deployer. Effective use requires them to establish clear ownership and points of contact for users, maintain logs and versioning records, secure monitoring data, and provide user-facing mechanisms for reporting and resolving issues.

LibreTranslate offers strong technical foundations for accountability, but relies on deployers to implement a complete accountability framework.

8) Overall assessment

Being an open-source, self-hosted, offline-capable tool, LibreTranslate is well-suited to the HLEG framework, especially with regard to privacy, transparency, and operator control.

Whisper¹⁷⁹

Whisper, provided by OpenAI, is an automatic speech recognition tool that converts spoken language into written text, supporting multiple languages and transcription tasks.

1) Human agency and oversight

Whisper, as an open-source speech recognition model, supports local deployment and enables human-in-the-loop review of transcriptions. Its documentation clearly cautions against inappropriate uses, such as inferring personal attributes or applying the model to subjective classification tasks, thereby reinforcing responsible use. The model cards also highlight known limitations, including hallucinations and segmentation constraints, which underline the need for human review in sensitive or high-stakes contexts. Effective oversight is not built into the system and must be implemented by deployers, who should introduce safeguards such as human validation of outputs, especially where decisions may affect individuals, and avoid relying solely on automated transcription in consequential settings.

¹⁷⁹ Resources: OpenAI: Introducing Whisper, published September 21, 2022, available on: <https://openai.com/index/whisper/> (accessed October 17, 2025), and Hugging Face: Whisper, available on: <https://huggingface.co/openai/whisper-large-v3> (accessed October 17, 2025).

Whisper supports human agency through its design and transparency, but alignment with HLEG requirements depends on the deployment of appropriate governance and review processes.

2) Technical robustness and safety

Whisper demonstrates strong technical robustness, being trained on large and diverse datasets and designed for generalised performance across languages and conditions. Documentation highlights resilience to noise and improved error rates compared to other specialised models, indicating reliable performance in varied real-world scenarios. At the same time, important limitations are acknowledged, including hallucinated outputs, repeating of text, variability across languages, and constraints linked to its processing window. These risks necessitate safeguards such as validation procedures, human review, and fallback mechanisms in high-risk contexts.

Whisper is broadly aligned with HLEG requirements for robustness, provided that deployers implement appropriate evaluation, monitoring, and safety controls in practice.

3) Privacy and data governance

Whisper's training data is described only at a high level as publicly sourced audio-text pairs, with limited detail on data composition or any formal privacy assessment. The documentation does mention that heuristics were used to filter machine-generated transcripts. Although heuristics improve data quality, available documentation does not provide a data inventory or a privacy impact assessment of the training source. As a result, there is uncertainty regarding the presence and handling of personal data in training, and deployers should avoid making assumptions about data provenance.¹⁸⁰ In deployment, however, Whisper supports strong privacy practices. Its open-source/open-weights design under MIT license allows local processing without sending audio to third parties, enabling data minimisation and greater control. The documentation also cautions against transcribing without consent or using outputs to infer personal attributes. Deployers should put policies in place for data governance: gathering consent for recordings, schedules for deleting audio and transcripts, and limiting access to logs.

Overall, Whisper aligns well with HLEG expectations at deployment level, but transparency around training data governance remains limited and should be treated cautiously by users.

4) Transparency

Whisper demonstrates a strong level of transparency through its public release of models, inference code, and a detailed research paper outlining its architecture and performance.¹⁸¹ Documentation provides practical information (e.g. model sizes, hardware requirements, supported tasks) and clearly communicates key limitations, including variability in performance across languages and potential misuse risks. Transparency regarding training data, on the other hand, is less comprehensive. While general sources and filtering methods are described, more detailed disclosures, such as dataset composition or structured

¹⁸⁰ Radford, A. et al.: Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision. In ICML'23: Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Machine Learning (2023), p. 2.

¹⁸¹ See OpenAI: Whisper.

evaluations across languages and dialects, would improve understanding of performance and limitations.

Whisper meets HLEG transparency requirements in terms of capabilities and limitations, with scope for improvement in training data disclosure and evaluation detail.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

Whisper's documentation is transparent about uneven performance across languages, accents, and demographic groups, with accuracy closely tied to the availability of training data. This highlights a key fairness risk: lower performance for under-resourced languages and certain dialects, which may lead to unequal outcomes. The large-v3 model card states that performance may vary by accent and demographic criteria, and the implied higher word-error rates by gender, race, or age. These remarks indicate valuable honesty but also document real gaps in fairness. While the tool does not include built-in fairness mitigation, deployers can address these risks by applying language identification, validating outputs for underrepresented groups, fine-tuning models where possible, and avoiding use in contexts and cases where performance is known to be insufficient.

Overall, Whisper acknowledges fairness limitations, but effective mitigation depends on deployment practices.

6) *Societal and environmental well-being*

Whisper provides clear societal benefits by enabling accessible, multilingual transcription, supporting communication and inclusion. However, its documentation also highlights dual-use risks, particularly the potential for large-scale surveillance through automated transcription, which requires careful governance.¹⁸² From an environmental perspective, the documentation provides practical information on model sizes and hardware requirements (GitHub table), which makes it possible to compute demand and, by extension, energy use (the large model has approx. 10GB VRAM, and the turbo variant provides faster speed-efficiency trade-offs). This allows deployers to make informed decisions about resource use (e.g. selecting smaller or more efficient models). Nonetheless, there is no explicit reporting on energy consumption or environmental impact.

Whisper is moderately aligned with HLEG principles on social and environmental well-being. It offers meaningful societal value and some support for energy-aware deployment, but responsible use, particularly to mitigate surveillance risks and manage environmental impact, depends on the deployer.

7) *Accountability*

Whisper's open-source design (MIT-licensed code and model weights) enables independent auditing and reproducibility, providing a strong foundation for accountability. Its documentation clearly outlines known limitations (e.g. hallucinations, variable performance) and explicitly discourages inappropriate uses, supporting informed and responsible deployment. However, formal accountability mechanisms are not built into the system. To meet HLEG expectations, deployers should implement organisational controls such as logging

¹⁸² Ibid.

and record-keeping, human escalation procedures, and clear processes for user complaints and redress in cases of errors.

Overall, Whisper provides strong technical accountability, but full compliance depends on governance measures established by deployers.

8) Overall assessment

Whisper aligns well with several HLEG principles, as it demonstrates adequate transparency, substantial technical robustness, and reasonable accountability with its open models, code, and documentation. It also supports human oversight, most notably via the ability to use it locally offline, and it presents clear warnings against uses intended to serve classification purposes that do not involve informed consent and are subjective. Notably, societal and environmental well-being are its weak points.

4.5.2.6. Gamification and Engagement Tools

Gamification and engagement AI tools in democratic deliberation may encourage participation, learning, and constructive interaction by incorporating game-like elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards. While these tools can enhance engagement and support pro-social dialogue, their ethical use depends on preserving genuine human agency: participation must remain voluntary, reversible, and under meaningful user control. Designs should therefore avoid coercion or subtle manipulation, and include clear opt-out mechanisms. Available literature highlights key risks, including power imbalances, paternalism, reduced voluntary choice, confidentiality concerns, and the effects of cognitive nudging and social comparison. As incentive-based systems, they require careful monitoring and guardrails in line with safe-by-design principles. Privacy and data governance are central, as gamification often relies on profiling user behaviour. Transparency must extend not only to system goals but also to how user activity is measured and how rewards are calculated. Fairness considerations are equally important: gamification mechanics should not disadvantage particular user groups, and inclusive design, such as offering alternative participation pathways, should be prioritised, especially given evidence that benefits are not universal. From a societal perspective, these tools can support authentic learning and civic engagement, but only if incentive structures are responsibly governed. Accountability requires clear ownership of design decisions, regular assessment of potential harms, and mechanisms for redress. Ultimately, gamification in democratic contexts can be ethically justified only where there is informed consent, full transparency, ongoing bias monitoring, and accessible, safe options for users to disengage.

Chamilo LMS¹⁸³

Chamilo LMS is a free, open-source educational tool designed to create, manage, and deliver online courses and training programs.

1) Human agency and oversight

Chamilo's AI plugin is designed as an assistive tool for instructors, with AI-generated questions explicitly presented as editable and subject to review before use. This reflects a clear human-in-the-loop approach, consistent with the HLEG requirements. More broadly, the platform's governance model, through role-based permissions, terms, user rights, and GDPR-related

¹⁸³ Main resources: Chamilo E_Learning & Collaboration Software, available on: <https://chamilo.org/en/> (accessed October 17, 2025), and Chamilo LMS, GitHub, published October 31, 2014, available on: <https://github.com/chamilo/chamilo-lms> (accessed October 17, 2025).

controls and consent flows (including Data Protection Officer contacts), ensures that responsibility remains with human operators rather than the system.

Chamilo aligns well with HLEG requirements, embedding human oversight both in the AI feature and in its wider governance structure.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

Chamilo has demonstrated responsiveness to security vulnerabilities, including several critical issues identified in 2023, which were addressed through patches, improved input validation, and safer default configurations. The platform also promotes limiting unnecessary plug-ins to reduce the attack surface, reflecting a cautious design approach.¹⁸⁴ The identified and addressed issues do not, in and of themselves, undermine trustworthiness (since open-source systems often have the ability to be revised continuously), but they certainly highlight the importance of continuous monitoring. The severity and recurrence of vulnerabilities, particularly remote code execution risks, highlight the need for continued strengthening of secure coding practices, systematic testing, and threat modelling. Chamilo's documentation emphasises the importance of limiting the proliferation of plug-ins and consolidating features to maintain a higher level of security. This represents a prudent design consideration, which also serves to reduce the potential attack risks.¹⁸⁵

Chamilo exhibits partial alignment with HLEG requirements in this area. It demonstrates responsible maintenance and improvement, but requires ongoing investment in security practices to ensure sustained robustness.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

Chamilo demonstrates strong alignment with GDPR requirements through built-in features that give users control over their personal data. The terms of use include extensive sections specifically verifying compliance with several aspects of GDPR: collection, storage, transfers and erasure of data, as well as profiling. Users can access, export, and request deletion of their data, withdraw consent, and view applicable terms, while a designated Data Protection Officer (DPO) provides accountability. Upon a user's request with relation to their personal data, the relevant record must be retained for the purpose of enabling a scheduled system process to notify the DPO or administrators, ensuring that the request is addressed within four weeks. The platform also documents processing activities (e.g. collection, storage, erasure) and supports auditability of consent and user requests. These features reflect key data protection principles such as consent, minimisation, and accountability. However, further clarity on technical safeguards, particularly encryption and breach notification procedures, would strengthen compliance.¹⁸⁶

¹⁸⁴ See Soares, G.: Critical unauthenticated command injection in Chamilo LMS exploited in the wild, published September 5, 2023, available on: <https://blog.imunify360.com/critical-unauthenticated-command-injection-in-chamilo-lms-exploited-in-the-wild> (accessed October 17, 2025), CVEFeed.io: CVE-2023-3368 – Chamilo LMS Unauthenticated Command Injection, available on: <https://cvefeed.io/vuln/detail/CVE-2023-3368> (accessed October 17, 2025), and StarLabs: (CVE-2023-4220) Chamilo LMS Unauthenticated Big Upload File Remote Code Execution, published November 28, 2023, available on: <https://starlabs.sg/advisories/23/23-4220/> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁸⁵ Warnier, Y.: How Chamilo (LMS), a European learning management platform, positions itself as a solid alternative to the Australian Moodle? Published July 18, 2023, available on: <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/education-culture-and-sport/solution/chamilo-lms/news/chamilo-lms-solid-alternative-moodle> (accessed October 17, 2025).

¹⁸⁶ Nokhbeh Zaeem, R. et al.: The Effect of the GDPR on Privacy Policies: Recent Progress and Future Promise. In Transactions on Management Information Systems (2020), volume 12, number 1, p. 15.

Overall, Chamilo is well aligned with HLEG requirements on privacy and data protection, with scope for improved transparency on certain security practices.

4) Transparency

Chamilo provides structured and comprehensive transparency through its Terms & Conditions, which aligns disclosures with GDPR requirements, and through clear communication of user rights and DPO contact details. This supports user understanding of how their data is processed and how to seek redress. However, transparency regarding the AI plugin and model outputs is less refined. While human review is implied, there is no clear communication to end users (e.g. learners) that AI-generated content may be used. This makes transparency a weak point of the system, falling short of HLEG requirements.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Chamilo supports inclusion at the platform level through multilingual interfaces and a stated commitment to linguistic and cultural diversity.¹⁸⁷ However, fairness risks arise from the AI plugin (OpenAI/ChatGPT), as the generation of content (e.g. assessment items) depends on external models and is not accompanied by built-in bias mitigation. As a result, responsibility for fairness rests with deployers and educators. Effective use requires reviewing AI-generated content for bias or stereotypes, ensuring diversity in question banks, and applying structured evaluation practices (e.g. bias-checklists).

Overall, Chamilo supports fairness in access, but fairness in AI-generated content depends on local governance and review processes. This could be strengthened by providing users with bias-review checklists to guide their evaluation.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

Chamilo contributes positively to societal well-being as an open-source educational platform recognised as a Digital Public Good, promoting accessibility and inclusive learning.¹⁸⁸ Its design philosophy, prioritising integrated, secure features, also supports sustainable system management. However, the environmental impact of the AI plugin is not addressed, as computation is handled by external model providers. Deployers (educators) must therefore consider the sustainability practices of these providers and apply their own guidelines for responsible AI use.

In summary, Chamilo demonstrates strong societal value, while environmental considerations related to AI usage remain insufficiently documented.

7) Accountability

Chamilo demonstrates strong accountability through its GDPR features, including user data dashboards, export tools, consent withdrawal logs, DPO notification workflows, and deletion timelines aligned with regulatory requirements. Ongoing development activity also reflects a commitment to privacy-by-design, with efforts to enable GDPR features by default and ensure traceability of consent. In terms of security, Chamilo has shown responsiveness to vulnerabilities, providing timely disclosures, clear upgrade guidance, and subsequent patches. This indicates an active approach to maintaining system integrity.

¹⁸⁷ See Warnier, Y. How Chamilo (LMS), a European learning management platform, positions itself as a solid alternative to the Australian Moodle?

¹⁸⁸ Ibid.

Overall, Chamilo exhibits well-established accountability practices in both data governance and security, supported by transparent processes and continuous improvement.

8) Overall assessment

When deployed in an up-to-date, properly configured version with GDPR features enabled, Chamilo aligns strongly with HLEG requirements. It provides a solid foundation for trustworthy AI in education, though further enhancements, particularly clearer guidance on AI transparency and fairness, would strengthen its overall compliance.

4.5.2.7. Summarisation Tools

This sub-chapter evaluates three summarisation tools: the BART (Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers) transformer model, the SUMY open-source library and the STANZA open-source natural language processing library.

BART¹⁸⁹

BART (*Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers*) is a sequence-to-sequence transformer model widely used for abstractive text summarisation. It is pre-trained as a denoising autoencoder and fine-tuned to generate concise summaries by reconstructing coherent text from corrupted input sequences. It is a model pre-trained on the English language and fine-tuned on CNN Daily Mail.¹⁹⁰

1) Human agency and oversight

BART is a tool that lets other systems do things which could make people more or less in control, based on how it is used, what organisation it is in, and what people are encouraged to do. HLEG wants AI systems to “give people more power,” by letting them make good choices and safeguarding their rights. BART-based condensing of a text is often suggested due to too much text that people cannot handle (“very hard for people to look at and get what’s useful”), and due to automated text condensing. In that way, BART can comply with people being in control, and it makes information shorter in order for users to check it.

¹⁸⁹ Compliance assessment is based on the following:

- Attada, V., Srividya, K., & Cristin, R. (2022). Abstractive Text Summarisation Using BART. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MysuruCon55714.2022.9972639>,
- <https://huggingface.co/facebook/bart-large-cnn> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://github.com/matannagar/Bart-Text-Summarisation> (13. 2. 2026),
- Rao, R., Sharma, S. & Malik, N. Automatic text summarisation using transformer-based language models. *Int J Syst Assur Eng Manag* 15, 2599–2605 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13198-024-02280-4>,
- Munyai, C., Ndia, J. (2025). Natural Language Processing with Transformer-Based Models: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal on Artificial Intelligence*, 7(1), 329–346. <https://doi.org/10.32604/jai.2025.069226>,
- Lewis, M., Liu, Y., Goyal, N., Ghazvininejad, M., Mohamed, A., Levy, O., Stoyanov, V., & Zettlemoyer, L. (2019). BART: Denoising sequence-to-sequence pre-training for natural language generation, translation, and comprehension. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.13461> (13. 2. 2026),
- Sharma, N., Singh, S. A Hybrid Extractive and Encoder-Decoder-Based Approach for Mitigating Hallucination in Automatic Text Summarisation. *J. Transform. Technol. Sustain. Dev.* 9, 15 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41314-025-00083-4>.

¹⁹⁰ It was introduced in the paper: Lewis, M., Liu, Y., Goyal, N., Ghazvininejad, M., Mohamed, A., Levy, O., Stoyanov, V., & Zettlemoyer, L. (2019). BART: Denoising sequence-to-sequence pre-training for natural language generation, translation, and comprehension. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.13461> (13. 2. 2026),

Being in control and reviewing what has been done is not achieved simply by the desire to do so. It also depends on whether those who use the system are able to question its outputs, modify them when necessary, and contribute their own knowledge and judgement.

The common way of presenting BART for text summarisation—simply stating that “this model can be used to condense text”—tends to frame automation as the normal and expected approach. This, in turn, risks encouraging excessive trust in the system’s outputs. In the use case we examined, the system clearly records which condensations have already been produced. This may influence how users approach the material, leading them to treat these condensations as final and authoritative versions, rather than as drafts that remain open to further consideration and revision.

BART may be regarded as a helpful aid for individuals who need to review material of importance. At the very least, the interface presented to users should: (i) display condensations as drafts that users can edit and refine; (ii) require users to give explicit confirmation before the text is shared or published; and (iii) introduce additional safeguards or friction when the content concerns sensitive matters or when the decisions involved carry significant consequences. Within organisations, effective oversight also requires differentiated access rights for different roles, as well as clearly documented procedures for review and verification. BART can support such requirements, but only if the system is deliberately designed and implemented in a way that keeps human users firmly in control.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

The BART presentation reflects a very detailed pretraining method: it is “a denoising autoencoder”, meaning it is trained by damaging text and then learning to “put the original text back together”. In practical testing, BART does well, e.g. Rao et al. (2024) found BART was better than T5 at CNN Daily Mail, gaining “3.02% in ROUGE-1”. These qualities indicate a form of toughness, understood here in a limited sense: the ability to perform well in tests and to maintain processes that consistently produce the same results.

However, the HLEG idea of robustness is wider: it aims at “avoiding risks beforehand”, including being able to cope with mistakes and proper protection throughout a system’s life. Systems for summarisation – and BART-based ones are no exception – have a known way of failing: they invent information and are not consistent with what is actually true. A current review of transformer models points out that “making things up still happens”, as well as cost in computing and prejudice in the data. More to the point for summarising, making things up is said to damage “truth, accuracy and being able to be relied on”. Higher ROUGE scores, taken on their own, do not demonstrate that a system is safe for real-world use, as measures based on word overlap may reward fluent rephrasing even when the underlying facts have been altered.

A robust BART system should hence include (i) testing that goes past ROUGE, including testing for truth and people testing in areas where it is very important; (ii) things to stop dangerous or badly-formed inputs (for example, very long texts, or commands hidden in the text like prompt-injection); (iii) being able to give a proper idea of how certain it is (for example, signs of trust based on how much of the input is covered); and (iv) ways to fall back on, like summaries which only take from the original, or showing parts with references when making new text is dangerous.

The result is therefore mixed: BART’s structure and training enable it to handle novel inputs reasonably well, yet BART summarisation in its default form cannot be considered “safe” in the sense intended by the HLEG unless systematic controls are added to reduce potential risks.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

As BART is a model that has already been trained, concerns about privacy arise primarily from the data used during its training and subsequent refinement, as well as from the data processed when the system is in use. The standard summarisation checkpoint, which is fine-tuned on the CNN/Daily Mail dataset, shapes the model's expectations about subject matter and writing style; however, it does not in itself address the risk that sensitive information might be disclosed when the system is deployed.

The job of governing the system is clearest in the application code. The version of the system which was looked at describes summarising “text through files or links”, and very clearly allows account making and keeping: users can “sign up, log in and see their past summarisation”. That decision, in its design, is not without ethical effect.

Retaining summaries together with the inputs from which they were produced may make the system easier to use and audit, but it also creates a repository of data that may contain personal information, commercially sensitive material, or regulated content (such as health, educational, or legal information). The available description of this repository does not specify key safeguards, including how long the data are retained, how deletion is handled, how the information is secured, who is permitted to access it, or what level of visibility system administrators have.

To ensure compliance with the HLEG requirements, a system using BART should implement privacy-by-design principles. This includes retaining only the minimum amount of data necessary, establishing clear data-retention periods, allowing users to delete their data, securing information both in transit and at rest, and clearly separating authentication data from the content of the data itself.

If the system allows summarisation from external links, it must also address the lawful basis for obtaining and using content created by others. In other words, BART itself does not prevent compliance with privacy rules; however, common “convenience” features—such as maintaining a persistent record of activity—must be carefully governed in order to meet privacy and data-governance requirements throughout the system's entire lifecycle.

4) Transparency

BART complies with scientific transparency in a particular way: it fully explains the technique – a “denoising autoencoder”, the corruption process, and reconstruction – and shows how it relates to what came first. The model card also gives a short account of how it is built and says what dataset was used to refine it.

Transparency, however, also requires clearly stating what a system cannot do, where it originates from, and who bears responsibility for it. A notable indication of limited transparency is the disclaimer on the model card: “The team releasing BART did not write a model card.” While this is not a technical flaw, it represents a governance issue, as it leaves subsequent users to determine for themselves the model's intended purposes, its likely limitations, and the scope of its testing. The *Intended Uses & Limitations* section of the model card, at least in the cited section, is very brief and appears more to grant permission for use than to provide a clear account of the situations in which the model may perform poorly or should not be relied upon.

At the point of use, transparency also requires informing users when they are reading text generated by a machine, explaining how it was produced, and indicating what it may omit or misrepresent. A full web application that enables users to share results via email and social media makes it even more important to indicate the origin of the information and to state clearly that a machine was involved in producing it. Transparency in line with the HLEG approach would therefore involve clearly labelling the text (for example, “summary generated

by a machine”), providing a brief description of the nature of the training data (such as news content in the style of CNN Daily Mail), and making easily accessible explanations of the known risks—particularly the tendency of the model to invent information.

For this reason, transparency in the use of BART remains incomplete: although the underlying scientific work can be understood, the typical documentation and product practices do not fully explain the model’s limitations in real-world use.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

Regarding summarisation with BART, fairness problems are more likely to come from representational damage – which viewpoints are at the centre of the training data, which kinds of speech and formality the model deals with effectively, and which social groups may be misrepresented or rendered invisible through the process of summarisation – than from definite judgements in classification.

The papers on BART admit these issues within the system for transformer models. The meta-analysis by Munyao and Ndia (2025) observes that “biases within... data sets are often carried over to the results of the model”, and names “data bias” as a continuing difficulty. When it comes to summarisation, fine-tuning BART on the CNN Daily Mail dataset—and, more broadly, on news material—may introduce editorial perspectives that are not culturally neutral. This is particularly relevant in relation to global politics, marginalised social groups, and contested historical events.

A test of whether a system meets this requirement must therefore consider what “fairness” means in the context of summarisation. It is not merely a matter of producing the same number of errors for all groups, but also of avoiding systematically distorted representations of people, events, or viewpoints. The available responses to this issue are well understood, though often neglected. These include examining summaries across different sections of the population and across different subject areas, where the intended use requires it, testing the system across linguistic varieties and in multiple languages, establishing mechanisms through which biased omissions can be identified and reviewed, and allowing users to consult the most relevant parts of the original material to reduce the risk of unnoticed shifts in representation.

BART is not unique in this respect; rather, it reflects a broader pattern among transformer systems, where fairness is seldom built in by default. Meeting the relevant requirements, therefore, depends on careful bias assessment and inclusive evaluation, rather than relying solely on performance in standard benchmark tests.

6) *Societal and environmental well-being*

Summaries produced with BART can have clear social benefits. They reduce the volume of information that people must process, make material more accessible to those with limited time or with difficulties in absorbing large amounts of text, and support academic and governmental work. Practical studies point to the same need: when texts become very large, “summarising takes longer”, which explains the growing demand for automated approaches.

At the same time, the risks are equally social in nature. Summarisation is not simply a mechanical shortening of text; it also shapes how information is perceived. A fluent and well-written summary can still spread misinformation if it subtly alters causal relationships, omits important warnings, or introduces fabricated details. The problem of invented information is therefore not merely technical: it has broader societal consequences, as it may undermine confidence in established knowledge and distort public debate.

Environmental considerations must also be taken into account. Transformer-based models require significant computational resources. The available documentation for BART does not

provide detailed information about energy consumption or carbon footprint, which means that much of the environmental responsibility falls on those who deploy the model. To align more closely with responsible practice, applications built on BART should favour computational efficiency—for example, by using lower-precision numerical representations or simplifying processing where appropriate—should disclose the main computational choices involved, and should consider whether the marginal benefit of producing a new summary justifies the resources required when compared with simply extracting relevant passages from the original text. In this way, the social and environmental value of the technology depends not only on its capabilities but also on careful system design that addresses misinformation risks and manages computational resources responsibly.

7) *Accountability*

The fact that BART's original developers did not produce a model card also raises concerns about accountability, as it makes it more difficult to trace responsibility for documenting risks and for setting out safe practices for its use.

At the same time, the broader BART ecosystem is comparatively open to scrutiny when set against many closed systems. The methods and common implementations are open source; the system structure—typically consisting of a front end, a back end, and a summarisation engine—can be inspected; and licensing information is publicly available. In addition, account-based systems that retain a history of generated summaries may, if properly governed, provide useful audit trails that support accountability, incident investigation, and user redress. That same design, however, also introduces privacy obligations, highlighting that accountability mechanisms must be accompanied by robust data-management practices.

To meet the HLEG expectations for accountability, a BART-based system should include clear versioning of model checkpoints, logging of key configuration settings used in generation, documented evaluation procedures, and mechanisms through which users can challenge or seek correction of harmful or misleading summaries. In institutional settings, accountability should also involve clearly identified responsible roles and established procedures for handling incidents. While BART's openness and reproducibility make accountability possible in principle, the typical patterns of documentation and deployment do not, on their own, meet HLEG standards. Accountability must therefore be actively established through governance structures around the model, rather than assumed simply because the underlying research has been published.

8) *Overall assessment*

At best, BART aligns only partially with the HLEG requirements, and the degree of alignment varies considerably in practice. With appropriate governance and safeguards in place, it may satisfy these requirements in applications that involve low or moderate levels of risk. However, it should not be regarded as meeting HLEG standards in high-stakes or critical contexts unless it has undergone thorough evaluation, its limitations are clearly and openly documented, and meaningful human oversight is firmly integrated into its use.

SUMY¹⁹¹

SUMY is an open-source library for automatic summarisation of text documents and HTML pages, primarily implementing extractive summarisation algorithms. It supports multiple

¹⁹¹ Compliance assessment is based on the following:

- <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/miso-belica/sumy/main/docs/index.md> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://github.com/miso-belica/sumy> (13. 2. 2026).

classical methods (e.g., LSA, Luhn, LexRank, TextRank) and selects the most relevant sentences from the original text rather than generating new ones.

1) *Human agency and oversight*

SUMY is not an autonomous decision-making system but a software tool that produces summaries by extracting sentences from the original text. The available documentation states that SUMY produces an “extractive summary”, meaning that it “attempts to discover the most important sentences” and assembles them, and that generating new, abstractive summaries is “not what SUMY can currently do”. In HLEG terms, this design supports human oversight because the output remains directly traceable to the source document. Since SUMY selects existing sentences rather than inventing information, users can more easily verify the results by checking the original text.

SUMY encourages user control, as it is presented as a command-line tool and a library of code that exposes its configuration options. Users can adjust parameters such as the summarisation method and the desired summary length, rather than having these decisions concealed within an opaque service.

Nevertheless, the principal risk to human agency does not arise from the system “making choices” on its own. Rather, it lies in the possibility that users may place undue reliance on the “extractive summary” of the original text, allowing the summary to substitute for careful reading and interpretation that should properly remain a human responsibility. Moreover, there is some framing on how information is perceived. Even the simple act of selecting passages from a text can alter what appears most important, omit minority viewpoints present in the full document, or change the perceived relationship between cause and effect by removing surrounding context. For this reason, the use of SUMY in a manner consistent with the HLEG principles should include design constraints that maintain human oversight. These might include presenting summaries as navigational aids to the text, providing one-click access to the highlighted sections of the original document, and preventing automated downstream actions—such as public dissemination, or even medical decisions—without human review.

Another feature that supports human control is SUMY’s emphasis on evaluation. The system includes a “test structure for summaries of text”, which helps keep humans involved as evaluators who determine whether the system performs adequately and is suitable for its intended purpose.

In summary, SUMY can operate in a manner consistent with human oversight and control. However, compliance in practice depends on how it is deployed: summarisation should be treated as an aid to human judgement rather than a replacement for it, and users should avoid placing undue confidence in automated outputs, particularly in high-stakes contexts.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

SUMY exhibits several signs of engineering maturity and a degree of attention to safety. To begin with, it is explicit about its intended uses. The documentation states that the “Random” method is a “test method” and that “you shouldn’t use this one for applications in the real world”. This is a small but important safety feature: it clearly distinguishes between tools intended for testing and those suitable for operational use, thereby helping to prevent accidental misuse.

Secondly, SUMY highlights configuration choices that materially affect its performance. For example, in the case of Luhn summarisation,¹⁹² The documentation warns that without stop-words the system would “almost certainly produce very poor results”. In effect, this acknowledges a degree of fragility: the quality of the output depends significantly on appropriate language resources and pre-processing. Similarly, the Edmundson method is described as “the most language-dependent”, requiring language-specific “bonus words” and “stigma words”. These points should be understood as potential limits to robustness. Anyone deploying the system cannot reasonably claim robust performance across languages or genres without demonstrating that the necessary linguistic resources exist, are maintained, and are appropriate for the relevant domain.

Thirdly, SUMY includes a “simple evaluation framework for text summaries”. From the perspective of responsible deployment, such evaluation only functions as a safety mechanism if it is actively used throughout the implementation lifecycle. A prudent approach would involve running regression tests on representative text collections, defining acceptance thresholds, and documenting known failure cases—for example, very short texts, poorly scanned OCR material, highly technical domain language, or heavily formatted HTML.

Safety also encompasses security and resilience to misuse, and here SUMY’s capabilities introduce integration risks that the library itself cannot entirely prevent. SUMY supports summarisation from URLs and the parsing of HTML, and its “HtmlParser” can “extract the main article” from HTML using the third-party “breadability” library. If SUMY is incorporated into a web service that accepts any URLs, responsible deployment requires consideration of common web-security risks, including SSRF-style attacks, harmful HTML content, denial-of-service through extremely large pages, and failures when extraction does not function correctly. These are not hypothetical concerns but well-known risks associated with retrieving data from the web. Compliance with HLEG principles in this context, therefore, requires secure system design, including measures such as strict URL allow-lists or sandboxed fetching environments, request timeouts, page-size limits, and careful dependency management.

Overall, SUMY aligns reasonably well with robustness and safety in lower-risk contexts, largely because it extracts existing sentences rather than generating new content. Its principal compliance gaps lie less in the underlying concepts than in how the system is deployed. Robustness depends heavily on the availability and quality of language resources and assumptions in parsing, while safe deployment in practice requires careful engineering to manage the risks associated with HTML processing and user-supplied data.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

SUMY’s standard mode of operation is generally compatible with privacy considerations, as it functions as a local archive. It is not – and was never intended to be – a service that hosts user content in a centralised location. Its primary description presents it as a local “archive and command-line program” that generates summaries from “web pages or simple text”. In most cases, this means that the information remains within the user’s own system, which offers a clear privacy advantage when compared with cloud-based summarisation services.

Nevertheless, certain privacy and data governance issues may arise in two foreseeable ways. The first concerns the use of URL inputs. When SUMY is used to summarise websites, it must retrieve content over a network. Although this does not amount to sending internal or confidential documents to an external model provider, it may still give rise to privacy or legal

¹⁹² Luhn summarisation is one of the earliest automatic text summarisation methods. It was proposed by Hans Peter Luhn at IBM in 1958 and is a form of extractive summarisation, meaning it creates a summary by selecting sentences from the original text rather than generating new ones.

concerns if the summarised content contains personal data and the process of accessing or recording that content is not properly controlled. The HTMLParser's ability to extract the "main piece" of a webpage suggests that some processing of content and retrieval of metadata from online sources takes place. Organisations implementing SUMY should therefore clarify whether personal data may be involved, identify the relevant legal basis for processing, and establish appropriate rules regarding retention and access.

A second issue concerns storage and logging within the surrounding application layers. SUMY itself does not require storage; however, many systems built around it store inputs, generated summaries, and user identifiers for convenience or operational purposes. Data governance in line with HLEG principles would require clear data-minimisation practices, defined access controls, encryption where appropriate, and transparent deletion procedures. As SUMY is typically integrated as a component within a larger system, responsibility for privacy compliance largely rests with the party deploying it. Nevertheless, a legal assessment should acknowledge that SUMY's ability to process URLs and HTML content may increase the risk of inadvertently collecting personal data if it is implemented without appropriate safeguards.

In summary, SUMY is designed in a manner that can support favourable privacy outcomes, particularly because it can operate locally on a user's machine. However, the overall privacy and data governance estimate ultimately depends on how the tool is integrated. The handling of URLs, logging practices, and storage policies must therefore be clearly defined and documented in order to meet the requirements set out by the HLEG.

4) Transparency

One of SUMY's most evident strengths is its transparency, particularly when compared with many contemporary neural summarisation systems. SUMY is explicit about its capabilities and limitations. It clearly states that it produces "extractive summaries" and that generating abstractive summaries is "not something Sumy can currently do". This clarity helps manage users' expectations, as it reduces the likelihood that users will assume the system understands meaning or can synthesise information beyond selecting and arranging sentences from the source text.

The design of SUMY also contributes to its transparency. The tool is described as "a collection of separate parts which a user can change", and the documentation identifies its principal components, including the tokeniser, parser, stemmer, and summariser. From a governance and oversight perspective, this modular structure makes it easier to trace how the system operates and to modify individual components if required. It also enables comparison between different summarisation methods, as alternative approaches can be implemented and evaluated side by side.

However, transparency involves more than conceptual clarity; it also requires documentation that is sufficiently complete and accessible. The project's own website acknowledges that "the documentation is not complete, and there are occasionally features in the code which are fixed for Slovak and Czech, which are not explained." While this admission reflects commendable openness, it also suggests that transparency may be limited for non-expert users. When assumptions or design choices are not fully documented, there is a greater risk that the system will be used incorrectly without the user being aware, thereby reducing transparency for those ultimately relying on the output.

For deployment consistent with the HLEG's requirements, transparency should also extend to how the system communicates with users. Although SUMY itself functions as a library, applications built on it should clearly inform users about automated "extractive summaries" and explain the system's limitations. The HLEG guidelines emphasise that systems should

communicate “what they are capable of, and what they are not”. Accordingly, responsible implementations would clearly label summaries as machine-generated, indicate which algorithm has been used, and allow users to easily access the original text from which the sentences were extracted.

In summary, SUMY demonstrates a strong degree of transparency through its open implementation, its clear description of its capabilities, and its modular architecture. The principal limitation lies in the relative incompleteness of its documentation and in the fact that applications built upon it do not always provide users with sufficient information about how the summaries are produced.

5) *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*

SUMY is designed with the intention of supporting a wide range of languages. Its documentation notes that there is a “reasonable possibility” that a user’s language will be covered, and that adding support for additional languages is “not too difficult”. The documentation further explains that several key components of the system are language-specific and can be replaced or adapted. In principle, this modular design promotes inclusivity, as communities or developers may extend the toolkit to support additional languages or improve existing resources.

At the same time, the documentation indicates that the degree of support varies considerably between languages. Some summarisation methods depend heavily on language-specific resources. For example, the Edmundson method is described as “the most language-dependent”, as it requires lists of so-called “bonus words” and “stigma words”. Even the Luhn method may perform significantly worse if it does not have access to appropriate stop-word lists. These dependencies have clear implications for the principle of fairness, and the system may systematically produce poorer results for certain linguistic groups.

To comply with the HLEG principle of fairness, the evaluation of SUMY in practical deployments should therefore go beyond general claims of “support for many languages”. Responsible use requires that the quality of summaries be tested across the languages and forms of language that are relevant to the specific use case. It should also involve clearly documenting known limitations and avoiding the use of methods that rely heavily on language resources in contexts where such resources are unavailable or incomplete. Where a risk of unequal performance exists, implementers should either select methods that are less language-dependent or invest in developing the necessary linguistic resources.

In summary, SUMY has the potential to support fairness through its extensible architecture and the availability of multiple summarisation methods. However, fairness across languages cannot be assumed. It requires deliberate evaluation, appropriate resource support, and careful selection of methods in order to ensure that different language communities are not disadvantaged.

6) *Societal and environmental well-being*

SUMY’s contribution to societal well-being is relatively straightforward: it reduces the cognitive effort required to engage with large volumes of text by producing concise extracts that highlight the main points. This can be valuable in contexts such as education, academic research, journalism, and civic participation, particularly where users must navigate extensive collections of documents. The SUMY toolkit itself provides examples of such applications and includes tools designed to summarise large discussions collectively, suggesting that the system is intended not only to assist individuals but also to support shared understanding. In this respect, its use is broadly consistent with the HLEG principle that AI systems should

benefit individuals and society, provided they do not undermine democratic debate or fundamental rights.

At the same time, certain social risks should be acknowledged. Summaries inevitably shape what readers pay attention to, and this influence can become problematic in sensitive contexts. When applied to political speeches, legal evidence, complaints, or other forms of contested material, the removal of sentences from their original context may still produce a misleading impression, even if the summary remains technically extractive and does not introduce new information. In order to align with the HLEG principles, systems that employ SUMY should therefore encourage users to consult the original texts whenever the subject matter is consequential. They should also ensure continued access to diverse or dissenting viewpoints when multiple texts are summarised and should avoid presenting summaries as authoritative substitutes for full records.

Regarding environmental well-being, SUMY's underlying methods typically require far fewer computational resources than training and deploying large neural models. Although the project documentation does not provide explicit figures for energy consumption, the system is more environmentally friendly compared to the training of large-scale machine-learning models. Such an approach is generally more sustainable and lowers barriers to access, as summaries can be generated on modest hardware and even in offline environments.

Overall, SUMY can support both societal and environmental well-being when it is used in contexts where the primary aim is to facilitate access to information. Nevertheless, responsible use requires careful attention to the risk of removing material from its context and particular caution when summarising sensitive, contested, or high-stakes content.

7) *Accountability*

SUMY supports accountability primarily through transparency and reproducibility. Its Apache-2.0 licence allows organisations to inspect and modify the software they deploy. In addition, the project includes a framework for evaluating text summaries, which enables users to record performance, compare different summarisation methods, and justify choices regarding configuration. The documentation also demonstrates a degree of responsibility by design; for instance, it explicitly notes that the Random method is not suitable for practical use. By stating this limitation clearly, the project helps to prevent inappropriate deployment and clarifies the intended scope of the system.

However, accountability, as articulated by the HLEG, extends beyond the code itself and includes mechanisms for oversight, contestability, and redress. SUMY does not natively provide features such as audit trails, explanation interfaces, or impact assessments. As a result, the primary responsibility for accountability rests with the organisation that deploys the system. If a public authority or online platform were to use SUMY-generated summaries to prioritise investigations, moderate public discourse, or allocate services, it would need to establish appropriate governance measures. These would include procedures for challenging decisions and correcting errors, maintaining records of changes to the selected summarisation algorithms and preprocessing resources, and documenting the configuration settings used to generate summaries that may have significant consequences.

A further accountability risk arises from the variability of methods and linguistic resources. The quality of SUMY's output depends on factors such as stop-word lists, tokenisation strategies or ways of breaking text and language-specific processing tools. The documentation itself highlights this sensitivity, noting, for example, that the absence of appropriate stop-word lists can lead to very poor results. Organisations deploying SUMY should therefore treat these language resources as part of the accountable system, ensuring that they are properly

documented, version-controlled, and subject to regular review for potential biases or performance issues.

In summary, SUMY provides a solid foundation for accountability through its open licensing and the availability of evaluation tools. Nevertheless, meeting the HLEG requirements ultimately depends on the governance framework established by the deploying organisation. Effective accountability will require systematic documentation of configurations, the ability to audit the system in practice, and accessible mechanisms for contesting outcomes and correcting errors.

8) Overall assessment

Overall, SUMY largely aligns with several of the requirements associated with Trustworthy AI. Its design is explicitly extractive, its architecture is modular, it can be operated locally on a user's own systems, and the project is transparent about its capabilities and limitations. These characteristics support transparency, reproducibility, and a degree of user control.

The main risks arise from how the tool is deployed rather than from its design. Overreliance on automated summaries may discourage users from consulting original texts and weaken independent judgment. Privacy concerns may arise if systems retrieve and log website content through URLs without appropriate controls, potentially exposing personal data. Performance may also vary across languages due to unequal linguistic resources, creating potential fairness issues. Finally, applications built around SUMY may lack adequate mechanisms for auditing outputs, contesting results, or correcting errors.

In short, while SUMY's design provides a sound basis for responsible use, compliance with Trustworthy AI principles ultimately depends on careful implementation. Organisations deploying the tool must ensure that appropriate safeguards are in place regarding privacy, fairness across languages, human oversight, and mechanisms for accountability.

STANZA¹⁹³

STANZA is an open-source natural language processing library that provides linguistic analysis tools, including tokenisation, POS tagging, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition. It is not a dedicated summarisation tool, but it can support summarisation tasks by supplying high-quality linguistic annotations for downstream models.

1) Human agency and oversight

Stanza is a collection of tools for the linguistic analysis of many human languages rather than a system that makes decisions autonomously. It is best understood as a toolkit for constructing natural language processing (NLP) pipelines. The software processes text through a series of explicit components and offers a modular pipeline architecture, which enables humans to assemble and control the system. This structure emphasises the user's ability to select which tasks to perform and in what order. In addition, the system is designed to be extensible. Users may replace components through "processor variants", and they may also "create a Processor class and add it to the system". This allows individuals to modify or constrain the behaviour of the system rather than being limited to a fixed pipeline.

¹⁹³ Compliance assessment is based on the following:

- <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/stanza/> (13. 2. 2026),
- [Stanza: A Python Natural Language Processing Toolkit for Many Human Languages](https://nlp.stanford.edu/pubs/qi2020stanza.pdf) (Qi et al., ACL 2020) (<https://nlp.stanford.edu/pubs/qi2020stanza.pdf>),
- <https://github.com/stanfordnlp/stanza> (13. 2. 2026).

However, Stanza does not provide built-in oversight mechanisms, such as interfaces for human review or facilities for audit logging. These forms of oversight must therefore be implemented within any system that is built around Stanza. Moreover, Stanza includes functions – such as named entity recognition and sentiment analysis – that are often used to classify individuals or groups, particularly in contexts related to monitoring or surveillance. The ethical risk is that organisations may treat the labels produced by the system as definitive, thereby placing greater trust in automated outputs than in human judgment.

The HLEG emphasises the need for meaningful human oversight. A system built with Stanza that aims to meet the HLEG’s expectations should therefore incorporate routine verification practices. Outputs generated by the labelling processes should be treated as hypotheses requiring further examination rather than as final determinations. While Stanza itself cannot enforce such governance practices, its design – centred on user-configured pipelines – can facilitate oversight if organisations deliberately incorporate review stages and provide opportunities to challenge or reassess results at later points in the processing workflow.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

The available documentation for Stanza provides particularly strong support for claims of reliability, at least when considered in terms of scientific standards such as systematic evaluation and reproducibility. The performance section of the documentation presents results across many languages, noting that “results... for all of the languages supported” are reported and that the models were “trained and tested using... Universal Dependencies v2.12.” The documentation further explains that the reported outcomes derive from an “end-to-end evaluation” using the official “CoNLL 2018 UD shared task... evaluation script,” which directly supports the ability of other researchers to reproduce the results.

In addition, Stanza has been trained and evaluated on a large scale. The system is reported to have been “trained... on a total of 112 datasets”, and its performance is shown to be competitive across a range of linguistic tasks. These evaluation practices align with several aspects of robustness identified by the HLEG, particularly those relating to precision, dependability, and reproducibility.

However, the HLEG concept of robustness also encompasses the secure functioning of systems under changing deployment conditions, when confronted with adversarial input, or when applied to new domains. In this respect, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The performance of Stanza models may decline when applied outside the contexts for which they were originally developed. As a result, pipelines provided “out of the box” may perform less effectively in specialised domains, such as medical records, legal documents, youth language, or texts involving code-switching. Responsible use, therefore, requires local validation and, where necessary, retraining or adaptation of the models.

The documentation also recognises a trade-off between precision and computational efficiency. Stanza was designed to “maximise accuracy... [at] the cost of computational speed”, and it “takes considerably longer than spaCy to annotate text.” This consideration is relevant to operational safety in real-world settings, as slower pipelines may encourage unsafe shortcuts, such as skipping validation steps or reducing the volume of text analysed. On the positive side, Stanza was intentionally designed with relatively compact models to reduce memory requirements and facilitate distribution. This design choice may reduce the risk of system failures caused by deployment constraints.

To align more closely with the HLEG recommendations, organisations implementing Stanza should therefore establish preventative risk controls. These might include evaluating performance on domain-specific texts before deployment, monitoring for shifts in data

characteristics, documenting fallback procedures in the event of system failure (for example, reverting to simpler tokenisation methods or disabling named-entity recognition when confidence is low), and locking software versions to preserve reproducibility as updates occur.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

By its very nature, Stanza can be advantageous for deployments that require strong protection of privacy, as it is capable of operating entirely on the user's own machine and storing its models locally. The documentation notes that by default, Stanza stores its models in the user's home directory, and it also supports "offline usage" by allowing users to "download the models beforehand" and configure the pipeline in advance. This makes it relatively straightforward for organisations to incorporate privacy by design, since textual data may be processed locally rather than transmitted to external services.

Nevertheless, certain aspects of Stanza involve network interaction. The FAQ section explains that, when constructing a pipeline, Stanza may attempt to download resources and "newer models," although users can disable this behaviour by setting the parameter "download_method = None". While this functionality primarily concerns robustness and software maintenance, it also has implications for privacy and operational control. In environments where security requirements are stringent, network access may be restricted or entirely prohibited, and the ability to prevent automatic downloads therefore provides an important means of maintaining control over the system.

The documentation also refers to a publicly accessible demonstration server, where "annotation happens on the server", although it emphasises that the system "can also be run locally." From a governance perspective, transmitting private or personal text to a public server could conflict with organisational policies or legal obligations. Consequently, any trustworthy deployment should treat the public demonstration as unsuitable for sensitive information and should provide clear guidance to staff regarding which configurations and usage contexts are permitted.

With regard to the governance and provenance of training data, Stanza provides a modest but useful degree of transparency. The documentation indicates that training draws upon "100 treebanks... that have training data which is not under copyright", suggesting an awareness of intellectual property considerations and the legal conditions governing the reuse of linguistic data. However, the licensing status of models derived from Universal Dependencies (UD) resources is not entirely explicit. While this level of disclosure is preferable to the absence of information, it nonetheless places a responsibility on organisations adopting Stanza to ensure regulatory compliance. In practice, this means verifying the licences associated with the language packages they employ and documenting these checks as part of their broader data governance procedures.

4) *Transparency*

Stanza performs well with regard to transparency—particularly in terms of traceability and documentation as understood within the HLEG principles—largely because it is open-source and makes its evaluation materials publicly available. The Stanza repository is distributed under the "Apache License, Version 2.0," which allows the code and its development history to be openly examined. In addition, the performance page explains the evaluation procedures and scripts in sufficient detail to enable others to reproduce the reported results, e.g. the figures presented are complete and are generated using a formal evaluation script. Such practices correspond with the HLEG's requirement for transparency, namely that "the datasets and the processes used to produce the AI system's outcomes... should be

documented... to allow traceability,” thereby supporting the identification and correction of errors.

Stanza’s modular pipeline architecture further contributes to technical transparency. Because users explicitly configure the processors that will run, and may also substitute alternative processor variants, the framework encourages a clear record of which analytical steps have been applied. In this sense, the structure of the pipeline itself promotes traceability of the processing stages. Nevertheless, transparency for end users is not automatically achieved. In a system built using Stanza, those interacting with the application may be unaware that their text is being analysed, what annotations are being extracted, or how those annotations are subsequently used.

According to the HLEG guidance, transparency also requires that individuals are informed when they are interacting with an AI system and that they receive accessible explanations of the system’s capabilities and limitations. In particular, users should be made aware of the constraints associated with the data on which the models were trained. Accordingly, a responsible application built with Stanza should present clear, plain-language information indicating which Stanza components are operating (for example, named-entity recognition or sentiment analysis), how the resulting annotations should be interpreted, and what conclusions should not be drawn from them. It should also disclose any relevant domain limitations that arise from the characteristics of the training data.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Stanza’s principal objective is to support linguistic analysis across many languages—currently around 70—through the use of the “Universal Dependencies (UD) framework”, which reflects a clear intention to treat different languages on broadly equal terms. This represents a valuable step towards impartiality compared with toolkits primarily designed for English. Furthermore, the evaluation of the system across “112 datasets” and the publication of UD-based performance reports for multiple languages provide a sound basis for identifying differences in performance rather than obscuring them.

Nevertheless, fairness cannot be measured solely by the number of languages included. The UD training data used by Stanza draws on “100 treebanks... that have training data not under copyright.” While this is a necessary condition for responsible data management, it may also introduce structural bias, as publicly available linguistic resources are unevenly distributed across languages and communities. In addition, support for different tasks is not uniform across languages. For example, the documentation indicates that “NER models... give support for naming-object labelling for 8 languages”, which is considerably fewer than the languages supported for UD-based syntactic analysis. As a result, applications built on top of Stanza may inadvertently offer fewer capabilities to speakers of certain languages. A further consideration arises from the fact that many downloadable models are trained on only one dataset, which means that fairness across dialects, registers, or varieties of a language cannot be assumed.

In line with the HLEG approach to fairness, systems built using Stanza should therefore incorporate additional evaluation measures. Organisations deploying the toolkit should test its performance with the linguistic communities and user groups relevant to their context of use. They should also avoid using Stanza outputs to infer sensitive personal characteristics or to automatically trigger adverse decisions without human verification. In summary, while Stanza’s multilingual design supports a more inclusive technical foundation, responsible deployment still requires careful testing across dialects, styles, and social groups, as well as thoughtful management of the functional gaps that exist between languages and tasks.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

The principal benefit of Stanza is most evident in its potential contribution to community welfare. It provides accessible natural language processing tools that enable researchers, educators, and professionals working with language to analyse text in many different languages. In doing so, it can support a range of socially beneficial activities, including education, translation, accessibility tools for people with disabilities, and academic research.

This reflects the positive dimension of making NLP technologies widely available. Nevertheless, the same capabilities may also be used for less desirable purposes, such as profiling large populations, monitoring behaviour, or influencing political processes—particularly when combined with functions such as named-entity recognition or sentiment analysis. The recommendations of the HLEG expressly warn that AI technologies may affect “democracy and society more broadly” and therefore require careful consideration in contexts related to democratic activity. Responsible use of Stanza in socially sensitive settings should consequently involve clear governance rules, particularly within governmental or public-sector applications. Moreover, language-based outputs should not be presented as neutral or purely technical results when they may in fact be used in ways that single out individuals or groups.

Environmental considerations in this context depend largely on computational requirements. Stanza openly acknowledges that it prioritises accuracy “even if that reduces computational speed,” and it may therefore operate more slowly than some lighter NLP toolkits. At the same time, the models are designed to be relatively compact, in order to “use less memory and be easier to distribute.” The system can also operate effectively on standard central processing units, noting that while it is “ready to use GPUs,” it runs well on a CPU. These design choices provide practical options for managing energy consumption. For example, organisations may select smaller model configurations, rely on CPUs for modest workloads, or employ GPUs only when the scale of processing justifies their use.

Viewed in light of the HLEG principles, the environmental impact of Stanza should therefore not be regarded as inherently problematic nor automatically beneficial. Rather, its effects depend on how the system is configured and deployed. Responsible implementation requires practitioners to select appropriate computational settings in accordance with operational needs and to document these decisions as part of broader responsible AI governance practices.

7) *Accountability*

Stanza supports accountability more effectively than many NLP tools, as it is open source, distributed under an Apache licence, and thoroughly documented. The performance page provides a clear framework for evaluating system performance, while the start-to-finish annotation process enables users to audit outputs more easily. In addition, the pipeline architecture enhances traceability, as the system’s behaviour is determined by explicit choices of processors and configurations. Stanza also allows users to customise workflows through registered processors and model versions, enabling organisations to implement accountable design practices and to publish their standards for conducting NLP analysis.

Nevertheless, certain accountability challenges remain in areas where the documentation itself signals caution. For example, the note that “license information... isn’t clear” for some resources from Universal Dependencies (UD) means that legal and ethical responsibility cannot be delegated entirely to Stanza. Users must therefore verify and document the licences and provenance of any language packs they employ. Furthermore, as Stanza is a toolkit that enables downstream applications, responsibility for harmful outcomes—such as unfair profiling or unjust automated decisions—will largely rest with the organisations deploying it. To align a Stanza-based system with the HLEG requirements, organisations should maintain

records of model versions and pipeline configurations, document performance on domain-specific data, and provide mechanisms through which affected individuals can seek correction when Stanza's annotations contribute to consequential decisions.

8) Overall assessment

Stanza is broadly consistent with the HLEG requirements when it is used as a research or support tool and is subject to appropriate governance. It performs particularly well in terms of transparency, traceability, and reproducibility. The framework also includes features that can support privacy and human oversight, such as the ability to run models locally on a user's machine and clearly defined options for operating without an internet connection.

Nevertheless, certain challenges remain; in particular, difficulties may arise if Stanza is incorporated into systems that interpret NLP outputs as direct indicators of a person's intentions, characteristics, or potential risk. Moreover, the model's performance and fairness are inherently constrained by the data on which it has been trained, the range of tasks it is designed to perform, and the extent to which the surrounding context may change over time.

4.5.2.8. Clustering Tools

BERT¹⁹⁴

BERT is a system that employs contextual embeddings produced by Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers to represent textual data as dense semantic vectors. These vectors capture the contextual meaning of words within a text and provide a rich numerical representation of its semantic content. Subsequently, clustering algorithms are applied to these vectors to group documents or sentences according to their semantic similarity. In this way, the system automatically organises textual data into coherent clusters that reflect underlying thematic or contextual relationships.

1) Human agency and oversight

BERT is not a system that can make judgments independently; rather, it is a model designed to facilitate tasks by generating contextual representations of language. It creates embeddings that capture the context of words within text and can subsequently be adapted for a wide range of applications. The model is intended to be fine-tuned with relatively small task-specific additions, which typically place the responsibility for decision-making with the system's designers and operators rather than with the model itself. This architecture has two related ethical implications for human agency and for maintaining oversight.

¹⁹⁴ Compliance assessment is based on the following:

- <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://bertopic.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://github.com/rakmakan/Clustering-with-BERT> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.07403> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://github.com/google-research/bert> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://gayathri-siva.medium.com/bert-bidirectional-encoder-representations-from-transformer-8c84bd4c9021> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.08305> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://www.geeksforgEEKS.org/nlp/explanation-of-bert-model-nlp/> (13. 2. 2026).

The process of fine-tuning BERT can enhance the agency of practitioners, as it allows them to determine the objectives, select the training data, establish performance thresholds, and define acceptable margins of error. Furthermore, the practical deployment of BERT often places human actors at the centre of iterative improvement. In many real-world applications, BERT embeddings are incorporated into broader processing pipelines—such as topic-discovery workflows or clustering systems—which can be configured, evaluated, and adjusted by analysts. In such settings, oversight is not merely an afterthought; it can be achieved through the inspection of cluster labels, the review of representative samples of model outputs, and the establishment of escalation procedures for ambiguous or high-impact cases.

At the same time, the very flexibility that allows BERT to be integrated into operational systems with relatively minimal architectural modification can also create risks. It may encourage excessive reliance on automated outputs if system designers prioritise performance optimisation without establishing appropriate governance structures. Deploying BERT in a trustworthy and responsible manner requires explicit design commitments. These include ensuring human reviews where decisions may have significant consequences, communicating model confidence where relevant, and maintaining clear documentation that distinguishes between situations in which BERT's outputs are advisory and those in which they are treated as determinative.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

The central technical feature of BERT is its bidirectional contextual modelling, together with the training objectives of masked language modelling and next sentence prediction, which were designed to enable the model to adapt effectively to a wide range of tasks. While this architecture substantially improves performance, genuine reliability and security require additional safeguards. In practice, this includes the capacity to withstand distributional changes in input data, to resist adversarial manipulation, and to manage the various ways in which the model may fail when deployed in real-world environments.

Some studies examining adversarial attacks on text classification systems—particularly those based on synonym substitutions or similar word replacements—have found that many successful attacks generate outputs that human evaluators regard as semantically incoherent. This suggests that a portion of the reported weaknesses may arise from attack strategies that lack genuine semantic plausibility. Nevertheless, the continued and active development of both attack and defence methods for BERT-based classifiers demonstrates that robustness must be deliberately engineered and rigorously evaluated within the specific domain in which the model will be applied.

Robustness also encompasses reproducibility and long-term maintainability. An important development in this regard is that the official google-research/bert repository has been archived and made read-only as of 25 September 2025. This change may complicate the long-term maintenance and security patching of systems that rely on that repository as their primary implementation reference. Although this does not in itself render BERT unsafe, it does shift greater responsibility onto system developers. Secure deployments should therefore rely on actively maintained forks or more recent implementations, and should introduce appropriate governance measures, such as version pinning, verification of model provenance, systematic dependency auditing, and ongoing monitoring for vulnerabilities.

Finally, the widely used paradigm of pre-training followed by task-specific fine-tuning introduces certain well-documented technical limitations. In particular, the objectives used during pre-training do not always align perfectly with the requirements of downstream tasks, which can lead to brittle behaviour in edge cases. For this reason, deployment of BERT-based systems requires rigorous evaluation procedures, including domain-relevant adversarial

testing, that allow the system to revert to more conservative predictions when the model's confidence is low.

3) *Privacy and data governance*

Privacy risks associated with BERT arise in two distinct phases: during pre-training and during subsequent deployment. In the pre-training stage, BERT is trained on very large, publicly available corpora, most notably Wikipedia and BooksCorpus. Although these datasets are publicly accessible, they may nevertheless contain material that is sensitive. This raises important concerns relating to representativeness and the proof of the data used to construct the training corpus. When BERT is later deployed, it is frequently fine-tuned on organisational datasets that may contain personal data—for instance, student assignments, clinical notes, or customer support transcripts. In such contexts, the use of the model becomes directly subject to applicable data protection regulations.

Empirical research indicates that privacy leakage is not merely a theoretical concern. In the healthcare domain, for example, studies have demonstrated a measurable risk of inferring whether particular records were included in the training data of language models, including architectures based on BERT. This finding is particularly relevant in light of the HLEG guidelines, which require that privacy protection extend throughout the entire lifecycle of the data. In other words, safeguarding privacy involves not only removing obvious identifiers but also maintaining effective control over how data are processed, stored, and reused.

It is important to note that BERT itself does not incorporate built-in privacy-preserving mechanisms. The model was not originally designed to employ techniques such as differential privacy during training, nor does it inherently provide audit trails or mechanisms for tracing the provenance of training data. Consequently, additional governance measures are needed, e.g. careful dataset management—such as ensuring lawful data collection, documenting legal bases for processing, and applying data minimisation principles—as well as restricting access to both training datasets and model outputs.

In particularly sensitive domains, organisations should seriously consider adopting stronger privacy-preserving approaches. These may include techniques such as differential privacy during fine-tuning, the use of controlled or secure execution environments for model deployment, and mechanisms for data deletion or redaction where necessary. It is also important to recognise that the open-source availability of a model does not in itself guarantee that its use will be privacy-safe.

4) *Transparency*

BERT performs relatively well in transparency, particularly compared to models that are not openly available. The architecture of the model and its training objectives have been publicly documented; the reference implementation and pre-trained models are openly distributed; and extensive technical documentation is available. Furthermore, the licensing terms permit external researchers and practitioners to inspect, evaluate, and reuse the system. These characteristics facilitate traceability, independent verification, and reproducibility, all of which are central to the transparency requirements articulated by the HLEG.

However, transparency has two distinct dimensions: the transparency of the system to relevant stakeholders and the interpretability of the model's internal processes. BERT remains a highly complex neural architecture, and the internal representations it produces are not readily interpretable to most users. This does not mean that BERT itself lacks transparency; rather, it implies that compliance with HLEG transparency principles depends significantly on the surrounding governance and documentation practices. Responsible deployment requires clear descriptions of the model's intended use, evidence of its performance across different populations or contexts, documentation of known limitations and failure modes, and explicit

communication of its operational boundaries. The fact that the primary reference repository is now archived further increases the importance of rigorous version control and provenance documentation. Organisations deploying BERT should therefore clearly record which implementation and pre-trained model they are using, as well as how these components are maintained or updated over time.

An additional advantage arises from the modular structure of many analytical workflows built around BERT. In practice, BERT embeddings are often incorporated into pipelines composed of distinct and separable processing steps. This modularity supports transparency at the level of the analytical process, since each stage—such as the generation of embeddings, their dimensional reduction, and the subsequent clustering or classification—can be independently examined. Such architectural transparency is ethically significant, particularly in contexts where stakeholders may need to understand how conclusions or classifications are derived from textual data.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

A well-established fairness risk associated with BERT is that, because the model learns statistical patterns from very large textual corpora, it may absorb and reproduce stereotypes present within those data. Empirical studies have indeed warned that contextualised language models can internalise, and in some circumstances even amplify, stereotypical associations embedded in the training material.

The manner in which a BERT-based system may produce unfair outcomes depends on several interrelated factors: first, the composition of the training data and the design of the downstream task during fine-tuning; secondly, the decision rules used to interpret and operationalise the model's outputs; and thirdly, the broader social and institutional context in which the system is deployed. For example, BERT can support the exploration of textual corpora through clustering or topic modelling, potentially reducing the amount of manual analysis required and revealing themes that might remain overlooked. However, these same processes may inadvertently marginalise minority linguistic forms or misclassify certain groups if the embeddings primarily reflect dominant language patterns.

Consequently, alignment with the expectations articulated by HLEG requires more than a general awareness of bias. It calls for systematic and measurable assessments, meaningful participation by affected stakeholders in determining what constitutes harm, and mitigation strategies that are tailored to the specific application context. In practical terms, BERT-based systems should therefore include subgroup performance reporting, targeted bias evaluations, the expansion or rebalancing of datasets where appropriate, explicit constraints on the inference of sensitive attributes, and human review of outputs that may carry risks for communities. Although the open availability of BERT facilitates such scrutiny, these safeguards must be deliberately implemented by those who design and deploy the system.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

The original documentation makes clear that the initial pre-training process is both time-consuming and computationally intensive, requiring substantial hardware resources. At the same time, it emphasises that adapting a pre-trained model for specific tasks—through fine-tuning—is considerably less demanding. This distinction has an important implication: the reuse of pre-trained models can reduce the need for repeated large-scale training across the field. Nevertheless, it does not eliminate the environmental costs associated with the original large-scale pre-training, nor does it address the cumulative impact of deployment and extensive task-specific adaptation.

Societal welfare considerations are inherently more difficult to capture through a single metric. BERT has significantly improved performance across many NLP tasks and supports

applications for searching, clustering, summarising, and analysing large collections of text. These capabilities can provide clear social benefits in domains such as education and scientific research, where the ability to navigate extensive textual information can enhance access to knowledge and facilitate informed discussion.

However, the same technical capabilities may also be applied in ways that enable surveillance or restriction if deployed without appropriate safeguards. For instance, a BERT-based classification system may be used to filter or prioritise content, or to generate user profiles. In practice, these imply the need for impact assessments and ongoing monitoring.

7) *Accountability*

BERT's open release, extensive documentation, and accessible tooling support certain forms of accountability: independent evaluation is possible, errors can be reproduced, and the research community is able to scrutinise the model's limitations. At the same time, the broad availability of the model can diffuse responsibility, since harmful outcomes typically arise not from the base model itself but from decisions made during fine-tuning, threshold setting, dataset selection, and integration into operational workflows.

The archival status of the primary code repository also affects accountability. Organisations that deploy BERT-based systems must determine how they will manage versioning, address emerging vulnerabilities, monitor potential performance degradation, and document the technical and organisational decisions taken during deployment and maintenance. To meet the accountability requirements set out by HLEG, systems built upon BERT should therefore incorporate clear governance structures. In practice, this includes establishing identifiable responsibility for the behaviour of the model in operation, maintaining logs and audit trails for significant outputs or decisions, providing mechanisms through which adverse impacts can be reported, and ensuring that individuals affected have accessible means to challenge those outcomes or seek remedies.

8) *Overall assessment*

BERT may be incorporated into systems that either support or undermine the development of trustworthy AI. Its principal contribution to reliability lies in its transparency: the architecture of the model, its source code, and its pre-trained weights have all been publicly released. In addition, the model can be readily adapted to specific tasks and integrated into broader analytical pipelines, which allows practitioners to evaluate and monitor its behaviour when it is deployed with appropriate care. At the same time, the most significant ethical risks associated with BERT—particularly those relating to fairness and privacy—are well documented. Research has shown that the model can reproduce and, in some circumstances, amplify stereotypes present in its training data. The responsible use of BERT requires deliberate mitigation measures, including bias evaluation, careful dataset governance, and privacy-protective deployment practices.

4.6. Assessment of AI tools provided by Consortium Partners

4.6.1. ECHO by Dembrane

Dembrane's AI-supported deliberation tool ECHO will be used within the AI4Deliberation project by the pilot partner ActionAid International Italia in their mass deliberation pilot study on climate change. After initial testing in the early sprint rounds, ECHO might be considered for inclusion into the AI toolkit, being one of the main deliverables of the AI4Deliberation project. This D2.1 deliverable, however, does not (yet) assess other AI tools used in other pilots, as it is not clear what kind of AI tools these pilots will, in fact, deploy (TBU). The only AI tool that will definitely be used in pilot trials is the ECHO tool in the Italian pilot. Platforms

used for other pilots, i.e. Consul, Debategraph, and openGov.gr could be assessed on whether they could responsibly integrate AI tools, but it is not clear which tools exactly the pilots would eventually decide to use, while assessment of tools potentially relevant for pilots is presented in chapter 4.5.2.

We analysed ECHO on the basis of the **EU High-Level Expert Group's (HLEG) Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (2019)**, and specifically the **Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)**. It should be noted that at the point of writing this review, the ECHO tool has not been utilised or tested (apart from a demonstrative presentation) within the AI4Deliberation pilot studies. Many key ethics aspects of ECHO will therefore need to be reassessed after the initial sprint rounds. The ethical and legal issues with regard to personal data protection have been extensively addressed in the DPIA, and are therefore omitted here to avoid overlap.

ECHO is an AI deliberation tool that voice-records participants' discussions on a given topic, transcribes them (1-on-1) and enables summarisations and analyses of the discussion. The discussions are initiated by hosts (which Dembrane calls "users"), who set up a profile on ECHO, and enable participants to partake in the discussion via scanning a QR code. Currently, ECHO is intended to be used in a live setting, with one or multiple devices (smartphones) recording the discussion between participants, then offering various functionalities (like summarisation, extraction of key points, etc.) in real time. In the future, Dembrane intends to adapt ECHO to function as an online app, enabling discussion between participants who are not physically present.

The AI4Deliberation project also aims to explore how video functionalities could be used to enhance deliberative processes. While ECHO enables real-time audio recording and discussion analysis, it does not facilitate video interactions between participants. During the course of the AI4Deliberation project, Dembrane entered into negotiations for a possible collaboration with Frankly – an open-source online video-based discourse platform designed to facilitate dialogue and collaborative decision-making. Frankly is operated by Harvard's Applied Social Media Lab at the Berkman Klein Centre for Internet & Society. Within the AI4Deliberation consortium, Dembrane and Frankly would integrate their platforms so that online video deliberation (Frankly) feeds into AI-powered sense-making (Dembrane's ECHO). Konnektable would be responsible for building the bridge software that connects the two platforms. The bridge is envisioned as a separate tool with its own license, which would keep Frankly's AGPL-3.0 copyleft from crossing into Dembrane's source-available BSL 1.1 license. All infrastructure enabling deliberations within the AI4Deliberation projects would be hosted in the EU (possibly using existing Dembrane or Konnektable infrastructure), meaning Frankly would be hosted on European servers, as the US-hosted version cannot be used for consortium work. This way, no participant's personal data would transit through US servers. In the initial sprints, participants would engage in an online video deliberation via the Frankly platform. The audio (but not video) recordings of the deliberation would then be sent to Dembrane for AI analysis. Participants would be informed about the AI4Deliberation project, the functionalities of both platforms, and their rights under GDPR before joining the discussion. During the course of the AI4Deliberation project, the Dembrane x Frankly integration would be tested mainly in the German and Italian pilots, possibly even in the Greek pilot (TBU). In the long term, a more intensive and multifunctional collaboration is envisioned, with participants in the deliberation process on Frankly having Dembrane's analysis functionalities at their disposal in real time during the discussion.

1. Human Agency and Oversight

Interaction with AI – Informing the user:

When users interact with the AI tool, which is possible through ECHO's chat feature, there is a disclaimer in the bottom of the chatbox that states the following: "ECHO is powered by AI. Please double-check responses." With this disclaimer, users are informed at all times that they are interacting with an AI tool, thus avoiding confusion.

Ensuring the human-in-the-loop:

ECHO offers a dashboard where hosts have full control over all content of their projects (discussions). There are several intervention mechanisms that hosts can use to correct the output, if they notice any erroneous or false results:

- Chat-based corrections: hosts can use the chat feature to effectively correct ECHO outputs by asking clarifying questions or requesting a new (different) analysis;
- Regeneration of outputs: hosts are able to regenerate summaries of a conversation if they spot inconsistencies;
- Hosts are able to ask for a re-transcription of a conversation if they spot inaccuracies in the initial transcription.

Measures against inappropriate outputs (e.g., slurs, hate speech and toxic content):

ECHO's transcription function transcribes the conversation word for word (1-on-1) without any alteration. This is necessary to ensure the accuracy of the source material, transparency of outputs and reproducibility, but also results in any inappropriate, damaging or toxic content being transcribed and not filtered out or redacted. However, within the analysis and summarisation functionalities, ECHO has built-in qualitative filters that should filter out inappropriate content (like swear words, slurs, etc.) and not include those in the output. Moreover, ECHO's outputs will be regularly compared with other common forms of note-taking and agreements, and there will be a peer review process as outcomes are presented to discussion participants, which enables them to verify the validity of the output.

Training of hosts:

Dembrane offers training for hosts to ensure that they have all the tools and knowledge necessary to moderate ECHO's actions and outputs, ensuring appropriate oversight of the AI tool and the human-in-command.

2. Technical Robustness and Safety

Misuse by users and adversarial effects:

ECHO can be vulnerable to misuse by malicious actors. There is always a possibility that users (hosts) use it to extract sensitive information from transcriptions without the proper consent of discussion participants, or carry out unauthorised surveillance of participants, effectively violating ECHO's Code of Conduct¹⁹⁵. However, this behaviour is mitigated by Dembrane's legal agreements with users and security measures. For example, authorised Dembrane staff

¹⁹⁵ https://github.com/Dembrane/echo/blob/main/CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md

can look at logs for any suspicious behaviour. This could also potentially cause a termination of the contract with the user if the tool is being misused.

Vulnerability to cyber-attacks, loss of data and tampering with data:

ECHO was not initially built with privacy-by-design or security-by-design principles. This could potentially lead to vulnerabilities such as tampering with data. However, as of recently, Dembrane is actively improving and advancing ECHO with a privacy- and security-based approach. ISO27001 certification ensures a robust Information Security Management System (ISMS) that adheres to the high standards of information security and mandates the implementation of security controls to prevent exploits and mitigate security risks.

Security updates:

Dembrane performs regular security checks with development tools that detect security risks and weak spots, as part of their ISMS.

Identified risks (design faults, technical faults, vulnerabilities for external attacks):

Because Dembrane did not initially develop ECHO with privacy and security principles at their core, they have identified some design faults. Following the ISO27001 certification, their approach to cybersecurity has been actively improved.

Ensuring secure storage and availability of data:

ECHO's data (recordings, transcripts, as well as outputs like reports and analyses) is securely stored in enterprise-level cloud storage (Microsoft Azure and DigitalOcean, both being processed in North-west Europe, without data export to third countries). Dembrane ensures secure storage through a compliance check of the provider to see if they comply with security standards.

Identification and mitigation of system errors:

Dembrane employs an internal project management tool to triage system errors. They also identify system errors through customer feedback, quality assurance testing and various tools that indicate vulnerabilities. Depending on the severity of the error, the development team acts accordingly and addresses the error. The error mitigation process is certified by ISO27001.

3. Transparency

Traceability of outputs:

ECHO stores complete transcripts of all conversations and uses references and citations to the quotes/dialogue lines it used in order to ensure what its analysis or summary is based on.

Transparency of the decision-making process:

For its summaries and analyses, ECHO only uses data from the conversation that the host themselves chooses through the user interface (through selecting the relevant conversation). If ECHO cannot find a reference within the individual discussion to answer the user prompt, it will utilise external sources to generate the insight, which will also be notified to the user.

Recording/logging the decision-making process:

The chat feature logs what data/conversation was used during the time of the prompt. Through this log, the user can see how ECHO shaped its answer in the chat. From ECHO's output in the chat, the user can also obtain information about how and why a certain summary or analysis was created, based on which conversations were used.

Reproducibility of outputs:

Due to ECHO's design, it is possible to reproduce ECHO's outputs with a high degree of similarity. At the moment, the supporting LLM's Dembrane uses (Gemini and Claude) utilise a probabilistic model, meaning that the output is based on probabilities that the LLM's calculate. This creates a layer of randomness, which leads to varying possibilities of outputs from the LLM. The reproduced outputs will usually be very similar, but not entirely 1-on-1 identical. Dembrane is attempting to move to a more deterministic approach, meaning that the output is based on precise input values that would lead to a more reproducible and consistent output.

Verification of outputs:

ECHO's code is open-sourced, meaning that everyone can see how the model formulates an output. However, Dembrane cannot verify how the supporting LLM is processing the information, as the LLMs use a probabilistic approach. This ensured a stable degree of reproduction, and thereby a high probability of verification of the output, but complete verification cannot be achieved due to the black box effect of the supporting LLM.

Communication of limitations to users:

ECHO has a Data compliance room¹⁹⁶ where users can find information on how ECHO is built, what security and safety features it includes and which possible legal or technical limitations the model exhibits. Furthermore, in their host training sessions and discussion rounds, Dembrane educates users on how to exercise control over ECHO and which capabilities ECHO has.

4. Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness

Mitigation of unfair bias:

ECHO employs various technical and procedural safeguards to mitigate unfair bias (like differentiation between male/female voice, accents, opinions being given priority because they are spoken more loudly/clearly, etc.):

1. Active model evaluation with documented processes for identifying and addressing bias
2. Speaker anonymisation prevents identity-based bias
3. Balanced analysis mandates require equal treatment of all speakers
4. Multilingual support with language-specific considerations
5. Real-world testing with diverse authentic sources
6. Open-source transparency enables community scrutiny

¹⁹⁶ <https://dembrane.notion.site/compliance-trust-at-dembrane>.

7. Configurable model selection allows optimisation for specific use cases

8. Ongoing monitoring and improvement (process exists but could be strengthened)

The open-source nature of the platform enables continuous community contribution to fairness improvements, and the documented model evaluation process ensures that biases can be identified and addressed when detected.

Identifying fairness issues:

Dembrane employs a Quality Assurance team that actively tests ECHO's reactions to ensure the quality of outputs. They perform continuous monitoring of the model as well as rely on external feedback to detect possible issues and discrepancies and address them (like speaking with a very strong accent, unclear pronunciation, etc.).

Continuous monitoring and flagging and redress mechanisms:

ECHO's outputs are presented to users and discussion participants, allowing them to verify the quality of the outputs. In the initial stages of development of the model, the AI results were compared with other common forms of taking minutes and making summarisations. There is no built-in redress mechanism for user complaints, but the host can create a new output if the original one is found insufficient or misleading.

Guidelines and awareness initiatives for development staff:

The feedback relating to fairness and possible bias, which is identified by the Quality Assurance team, as well as users and discussion participants, is forwarded to the Development Team, which then integrates appropriate adjustments to the model.

Access for users with disabilities:

Currently, ECHO allows only for text input for deaf and hearing-impaired people.

5. Societal and Environmental Well-being

Environmental issues and measures to reduce negative impact:

Dembrane has implemented a Climate Policy¹⁹⁷, based on a study¹⁹⁸ of the impact of using AI models. Key takeaways are:

- The biggest contributor to the carbon footprint of AI models is the electricity consumption needed for the computing power
- The carbon footprint of an AI model can be split into the training of the model and the usage of the model
- Sending an email has about the same impact as asking an AI model a question.
- Addressing the global climate crisis requires systemic change

The next steps which will be taken by Dembrane in this regard are:

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.dembrane.com/en-US/notion/1a49cd8427058081a4abcc8a03722588>.

¹⁹⁸ See <https://nationalcentreforai.jiscinvolve.org/wp/2025/05/02/artificial-intelligence-and-the-environment-putting-the-numbers-into-perspective/>

- Quantifying the carbon footprint associated with the usage of ECHO
- Green electricity procurement
- Supporting organisations working on climate change to facilitate systemic change

Potential risks for human work arrangements, society or democracy:

In democratic deliberations processes, ECHO exhibits deficiencies especially with regard to possible poorer outcomes when users are non-English speakers, as well as limitations with regard to deletion of personal data (individual voice from multi-user conversations). So far, no potential risks for work arrangements or society at large were identified. Dembrane is actively discussing the impact of ECHO with governmental organisations, and advocacy and research groups like DemNext and the Institute for the Future of Technology.

6. Accountability

Traceability of the development process:

Dembrane uses various platforms to control and log the development process of ECHO. They utilise Git version control and peer reviews to monitor what code is deployed and when.

Third-party audit:

Because ECHO is open-sourced, third-party audits are possible, as everyone can look into the code and how it is built. Dembrane can also provide accounts for third parties to navigate through ECHO's dashboard and portal.

Consultation with external experts, ethics reviews and risk trainings:

Dembrane engages in ongoing ethics discussions with DemNext. For their ISO27001 audit, an external Information Security advisor was employed, with the task of structuring a robust Information Security Management System. As part of their ISMS, Dembrane has organised security awareness training for its staff.

Reporting and redress mechanisms and mitigation measures:

As part of their ISO 27001-certified ISMS, Dembrane maintains an Incident Response Procedure that accepts reports from internal staff, users, and third parties. Reports can be submitted through various channels (e.g. in person, website, e-mail). Once received, incidents are triaged, escalated according to severity, and tracked to resolution under the ISMS framework.

4.6.2. oAMF by University of Dundee (UNIVDUN)¹⁹⁹

oAMF is a system designed to automatically identify, extract, and structure argumentative elements—such as claims, premises, and their relationships—from textual data. It applies NLP

¹⁹⁹ Compliance assessment is based on the following:

- <https://oamf.arg.tech/> (13. 2. 2026),
- <https://github.com/arg-tech/oAMF> (13. 2. 2026),
- Debela Gemechu, Ramon Ruiz-Dolz, John Lawrence, and Chris Reed. 2025. Practical Solutions to Practical Problems in Developing Argument Mining Systems. In Proceedings of the 12th Argument mining Workshop, pages 100–106, Vienna, Austria. Association for Computational Linguistics,

techniques to model argument structures for tasks such as legal analysis, policy evaluation, or research synthesis.

1) *Human agency and oversight*

oAMF is particularly effective in giving individuals meaningful control over their actions. The information on oAMF emphasises user choice in how processes are created and executed, offering both local and remote options as well as different ways of interacting with the system depending on the user’s level of experience. The platform is described as “allowing a public which is not very skilled in technology to use argument mining” and includes a “no coding needed” function. This is an example of enhancing user agency, as it enables a wider range of people—not only those with technical expertise—to experiment with and explore how arguments are structured. When considered through the HLEG framework, this represents a constructive step towards supporting human agency, provided that oAMF is used to assist individuals in forming their own views rather than to automatically make decisions on their behalf.

The same features that empower users may, however, also encourage excessive reliance on the system. For example, the website allows users to upload text and run processes “straight on the oAMF server”, yet it does not provide guidance about appropriate uses of the tool, situations in which it should not be relied upon, or the steps users should take to verify results before acting upon them. A trustworthy AI system would normally accompany a no-coding interface with clearly stated limitations, explicit warnings about contexts in which performance may be unreliable, and guidance on when human review is necessary. Such safeguards are particularly important when outputs may influence the moderation of speech, the identification of individuals involved in discussions, or the summarisation of contested public debates.

2) *Technical robustness and safety*

oAMF’s design is clearly modular and container-based. The documentation describes modules implemented as Flask web services and deployed within containers. This approach generally improves reproducibility, separates dependencies more effectively, and supports more stable operation compared with ad hoc scripting solutions. The tutorial also explains that modules are “loaded when needed” in order to reduce memory and processing demands. This contributes to the sustainability and maintainability of the system, as it encourages the use of only the resources required for a particular task rather than keeping the entire system running continuously. In addition, the available documentation presents evaluation results, including benchmark comparisons in which example pipelines are tested against leading methods on standard tasks such as argument component and relation identification. Providing this type of evaluation is an appropriate way to demonstrate technical robustness, as it shows not merely that the system functions, but that it performs well under measurable conditions.

Nevertheless, robustness in the sense used by the HLEG framework also encompasses safety and resilience to misuse or attack, and the publicly available material raises some concerns in this respect. The documentation and diagrams indicate that many module endpoints are accessed via basic HTTP rather than HTTPS, and the web service architecture is described as operating through HTTP requests. Although HTTP may not necessarily be insecure within a tightly controlled environment, it is not an ideal default for a server that may be accessible

- Debela Gemechu, Ramon Ruiz-Dolz, Kamila Górka, Somaye Moslemnejad, Eimear Maguire, Dimitra Zografistou, Yohan Jo, John Lawrence, and Chris Reed. 2025. The Open Argument Mining Framework. In Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 3: System Demonstrations), pages 318–328, Vienna, Austria. Association for Computational Linguistics.

over the internet, particularly when users might upload text containing sensitive information. Furthermore, the documentation refers to shared passwords for the drag-and-drop interface, and the example password appears extremely simple and easily guessable, which represents poor practice in secure deployment. From the perspective of the HLEG requirements, these are relevant issues: inadequate access control and the absence of encrypted communication can directly affect user safety, data confidentiality, and the reliability of the system's outputs.

A proportionate and rule-compliant response would be to treat a publicly accessible demonstration environment as a distinct and restricted mode of deployment. Such a mode could include strict limits on the volume of uploaded data, rate-limiting of requests, logging of activity, encrypted communication channels, and the use of temporary or single-use authentication credentials. At the same time, documentation should clearly recommend local deployment for any use involving sensitive or potentially harmful data. oAMF's architecture already supports running the system locally, so the technical capability is in place; what appears to be missing is clearer guidance and a secure-by-default configuration in the publicly available materials.

3) Privacy and data governance

The oAMF web interface suggests that privacy could present a potential concern, as users are able to upload input data and then run pipelines on the server. In practice, the text uploaded could contain, e.g. personal data or political opinions, that individuals would ordinarily expect to remain private. This risk is particularly relevant given that argument mining is often applied to debates and public discussions. The section of the public oAMF website describing this functionality does not appear to include a privacy notice, a policy explaining how long uploaded material may be retained, or guidance on the kinds of data that should not be submitted to the public server. From the perspective of the HLEG requirements, this lack of communication regarding governance is problematic, as privacy protection involves not only internal safeguards implemented by developers but also the provision of clear information that enables users to act in ways that protect their own data.

At the same time, the system's design includes a feature that can support stronger privacy protection. oAMF allows modules and pipelines to be installed and executed locally, and the documentation indicates that processes can run either locally or remotely on the server. If users are encouraged to operate pipelines on infrastructure they control—e.g., on local machines, or within secure research environments—privacy risks can be significantly reduced when working with datasets that contain personal data. In addition, the use of a standardised interchange format such as xAIF, together with module metadata files, can support governance by making the movement of data and its provenance more transparent.

To align more closely with the expectations outlined in the HLEG framework, it would be advisable for a project to publish a clear, accessible statement on data governance for the hosted server. Such a statement should explain what information is logged, what data may be retained, how long it is stored, and who may have access to it. It would also be appropriate for the statement to recommend local deployment when working with personal data. Based on the materials reviewed, it is not clear whether uploaded data is retained at all; this uncertainty represents a weakness in governance for a tool that aims to support high standards of reliability and trustworthiness.

4) Transparency

oAMF's most significant alignment with the HLEG requirements lies in the transparency of its design and development. The framework is open-source, accompanied by documentation and tutorial materials, and uses the xAIF format to standardise input and output representations.

In addition, the system incorporates evaluation and visualisation components, allowing results to be inspected rather than remaining opaque. The cited research work also provides comparative performance data, enabling users to form an informed view of the system’s capabilities. These features represent meaningful forms of transparency, particularly when compared with argument-mining services that are closed and accessible only through an API, where users have little or no visibility into how the analysis is produced.

Nevertheless, transparency also requires that the information presented to users be clear, and coherent. In this respect, there appears to be a notable discrepancy in the licensing information. The available documentation indicates that the framework is released under the LGPLv3 licence, whereas the licence file within the repository specifies GNU GPLv3, and the repository page itself lists GPL-3.0. This is not merely a minor legal detail: the licence determines who may use the software, what obligations apply to those who build upon it, and how confidently users can rely on the accuracy of the documentation.

Transparency about the limitations of the underlying models is also relatively underdeveloped. While the documentation describes the system’s modules and interfaces, it does not systematically provide module-level model cards that would explain issues such as potential biases in the training data, intended domains of use, or the types of errors that may occur in practice. The system’s architecture appears capable of supporting this form of disclosure, as the module metadata schema includes fields relating to training data and licensing. However, the documentation does not establish a clear requirement or standard practice for completing and presenting this information, which limits the degree of transparency.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

oAMF supports a form of diversity that is widely valued within the argument mining research community: pluralism in theoretical approaches. The available documentation emphasises that argumentation can take a variety of forms, and that the framework allows components based on different theoretical traditions to “live with, and assist, one another”. This represents an important design principle, as it avoids the implicit bias of imposing a single model of argumentation across all disciplines, languages, and cultural contexts.

However, the HLEG requirements address non-discrimination and fairness in terms of the real-world effects that systems may have on individuals and groups. In the field of NLP, these concerns often relate to biases present in datasets and pre-trained models. Although the oAMF publications report evaluations using commonly used datasets and include components that rely on contemporary language models, they do not appear to provide fairness assessments across demographic groups, dialects or similar. In public discourse, argument mining tools could easily be interpreted as mechanisms for evaluating or “scoring” the quality of people’s reasoning. If the underlying models perform less reliably for certain communities, there is a risk that the system could inadvertently reinforce injustice by misinterpreting or undervaluing arguments originating from marginalised groups.

Accessibility is addressed to some extent through the provision of multiple interfaces. The framework offers an API, a drag-and-drop interface, and a web interface, which may encourage participation from users with different levels of technical expertise. Nevertheless, accessibility in the sense intended by the HLEG framework also involves principles of inclusive and universal design—for example, compatibility with screen readers, multilingual support, and clearly written documentation. The available documentation does not provide evidence of such measures, and therefore, it cannot be concluded that the system meets such a broader accessibility standard.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

oAMF is associated with research initiatives concerning collective intelligence and democratic deliberation, which indicates that it is clearly intended for use in societal contexts. From the perspective of human and societal well-being, the potential benefits of oAMF are considerable, as, e.g. it could assist researchers and developers of civic technologies in analysing the quality of public discussions and identifying argumentative patterns.

At the same time, the potential risks are equally significant. A system that allows users to submit text and extract argument structures at scale could also be used to profile large groups of individuals, optimise persuasive messaging, or selectively moderate or suppress particular viewpoints, depending on the intentions of those deploying it. The publications reviewed do not include a responsible-use policy, a discussion of possible misuse, or guidance for deployment in civic contexts where the stakes are high. The absence of such socio-political risk analysis represents a shortcoming, especially given that the tool is designed to lower the technical barriers to using argument mining.

With regard to environmental sustainability, oAMF incorporates at least one design choice that may contribute positively to environmental considerations: modules are loaded only when required, which reduces unnecessary computational resources. The associated publications also note performance differences between modules based on large language models and faster, lighter alternatives, a distinction that may influence both energy consumption and the feasibility of deployment in resource-constrained environments. Nevertheless, the available materials do not provide a full lifecycle assessment, guidance on energy-efficient deployment, or recommended configurations that prioritise a lower carbon footprint. To strengthen alignment with sustainability principles, it would be beneficial to provide “efficiency profiles” and estimated computational costs for individual pipelines, enabling users to make more informed decisions about the environmental impact of their deployments.

7) Accountability

The modular architecture of oAMF, its use of the standardised xAIF exchange format, and its support for evaluation metrics are valuable features in terms of accountability. Together, these elements make the structure of a pipeline easier to inspect, results easier to reproduce, and individual modules easier to evaluate through common visualisations and benchmarks. This reflects the way accountability is typically realised in technical systems: by enabling others to replicate, scrutinise, and question outcomes rather than relying solely on claims made by the developers.

However, accountability in the sense envisaged by the HLEG framework also involves clear mechanisms for redress and procedures for managing risks and incidents. In this respect, the publicly available documentation provides limited evidence. There does not appear to be a clear statement outlining the responsibilities of those operating the hosted service, a dedicated channel for reporting security vulnerabilities, a process for reporting harm or misuse, or transparent logging of activity on shared systems that users could consult. The previously noted inconsistency in licensing information also raises accountability concerns, as it may make it more difficult for users and developers to understand and comply with the applicable legal obligations.

To better align with the HLEG requirements, oAMF could benefit from several governance improvements, e.g. a transparent page describing how the service is governed, a documented security posture covering issues such as encryption in transit, authentication practices, and a clear statement explaining data ownership when materials are uploaded. In addition,

publishing provenance information for each module—indicating its origin, maintainers, and version history—would further strengthen the system’s accountability.

8) Overall assessment

oAMF aligns well with the principle of transparency through its commitment to open science and practical reproducibility. Its modular architecture, the use of standardised data formats, and the availability of multiple ways to interact with the system all contribute to making the framework inspectable and replicable. These are precisely the kinds of structural design choices that help ensure trustworthy AI can be meaningfully examined and reused by those who adopt it later. In this sense, oAMF provides a strong technical foundation for transparency and scientific accountability.

At the same time, certain weaknesses remain in areas such as the communication of privacy policies, the security of the system by default, and the mechanisms through which responsibility is assigned and exercised. Addressing these issues would not necessarily require substantial technical changes; rather, it would largely involve strengthening the public-facing documentation and formalising guidance on responsible use. Clearer governance information, explicit privacy and security policies, and documented procedures for accountability would help bring the tool into closer alignment with the HLEG framework.

4.7. Pilot Trial Assessment

Sprint 1 of pilot trials featured initial stages of AI tools testing and evaluation, identifying and mapping possibilities of enhancing pilot deliberation processes with AI capabilities. At this stage, only third-party AI tools and ECHO (see 5.5 above) were tested, as other proprietary AI tools were still under development and not yet ready for deployment in pilot projects. In cooperation with WP5 leaders, pilots either contributed pre-existing datasets (Greek Pilot, International pilot) or conducted internal small-scale deliberation rounds involving only pilot staff (German and Italian Pilots). The collected data and deliberation transcripts were subsequently processed with AI tools to create summaries, extract arguments or test moderation capabilities. Ethics risks in Sprint 1 were assessed against HLEG Guidelines for trustworthy AI. The ethics risk assessment includes risk situations encountered by pilots in Sprint 1 as well as risk situations which could potentially arise in the subsequent sprints, as far as those can already be anticipated. Generally, across all pilot partners, the risks were assessed as low, mainly because no personal data were processed and no research participants were recruited in the pilot trials. Nonetheless, by applying the principles of privacy-by-design and ethics-by-design across all stages of the AI4Deliberation project, risk scenarios were identified and mapped, and potential risk mitigation measures were proposed.

4.7.1. Greek Pilot (GFOSS)

During Sprint 1 the Greek pilot collected historical data from past public consultations hosted on the opengov.gr platform. No live deliberation with research participants took place. Specifically, GFOSS used already publicly available citizens’ comments from past government consultation rounds on the opengov.gr platform. Personal identifiers (usernames and email addresses) were removed prior to any use of the data. The comments were then used to evaluate and benchmark AI tools developed under WP4, including moderation pipelines (hate speech detection, spam/off-topic filtering), summarisation tools, and argument extraction capabilities. Moderation testing was performed on 42 annotated synthetically generated

Greek-language comments, including inappropriate, appropriate and borderline comments, which were evaluated using three pipeline configurations (LLM-only, LlamaGuard → LLM, and Detoxify → LlamaGuard → LLM). For summarisation and argument extraction, selected comments from actual previous deliberations on the opengov.gr platform were used.

In Sprint 2, an integration with active (current or upcoming) public consultations on an AI4Deliberation replica of opengov.gr is planned (TBU – as of today the pilot has not decided whether a parallel deliberation will be held or not). The following activities will be carried out:

- (a) applying a formal anonymisation technique (involving NER-based detection and removal of personal identifiers from comment text) before updating the dataset;
- (b) deploying validated AI tools for moderation, argument extraction, topic modelling and automated summarisation on new consultation data;
- (c) engaging Ministry administrators to evaluate AI-generated summaries against manually produced consultation reports; and
- (d) updating the platform terms and conditions to inform participants about the AI4Deliberation project and the use of their comments for research purposes.

If the pilot proceeds with current/live consultations, a public notice will be posted on the opengov.gr platform informing citizens about the project. An external ethics review will also be pursued, and Sprint 2 will not commence before obtaining local, Greek institution's, ethics approval.

Table 1: Greek Pilot - Risk identification

Risk situation	Description	Mitigation measure
Human agency and Oversight		
Inadequately informing participants about interacting with an AI system	There was no participant interaction with AI tools in the first sprint.	Should participants interact with AI systems during Sprint 2, they will be informed about this with explicit notices, either included in terms and conditions on the respective platform and/or a public notice explaining the AI4Deliberation project and informing participants about the use of AI tools. Most probably, AI tools will operate in back-end analysis mode rather than in direct participant interaction.
Failing to ensure adequate human intervention in the actions of the AI tool (human-	There was no participant interaction with AI tools in the Sprint 1. AI tools were	As AI tools will most probably operate in the back-end in Sprint 2 as

in-the-loop), risking false, untrue or misrepresented outputs	used under the supervision of the pilot and beneficiary CERTH for summarisation, argument extraction and moderation.	well, GFOSS and opengov.gr platform administrators will retain full control over AI tool outputs. All AI-generated summaries, moderation decisions and analysis reports will be reviewed before any external dissemination to citizens.
Autonomous decision-making by an AI tool	No autonomous decisions were made by the AI tools in Sprint 1 and no such decision making is planned in the upcoming sprints. All AI outputs (moderation flags, summaries, argument clusters) are advisory and subject to human review. No automated actions (such as automatic comment removal) are implemented or planned. Content moderation flags serve as recommendations for human moderators, not automated decisions.	No autonomous decision making by the AI tool is envisioned for Sprint 2.
Inadequate training of admin staff on exercising control	No specific training on AI tools tested in Sprint 1 was received by pilot staff.	Should the use of the AI tools require training or explanation for the admin of the graph, we recommend appropriate training sessions and materials be prepared by technical partners.
Technical Robustness and Safety		
Exposure of AI system to cyber-attacks and data tampering	In Sprint 1 only third-party AI tools were used.	See relevant third-party AI tools risk evaluation for safety features (chapter 4.5.2.4). The opengov.gr platform is managed by the Greek government and operates under government cybersecurity standards. GFOSS's data infrastructure uses GRNET hosted servers and services within the EU with restricted access. No incidences of cyber

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		attacks have been reported.
Insecure storage and data unavailability	Data extracted from the opengov.gr platform is made permanently publicly available by the Greek government, ensuring long-term availability of data sets. Additionally, for the purposes of the AI4 Deliberation project, data was extracted from the platform and stored on GFOSS and project servers.	The opengov.gr platform is managed by the Greek government and operates under government cybersecurity standards. GFOSS's data infrastructure uses GRNET hosted servers and services within the EU with restricted access for authorised project staff. AI processing outputs (reports, summaries, evaluations) are stored in the same secure environment and shared with consortium members via secure channels. Regular backups are maintained.
Transparency		
Opacity of AI output generation	GFOSS in cooperation with CERTH can explain that AI tools process comments using large language models (LLMs) for tasks such as summarisation, argument extraction, and content moderation. The specific AI tools used (e.g., Claude Sonnet, LLaMA, Detoxify, LlamaGuard) and their general methodology can be described. However, as with all LLM-based tools, providing a detailed mechanistic explanation of individual outputs is inherently limited. GFOSS can explain the purpose, methodology, and general approach, but not a deterministic rationale for each specific output.	For the use of AI tools in the coming sprints GFOSS can explain the purpose, methodology, and general approach of their use, but not a deterministic rationale for each specific output.
Inadequate documentation of the AI-supported deliberation process	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	

Inadequate communication of AI system's limitations to participants	Specific limitations of the used AI system were not evaluated and addressed in Sprint 1.	In future pilot trials with civil society participants, the limitations of specific AI systems will need to be communicated to participants.
Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness		
Failure to ensure diversity and non-discrimination of participants	During Sprint 1, no participants were involved.	The coming sprint trials will take place via the opengov.gr platform. The platform is open to all Greek citizens and residents, with no registration barriers beyond providing a username and email. The platform does not restrict participation based on any demographic criteria, and the open-access nature inherently supports broad participation, though self-selection bias is an acknowledged limitation of any voluntary online consultation.
Inadequate handling of vulnerable participants	In Sprint 1 no vulnerable participants were included.	As participation in online deliberative processes via the opengov.gr platform are open to all Greek citizens and residents, participation of vulnerable participants can be expected. Their specific vulnerabilities will not be specifically addressed, and platform use will be available to them under its general operating conditions.
Failure to provide redress mechanisms for participants, who feel they have been discriminated against	During Sprint 1 no participants were involved.	In Sprint 2 pilot partners will explore the feasibility of introducing a feedback mechanism for participants to report concerns about AI-related outputs.
Inadequate fairness guidelines for admin staff	During Sprint 1 no participants were involved.	Fairness and bias mitigation should be internally addressed by

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		the pilot partner, with carefully structured methodology of testing AI tools on datasets collected via the opengov.gr platform, to ensure adequate representativeness and inclusion of participant groups.
Societal and Environmental Well-being		
Inadequate evaluation of environmental impact	A formal environmental impact assessment of the deliberation process has not been conducted for Sprint 1.	The use of third-party AI tools (e.g. LLMs) is energy-intensive, which should be addressed on a broader scale within the AI4Deliberation project.
Risks to human work arrangements, society and democracy	No such risks identified in Sprint 1.	In the forthcoming pilots a key risk identified through the AI4Deliberation project is the so-called “AI penalty” – research evidence suggesting that citizens may be less willing to participate in deliberations when they know AI tools are involved. This poses a risk to democratic engagement. Mitigation measures include transparent communication about the AI’s role (advisory, not decision-making), human oversight of all outputs, and designing AI integration to enhance rather than replace human analysis of public consultation contributions.
Accountability		
Inadequate technical documentation and inability of external audit	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	

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Failing to conduct an external ethics review (where applicable)	For Sprint 1, the external ethics review was not necessary, as no research participants were recruited and only publicly available data from the opengov.gr platform was processed.	Before the activities of Sprint 2, the pilot should apply for an external ethics review by an appropriate institution providing ethics assessments for research projects.
Inadequate flagging mechanisms for participants reporting vulnerabilities, risks and biases	In Sprint 1 no such risk was present as no research participants were recruited.	For Sprint 2, GFOSS should explore the feasibility of implementing a feedback channel (e.g., a contact form or email address of a DPO) where participants can raise concerns about AI-related aspects of the consultation process.

4.7.2. German Pilot (CBAM)

In Sprint 1, the pilot simulated a deliberation round with five staff members of the Bamberg Municipality, discussing a mock topic regarding the trade-off between parking lots and bicycle infrastructure in the inner city of Bamberg. The single deliberation round lasted about a half hour, with participants assuming preassigned roles (pro, against, mediator and uncivil (rude) debater). The debate was conducted in German. Despite participants being employees of Bamberg City – consortium members, the discussion moderator asked for their consent to be recorded and provided information about the aim of the discussion, similar to what would be provided to civil society participants in future trials. The discussion was recorded via the ECHO tool on one of the participants' laptops. ECHO produced a word-for-word transcript of the discussion in German, which was exported and sent to CERTH for processing with third-party AI tools for summarisation, argument extraction and content moderation (civility).

For the summarisation task, LLM models Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1, and Pixtral Large 25.02 were tested, as well as the built-in summarisation function of the ECHO tool, which reportedly performed better than the LLMs.

For moderation, three pipelines that combine three different third-party AI tools (Detoxify, LLaMA Guard, LLMs) were developed and evaluated. The results (detecting uncivil behaviour) were most promising when all three were used.

For argument extraction LLM models Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, and Pixtral Large 25.02 were used, in combination with oAMF (a collection of open-source modules for argument mining tasks).

The format of Sprint 1 (small-scale and in-person deliberation) does not reflect the format in which citizen participation in Bamberg regularly occurs, as the deliberative process takes place primarily online via the Consul platform (provider DemokratieToday) operated by the Bamberg municipality, whereas Sprint 1 of the pilot trial was held as a small-scale face-to-face deliberation process. In Sprint 2, participation is expected to be expanded to approximately

20-50 citizens, recruited through an open call and representatives of diverse civil groups (e.g., people with disabilities, students, women, migrants). Expectedly, the participants will be invited to a face-to-face information session, but will proceed with the asynchronous online discussion. Due to technical constraints, ECHO will likely be used again as a standalone environment, with the same tools retested alongside additional candidates. The possibility of including not only a voice but also a video recording of participants (via the ECHOxFrankly integration) might be explored in the upcoming sprints (TBU). In the final sprint, ECHO and Consul might be used in parallel, as possible cooperation talks are already ongoing with the providers of the Consul tool, who might support the AI4Deliberation project with the necessary interface definition (TBU).

Table 2: German Pilot - Risk identification

Risk situation	Description	Mitigation measure
Human agency and Oversight		
Inadequately informing participants about interacting with an AI system	During Sprint 1, no research participants were recruited, as employees of the pilot beneficiary conducted a mock deliberation instead. In Sprint 2 the participation of civil society members is envisioned, whereby it is necessary to obtain their informed consent for participation in the research project, for personal data processing and voice recording.	In Sprint 2, before the asynchronous online deliberation process, an in-person information session is planned, where participants will be given all necessary information about their participation in the project. Their explicit consent to personal data processing and audio recording will also be obtained (either in writing or online). A disclaimer will be included in the header of the online deliberation space, where participants will be able to find all necessary information.
Failing to ensure adequate human intervention in the actions of the AI tool (human-in-the-loop), risking false, untrue or misrepresented outputs	In Sprint 1 transcripts of the debate were processed subsequently with AI tools, to create a summary, extract arguments and detect uncivil behaviour (moderation). The accuracy of results was evaluated manually by CERTH and the pilot.	The process of manual evaluation of AI outputs by comparing them to the input debate transcript will probably (TBU) be the same in Sprint 2.
Autonomous decision making by AI tool	No autonomous decisions were made by the AI tools in Sprint 1, apart from moderation tools identifying content as potentially	No autonomous decision-making by the AI tool is envisioned for Sprint 2.

	uncivil (racism, swear words, insults), that was subsequently checked by the research team.	With regard to content moderation (civility detection), the pilot considers two options of human intervention in the decision-making process of the AI tool: (1) either the tool is programmed to ping a human moderator to doublecheck the decision about the potentially problematic participant comments or (2) warning the participants directly by the tool informing them, that their comment might be inappropriate, and whether they want to reformulate it. In either case, we advise against an option where the AI tool would autonomously edit or delete a comment it identifies as offensive, discriminatory or inappropriate, as this could lead to censorship and skew the results of the deliberation.
Inadequate training of admin staff on exercising control	No specific training received by pilot' research team, apart from how to exercise admin control over the ECHO tool.	Should the use of the AI tools require training or explanation for the host of the deliberation, we recommend appropriate training sessions and materials be prepared by technical partners of the AI4Deliberation project.
Technical Robustness and Safety		
Exposure of AI system to cyber-attacks and data tampering	In Sprint 1 only third-party AI tools and ECHO were used and no risks were identified.	See relevant third-party AI tools and ECHO risk evaluation for safety features above. When the Bamberg City Consul platform will be used in Sprint 2 the deliberation process will be embedded in the municipal systems and therefore underly the same high data security

		measures as over every citizen data.
Insecure storage and data unavailability	Voice recordings and transcripts from Sprint 1 are stored via ECHO storage capacities.	See relevant third-party AI tools and ECHO risk evaluation for safety features above. When the Consul platform will be used, data will be stored on municipal servers, where only administrators and research team members have access to it.
Transparency		
Opacity of AI output generation	Third-party AI tools were used on transcripts generated by ECHO to extract a summary and debate arguments and detect uncivil language.	<p>ECHO transcribes voice recordings word-for-word.</p> <p>For the use of ECHO summarisation and the processing of transcripts with third-party AI tools for summarisation, argument extraction and moderation, the pipelines of utilised AI tools are documented.</p> <p>While the innermost workings of ECHO and other AI tools used are subject to a level of opacity, the accuracy of the summary and extracted arguments can reliably be traced by research staff from the transcript. For future deliberation rounds, it is advisable to integrate a notice-and-action mechanism for cases where admins/participants notice errors or irregularities in the functioning of the tools (for example inconsistent summaries, errors in argument identification, etc.). A procedure for correction of the</p>

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		erroneous outputs should also be put in place.
Inadequate documentation of the AI-supported deliberation process	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	
Inadequate communication of AI system's limitations to participants	Specific limitations of the used AI system were not evaluated and addressed in Sprint 1.	In future pilot trials with civil society participants the limitations of specific AI systems should be communicated to participants, such as the inability of participants to request deletion of their voice pattern from the ECHO recording. For Sprint 2 an information session before the start of the sprint is planned, as well as a feedback loop after evaluating the test results.
Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness		
Failure to ensure diversity and non-discrimination of participants	Sprint 1 was a mock deliberation with only CBAM team. A relatively good spread over age and gender was ensured, but the educational and professional background of participants was very similar.	For Sprint 2 the pilot will actively address representatives of diverse citizen groups as well as the 'citizen associations' of several districts. Since district-residents often share the same socio-economic backgrounds, they seek to get a representative view over Bamberg's citizenship.
Inadequate handling of vulnerable participants	In Sprint 1 no vulnerable participants were included.	For Sprint 2, no participants will be specifically targeted solely on the basis of vulnerability or disadvantage in the use of platforms or AI tools.
Failure to provide redress mechanisms for participants, who feel they have been discriminated against	Only 5 municipality staff members participated in Sprint 1. Civil society participants are planned to be included in Sprint 2.	There is no specific redress mechanisms envisioned for Sprint 2, but Bamberg city has an official anti-discrimination-officer who can be contacted in such a case along with the admin

		of the planned deliberation.
Inadequate fairness guidelines for admin staff	Only 5 municipality staff members participated in Sprint 1.	The municipality's anti-discrimination-officer is involved in the project activities on the side of CBAM.
Societal and Environmental Well-being		
Inadequate evaluation of environmental impact	Besides minimal server costs there were no significant environmental impacts identified in Sprint 1.	
Risks to human work arrangements, society and democracy	No such risks identified in Sprint 1, as the deliberation process is designed to foster democracy and civic virtue.	
Accountability		
Inadequate technical documentation and inability of external audit	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	
Failing to conduct an external ethics review (where applicable)	For Sprint 1 the external ethics review was not necessary, as the only participants are consortium member employees.	For Sprint 2 the pilot plans to have an ethics review by the University of Bamberg's ethics board, which will be presented with an exhausting description of the research project and its ethics implications.
Inadequate flagging mechanisms for participants reporting vulnerabilities, risks and biases	In Sprint 1 no such risk was present.	For Sprint 2, participants can file a report or complaint with the responsible person at the municipal participation office, beneficiary's DPO and the admin of the planned deliberation.

4.7.3. International Pilot (TG)

In Sprint 1 the International pilot focused on the internal development of the Long Covid graph, which was not yet opened to, nor shown to external participants. The International pilot provided three datasets (e.g., parliamentary debate transcripts and a research briefing, among others). The current capabilities of the early versions of the AI4Deliberation AI tools were tested: Llama, Pixtral and Claude were used for argument extraction, and the UNIVDUN tool oAMF for argument mining. Upon manual review by the pilot, no immediate utility of the tested tools could be established. The pilot team, however, explicitly notes that this first round

was exploratory and context-specific, and that a more conclusive assessment would require a substantially larger corpus.

Sprint 1 tests have identified promising pathways for Sprint 2, including experimenting with using the outputs of the LLMs as inputs for the argument mining tools. During Sprint 2, the internal curation of the Long Covid graph will continue in parallel with initial outreach to Long Covid stakeholder groups to introduce the AI4Deliberation project, the International pilot, and the Long Covid graph, and to gather feedback on the pilot and the graph (including on the aims, content, and ethical framing of the pilot).

Table 3: International Pilot - Risk identification

Risk situation	Description	Mitigation measure
Human agency and Oversight		
Inadequately informing participants about interacting with an AI system	N/A. There was no participant interaction with AI tools in the first sprint.	Any participation involving AI tools in Sprint 2 will be preceded by explicit notices, clearly informing participants that they are interacting with an AI system or that they are being asked to provide feedback on examples of AI-generated outputs. The notice will either be part of the Privacy policy or displayed at the landing page of the graph (TBU).
Failing to ensure adequate human intervention in the actions of the AI tool (human-in-the-loop), risking false, untrue or misrepresented outputs	There was no participant interaction with AI tools in the first sprint. AI tools were used under the supervision of the pilot team and CERTH for argument extraction and argument mining from selected datasets.	In Sprint 2 no integration of AI tools into the graph is envisioned. But when such integration will occur (possibly in later sprints – TBU), it could be in the format of participants prompting the AI tool to make a contribution to the graph (expanding meaning, adding nodes, creating a visual abstract or summary, etc.). In such cases AI outputs will be labelled as such, and participants will be able to give feedback on false AI outputs. Ensuring human oversight in the later

		sprints will depend on the choice of AI tools, which is yet to be decided upon.
Autonomous decision making by AI tool	No autonomous decisions were made by the AI tools in Sprint 1 and no such decision making is planned in the upcoming sprints. The AI tools could merely suggest new content which could be added to the graph, if the participants so choose.	No autonomous decision making by the AI tool is envisioned for Sprint 2.
Inadequate training of admin staff on exercising control	No specific training on AI tools tested in Sprint 1 was received by pilot staff. However, the staff did attend external training sessions, seminars open to the public, aimed primarily at public officials interested in using AI in public deliberation.	Should the use of the AI tools require training or explanation for the admin of the graph, we recommend appropriate training sessions and materials be prepared by technical partners.
Technical Robustness and Safety		
Exposure of AI system to cyber-attacks and data tampering	In Sprint 1 only third-party AI tools were used and no such risks were identified.	See relevant third-party AI tools risk evaluation for safety features above.
Insecure storage and data unavailability	Data included in the graph is stored on secure TG servers.	See DPIA for TG security features.
Transparency		
Opacity of AI output generation	In Sprint 1 the argument extraction from selected datasets was unsatisfactory.	The pilot team is aware that AI outputs cannot be fully transparent, but they do expect a sufficiently granular explanation of AI outputs in the coming trials, depending on the AI tools chosen.
Inadequate documentation of the AI-supported deliberation process	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	
Inadequate communication of AI system's limitations to participants	Specific limitations of the used AI system were not evaluated and addressed in Sprint 1.	In future pilot trials with research participants the limitations of specific AI systems will be communicated to participants, and their

		feedback will also be sought.
Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness		
Failure to ensure diversity and non-discrimination of participants	The aim of the graph's mapping process is to actively seek out and include all ideas and perspectives. As the mapping process is open and participants can expand on or contradict other participant's content this adds to the inclusivity of the process.	
Inadequate handling of vulnerable participants	In Sprint 1 no vulnerable participants were included.	See DPIA for inclusion of vulnerable participants.
Failure to provide redress mechanisms for participants, who feel they have been discriminated against	In Sprint 1 no research participants were recruited or civil society members participated at the creation of the graph.	In Sprint 2, research participants will be able to raise concerns or complaints related to discrimination or unfair treatment directly with the pilot staff (via email or call).
Inadequate fairness guidelines for admin staff	In Sprint 1 no research participants were recruited or civil society members participated at the creation of the graph.	Pilot staff includes a professionally trained/qualified mediator, which reduces the risk of biases and discrimination going unnoticed or remaining unaddressed.
Societal and Environmental Well-being		
Inadequate evaluation of environmental impact	The deliberation process is entirely virtual – which limits some of the potential dimensions of the environment impact associated with physical deliberations. The pilot has also selected a data centre provider (IBM) that conducts comprehensive environmental impact assessments of its data centre operations and is committed to achieving net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030.	It is possible that the use of third-party AI tools (like big LLMs) is energy-intensive, which should be addressed on a broader scale within the AI4Deliberation process.
Risks to human work arrangements, society and democracy	No such risks identified in Sprint 1.	As research participants will be able to contribute their personal health

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		<p>data to the graph in the coming sprints, it is possible that such disclosure could negatively affect their relationship with employers and insurance companies. The information sheet, consent form and/or privacy policy should include explicit warnings that the disclosure of health data might impact their work arrangements or influence their rights. Participants will be required to explicitly acknowledge these risks, before they can contribute to the graph.</p>
Accountability		
Inadequate technical documentation and inability of external audit	<p>The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1). Additionally, the deliberation process occurs, and is documented, openly and transparently through the evolving of the structure and content of the graph, with all changes to content remaining visible.</p>	
Failing to conduct an external ethics review (where applicable)	<p>For Sprint 1 the external ethics review was not necessary, as no external research participants contributed to the graph.</p>	<p>Before the activities of Sprint 2 the pilot plans to apply for an external ethics review by an appropriate institution or body providing ethics assessments for research projects.</p>
Inadequate flagging mechanisms for participants reporting vulnerabilities, risks and biases	<p>In Sprint 1 no such risk was present.</p>	<p>For Sprint 2, research participants will be provided with contact points to report potential risks, vulnerabilities or biases. Feedback on</p>

		these issues will be actively solicited, noted, and shared with the whole consortium, with the aim of promptly addressing any issues arising.
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4.7.4. Italian Pilot (AAIT)

The Italian pilot focuses on a national-level deliberation on the governmental National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (NCCAP). Within the AI4Deliberation project, AAIT aims to test how AI-supported tools can enhance their deliberative processes, which have previously been held as live sessions (town hall concept). In Sprint 1, AAIT organised three deliberation rounds: 1 online and 2 face-to-face, each attended by 4 different participants, all AAIT staff members. At the online session, a transcript of the conversation was made by the Microsoft Teams tool, and at the live sessions by the ECHO tool. The conversation was held in Italian, with different roles assigned to participants to ensure contrasting positions. The transcripts were subsequently sent to beneficiary CERTH for summarisation and argument extraction using third-party AI tools, as well as ECHO for summarisation.

Sprint 2 foresees the involvement of citizens in a small-scale deliberative process comprising three online meetings with 25-30 participants each. Expectedly, the ECHO tool, combined with the Frankly video functionality, will be tested. Ideally, the deliberation process will be enhanced with the following AI tool functionalities: live (real-time) summarisation, live AI facilitation, report generation and voting procedure.

Table 4: Italian Pilot - Risk identification

Risk situation	Description	Mitigation measure
Human agency and Oversight		
Inadequately informing participants about interacting with an AI system	In Sprint 1, consent by research participants was not necessary, as only research team was involved. Still, the participants were adequately verbally informed at the beginning of every session, that they will be interacting with AI systems for research purposes.	In Sprint 2 the participation of civil society members is envisioned, whereby their informed consent for participation in the research project, personal data processing and voice recording will be obtained. They will also be adequately informed that they are interacting with an AI system.
Failing to ensure adequate human intervention in the actions of the AI tool (human-in-the-loop), risking false, untrue or misrepresented outputs	In Sprint 1 transcripts of the discussion were processed subsequently with AI tools, to create a summary and extract arguments. The accuracy of results was	Ensuring human oversight in Sprint 2 will depend on the choice of AI tools, which is yet to be decided upon.

	<p>evaluated manually by CERTH and the members of the pilot team.</p> <p>With regard to the ECHO tool (used for transcription and summarisation), the facilitator of the discussion (host) can intervene, contextualise, correct or disregard AI-generated outputs if they appear inaccurate, misleading or incomplete.</p>	
Autonomous decision making by AI tool	No autonomous decisions were made by the AI tools in the first sprint.	No autonomous decision making by the AI tool is envisioned for Sprint 2.
Inadequate training of admin staff on exercising control	<p>AAIT staff received specific information and guidance on the functioning, scope and limitations of the ECHO tool, enabling them to exercise informed oversight throughout the process.</p> <p>With regard to third-party AI tools no such training was received, but the AAIT staff were knowledgeable about the use of the Microsoft Teams recording and transcript generation option.</p>	<p>Should the use of the AI tools require training or explanation for the host of the deliberation, appropriate training sessions and materials are recommended to be prepared by the technical partners, especially with regard to the use of Frankly video functionalities.</p> <p>With regard to the moderation of debates among research participants, break-out sessions may present certain challenges, as the team members will not be able to provide a moderator for every group. To mitigate this risk, participants must be informed about the functionalities of the AI tools and equipped with the necessary skills to support effective self-moderation.</p>
Technical Robustness and Safety		
Exposure of AI system to cyber-attacks and data tampering	In Sprint 1 only third-party AI tools and ECHO were used and no risks were identified.	See relevant third-party AI tools and ECHO risk evaluation for safety features above.

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Insecure storage and data unavailability	Voice recordings and transcripts from Sprint 1 are stored via ECHO storage capacities. Transcripts are also stored by the pilot and CERTH, using their own storage facilities with access limited to project staff.	See relevant third-party AI tools and ECHO risk evaluation for safety features.
Transparency		
Opacity of AI output generation	Third-party AI tools and built in ECHO functionalities were used on transcripts generated by Microsoft Teams and ECHO to extract a summary and debate arguments.	<p>ECHO transcribes voice recordings word-for-word. Microsoft Teams transcription was revised only to remove artefacts (e.g., “background noise” references and likely transcription hallucinations), while the substantive content of participants’ contributions was left unchanged.</p> <p>For the use of ECHO summarisation and the processing of transcripts with third-party AI tools for summarisation and argument extraction, the pipelines of utilised AI tools are documented. While the innermost workings of ECHO and other AI tools used are subject to a level of opacity, the accuracy of the summary and extracted arguments can reliably be traced by research staff from the transcript.</p> <p>For future deliberation rounds, it is advisable to integrate a notice-and-action mechanism for cases where admins/participants notice errors or irregularities in the functioning of the tools (e.g. inconsistent summaries, errors in argument identification,</p>

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		etc.). A process for correction of the erroneous outputs should also be put in place.
Inadequate documentation of the AI-supported deliberation process	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	
Inadequate communication of AI system's limitations to participants	Specific limitations of the used AI system were not evaluated and addressed in Sprint 1.	In future pilot trials with civil society participants the limitations of specific AI systems should be communicated to participants (e.g. the inability of participants to request deletion of their voice pattern from the ECHO recording).
Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness		
Failure to ensure diversity and non-discrimination of participants	Sprint 1 was a mock deliberation round with only 4 participants, all AAIT staff, therefore diversity and representation could not be ensured.	For Sprint 2 the pilot will apply recruitment procedures aimed at ensuring diversity among participants, but with a limited number of participants, a representation structure completely reflecting the demographic structure of Italian civil society will most probably not be achievable. Recruitment of participants will be effectuated via an online open call, with participants most probably belonging to public groups interested in climate change and testing of AI tools.
Inadequate handling of vulnerable participants	In Sprint 1 no vulnerable participants were included.	Sprint 2 trials will be open to adult participants only. While vulnerable individuals are not specifically targeted, their participation is not excluded. If vulnerabilities emerge, AAIT addresses them on a case-by-case basis.

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Failure to provide redress mechanisms for participants, who feel they have been discriminated against	Sprint 1 was a mock deliberation round with only 4 participants, all AAIT staff, therefore diversity and representation were not sought.	In Sprint 2 participants will be able to raise concerns or complaints related to discrimination or unfair treatment directly with AAIT facilitators.
Inadequate fairness guidelines for admin staff	Sprint 1 was a mock deliberation round with only 4 participants, all AAIT staff, therefore diversity and representation were not sought.	AAIT adopted internal documents to address awareness of bias and fairness issues among staff and users of their services, such as the Sexual Harassment, Exploitation, and Abuse Policy, Data Protection Policy and On-line speech Policy.
Societal and Environmental Well-being		
Inadequate evaluation of environmental impact	The environmental impact was not evaluated in Sprint 1, but remains limited as all activities are conducted online, reducing travel and associated emissions. It is possible that the use of third-party AI tools (like big LLMs) is energy-intensive.	
Risks to human work arrangements, society and democracy	No such risks were identified in Sprint 1.	No such risks are anticipated for Sprint 2.
Accountability		
Inadequate technical documentation and inability of external audit	The activities in Sprint 1 were documented adequately by the pilot and WP5 leader CERTH (see Deliverable 5.1).	
Failing to conduct an external ethics review (where applicable)	For Sprint 1 the external ethics review was not necessary, as the participants were research team members.	Before the activities of Sprint 2 the pilot plans to apply for an ethics review by the CNR (National Research Council), a national public body providing ethics assessments for research projects.
Inadequate flagging mechanisms for participants reporting vulnerabilities, risks and biases	In Sprint 1 no such risk was identified.	For Sprint 2 research participants will be provided with contact points to report potential

		risks, vulnerabilities or biases. Any such reports will be collected by AAIT and forwarded to technical consortium partners, to make necessary corrections to AI systems.
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5. Other

5.1. Intellectual Property Rights

Since one of the main aims of the AI4Deliberation project is the development of proprietary AI tools for democratic deliberation purposes, intellectual property rights (IPR) to those tools, as well as data sets, models, accompanying documentation, roadmaps, and other derived materials, should be addressed on a Consortium level. As per Article 38 of Regulation (EU) No 2021/695 establishing Horizon Europe, any materials which can be the object of IPR, and are generated by project partners, belong to the partner that has produced them. Where multiple partners jointly generate these materials and their respective contributions cannot be separated, the partners are deemed joint owners, unless otherwise agreed. Each project partner shall retain ownership of their “Background” – information, data, know-how and intellectual property rights held prior to the AI4Deliberation project and necessary for the execution or exploitation of project results, as stated in the Consortium Agreement. Access rights to Background shall be granted to other partners on a royalty-free basis for research and development activities within the project and, where agreed, on fair and reasonable conditions for further exploitation. The IPR framework should ensure that intellectual property derived from the AI4Deliberation project is managed in a manner consistent with EU legislation and open science principles, and balances the protection of innovation with ethical principles like transparency, inclusiveness and accountability.

5.1.1. Patent Rights

Under current legislation and jurisprudence, AI algorithms *per se* are generally excluded from patentability as abstract mathematical methods, except where they contribute to a technical effect or solve a technical problem beyond the mere processing of information. Patent protection may apply to technical inventions, including novel methods, architectures, or systems developed to support deliberation processes, but patent protection is difficult to obtain for software solutions.

Before filing any patent application, the potential risks as well as benefits should be assessed, including the chances of a successful application, costs, jurisdictions (national patents vs. European patent applications), potential overlaps with other partners’ IPR, dissemination obligations and open access obligations. The consortium will have to seek external legal representation before any attempts to file a patent application, as it does not have the necessary capacities to facilitate such an assessment.

5.1.2. Copyright and Related Rights

AI tools, including source code, documentation, data structures, and interfaces, as well as all other materials produced within the AI4Deliberation project (like guidelines, roadmaps, strategies, legal documents, impact assessments, scientific papers, etc.) are protected under copyright law as literary works (pursuant to national copyright legislation and EU legislation such as Directive 2009/24/EC on the legal protection of computer programs and EU Directive 2019/790 on copyright in the Digital Single Market).

As a basic principle of copyright law, the author is a natural person who has created the copyrighted work (writer of the text or the code), but can transfer material (but not moral) copyrights onto others, who become copyright holders (like his employer, the project

partner). The copyright holder, if so agreed with the author, may then transfer these rights to other third parties or grant licences for the use of the works. Since the Consortium as a whole does not constitute a legal entity, it cannot hold copyright; therefore, these rights shall remain with the individual project partners.

Another copyright-related aspect is the licensing of background materials – project partners should conclude appropriate agreements allowing the use of their proprietary AI tools as well as training data for the purposes of the project.

The use of third-party copyrighted materials (like user comments on public platforms) for training purposes must rely on lawful grounds such as licences, exceptions for text and data mining under Directive 2019/790, or public domain sources. If any third-party AI tools are to be integrated into the AI4Deliberation project results, appropriate licences for the use of the third-party IP must be obtained or reviewed (in case of open-code software), to ensure that the use of third-party tools is aligned with the aims of the Consortium with regard to dissemination and exploitation of project results. The project should encourage open-source dissemination of project results where feasible, but appropriate copyright notices and attribution requirements must be upheld.

5.1.3. Trademarks

Signs, project names, and logos developed in connection with the AI tools may be registered as trademarks – on a national or supra-national (EU) level. Ownership of such marks would normally reside with the partner in charge of project coordination, unless otherwise agreed by the Consortium. The use of trademarks by partners or third parties would require a written agreement, and branding guidelines should be established. Trademark protection does not extend to AI tools' functionality or content but serves as an indication of origin for the public.

5.1.4. Licensing and Exploitation

Each IPR holder may grant licences to other project partners and third parties for further research, development, or deployment of the AI tools, as well as the use of other materials created as a result of the AI4Deliberation project. Licensing deeds will be required when project results (like the AI toolkit) should be integrated into potential third-party software (like deliberation platforms of municipalities and governments). Such licensing must correspond with the project's objectives, internal agreements and EU funding conditions. Licensing terms should encourage responsible and ethical use of project results, ensuring inclusivity, accountability, and human oversight.

Where the AI tools will be released as open-source, standard licences such as EUPL, GPL, or Apache may be employed, depending on compatibility and the desired level of openness. Dual licensing strategies may be adopted to accommodate both open access and commercial exploitation. In accordance with Horizon Europe Grant Agreement provisions, the Consortium should endeavour to ensure open access to scientific publications and, where feasible, to research data underpinning the AI tools. All project results, including datasets, source code, and documents, that will be made available to the public, should contain clear licensing information and attribution statements.

Licences should specify at least:

- Rights granted (e.g., reproduction, modification, redistribution);

- Obligations regarding attribution and acknowledgement of EU support;
- Limitations concerning commercial use, if any;
- Compliance with ethical standards, including avoidance of bias, misinformation, or manipulation in public deliberation contexts.

5.1.5. End User License Agreement (EULA)

The AI tools developed under the AI4Deliberation project should be accompanied by an End User License Agreement (EULA) governing access, use, and modification of the tools.

The EULA should include the following elements:

- Identify the licensor (the owning partner);
- Specify permissible uses, emphasising public interest and non-manipulative application in democratic settings;
- Prohibit reverse engineering, decompilation, or circumvention of security mechanisms except as permitted by law;
- Require users to acknowledge the source of funding and comply with data protection and ethical obligations;
- Include disclaimers limiting liability for indirect or consequential damages arising from use of the software;
- Mandate compliance with applicable EU and national laws governing AI transparency, accountability, and human oversight (like the EU AI Act);
- If appropriate, clauses ensuring that derivative works generated by end users are shared under terms compatible with the project's objectives.

5.2. Terms and Conditions

Terms and Conditions (T&C) are essential for all AI tools developed within the AI4Deliberation project. They define the legal, ethical, and operational framework under which users may access and use the tools. Particularly for AI tools supporting democratic deliberation, T&C can help prevent misuse, manipulation, or discriminatory application of the technology. T&C should clearly outline the scope of permitted use, intellectual property ownership, licensing and attribution requirements, data privacy and processing obligations, liability disclaimers, and ethical use provisions. They should also specify applicable law, procedures for amendments or termination, and acknowledgement of EU funding.

TBU – IK's ability to assist with the legal maintenance of intellectual property (like the drafting of licensing agreements, assisting in trademark registration procedures, etc.) would depend upon the complexity of these actions, which at this point are hard to foresee. Should it turn out that the management of intellectual property rights in the project results will be too broad for IK's capacities, external legal counsel is advised.

6. KPIs

The KPIs for **ethics and legal aspects** of the AI4Deliberation project are set in the following way:

- ethics and legal aspects ≥ 5
- together with Guidelines ≥ 10

The KPIs have been achieved by identifying the ethics and legal aspects related to: personal data, vulnerable research participants and AI issues in eight groups of AI tools.

The **methodology** for reaching KPIs takes into consideration correspondence with beneficiaries with advice, meetings of the ethics and legal compliance team (IK) with consortium partners and providing partners with documentation and advice in the area of legal and ethics compliance of their work.

More specifically:

1. Ethics and legal aspects: obtaining informed consent from pilots' citizens, pilots' employees, best practice case owners, and platform owners

Guidelines issued by IK:

review of internal pilot consent forms and policies, guidance on key aspects of information sheets and consent forms, review of draft information sheet and consent form template for AI4Deliberation, guidance on survey tools, data storage and possible transfers outside the EEA, guidance on voice recording of interviews, review of external polling company IPSOS data protection policy for UBAM, reuse of project consent form for workshops organised by partners (TUD).

Date: dedicated meetings on 15.1.2025 and 24.1.2025, correspondence exchanged between January 6 and March 10, 2025.

2. Ethics and legal aspects: Obtaining external ethics approval

Guidelines issued by IK:

Identification of cases and pilots, for which an external ethics approval is necessary/advisable, how to find and contact entities that could conduct an external ethics approval (specifically for beneficiary AAIT), review of external ethics approvals for CERTH and UBAM.

Date: meeting (interim plenary) on 31.1.2025

3. Ethics and legal aspects: Intellectual Property Issues

Guidelines issued by IK:

addressing and explaining all possible IP rights which could be relevant for AI4Deliberation projects' outputs (copyright for software, T&Cs, roadmaps and other accompanying documentation, trademarks for names and logos, know-how), addressing the problems with obtaining patent protection for software solutions.

Date: plenary meeting Delft 13.3.2025 - 14.3.2025

4. Ethics and legal aspects: Data Management Plan

Guidelines issued by IK: review of the draft DMP with comments and suggestions in relation to its content and structure.

Date: email correspondence of 17.3.2025 and 29.4.2025

5. Ethics and legal aspect: DPIA

Guidelines issued by IK: guidance to pilot partners on addressing existing and potential personal data protection risks, guidance on how to mitigate identified risks.

Date: up to 30.10.2025

6. Ethics and legal aspects: AI ethics review

Guidelines issued by IK: Review of Tier 1 AI tools with identification of possible red flags and recommendations on tool choice and risk mitigation measures, and the ethics assessment of Dembrane's ECHO tool.

Date: up to 30.10.2025

7. Ethics and legal aspects: Echo+Frankly integration

Guidelines issued by IK: Review and meeting with Dembrane and coordination team on legal obligations related to the planned integration and use of new tool Frankly for capturing video.

Date: up to 13.1.2026

8. Ethics and legal aspects: evaluation of the KT's proposal for anonymisation

Guidelines issued by IK: review of the technical description of anonymisation.

Date: up to 13.2.2026

9. Ethics and legal aspects: Deliverable D4.1

Guidelines issued by IK: review of Deliverable 4.1: AI toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph, on the ethics and legal compliance of the AI4Deliberation architecture.

Date: up to 24.2.2026

10. Ethics and legal aspects: WP4 AI toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph

Guidelines issued by IK: attending weekly WP4 meetings on AI toolkit development and architecture building.

Date: up to 11.3.2026

11. Ethics and legal aspects: meetings with pilot and technical partners

Guidelines issued by IK: ethical and legal advice on the design and deployment of AI tools in pilots, including personal data protection updates related to DPIA.

Date: up to 11.3.2026

7. List of Annexes

Annex 1 – CERTH: Citizens Questionnaire in English

Annex 2 – CERTH: Semi-structured interview for external experts who have conducted deliberations

Annex 3 – CERTH: Semi-structured interview with experts who own deliberation platforms

Annex 4 – CERTH: Semi-structured interview for the Greek pilot

Annex 5 – CERTH: Citizen Questionnaire in Greek

Annex 6 – CERTH: A self-assessment

Annex 7 – CERTH: Research protocol

Annex 8 – CERTH: The ethics approval

Annexes 9-10 – UBAM: Application and the ethics approval

Annexes 11-12 – DebateGraph’s privacy policies and registration page

Annex 13 – Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

Annex 14 – AI tools shortlist

Annex 15 – AI tools initially assessed, but later not used in WP4

Annex 16 – AI4Deliberation Architecture

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Annex 16 – AI4D Architecture

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Annex 1
CERTH: Citizens Questionnaire in English

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Consent form

Purpose of the Questionnaire: This survey is conducted as part of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using, and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The aim of this questionnaire is to understand: a) your opinion regarding some features and functionalities of an AI-enabled deliberation platform, b) your perceptions regarding this platform's security and your readiness to use it, and c) your perception regarding its usefulness. If you continue, there will be a short introduction to further facilitate your understanding.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the survey is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate without any reason or justification. You may withdraw at any time while completing the questionnaire without any reason, justification, or consequences. **After the submission** of the questionnaire **you do not have** the option to withdraw.

Data collected: To participate in the survey, you will be asked to complete a questionnaire in which the information you will fill is **Gender, Age, Education Level, and Country of residence**. The above are optional, and you can complete and submit the questionnaire without sharing any of these.

We have selected the anonymous survey mode to prevent the saving of any personal data, including your IP address. The privacy statement on the protection of your personal data while using the EUSurvey tool can be found here:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/privacystatement>

However, the **IP** of every connection may be saved by the provider of EUSurvey for security reasons. For more information see:

https://surveys.acer.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/helpauthors#_Toc14

Please note, that Centre for Research & Technology Hellas, which is responsible for the International Pilot, is not the provider of the EUSurvey tool and your IP address will not be shared with us.

Confidentiality: All responses will be kept confidential and stored securely. The provided information is anonymized. Only authorized research personnel from Centre for Research & Technology Hellas, which is responsible for the International Pilot, will have access to the raw data.

If you have any questions about conducting the survey, you can contact us here themis@iti.gr.

Potential Risks: No risks from participating in the questionnaire are foreseen. However, if you feel uncomfortable at any point, you may choose to stop.

Benefits: Your participation contributes valuable insights for the project's AI tool kit. While there are no direct personal benefits to you, your support is greatly appreciated.

DECLARATION OF CONSENT - I declare that I have been fully informed about the terms of my participation in the survey.

By checking **Yes I consent**, I confirm that:

- I have read and understood the information provided above.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this survey.
- I am at least 18 years old.

Yes I Consent

No, I do not Consent

Gender

- Male Female Other I do not wish to answer

Age

- 18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+

- I do not wish to answer

Education Level

- No formal education Primary School Secondary school
 Associate Degree or Vocational Training Bachelor's Degree
 Master's Degree Professional Degree Doctorate (PhD)
 I do not wish to answer

Country of residence

- Germany Greece Italy United Kingdom Other (Free text)
 I do not wish to answer

Introduction

In its ideal form, democracy is based on dialogue and deliberations between citizens, where everyone is given an equal opportunity to express their opinion (e.g., propose topics, share arguments, vote on alternatives). However, this process can be challenging to conduct and sustain at a large scale in modern societies. AI-enhanced tools might offer new ways to support dialogue at larger scales and move public deliberations closer to the democratic ideal.

Our goal is to understand how AI tools can be used to support public deliberation in democracies and, through this, to build a freely available AI toolkit that groups anywhere in the world can use to enhance their own deliberations. The answers you share in the questionnaire will help us identify and prioritise the initial features of the AI toolkit, which we will then test and refine in four deliberative projects – starting later this year – in Germany, Greece, Italy, and an international initiative based in the UK.

Estimated completion time: 20 minutes

1. Have you used Artificial Intelligence tools in any context, if yes was it helpful?
 - Definitely not helpful
 - Probably not helpful
 - Not sure
 - Probably helpful
 - Definitely helpful
 - I have not used
2. If yes, could you describe briefly the context and what you found helpful or not? (open question/optional)

For each of the following platform functions, please indicate your preferred balance between AI support and human oversight.

1 = Fully human-led 2 = Mostly human-led with AI support 3 = Equal balance between human and AI involvement 4 = Mostly AI-led with human oversight 5 = Fully AI-led

	1	2	3	4	5
Discussion summarization	<input type="radio"/>				
Discussion moderation	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking	<input type="radio"/>				
Translation services	<input type="radio"/>				
Identifying areas of agreement	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggesting alternative perspectives	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing user feedback	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracking discussion patterns	<input type="radio"/>				

Below, you will find a series of features and functionalities of an AI-enabled deliberation platform.

Please indicate how important each of the following features are, on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Definitely not Important, 2 = Probably not important, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Important, 5 = Very important

	1	2	3	4	5
Discussion summarization (Automatically generates summaries of discussions)	<input type="radio"/>				
Discussion moderation (Automatically suggests guidelines and flags inappropriate content)	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking (Identifies and addresses factuality, providing verified information to ensure that facts being used are correct during deliberations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Translation services (Offers automated translations)	<input type="radio"/>				

Identifying areas of agreement (Clusters similar points and identifies key categories in discussions)	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggesting alternative perspectives (Proposes diverse viewpoints to enrich discussions and encourage critical thinking)	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing user feedback (Analyzes feedback to prioritize improvements)	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracking discussion patterns (Monitors engagement trends and dynamics to optimize future deliberations)	<input type="radio"/>				

For each of the following questions, state which of the following functionalities an AI-enabled deliberation platform is important to have based on your own perspective:

	1	2	3	4	5
3. How important is it to enable participants to flag the AI-generated summaries of discussions for errors?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. How important is it for the AI to actively moderate (monitor, regulate, facilitate) discussions to ensure inclusiveness?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. How important is it to have AI to suggest relevant sources and evidence during discussions?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. How important is it for AI to flag potentially misleading information?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. How important is it for AI to provide clear explanations when content is identified as potentially misleading?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. How important is it to allow participants to suggest improvements to automatic translations?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. How important is it for the AI to suggest deliberations and topics based on your preferences and previous activity?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. How important is it to be connected with different perspectives on the topics being discussed?	<input type="radio"/>				

11. How important is it to provide evidence for the suggested different perspectives?	<input type="radio"/>				
12. How important is it for you to know how and why AI acts when contributing to discussions (e.g., content moderation, summarization, consensus building)?	<input type="radio"/>				
13. How important is it to save and make publicly available audit logs of significant AI interventions in discussions (e.g., content removal, fact-checking decisions, consensus summaries)?	<input type="radio"/>				
14. How important is it to allow participants to provide feedback on AI features and contribute to their improvement through structured feedback mechanisms?	<input type="radio"/>				
15. How important is it to encourage meaningful participation in public discussions through civic engagement incentives (such as deliberation expertise badges, consensus-building achievements, dialogue quality recognition, etc.)?	<input type="radio"/>				
16. How important is it to recognize meaningful contributions from participants through contextualized achievement signals that reflect the quality and impact of participation (e.g., bridging opposing viewpoints, elevating evidence-based discussion, and fostering inclusive dialogue, community-building karma)?	<input type="radio"/>				
17. How important is it to have the option to upload an avatar instead of using your photo?	<input type="radio"/>				
18. How important is it to enable participation in discussions via video?	<input type="radio"/>				
19. How important is it to enable participation in discussions via audio?	<input type="radio"/>				
20. How important is it to offer an option of participating under a pseudonym instead of your real name?	<input type="radio"/>				

The following statements evaluate your perceptions of the platform's security and your readiness to use an AI-enabled deliberation platform. Please rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. I do not consider it safe to provide personal information on an AI-enabled deliberation platform.	<input type="radio"/>				
22. I worry that the information I make available over an AI-enabled deliberation platform may be misused by third parties.	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Whenever something gets automated using AI, it is important to check carefully that there are no mistakes.	<input type="radio"/>				
24. I feel uneasy about AI systems shaping important deliberations without human oversight.	<input type="radio"/>				
25. I worry that my input in the AI-enabled platform's deliberation process could be misinterpreted by the AI systems.	<input type="radio"/>				

The following statements assess your perceptions of an AI-enabled deliberation platform's usefulness. Please rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

	1	2	3	4	5
26. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would enhance the effectiveness of my participation in deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
27. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would make it easier for me to participate in deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
28. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would increase my ability to participate in more deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
29. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would enable me to contribute more meaningfully to shaping and improving deliberation processes.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Do you have any other suggestions about how AI could be used to enhance deliberation processes? (Open question/optional)

31. Do you have any other specific concerns about the use of AI in deliberations? (Open question/optional)

Annex 2

CERTH: Semi-structured interview for external experts
who have conducted deliberations

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Consent form

Purpose of the interview: This interview is being conducted as part of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using, and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The interview aims to obtain critical information (requirements) about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the interview is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate without any reason or justification. You may withdraw at any time during the interview without any reason, justification, or consequences. After the submission of your answers you do not have the option to withdraw.

Data collected: In this interview, you will be asked only about your **role** in the organisation without mentioning the organisation's name.

In the interview, there will be a **voice recording** and it will be stored locally on the computer of the interviewer for a calendar week at max. After the transcription of your answers, the voice recording will be destroyed. The transcripts may also be shared with other entities who are part of the research project consortium and their employees, to which the controller entrusts the performance of specific activities in the scope of the research project.

Confidentiality: All responses will be kept confidential and stored securely. Only authorized research personnel from Centre for Research & Technology Hellas will have access to the raw data. If you have any questions you can contact the data controller here themis@iti.gr.

The data will be processed based on consent to the processing of personal data and a statement of the purpose(es) for the processing (taking part in this research project). You may revoke your consent to the processing of personal data at any time before the data is aggregated. Such revocation does not affect processing which had already been completed upon consent before its revocation.

Data retention period: Your personal data collected for this research project shall be processed within the duration of the project and retained only as long as it is necessarily required to achieve the purpose of this project. Upon completion of the project, personal information will be deleted/anonymized.

Your rights are the following:

- to access data and to receive copies of the actual data;
- to correct (rectify) your personal data;
- to restrict processing of personal data;
- to erase personal data, subject to provisions of Art. 17 section 3 of the GDPR;
- to file a claim with the relevant authorities, if you believe data processing violates the law.

Consent:

By signing below, you confirm that:

- You have read and understood the information provided above.
- You voluntarily agree to participate in this interview.
- You consent to the voice recording of the interview.
- You understand that the recording will be stored locally for a maximum of one week and then deleted or earlier if the transcription is completed.
- You are at least 18 years old.

For the participant

Questions for the interview:

1. What's the role of the interviewee in their organisation? (Do not mention the organisation name)
2. What deliberation process have you used and for what purpose?
3. What platform did you use within that process?
4. What AI features, if any, did that platform have?
5. Was the deliberation successful, Yes or No and why?
6. What were the benefits and challenges of conducting the deliberation, how use of AI helped?
7. What would be your advice for the AI4Deliberation project? What AI features should we implement?

General opinion

8. Is there anything else you would like to mention?

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Annex 3

CERTH: Semi-structured interview with experts who own deliberation platforms

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Consent form

Purpose of the interview: This interview is being conducted as part of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using, and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The interview aims to obtain critical information (requirements) about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the interview is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate without any reason or justification. You may withdraw at any time during the interview without any reason, justification, or consequences. After the submission of your answers you do not have the option to withdraw.

Data collected: In this interview, you will be asked only about your **role** in the organisation without mentioning the organisation's name.

In the interview, there will be a **voice recording** and it will be stored locally on the computer of the interviewer for a calendar week at max. After the transcription of your answers, the voice recording will be destroyed. The transcripts may also be shared with other entities who are part of the research project consortium and their employees, to which the controller entrusts the performance of specific activities in the scope of the research project.

Confidentiality: All responses will be kept confidential and stored securely. Only authorized research personnel from Centre for Research & Technology Hellas will have access to the raw data. If you have any questions you can contact the data controller here themis@iti.gr.

The data will be processed based on consent to the processing of personal data and a statement of the purpose(es) for the processing (taking part in this research project). You may revoke your consent to the processing of personal data at any time before the data is aggregated. Such revocation does not affect processing which had already been completed upon consent before its revocation.

Data retention period: Your personal data collected for this research project shall be processed within the duration of the project and retained only as long as it is necessarily required to achieve the purpose of this project. Upon completion of the project, personal information will be deleted/anonymized.

Your rights are the following:

- to access data and to receive copies of the actual data;
- to correct (rectify) your personal data;
- to restrict processing of personal data;
- to erase personal data, subject to provisions of Art. 17 section 3 of the GDPR;
- to file a claim with the relevant authorities, if you believe data processing violates the law.

Consent:

By signing below, you confirm that:

- You have read and understood the information provided above.
- You voluntarily agree to participate in this interview.
- You consent to the voice recording of the interview.
- You understand that the recording will be stored locally for a maximum of one week and then deleted or earlier if the transcription is completed.
- You are at least 18 years old.

For the participant

Questions for the interview:

1. Some information about the platform (e.g. open-source, maintenance, owner, hosting)
2. What are the main features of the platform? (e.g. gamification, multimodal, video, massive deliberations, AI features);
3. Where and how has the platform been used?
4. What are the problems they face?
5. How do you see the role of artificial intelligence in your platform?
6. Are you planning to adopt AI? If so, what features?
7. What do you see as the advantages and what are the difficulties?
8. What would be your advice for the AI4Deliberation project? What AI features should we implement?

General opinion

9. Is there anything else you would like to mention?

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Annex 4

CERTH: Semi-structured interview for the Greek pilot

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Φόρμα συναίνεσης

Σκοπός της συνέντευξης: Αυτή η συνέντευξη πραγματοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του έργου AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) που χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση. Ο στόχος του έργου AI4Deliberation είναι να παράσχει εργαλεία ηθικής τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ολοκληρωμένη καθοδήγηση, ώστε να βοηθήσει τις κυβερνήσεις στη θεσμοθέτηση, τη χρήση και την αξιολόγηση πολυτροπικών, παιχνιδιοποιημένων, μαζικών δημόσιων διαβουλεύσεων.

Η συνέντευξη στοχεύει να συγκεντρώσει τις ανάγκες των πιλότων σχετικά με τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις. Αυτός είναι ένας αποτελεσματικός τρόπος για να συλλέξουμε ποικίλες πληροφορίες σε πραγματικό χρόνο απευθείας από εσάς που ασχολείστε καθημερινά με διαδικασίες και εργαλεία.

Εθελοντική Συμμετοχή: Η συμμετοχή σας στη συνέντευξη είναι απολύτως εθελοντική. Μπορείτε να αρνηθείτε να συμμετάσχετε χωρίς κανένα λόγο ή αιτιολόγηση. Μπορείτε να αποσυρθείτε οποιαδήποτε στιγμή κατά τη διάρκεια της συνέντευξης χωρίς κανένα λόγο, αιτιολόγηση ή συνέπειες. Μετά το τέλος της συνέντευξης δεν έχετε την επιλογή να υπαναχωρήσετε.

Δεδομένα που συλλέχθηκαν: Σε αυτή τη συνέντευξη, θα ερωτηθείτε μόνο για το δικό σας **ρόλο** στον οργανισμό (πιλότος) χωρίς να αναφέρετε το όνομα του οργανισμού.

Στη συνέντευξη θα υπάρξει **ηχογράφηση φωνής** και θα αποθηκευτεί τοπικά στον υπολογιστή του ερευνητή για μια εβδομάδα το μέγιστο. Μετά τη μεταγραφή των απαντήσεών σας, η ηχογράφηση φωνής θα καταστραφεί. Αντίγραφα της συνέντευξης μπορούν επίσης να κοινοποιηθούν σε άλλες οντότητες που αποτελούν μέρος της κοινοπραξίας του ερευνητικού έργου και στους υπαλλήλους τους, στους οποίους ο υπεύθυνος επεξεργασίας εμπιστεύεται την εκτέλεση συγκεκριμένων δραστηριοτήτων στο πλαίσιο του ερευνητικού έργου.

Εμπιστευτικότητα: Όλες οι απαντήσεις θα παραμείνουν εμπιστευτικές και θα αποθηκευτούν με ασφάλεια. Μόνο εξουσιοδοτημένο ερευνητικό προσωπικό θα έχει πρόσβαση στα πρωτογενή δεδομένα. Εάν έχετε οποιοδήποτε ερωτήσεις, μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με τον ελεγκτή δεδομένων του πιλότου για το orengon.gr, στο dataadmin@eellak.gr

Τα δεδομένα θα υποβληθούν σε επεξεργασία με βάση τη συγκατάθεση για την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών δεδομένων και τη δήλωση του σκοπού ή των σκοπών της επεξεργασίας (συμμετοχή σε αυτό το ερευνητικό έργο). Μπορείτε να ανακαλέσετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας για την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων ανά πάσα στιγμή πριν από τη συγκέντρωση των δεδομένων. Αυτή η ανάκληση δεν επηρεάζει την επεξεργασία που είχε ήδη ολοκληρωθεί κατόπιν συναίνεσης πριν από την ανάκλησή της.

Περίοδος διατήρησης δεδομένων: Τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα που συλλέγονται για αυτό το ερευνητικό έργο θα υποβληθούν σε επεξεργασία κατά τη διάρκεια του έργου και θα διατηρηθούν μόνο για όσο διάστημα απαιτείται αναγκαστικά για την επίτευξη του σκοπού αυτού του έργου. Με την ολοκλήρωση του έργου, τα προσωπικά στοιχεία θα διαγραφούν/ανωνυμοποιηθούν..

Τα δικαιώματά σας είναι τα εξής:

- να έχετε πρόσβαση σε δεδομένα και στη λήψη αντιγράφων των πραγματικών δεδομένων
- να διορθώσετε τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα
- να περιορίσετε την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων
- να ζητήσετε την διαγραφή προσωπικών δεδομένων, με την επιφύλαξη των διατάξεων του άρθ. 17 ενότητα 3 του GDPR.
- να υποβάλετε αξίωση στις αρμόδιες αρχές, εάν πιστεύετε ότι η επεξεργασία δεδομένων παραβιάζει το νόμο.

Συγκατάθεση:

Υπογράφοντας παρακάτω, επιβεβαιώνετε ότι:

- Έχετε διαβάσει και κατανοήσει τις πληροφορίες που παρέχονται παραπάνω.
- Συμφωνείτε οικειοθελώς να συμμετάσχετε σε αυτή τη συνέντευξη.
- Συναινείτε στην ηχογράφιση της συνέντευξης.
- Κατανοείτε ότι η εγγραφή θα αποθηκευτεί τοπικά για ένα μέγιστο διάστημα μίας εβδομάδας και στη συνέχεια θα διαγραφεί ή νορτίτερα εάν ολοκληρωθεί η μεταγραφή.
- Είστε τουλάχιστον 18 ετών.

Για τον συμμετέχοντα

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Ερωτήσεις συνέντευξης

Δημογραφικά στοιχεία

Ο ρόλος του συμμετέχοντος στον φορέα/οργανισμό του.

Στρατηγικός και Οργανωτικός Αντίκτυπος

1. Πιστεύετε ότι οι τρέχουσες διαδικασίες/πλατφόρμες διαβούλευσης πρέπει να αλλάξουν; Αν ναι, γιατί; (*υπάρχουσα πλατφόρμα*)
2. Πώς πιστεύετε ότι μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN συμβάλλει στους μακροπρόθεσμους στρατηγικούς στόχους του οργανισμού; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
3. Γνωρίζετε εθνικές και διεθνείς πολιτικές που ενδέχεται να περιορίσουν τη χρήση μιας τέτοιας πλατφόρμας; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
4. Πώς θα μπορούσε αυτή η πλατφόρμα να βελτιώσει τη θεσμοθέτηση των πρακτικών δημόσιας διαβούλευσης; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
5. Τι αντίκτυπο θα μπορούσε να έχει αυτή η πλατφόρμα στη διαφάνεια και τη λογοδοσία στις διαδικασίες λήψης αποφάσεων; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
6. Γιατί, για εσάς, είναι σημαντικό να γίνει (μεγάλης κλίμακας χωρίς αποκλεισμούς) διαβούλευση;

Προσδοκίες εμπειρίας πλατφόρμας και διεπαφής χρήστη (UI/UX).

7. Ποιες είναι οι προσδοκίες για τη διεπαφή χρήστη; (π.χ. διαισθητικός σχεδιασμός, φιλικός προς κινητά, δυνατότητες προσβασιμότητας) (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
8. Υπάρχουν συγκεκριμένες απαιτήσεις προσβασιμότητας; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)

Διαχείριση Αλλαγών και Επικοινωνία

9. Τι επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης και τεκμηρίωσης πρέπει να παρέχεται στους χρήστες; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)

Τεχνικές και Λειτουργικές Απαιτήσεις

10. Πώς πρέπει να οργανώνονται, να αποθηκεύονται και να έχουν πρόσβαση τα δεδομένα της πλατφόρμας; Γνωρίζετε κάποια πρότυπα (δεδομένων) που ήδη υπάρχουν/δημιουργούνται; (*αλληλεπίδραση μεταξύ των δύο πλατφορμών*)
11. Ποιες είναι οι απαιτήσεις για απόδοση και επεκτασιμότητα (π.χ. αναμενόμενη επισκεψιμότητα, αριθμός χρηστών); (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
12. Ποια πρότυπα ασφάλειας και συμμόρφωσης πρέπει να πληρούνται; (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
13. Υπάρχουν τεχνικοί περιορισμοί (π.χ. λειτουργικά συστήματα, προγράμματα περιήγησης, συσκευές); (*αλληλεπίδραση μεταξύ των δύο πλατφορμών, πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)
14. Ποιες είναι οι βασικές λειτουργίες που πρέπει να παρέχει η πλατφόρμα; (π.χ. έλεγχος ταυτότητας χρήστη, αναφορές, πίνακες εργαλείων, οπτικοποίηση δεδομένων, διαχείριση δεδομένων) (*πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit*)

Annex 5
CERTH: Citizen Questionnaire in Greek

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Φόρμα Συναίνεσης

Σκοπός του ερωτηματολογίου: Αυτή η έρευνα πραγματοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του έργου AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) που χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση. Ο στόχος του έργου AI4Deliberation είναι να παράσχει εργαλεία ηθικής τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ολοκληρωμένη καθοδήγηση, ώστε να βοηθήσει τις κυβερνήσεις στη θεσμοθέτηση, τη χρήση και την αξιολόγηση πολυτροπικών, παιχνιδιοποιημένων, μαζικών δημόσιων διαβουλεύσεων.

Ο στόχος αυτού του ερωτηματολογίου είναι να κατανοήσει: α) τη γνώμη σας σχετικά με ορισμένα χαρακτηριστικά και λειτουργίες μιας πλατφόρμας διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητες TN, β) τις αντιλήψεις σας σχετικά με την ασφάλεια αυτής της πλατφόρμας και την ετοιμότητά σας να τη χρησιμοποιήσετε και γ) την αντίληψή σας σχετικά με τη χρησιμότητά της. Εάν συνεχίσετε, θα υπάρξει μια σύντομη εισαγωγή για να διευκολυνθεί περαιτέρω η κατανόησή σας.

Εθελοντική Συμμετοχή: Η συμμετοχή σας στην έρευνα είναι απολύτως εθελοντική. Μπορείτε να αρνηθείτε να συμμετάσχετε χωρίς κανένα λόγο ή αιτιολόγηση. Μπορείτε να αποσυρθείτε ανά πάσα στιγμή κατά τη συμπλήρωση του ερωτηματολογίου χωρίς κανένα λόγο, αιτιολόγηση ή συνέπειες. **Μετά την υποβολή** του ερωτηματολογίου **δεν έχετε** την επιλογή υπαναχώρησης.

Δεδομένα που συλλέχθηκαν: Για να συμμετάσχετε στην έρευνα, θα σας ζητηθεί να συμπληρώσετε ένα ερωτηματολόγιο στο οποίο βρίσκονται τα στοιχεία που θα συμπληρώσετε **Φύλο, ηλικία, επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης και χώρα διαμονής**. Τα παραπάνω είναι προαιρετικά και μπορείτε να συμπληρώσετε και να υποβάλετε το ερωτηματολόγιο χωρίς να παρέχετε κάποιο από αυτά.

Έχουμε επιλέξει τη λειτουργία ανώνυμης έρευνας για να αποτρέψουμε την αποθήκευση οποιωνδήποτε προσωπικών δεδομένων, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της διεύθυνσης IP σας. Η δήλωση απορρήτου σχετικά με την προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων κατά τη χρήση του εργαλείου EUSurvey μπορείτε να βρείτε εδώ: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/privacystatement>.

Ωστόσο, η IP κάθε σύνδεσης μπορεί να αποθηκευτεί από τον πάροχο του EUSurvey για λόγους ασφαλείας. Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες βλ <https://surveys.acer.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/helpauthors# Toc14>. Λάβετε υπόψη ότι το πιλοτικό για το opengov.gr δεν είναι ο πάροχος του εργαλείου EUSurvey και η διεύθυνση IP σας δεν θα κοινοποιηθεί σε εμάς.

Εμπιστευτικότητα: Όλες οι απαντήσεις θα παραμείνουν εμπιστευτικές και θα αποθηκευτούν με ασφάλεια. Οι παρεχόμενες πληροφορίες είναι ανώνυμες. Μόνο εξουσιοδοτημένο ερευνητικό προσωπικό από τον πιλότο για το opengov.gr θα έχει πρόσβαση στα πρωτογενή δεδομένα.

Εάν έχετε οποιεσδήποτε ερωτήσεις σχετικά με τη διεξαγωγή της έρευνας, μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε μαζί μας στο dataadmin@eellak.gr

Πιθανοί κίνδυνοι: Δεν υπάρχουν προβλέψιμοι κίνδυνοι που σχετίζονται με τη συμμετοχή σε αυτό το ερωτηματολόγιο. Ωστόσο, εάν αισθάνεστε άβολα σε οποιοδήποτε σημείο, μπορείτε να επιλέξετε να σταματήσετε.

Οφέλη: Η συμμετοχή σας θα προσφέρει πολύτιμες πληροφορίες για το κιτ εργαλείων AI του έργου. Αν και δεν υπάρχουν άμεσα οφέλη για εσάς, η συμβολή σας εκτιμάται ιδιαίτερα.

ΔΗΛΩΣΗ ΣΥΝΑΙΝΕΣΗΣ - Δηλώνω ότι έχω ενημερωθεί πλήρως για τους όρους συμμετοχής μου στην έρευνα.

Επιλέγοντας **Ναι Συναίνω**, επιβεβαιώνω ότι:

- Έχω διαβάσει και κατανοήσει τις πληροφορίες που παρέχονται παραπάνω.
- Συμφωνώ οικειοθελώς να συμμετάσχω σε αυτήν την έρευνα.
- Είμαι τουλάχιστον 18 ετών.

Ναι Συναίνω

Όχι, δεν συναίνω

Φύλο

- Άνδρας Γυναίκα Άλλο Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Ηλικία

- 18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+

- Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Επίπεδο Εκπαίδευσης

- Χωρίς επίσημη εκπαίδευση Δημοτικό Σχολείο Γυμνάσιο
 Πτυχίο Μεταδευτεροβάθμιας ή Επαγγελματικής Κατάρτισης Πτυχίο ΑΕΙ
 Μεταπτυχιακό Πτυχίο Ειδίκευσης Διδακτορικό (PhD)
 Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Χώρα διαμονής

- Γερμανία Ελλάδα Ιταλία Ηνωμένο Βασίλειο Άλλο (Ελεύθερο κείμενο)
 Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Εισαγωγή

Στην ιδανική της μορφή, η δημοκρατία βασίζεται στο διάλογο και τις διαβουλεύσεις μεταξύ των πολιτών, όπου και δίνονται σε όλους ίσες ευκαιρίες να εκφράσουν τη γνώμη τους (π.χ. να προτείνουν θέματα, μοιράζονται επιχειρήματα, ψηφίζουν εναλλακτικές). Ωστόσο, αυτή η διαδικασία μπορεί να είναι δύσκολο να διεξαχθεί και να διατηρηθεί σε μεγάλη κλίμακα στις σύγχρονες κοινωνίες. Τα εργαλεία που θα είναι ενισχυμένα με τεχνητή νοημοσύνη ενδέχεται να προσφέρουν νέους τρόπους υποστήριξης του διαλόγου σε μεγαλύτερη κλίμακα και να φέρουν τις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις πιο κοντά στα ιδανικά της δημοκρατίας.

Στόχος μας είναι να κατανοήσουμε πώς τα εργαλεία τεχνητής νοημοσύνης μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν για να υποστηρίξουν τις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις σε δημοκρατίες και, μέσω αυτού, να δημιουργήσουμε μια ελεύθερα διαθέσιμη εργαλειοθήκη τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που μπορούν να χρησιμοποιήσουν ομάδες οπουδήποτε στον κόσμο για να βελτιώσουν τις δικές τους διαβουλεύσεις. Οι απαντήσεις σας στο ερωτηματολόγιο θα μας βοηθήσουν να εντοπίσουμε και να δώσουμε προτεραιότητα στα αρχικά χαρακτηριστικά της εργαλειοθήκης TN, τα οποία στη συνέχεια θα δοκιμάσουμε και θα βελτιώσουμε σε τέσσερα έργα για διαβουλεύσεις – ξεκινώντας αργότερα φέτος – στη Γερμανία, την Ελλάδα, την Ιταλία και μια διεθνή πρωτοβουλία που βασίζεται στο HB.

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος ολοκλήρωσης: 20 λεπτά

1. Έχετε χρησιμοποιήσει εργαλεία Τεχνητής Νοημοσύνης σε οποιοδήποτε πλαίσιο, και αν ναι, ήταν χρήσιμη;
 - Σίγουρα δεν ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Μάλλον δεν είναι χρήσιμη
 - Δεν είμαι σίγουρος
 - Μάλλον ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Σίγουρα ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Δεν έχω χρησιμοποιήσει
2. Εάν ναι, θα μπορούσατε να περιγράψετε εν συντομία το πλαίσιο και τι βρήκατε χρήσιμο ή όχι; (ανοιχτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)

Για καθεμία από τις ακόλουθες λειτουργίες της πλατφόρμας, υποδείξτε την προτιμώμενη ισορροπία μεταξύ της χρήσης τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ανθρώπινης επίβλεψης.

1 = Εξ ολοκλήρου ανθρωποκεντρική 2 = Κυρίως ανθρωποκεντρική με υποστήριξη τεχνητής νοημοσύνης 3 = Ισορροπία μεταξύ ανθρώπινης εμπλοκής και τεχνητής νοημοσύνης 4 = Κυρίως καθοδηγούμενη από την τεχνητή νοημοσύνη και με υποστήριξη ανθρώπινης επίβλεψης 5 = Πλήρως καθοδηγούμενη από τεχνητή νοημοσύνη

	1	2	3	4	5
Περιλήψεις Συζητήσεων	<input type="radio"/>				
Εποπτεία συζήτησης	<input type="radio"/>				
Έλεγχος γεγονότων	<input type="radio"/>				
Μεταφραστικές υπηρεσίες	<input type="radio"/>				
Προσδιορισμός σημείων συμφωνίας	<input type="radio"/>				
Πρόταση εναλλακτικών προοπτικών	<input type="radio"/>				
Επεξεργασία ανάδρασης χρηστών	<input type="radio"/>				
Παρακολούθηση μοτίβων συζήτησης	<input type="radio"/>				

Παρακάτω, θα βρείτε μια σειρά από χαρακτηριστικά και λειτουργίες μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητες TN του έργου.

Υποδείξτε πόσο σημαντικό είναι καθένα από τα ακόλουθα χαρακτηριστικά, σε κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Σίγουρα όχι σημαντικό, 2 = πιθανώς όχι σημαντικό, 3 = ουδέτερο, 4 = σημαντικό, 5 = πολύ σημαντικό

	1	2	3	4	5
Περιλήψεις Συζητήσεων (Δημιουργεί αυτόματα περιλήψεις των συζητήσεων)	<input type="radio"/>				
Εποπτεία συζήτησης (Προτείνει αυτόματα οδηγίες και επισημαίνει ακατάλληλο περιεχόμενο)	<input type="radio"/>				
Έλεγχος γεγονότων (Εντοπίζει πραγματικά γεγονότα, παρέχοντας επαληθευμένες πληροφορίες για να διασφαλίσει	<input type="radio"/>				

ότι τα επιχειρήματα που χρησιμοποιούνται είναι σωστά κατά τη διάρκεια των συζητήσεων)					
Μεταφραστικές υπηρεσίες (Προσφέρει αυτοματοποιημένες μεταφράσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				
Προσδιορισμός σημείων συμφωνίας (Συγκεντρώνει παρόμοια σημεία και προσδιορίζει βασικές κατηγορίες στις συζητήσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				
Πρόταση εναλλακτικών προοπτικών (Προτείνει διαφορετικές απόψεις για να εμπλουτίσει τις συζητήσεις και να ενθαρρύνει την κριτική σκέψη)	<input type="radio"/>				
Επεξεργασία ανάδρασης χρηστών (Αναλύει τα σχόλια για να ιεραρχήσει τις βελτιώσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				
Παρακολούθηση μοτίβων συζήτησης (Παρακολουθεί τις τάσεις και τη δυναμική της συζήτησης για τη βελτιστοποίηση των μελλοντικών συζητήσεων)	<input type="radio"/>				

Για καθεμία από τις ακόλουθες ερωτήσεις και με βάση τη δική σας οπτική, αναφέρετε ποιες από τις ακόλουθες λειτουργίες είναι σημαντικό να έχει μια πλατφόρμα διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητες TN:

	1	2	3	4	5
3. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να επισημαίνουν σφάλματα στις περιλήψεις των συζητήσεων που δημιουργούνται από TN;	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι μεσολαβεί ενεργά η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη για να (παρακολουθεί, ρυθμίζει, διευκολύνει) τις συζητήσεις ώστε να διασφαλίσει τη συμπερίληψη;	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να προτείνει η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη σχετικές πηγές και στοιχεία κατά τη διάρκεια των συζητήσεων;	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επισημαίνει η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη δυνητικά παραπλανητικές πληροφορίες;	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να παρέχει σαφείς εξηγήσεις η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη όταν το περιεχόμενο προσδιορίζεται ως δυνητικά παραπλανητικό;	<input type="radio"/>				

8. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να προτείνουν βελτιώσεις στις αυτόματες μεταφράσεις;	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να μπορεί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη να προτείνει συζητήσεις και θέματα με βάση τις προτιμήσεις και την προηγούμενη δραστηριότητά σας;	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να συνδέεται με διαφορετικές οπτικές γωνίες για τα θέματα που συζητούνται;	<input type="radio"/>				
11. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να παρέχονται στοιχεία για τις προτεινόμενες διαφορετικές προοπτικές;	<input type="radio"/>				
12. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι για εσάς να γνωρίζετε πώς και γιατί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη λειτουργεί όταν συμβάλλετε σε συζητήσεις (π.χ. εποπτεία περιεχομένου, σύνοψη, δημιουργία συναίνεσης);	<input type="radio"/>				
13. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να αποθηκεύουμε και να διαθέτουμε δημόσια αρχεία καταγραφής ελέγχου σημαντικών παρεμβάσεων τεχνητής νοημοσύνης σε συζητήσεις (π.χ. αφαίρεση περιεχομένου, αποφάσεις ελέγχου γεγονότων, περιλήψεις συναίνεσης);	<input type="radio"/>				
14. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να παρέχουν σχόλια σχετικά με τις λειτουργίες TN και να συμμετέχουν στη βελτίωσή τους μέσω δομημένων μηχανισμών ανάδρασης;	<input type="radio"/>				
15. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να υπάρχουν κίνητρα συμμετοχής (όπως κονκάρδες εμπειρογνωμοσύνης σε διαβούλευση, επιτεύγματα οικοδόμησης συναίνεσης, αναγνώριση ποιότητας του διαλόγου κ.λπ.) για την ενθάρρυνση της ουσιαστικής συμμετοχής σε δημόσιες συζητήσεις;	<input type="radio"/>				
16. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να αναγνωρίζουμε τις ουσιαστικές συνεισφορές των συμμετεχόντων μέσω σημάτων επιτεύματος με βάση τα συμφραζόμενα που αντικατοπτρίζουν την ποιότητα και τον αντίκτυπο της συμμετοχής (π.χ. γεφύρωση αντίθετων απόψεων, βελτίωση της συζήτησης που βασίζεται σε στοιχεία και ενθάρρυνση του διαλόγου χωρίς αποκλεισμούς, κάρμα οικοδόμησης κοινότητας);	<input type="radio"/>				
17. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να έχετε την επιλογή να ανεβάσετε ένα avatar αντί να χρησιμοποιήσετε τη φωτογραφία σας;	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται η συμμετοχή σε συζητήσεις μέσω βίντεο;	<input type="radio"/>				
19. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται η συμμετοχή σε συζητήσεις μέσω ήχου;	<input type="radio"/>				
20. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να προσφέρεται η επιλογή συμμετοχής με ψευδώνυμο αντί για το πραγματικό σας όνομα;	<input type="radio"/>				

Οι παρακάτω προτάσεις αξιολογούν τις αντιλήψεις σας για την ασφάλεια της πλατφόρμας και την ετοιμότητά σας να χρησιμοποιήσετε μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN. Βαθμολογήστε κάθε δήλωση σε μια κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 2 = Διαφωνώ, 3 = Ουδέτερος, 4 = Συμφωνώ, 5 = Συμφωνώ απόλυτα.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. Δεν θεωρώ ασφαλές να παρέχω προσωπικές πληροφορίες σε μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN.	<input type="radio"/>				
22. Ανησυχώ ότι οι πληροφορίες που διαθέτω μέσω μιας πλατφόρμας συσκέψεων με δυνατότητα TN μπορεί να χρησιμοποιηθούν καταχρηστικά από τρίτους.	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Κάθε φορά που αυτοματοποιείται κάτι χρησιμοποιώντας TN, είναι σημαντικό να ελέγχεται προσεκτικά ότι δεν υπάρχουν λάθη.	<input type="radio"/>				
24. Νιώθω άβολα για τα συστήματα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που διαμορφώνουν σημαντικές συζητήσεις χωρίς ανθρώπινη επίβλεψη.	<input type="radio"/>				
25. Ανησυχώ ότι η συνεισφορά μου στη διαδικασία συζήτησης της πλατφόρμας με δυνατότητα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης μπορεί να παρερμηνευθεί από τα συστήματα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης.	<input type="radio"/>				

Οι ακόλουθες προτάσεις αξιολογούν τις αντιλήψεις σας για τη χρησιμότητα μιας πλατφόρμας διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN. Βαθμολογήστε κάθε δήλωση σε μια κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 2 = Διαφωνώ, 3 = Ουδέτερος, 4 = Συμφωνώ, 5 = Συμφωνώ απόλυτα.

	1	2	3	4	5

26. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα TN θα ενίσχυε την αποτελεσματικότητα της συμμετοχής μου σε διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
27. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα TN θα με διευκόλυνε να συμμετάσχω σε διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
28. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα TN θα θα αυξήσει την ικανότητά μου να συμμετέχω σε περισσότερες διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
29. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα TN θα μου επέτρεπε να συνεισφέρω πιο ουσιαστικά στη διαμόρφωση και τη βελτίωση των διαδικασιών διαβούλευσης.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Έχετε άλλες προτάσεις σχετικά με το πώς θα μπορούσε να χρησιμοποιηθεί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη για τη βελτίωση των διαδικασιών συζήτησης; (Ανοιχτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)
31. Έχετε άλλες συγκεκριμένες ανησυχίες σχετικά με τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στις διαβουλεύσεις; (Ανοιχτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Annex 6
CERTH: A self-assessment

PENDING EC APPROVAL

ΕΘΝΙΚΟ ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΚΗΣ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ

ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ ΗΘΙΚΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΔΕΟΝΤΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ ΤΗΣ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ

ΕΡΩΤΗΜΑΤΟΛΟΓΙΟ & ΕΚΘΕΣΗ ΑΥΤΟΑΞΙΟΛΟΓΗΣΗΣ

ΕΡΕΥΝΗΤΙΚΗ ΠΡΟΤΑΣΗ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΕΚΚΡΕΜΕΙ
1. Η ερευνητική πρόταση έχει αξιολογηθεί ως προς την επιστημονική αξία της;	ΝΑΙ
2. Αν ναι ή αν εκκρεμεί, προσδιορίστε το φορέα αξιολόγησης (Επιτροπή Αξιολόγησης Φορέα Χρηματοδότησης, άλλο):	Επιτροπή Αξιολόγησης του προγράμματος Horizon Europe της Ευρωπαϊκής Επιτροπής
3. Πρόκειται για χρηματοδοτούμενη έρευνα;	ΝΑΙ
4. Αν ναι ή αν εκκρεμεί, προσδιορίστε όλες τις πηγές χρηματοδότησης και τυχόν όρους από πλευράς του φορέα χρηματοδότησης που σχετίζονται με τη δημοσίευση των αποτελεσμάτων του ερευνητικού έργου:	Χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση στο πλαίσιο της συμφωνίας επιχορήγησης αριθ. 101178806
ΠΕΡΙΛΗΨΗ ΑΙΤΗΜΑΤΟΣ	
<p>Το έργο AI4Deliberation (https://www.ai4dproject.eu/) χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση (grant agreement No. 101178806) και συμμετέχει το ΕΚΕΤΑ – ΙΠΤΗΛ.</p> <p>Στόχος του έργου είναι να παράσχει εργαλεία ηθικής τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ολοκληρωμένη καθοδήγηση, ώστε να βοηθήσει τις κυβερνήσεις στη θεσμοθέτηση, τη χρήση και την αξιολόγηση πολυτροπικών, παιχνιδιοποιημένων, μαζικών δημόσιων διαβουλεύσεων.</p> <p>Στα πλαίσια του έργου θα γίνει έρευνα για την συλλογή απαιτήσεων των εμπλεκόμενων μερών μέσω ερωτηματολογίων και συνεντεύξεων που θα καθοδηγήσουν τα επόμενα βήματα του έργου.</p> <p>Το έτοιμο προς την επιτροπή Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας του ΕΚΕΤΑ αφορά την έγκριση της εν λόγω έρευνας.</p>	

ΧΡΗΜΑΤΟΔΟΤΗΣΗ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
5. Έχει υποβληθεί αίτηση για χρηματοδότηση;		ΝΑΙ
6. Αν ναι, σε ποιον φορέα;		Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση
7. Θα υπάρχουν αμοιβές ή άλλου είδους ανταλλάγματα που θα δίνονται στους συμμετέχοντες στην έρευνα;		ΟΧΙ
8. Αν ΝΑΙ, περιγράψτε:		
9. Ενδέχεται να υπάρξουν οικονομικές επιβαρύνσεις στους συμμετέχοντες στην έρευνα;		ΟΧΙ
10. Αν ΝΑΙ, περιγράψτε:		
11. Έχουν τεθεί όροι όσον αφορά τα δικαιώματα των ερευνητών για δημοσίευση των αποτελεσμάτων του έργου;		ΟΧΙ
12. Έχουν τεθεί όροι, από πλευράς χρηματοδότη, σε σχέση με τις δημοσιεύσεις που θα αφορούν αποτελέσματα του έργου;		ΟΧΙ
ΑΝΘΡΩΠΙΝΟ ΑΝΑΠΑΡΑΓΩΓΙΚΟ ΥΛΙΚΟ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
13. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ανθρώπινων εμβρυϊκών βλαστοκυττάρων;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι:	- Πρόκειται για υλικό που θα προέλθει από έμβρυα που θα χρησιμοποιηθούν κατά την υλοποίηση του παρόντος ερευνητικού έργου;	
	- Πρόκειται για υλικό που προέρχεται από υφιστάμενες κυτταρικές σειρές;	
14. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ανθρώπινων εμβρύων;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι:	- Πρόκειται η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου να προκαλέσει την καταστροφή τους;	
15. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ανθρώπινων εμβρυϊκών κυττάρων ή ιστών;		ΟΧΙ
16. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ανθρώπινων γαμετών (ωάρια, σπερματοζωάρια);		ΟΧΙ
Προσδιορίστε τον τύπο του γαμέτη και αναφέρετε συνοπτικά το σκοπό της χρήσης και την τύχη των γαμετών μετά την ολοκλήρωση της έρευνας:		
ΑΝΘΡΩΠΟΙ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
17. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη συμμετοχή ανθρώπων;		ΝΑΙ
Αν ναι:	- Πρόκειται για εθελόντριες/ντές που συμμετέχουν σε έρευνα με αντικείμενο τις κοινωνικές και ανθρωπιστικές επιστήμες;	ΝΑΙ
	- Πρόκειται για άτομα που αδυνατούν να συγκατατεθούν;	ΟΧΙ
	- Πρόκειται για ευάλωτα άτομα ή ευαίσθητες ομάδες πληθυσμού;	ΟΧΙ
	- Πρόκειται για ανήλικα άτομα (παιδιά ή έφηβοι);	ΟΧΙ
	- Πρόκειται για ασθενείς που συμμετέχουν σε βιοϊατρική έρευνα;	ΟΧΙ
	- Πρόκειται για υγιείς εθελόντριες/ντές που συμμετέχουν σε βιοϊατρική έρευνα;	ΟΧΙ
18. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει φυσική παρέμβαση στις/ους συμμετέχουσες/οντες;		ΟΧΙ
Αν	- Πρόκειται να χρησιμοποιηθούν επεμβατικές τεχνικές;	

ναι:	- Πρόκειται να συλλεχθούν βιολογικά δείγματα;	
	- Πρόκειται να δημιουργηθεί τράπεζα βιολογικών δειγμάτων;	
	- Πρόκειται για ιατρική έρευνα;	
	- Πρόκειται κάποιοι ασθενείς να λάβουν εικονική θεραπεία (φαρμακευτική, χειρουργική, ψυχοθεραπευτική, άλλη);	
19. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου, πέραν των επιδιωκόμενων αποτελεσμάτων, μπορεί να αποφέρει τυχαία/απροσδόκητα αποτελέσματα;		OXI
<p>Αν ναι, υπάρχει σχέδιο διαχείρισης τυχαίων απροσδόκητων αποτελεσμάτων; <i>Προσδιορίστε το σχέδιο διαχείρισης τυχαίων/απροσδόκητων αποτελεσμάτων:</i></p>		
ΑΝΘΡΩΠΙΝΑ ΚΥΤΤΑΡΑ ΚΑΙ ΙΣΤΟΙ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
20. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ανθρώπινων κυττάρων ή ιστών εκτός των ανθρώπινων εμβρυϊκών κυττάρων;		OXI
Αν ναι:	- Πρόκειται για κύτταρα ή ιστούς που διατίθενται στο εμπόριο;	
	- Πρόκειται για κύτταρα ή ιστούς που θα συλλεχθούν στα πλαίσια του παρόντος ερευνητικού έργου;	
	- Πρόκειται για κύτταρα ή ιστούς που έχουν συλλεχθεί στα πλαίσια άλλου ερευνητικού έργου, εργαστηρίου ή ιδρύματος;	
	- Πρόκειται για υλικό που προέρχεται από τράπεζα βιολογικών υλικών;	
<p><i>Αν ναι, προσδιορίστε το είδος, την κατάσταση αδειοδότησης και τη νομική υπόσταση της τράπεζας και αν τα δείγματα είναι επώνυμα, ανώνυμα, ψευδωνυμοποιημένα, κ.λπ.:</i></p>		
ΠΡΟΣΩΠΙΚΑ ΔΕΔΟΜΕΝΑ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
21. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων;		ΝΑΙ (ηχογράφηση φωνής)

Αν ναι:	- Περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία ειδικών κατηγοριών προσωπικών δεδομένων (ευαίσθητα δεδομένα) (π.χ. δεδομένα φυλετικής ή εθνοτικής καταγωγής, δεδομένα σεξουαλικών προτιμήσεων ή γενετήσιου προσανατολισμού, πολιτικών απόψεων, θρησκευτικών ή φιλοσοφικών πεποιθήσεων, συμμετοχής σε συνδικαλιστική οργάνωση)	OXI
	<i>Προσδιορίστε την κατηγορία:</i>	
	- Περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία δεδομένων υγείας (π.χ. γενετικών, βιομετρικών, άλλων δεδομένων υγείας);	OXI
	<i>Προσδιορίστε την κατηγορία και τον τύπο:</i>	
	- Περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία δεδομένων προσωπικού χαρακτήρα που αφορούν ποινικές καταδίκες και αδικήματα;	OXI
	- Περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων ανηλίκων προσώπων;	OXI

	<p>- Προβλέπεται η κατάρτιση προφίλ, η συστηματική παρακολούθηση ατόμων, η επεξεργασία ειδικών κατηγοριών προσωπικών δεδομένων σε μεγάλη κλίμακα, η χρήση παρεμβατικών μεθόδων συλλογής και επεξεργασίας προσωπικών δεδομένων (εντοπισμός, παρακολούθηση, ηχογράφηση, βιντεοσκόπηση, προσδιορισμός γεωγραφικής θέσης, κ.λπ.) ή άλλη επεξεργασία η οποία μπορεί να περιορίζει τα θεμελιώδη ανθρώπινα δικαιώματα και ελευθερίες;</p> <p><i>Προσδιορίστε την κατηγορία:</i></p>	
<p>22. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου περιλαμβάνει την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων που έχουν συλλεχθεί στο παρελθόν (δευτερεύουσα χρήση δεδομένων);</p>		<p>OXI</p>
<p>23. Προβλέπονται ενέργειες για την ασφάλεια των δεδομένων προσωπικού χαρακτήρα από και κατά την επεξεργασία; <i>Αν ΝΑΙ προσδιορίστε</i></p>		<p>ΝΑΙ</p> <p>Το μοναδικό προσωπικό δεδομένο που θα χειριστούμε είναι η ηχογράφηση των συνεντεύξεων. Για την ηχογράφηση θα υπάρχει ρητή συναίνεση του ατόμου που θα γίνει η συνέντευξη.</p> <p>Η ηχογράφηση φωνής θα αποθηκευτεί τοπικά στον υπολογιστή του ερευνητή για μια εβδομάδα το μέγιστο. Μετά τη καταγραφή των απαντήσεων, η ηχογράφηση φωνής θα καταστραφεί.</p>
<p>24. Πρόκειται να χρησιμοποιηθούν δημοσίως διαθέσιμα προσωπικά δεδομένα;</p>		<p>OXI</p>
<p>25. Προβλέπεται εξαγωγή προσωπικών δεδομένων από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση σε χώρες εκτός Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης; <i>Προσδιορίστε τις χώρες και το είδος των δεδομένων:</i></p>		<p>OXI</p>
<p>26. Προβλέπεται εισαγωγή προσωπικών δεδομένων από χώρες εκτός Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης στην Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση; <i>Προσδιορίστε τις χώρες και το είδος των δεδομένων:</i></p>		<p>ΝΑΙ</p> <p>Κάποιες από τις συνεντεύξεις θα γίνουν διαδικτυακά με άτομα που βρίσκονται εκτός Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης: Ηνωμένο</p>

		Βασίλειο, USA. Η ηχογράφιση των συνεντεύξεων θα χρησιμοποιηθεί για τους σκοπούς της έρευνας.
ΖΩΑ		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
27. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση ζώων;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι:	- Ασπόνδυλα;	

	- Σπονδυλωτά;	
	- Πρωτεύοντα πλην του ανθρώπου;	
	- Γενετικώς τροποποιημένα;	
	- Κλωνοποιημένα παραγωγικά ζώα;	
	- Είδη που απειλούνται με εξαφάνιση;	
<i>Παρακαλώ προσδιορίστε τα ζωικά είδη και τον αριθμό των ζώων που θα χρησιμοποιηθούν:</i>		
ΕΡΕΥΝΑ ΣΕ ΧΩΡΕΣ ΕΚΤΟΣ ΕΥΡΩΠΑΪΚΗΣ ΕΝΩΣΗΣ (ΤΡΙΤΕΣ ΧΩΡΕΣ)		ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
28. Αν η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου πρόκειται να πραγματοποιηθεί σε χώρα εκτός Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης, εγείρονται πιθανά ηθικά και δεοντολογικά ζητήματα λόγω της εμπλοκής τρίτων χωρών;		ΟΧΙ
<i>Παρακαλώ αναφέρετε τις χώρες και τα εγείρομενα ηθικά και δεοντολογικά ζητήματα:</i>		
29. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση τοπικών πόρων (π.χ. ιστικά δείγματα ζωϊκής ή ανθρώπινης προέλευσης, γενετικό υλικό, ζώα, ανθρώπινο πτωματικό υλικό, αντικείμενα ιστορικής αξίας, είδη ζώων ή φυτών που απειλούνται με εξαφάνιση, κ.λπ.);		ΟΧΙ
30. Προβλέπεται εισαγωγή υλικών ή άλλων πόρων από τρίτες χώρες στην Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι:	<i>Παρακαλώ προσδιορίστε τις χώρες και τα υλικά:</i>	
31. Προβλέπεται εξαγωγή υλικών ή άλλων πόρων από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση σε τρίτες χώρες;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι:	<i>Παρακαλώ προσδιορίστε τις χώρες και τα υλικά:</i>	
32. Αν η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου πρόκειται να πραγματοποιηθεί σε χώρα εκτός Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης, πρόκειται για χώρα με χαμηλό ή χαμηλό-μέσο εισόδημα;		ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι, τι μέτρα για αμοιβαία διαμοίραση των οφελών που θα επιφέρει η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου έχουν ληφθεί;		
<i>Παρακαλώ προσδιορίστε τα μέτρα που έχουν ληφθεί και τις ενέργειες που προγραμματίζονται:</i>		
33. Είναι πιθανό η εσωτερική κατάσταση στην τρίτη χώρα να θέτει σε κίνδυνο τις/τους ερευνήτριες/τές ή τις/τους συμμετέχουσες/οντες στην έρευνα;		ΟΧΙ

<p>Αν ναι, τι μέτρα για την προστασία των ερευνητριών/τών και των συμμετεχουσών/όντων στην έρευνα έχουν ληφθεί;</p> <p>Προσδιορίστε επιγραμματικά τα μέτρα που έχουν ληφθεί και τις ενέργειες που προγραμματίζονται:</p>	
ΠΕΡΙΒΑΛΛΟΝ, ΠΕΡΙΒΑΛΟΝΤΙΚΗ ΥΓΕΙΑ & ΑΣΦΑΛΕΙΑ & ΠΡΟΣΤΑΣΙΑ ΤΗΣ ΒΙΟΠΟΙΚΙΛΟΤΗΤΑΣ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
34. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση στοιχείων, μεθόδων ή υλικών που μπορεί να είναι βλαπτικά για το περιβάλλον, τα ζώα και τα φυτά;	ΟΧΙ
35. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση γενετικώς τροποποιημένων φυτών;	ΟΧΙ
36. Πρόκειται να επηρεαστούν είδη φυτών ή ζώων που απειλούνται με εξαφάνιση ή προστατευόμενες περιοχές;	ΟΧΙ
37. Η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου προϋποθέτει τη χρήση στοιχείων, μεθόδων ή υλικών που μπορεί να είναι βλαπτικά για τους ανθρώπους (συμπεριλαμβανομένων των ερευνητριών/τών);	ΟΧΙ
<p>Αν απαντήσατε ναι σε κάποια από τις παραπάνω ερωτήσεις, προσδιορίστε τα μέτρα που έχουν ληφθεί και τις ενέργειες που προγραμματίζονται για την ελαχιστοποίηση των κινδύνων:</p>	
ΕΡΕΥΝΑ ΔΙΠΛΗΣ ΧΡΗΣΗΣ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
38. Η ερευνητική πρόταση αφορά ερευνητικά αντικείμενα διπλής χρήσης (πολιτικής και στρατιωτικής) που εμπίπτουν στις διατάξεις του Κανονισμού 428/2009, ή άλλα ερευνητικά αντικείμενα για τα οποία απαιτείται ειδική αδειοδότηση;	ΟΧΙ
ΑΜΦΙΒΟΛΙΑ ΑΝΑΦΟΡΙΚΑ ΜΕ ΤΗΝ ΑΠΟΚΛΕΙΣΤΙΚΗ ΧΡΗΣΗ ΓΙΑ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΚΟΥΣ ΣΚΟΠΟΥΣ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
39. Μπορεί η υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου να προκαλεί ανησυχία αναφορικά με την αποκλειστική χρήση των αποτελεσμάτων του για πολιτικούς σκοπούς;	ΟΧΙ
ΚΑΚΟΒΟΥΛΗ ΧΡΗΣΗ ΕΡΕΥΝΗΤΙΚΩΝ ΑΠΟΤΕΛΕΣΜΑΤΩΝ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ
40. Υπάρχει πιθανότητα κακόβουλης χρήσης των ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων από τρίτους;	ΟΧΙ
<p>Αν ναι, έχετε καταρτίσει σχέδιο ελαχιστοποίησης της πιθανότητας κακόβουλης χρήσης των ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων;</p> <p>Προσδιορίστε τα μέτρα που έχουν ληφθεί και τις ενέργειες που προγραμματίζονται για την ελαχιστοποίηση των κινδύνων:</p>	
ΧΡΗΣΗ ΝΕΩΝ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΩΝ ΜΕ ΑΜΦΙΒΟΛΟ/ΑΝΥΠΑΡΚΤΟ ΠΛΑΙΣΙΟ ΗΘΙΚΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΔΕΟΝΤΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ	ΟΧΙ
Αν ναι, προσδιορίστε τον τύπο της τεχνολογίας:	
ΑΛΛΑ ΗΘΙΚΑ ΚΑΙ ΔΕΟΝΤΟΛΟΓΙΚΑ ΖΗΤΗΜΑΤΑ	ΝΑΙ/ΟΧΙ/ΑΣΑΦΕΣ

<p>41. Υπάρχουν άλλα ηθικά και δεοντολογικά ζητήματα που θεωρείτε σημαντικά ή πιθανά να ανακύψουν κατά την υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου, τα οποία δεν έχουν αναφερθεί;</p> <p><i>Περιγράψτε συνοπτικά επιπλέον ηθικά και δεοντολογικά ζητήματα που σχετίζονται με την υλοποίηση του ερευνητικού έργου:</i></p>	ΟΧΙ
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Σε περίπτωση που υπάρξουν αλλαγές στο ερευνητικό έργο αναφορικά που τροποποιούν τις ανωτέρω απαντήσεις θα πρέπει να αναφερθούν άμεσα στην Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας, η οποία θα γνωμοδοτήσει κατά πόσον η έγκριση που δόθηκε από την Επιτροπή εξακολουθεί να ισχύει ή πρέπει να ανακληθεί.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Annex 7
CERTH: Research protocol

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Ερευνητικό πρωτόκολλο

Σκοπός έρευνας

Αυτή η έρευνα πραγματοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του έργου AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) που χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση (grant agreement No. 101178806) και συμμετέχει το ΕΚΕΤΑ – ΙΠΤΗΛ.

Ο στόχος του έργου AI4Deliberation είναι να παρέχει εργαλεία ηθικής τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ολοκληρωμένη καθοδήγηση, ώστε να βοηθήσει τις κυβερνήσεις στη θεσμοθέτηση, τη χρήση και την αξιολόγηση πολυτροπικών, παιχνιδιοποιημένων, μαζικών δημόσιων διαβουλεύσεων.

Σκοπός της εν λόγω έρευνας για την οποία ζητείται έγκριση από την Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας του ΕΚΕΤΑ είναι η συλλογή απαιτήσεων των εμπλεκόμενων μερών μέσω ερωτηματολογίων και συνεντεύξεων που θα καθοδηγήσουν τα επόμενα βήματα του έργου.

Μεθοδολογία

1) Θα γίνει χρήση ερωτηματολογίου.

- Το ερωτηματολόγιο θα απευθύνεται σε πολίτες (ενήλικους, απαντούν εθελοντικά, δεν είναι μέλη της κοινοπραξίας του έργου) στην Ελλάδα και στην Ευρώπη. Για τον λόγο αυτό υπάρχουν δύο εκδόσεις του ίδιου ερωτηματολογίου στα Ελληνικά και στα Αγγλικά.
- Στόχος τους ερωτηματολογίου είναι να κατανοήσουμε α) τη γνώμη των πολιτών σχετικά με ορισμένα χαρακτηριστικά και λειτουργίες μιας πλατφόρμας διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητες Τεχνητής Νοημοσύνης, β) τις αντιλήψεις τους σχετικά με την ασφάλεια αυτής της πλατφόρμας και την ετοιμότητά σας να τη χρησιμοποιήσουν και γ) την αντίληψή τους σχετικά με τη χρησιμότητά της.
- Το ερωτηματολόγιο θα δημιουργηθεί online στο εργαλείο **EUSurvey**, με επιλογή ανώνυμης λειτουργίας (χωρίς να έχουμε πρόσβαση στην IP) ώστε να μην αποθηκεύεται κανένα δεδομένο των συμμετεχόντων.
- Ο σύνδεσμος για το ερωτηματολόγιο θα δημοσιευτεί από τα κοινωνικά δίκτυα του έργου και των εταίρων του έργου καθώς και μέσω ήδη υπαρχόντων προσωπικών επαφών.
- Αναμενόμενο πλήθος συμπληρωμένων ερωτηματολογίων ~50 (και για τις δύο γλώσσες μαζί)
- Από στοιχεία των συμμετεχόντων θα περιέχονται τέσσερις προαιρετικές ερωτήσεις σχετικά με το **Φύλο, την ηλικία, το επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης και τη χώρα διαμονής τους**.
- Στην αρχή των ερωτηματολογίων υπάρχει φόρμα συναίνεσης που ενημερώνει τους συμμετέχοντες για την έρευνα και τα δικαιώματά τους.

2) Θα διενεργηθούν τρία είδη **ημι-δομημένων συνεντεύξεων**:

- **Είδος 1:** αφορά υπαλλήλους των πιλότων που συμμετέχουν στο έργο και στοχεύει να συγκεντρώσει τις ανάγκες των πιλότων σχετικά με τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις. Τα άτομα που θα συμμετέχουν σε αυτές τις συνεντεύξεις συμμετέχουν ήδη στην κοινοπραξία του έργου.
- **Είδος 2:** αφορά άτομα που έχουν ήδη διεξάγει διαβουλεύσεις (είναι εντός και εκτός της κοινοπραξίας του έργου) και στοχεύει στη λήψη πληροφοριών (απαιτήσεων) σχετικά με τις διαδικασίες και τις πλατφόρμες συζήτησης με ή χωρίς χαρακτηριστικά τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που έχουν χρησιμοποιήσει στο παρελθόν. Για τα άτομα που είναι εκτός της κοινοπραξίας του έργου θα γίνει είτε επικοινωνία μέσω υπαρχόντων επαφών των εταίρων του έργου είτε επικοινωνία μέσω δημόσια διαθέσιμων email ή φορμών επικοινωνίας.
- **Είδος 3:** αφορά άτομα που έχουν αναπτύξει πλατφόρμες συζητήσεων (είναι εντός και εκτός της κοινοπραξίας του έργου) και στοχεύει στη λήψη πληροφοριών (απαιτήσεων) σχετικά με τις πλατφόρμες συζήτησης με ή χωρίς χαρακτηριστικά τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που έχουν χρησιμοποιήσει στο παρελθόν. Για τα άτομα που είναι εκτός της κοινοπραξίας του έργου θα γίνει είτε επικοινωνία μέσω υπαρχόντων επαφών των εταίρων του έργου είτε επικοινωνία μέσω δημόσια διαθέσιμων email ή φορμών επικοινωνίας.
- Πριν την έναρξη της συνέντευξης θα δοθεί φόρμα συναίνεσης στους συμμετέχοντες που θα τους ενημερώνει για την έρευνα και τα δικαιώματά τους καθώς και ότι θα γίνει ηχογράφηση φωνής.
- Στις συνεντεύξεις, θα υπάρξει **ηχογράφηση φωνής** και θα **αποθηκευτεί τοπικά** στον υπολογιστή (χρήση εργαλείου snipping tool των windows) του ερευνητή για **μια εβδομάδα το μέγιστο**. Μετά τη καταγραφή των απαντήσεων, η ηχογράφηση φωνής θα καταστραφεί.
- Αντίγραφα των απαντήσεων μπορούν επίσης να κοινοποιηθούν σε άλλες οντότητες που αποτελούν μέρος της κοινοπραξίας του ερευνητικού έργου και στους υπαλλήλους τους, στους οποίους ο υπεύθυνος επεξεργασίας εμπιστεύεται την εκτέλεση συγκεκριμένων δραστηριοτήτων στο πλαίσιο του ερευνητικού έργου.
- Αναμενόμενο πλήθος συνεντεύξεων ~20 (και για τα τρία ήδη μαζί)

Συνημμένα αποστέλλονται:

- Το ερωτηματολόγιο για τους πολίτες στα Ελληνικά (συμπεριλαμβάνεται η φόρμα συναίνεσης)
- Το ερωτηματολόγιο για τους πολίτες στα Αγγλικά (συμπεριλαμβάνεται η φόρμα συναίνεσης)
- Οι ερωτήσεις για το «Είδος 1» ημι-δομημένη συνέντευξη των υπαλλήλων των πιλότων (συμπεριλαμβάνεται η φόρμα συναίνεσης)
- Οι ερωτήσεις για το «Είδος 2» ημι-δομημένη συνέντευξη των ατόμων που έχουν

- διεξάγει διαβουλεύσεις (συμπεριλαμβάνεται η φόρμα συναίνεσης)
- Οι ερωτήσεις για το «Είδος 3» ημι-δομημένη συνέντευξη των ατόμων που έχουν αναπτύξει πλατφόρμες συζητήσεων (συμπεριλαμβάνεται η φόρμα συναίνεσης)

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Annex 8
CERTH: The ethics approval

PENDING EC APPROVAL

ΕΚΕΤΑ**Ταχ. Δ/ση:** 6ο χλμ. Χαριλάου-Θέρμης, Θέρμη ΤΚ 57001**Τηλέφωνο:** +30 2310498272**e-mail:** kopani@certh.gr**Θεσσαλονίκη:** 07/04/2025**Αρ. Πρωτ:** 023018**ΘΕΜΑ:** Απάντηση σε αίτησή σας**ΠΡΟΣ:** κ. Κωνσταντίνο Ταραμπάνη**Έγκριση της μελέτης**

Σας γνωρίζουμε ότι η Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας (Ε.Η.Δ.Ε.) του Εθνικού Κέντρου Έρευνας και Τεχνολογικής ανάπτυξης (Ε.Κ.Ε.Τ.Α.) εξέτασε το περιεχόμενο του ερευνητικού πρωτοκόλλου με τίτλο «**Διανομή ερωτηματολογίου στους πολίτες στο πλαίσιο του ερευνητικού έργου AI4Deliberation (κωδ. ΚΟΗ.021388)**» με αριθμό πρωτοκόλλου 023018 και Υπεύθυνο τον κ. Κωνσταντίνο Ταραμπάνη.

Λαμβάνοντας υπόψη:

1. Το πρωτόκολλο της μελέτης
2. Το ερωτηματολόγιο αυτοαξιολόγησης
3. Τα αρχεία των ερωτηματολογίων και των ημιδομημένων συνεντεύξεων

Η Επιτροπή έκρινε ότι η διεξαγωγή και το περιεχόμενο της μελέτης θα γίνει σύμφωνα με την υπάρχουσα νομοθεσία και τις παραδεδεγμένες θεμελιώδεις αρχές ηθικής, δεοντολογίας, ακεραιότητας και ορθής επιστημονικής πρακτικής της έρευνας.

Επισημαίνεται ότι σε περίπτωση οποιασδήποτε τροποποίησης της μεθοδολογίας διεξαγωγής της έρευνας ή/και των κατατεθέντων αρχείων απαιτείται εκ νέου αξιολόγηση και έγκριση της έρευνας.

Η Πρόεδρος της Ε.Η.Δ.Ε.

Αικατερίνη Τούλιου

Annexes 9-10
UBAM: Application and the ethics approval

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Antrag zur Ausstellung einer Unbedenklichkeitsbescheinigung durch den Ethikrat der Universität Bamberg

Antragsteller:in

Name, Vorname, Titel

Adresse

E-Mail

Lehrstuhl/Forschungseinrichtung

Antragsgegenstand

Antragsdatum

Antragstitel

Gegenstand (Studie/Projekt/Publikation)

Status: geplant– abgeschlossen

Wurde das Projekt bereits begutachtet? Ja Nein

Wenn ja, wie wurde es begutachtet?

Bitte fügen sie vorhandene externe Gutachten ihrem Antrag bei.

Das in diesem Antrag beschriebene Forschungsvorhaben weist in Bezug auf Fragestellung, Methoden und Probanden eine hohe Ähnlichkeit mit einem Forschungsprojekt auf, welches schon durch den Ethikrat der Universität Bamberg begutachtet wurde.

Ja (Bitte Originalantrag und Ethikvotum beifügen!)

Nein

Abstract (nicht mehr als 500 Wörter) *Ergänzungen auf Seite 3 möglich*

Hinweise auf besonderes ethisches Risiko

Die folgenden Punkte sind kein Ausschlusskriterium für die Ausstellung einer Unbedenklichkeitserklärung. Wenn Sie eine oder mehrere der folgenden Punkte mit Ja beantworten, nehmen Sie bitte anschließend dazu Stellung.

Ja/ Nein

1. Nicht alle Proband:innen sind voll geschäftsfähig.
2. Es werden vulnerable Proband:innen(-gruppen) teilnehmen (z.B. Patient:innen, Personen mit Behinderung oder Lernstörung etc.).
3. Es liegt eine Täuschung über Inhalt, Zweck, Methode, Setting und die Teilnahme vor.
4. Es werden Fragen gestellt, die intimer Natur sind.
5. Es werden Fragen gestellt, die stigmatisierend wahrgenommen werden können.
6. Es können Hinweise auf Suizidalität auftreten.
7. Es können Zufallsbefunde (z.Bsp. Hinweis auf das Vorliegen einer Depression) auftreten.
8. Es gibt körperliche o. mentale Belastungen und/oder Risiken für Proband:innen.
9. Den Proband:innen werden Medikamente, Placebos o.a. Substanzen verabreicht.
10. Es werden Blut- und/oder Gewebeproben entnommen.
11. Es gibt Probleme bei der Einhaltung der EU-Datenschutzrichtlinien.

Stellungnahme zu möglichen ethischen Risiken

Falls Sie eine oder mehrere Punkte bejaht haben, erläutern Sie bitte kurz, welche besonderen Vorkehrungen Sie getroffen haben, um mögliche ethische Risiken zu minimieren und nennen Sie die Stellen im Gesamtantrag, an denen Sie dazu Stellung genommen haben.

Abstract (Ergänzungen/Weiterführung von Seite 1)

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg

Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg • Ethikrat • 96045 Bamberg

Prof. Dr. Andreas Jungherr
Politikwissenschaft, insbes. Digital
Transformation
Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg
Feldkirchenstraße 21
96052 Bamberg

Ethikrat
Otto-Friedrich-Universität
Bamberg

Prof. Dr. Thomas Weißer (Laubach)

Tel. +49 (0) 951 / 863 1733
Fax +49 (0) 951 / 863 4734
ethikrat@uni-bamberg.de

Unbedenklichkeitsbescheinigung

Antrag: 2025-01/03

Bamberg, den 07.01.2025

Guten Tag, Andreas Jungherr,
die Studie

AI4Deliberation: Representative Survey

wurde dem Ethikrat der Universität vorgelegt und von ihm sorgfältig geprüft. Die Studie ist aus der Sicht des Ethikrates der Universität Bamberg ethisch unbedenklich.

Mit freundlichen Grüßen

Handwritten signature of Thomas Weißer in black ink.

Prof. Dr. Thomas Weißer (Laubach)

Vorsitzender des Ethikrates der Universität

BESUCHSADRESSE
Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg
An der Universität 2
Raum U2/02.11
96047 Bamberg

BRIEFADRESSE
Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg
96045 Bamberg

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ethikrat@uni-bamberg.de

Ethics Statement

Bamberg, den 07.01.2025

Dossier number 2025-01/03

Dear Andreas Jungherr,
the study

AI4Deliberation: Representative Survey

was reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the University of Bam-
berg, Germany, and an approval granted.

With best regards

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads 'Thomas Weißer'.

Prof. Dr. Thomas Weißer (Laubach)

Chairman of the Ethics Committee

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Annexes 11-12
DebateGraph's privacy policies and registration page

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Privacy Policy

Date of Last Revision: 30 November 2023

Privacy Policy

This is the Privacy Policy for Thoughtgraph's DebateGraph web application.

Thoughtgraph is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy online, and the collection and use of your personal information will be restricted to the minimum required to continue to deliver, develop and improve services for you. DebateGraph is not funded by advertising, so we don't collect data in order to advertise to you.

Thoughtgraph has strict security and confidentiality procedures covering the storage and disclosure of your information in order to safeguard it, to prevent unauthorised access and to comply with the *UK Data Protection Act 2018*—and only authorised personnel are permitted to have access to the information.

It is your right to be informed about how Thoughtgraph manages your personal information, and we are providing this Privacy Policy to explain how we collect, receive, use, store, share and disclose your data through our web application. If you have any questions about your personal data and our policies, please email:

PrivacyPolicy@thoughtgraph.com

Who We Are

Thoughtgraph creates the web application DebateGraph, and is incorporated in UK.

Our registered address is:

20 Gordon's Close, Taunton, Somerset, TA1 3DA, UK.

Privacy enquiries can be made via:

PrivacyPolicy@thoughtgraph.com

Personal data requests can be made via:

data@thoughtgraph.com

Collection and Use Of Information

Data Collected or Received from You

Our primary goals in collecting information are

- to provide and improve DebateGraph,
- to administer your use of DebateGraph (including your Account, if you are an Account holder),
- to provide you with updates, alerts and support and administrative notices and
- to otherwise enable you to enjoy and use DebateGraph.

Account Information. When registering to access DebateGraph, you are required to supply some personal information—at minimum your name and a valid e-mail address. At your discretion, you may also choose to share a fuller personal profile—including, for example, your professional and educational background, expertise, interests, age, affiliations, organisation, photograph etc.—and to make this information available to other users.

Information Related to Use of DebateGraph. Our software or servers automatically record certain information about how you use DebateGraph including both account holders and non-account holders. This data may include information such as your Internet Protocol (IP) address, URL request, browser type, operating system, the nodes or maps or nodes that you browsed, search terms, the links on which you clicked and other statistics. We use this data to administer and improve DebateGraph.

Information Sent by Your Mobile Device. We collect certain information that your mobile device sends when you use DebateGraph, like the manufacturer, model, operating system, and version of your device, as well as information about your use of DebateGraph. We use this information to administer and improve DebateGraph (including, for example, understanding which devices and software we need to support).

Location Information. When you use DebateGraph, we may collect and store information about your location by converting your IP address into a rough geo-location, and may use this information to improve and personalise DebateGraph for you (for example, by presenting times to in your local time zone).

Information Collected Using Cookies

Like many websites, we use cookies to track site usage and trends and to improve the quality and customise your experience of DebateGraph.

A cookie is a tiny text file that resides on your computer, mobile phone, or other device, and allows us to recognise you as a user when you return to DebateGraph using the same computer and web browser. For more details on how organisations use cookies on websites, please see www.allaboutcookies.org.

We may use both session cookies and persistent cookies to identify that you've logged

in to DebateGraph and to tell us how and when you interact with DebateGraph. These cookies, for example, help us to determine whether you have permission to access your private maps and whether or not you are a moderator. We may also use cookies to analyse how DebateGraph is used and is performing – so that we can maintain, operate and improve DebateGraph. Session cookies, unlike persistent cookies, are deleted when you log off from DebateGraph and close your browser.

Although most browsers automatically accept cookies, you have the ability to accept or decline cookies by modifying the settings in your browser. However, please note that by deleting our cookies or disabling future cookies you may not be able to fully use DebateGraph. If you want to delete any cookies on your computer, please refer to the instructions for your browser or file management software to locate the file or directory that stores cookies.

The Ways We Use Your Information

Thoughtgraph uses your data in various ways to provide DebateGraph to you, including:

- to create a User Account
- to allow you to log in to DebateGraph
- to track how DebateGraph is performing and to enable us to improve DebateGraph.
- to send you periodic digests of updates to the maps that you have created and/or subscribed.
- to contact you occasionally with news about DebateGraph (including, for example, about new features and initiatives).

Information That We Share With Third Parties

Information Shared with Other Users. The information you share about yourself or choose to upload on DebateGraph, including, but not limited to, your profile photo, website, location, contact information and your name, may be published and viewable to other users of DebateGraph. In some circumstances, you may adjust the permissions on your posts to make them private or to limit their visibility to others. Outside of these circumstances, posting or updating any content on DebateGraph is a public action, and all content may be publicly visible by other users of DebateGraph. Public identification of all contributed content may include, but is not limited to, display of your account name.

Information Shared with Our Services Providers. We may engage third-party services providers (also known as subprocessors) to work with us to administer and

provide DebateGraph (including, for example, hardware, software, networking, storage). These third-party services providers may have access to your personal information only for the purpose of performing services on our behalf and are expressly obligated not to disclose or use your personal information for any other purpose. We currently we use the cloud hosting and services platform SoftLayer/IBM Cloud to host DebateGraph, as well website backups and monitoring. You can learn more about SoftLayer/IBM Cloud's privacy policy here: <https://www.ibm.com/privacy/us/en>

Subprocessor Contact Details:

Name	Description	Address	Contact
IBM Cloud	Cloud service provider	1 New Orchard Road, Armonk, New York, 10504-1722, United States	Chief Privacy and Trust Officer chiefprivacyoffice@ca.ibm.com

Information Disclosed in Connection with Business Transactions. The information we collect from you, including personal information, may be considered to be a business asset. Thus, if Thoughtgraph were to be acquired by a third party as a result of a transaction such as a merger, acquisition or asset sale or if our assets were to be acquired by a third party in the event we go out of business or enter bankruptcy, some or all of our assets, including your personal information, may be disclosed or transferred to a third party acquirer in connection with the transaction.

Information Disclosed for Our Protection and the Protection of Others. In certain situations, we may be required to disclose personal information in response to lawful requests by public authorities, including to meet national security or law enforcement requirements. We may disclose personal information to respond to subpoenas, court orders, or legal process, or to establish or exercise our legal rights or defend against legal claims. We may also share such information if we believe it is necessary in order to investigate, prevent, or take action regarding illegal activities, suspected fraud, situations involving potential threats to the physical safety of any person, violations of our Terms of Use, or as otherwise required by law.

Data Protection Laws

Under Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation or "GDPR," we rely on the following legal basis to process personal data:

- With Your Consent given when you create an account and agree to the Privacy Policy.
- Where Necessary to the Performance of Contract with You (upon your request, or as necessary to make DebateGraph available to you)

- Where necessary to the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims
- Our Legitimate Business Interests
- Compliance with Law

Your Rights

Under Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation or “GDPR”, you have the right to:

- Access to the personal data we hold about you
- Correct any personal data we hold if it is incorrect or out of date
- Request the removal of any personal data we hold about you. In some cases, we may need to hold certain information for legal reasons or for performance of contract
- Object to the processing of information if you feel we have made an incorrect assumption, based on the data that we hold about you
- Restrict any processing of your data until we can verify your information
- Request the transfer of your data to another third-party of your choice where technically feasible
- Where your data is processed on the basis of your consent, you may withdraw your consent at any time

If you would like to exercise any of your rights, please email data@thoughtgraph.com. If you are not an EU citizen, we will still honour these rights wherever possible.

Please note for multiple requests within a short time-frame or requests for the same information, we may charge you an admin fee. If a third-party is making a request on your behalf, we will require proof of your permission before acting. All requests will be processed and completed within 30 days.

Your Choices

We offer you choices regarding the collection, use and sharing of your personal information and we'll respect the choices you make. Please note that if you decide not to provide us with the personal information that we request, you may not be able to access all of the features of DebateGraph.

Opt-Out. We may periodically send you newsletters and e-mails with news of

DebateGraph updates and initiatives. When you receive such communications from us, you will have the opportunity to “opt-out” (either through your Account or by following the unsubscribe instructions provided in the e-mail you receive).

Modifying Your Information. If you have an Account, you can access and modify the personal information associated with your Account. You can also delete your Account at any time. Editing your content or deleting your Account may alter the displayed state of the content, but will not permanently delete the content from DebateGraph and some information may remain in archived/backup copies for our records or as otherwise required by law.

If you would like your data permanently deleted contact us at data@thoughtgraph.com.

Responding to Do Not Track Signals

DebateGraph does not currently respond to “Do Not Track” signals received from various web browsers.

The Security of Your Information

Thoughtgraph is committed to protecting your personal information once we have it.

We take reasonable administrative, physical and electronic measures designed to protect the information that we collect from or about you from unauthorised access, use or disclosure (including, for example, encrypting data in transit using SSL and restricting open ports).

Please be aware, however, that no method of transmitting information over the Internet or storing information is completely secure. Accordingly, we cannot guarantee the absolute security of any information, and if we learn of a security breach, we'll notify you so that you can take appropriate protective steps.

If you would like to report a vulnerability or have any security concerns with DebateGraph, please contact SecurityPolicy@thoughtgraph.com.

How Long We Keep Your Data

We will generally retain your profile and related personal information for as long as you have an account with us. If you wish to “be forgotten” by DebateGraph (i.e., request the deletion of your personal information from DebateGraph), you will need to delete your account (using the Remove button on your My Account page).

If you delete your account, to the extent permitted by applicable law, we may retain and use your personal information as necessary to comply with our legal obligations,

resolve disputes, maintain appropriate business records, and enforce our agreements. Further, any maps, nodes, comments, ratings, citations, cross-links etc. that you have posted to DebateGraph may continue to appear on DebateGraph, but your user name will be removed from such content, and your account will be indicated as deleted. Data may remain in offline backups indefinitely.

Support requests

If you contact our support team - through help@debategraph.org - we retain those messages indefinitely, unless you request we delete them.

Links to Other Sites

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Annex 13
Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

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AI4Deliberation

**DATA PROTECTION IMPACT
ASSESSMENT
(DPIA)**

April 17, 2026

PENDING ECR APPROVAL

Document History

Version	Date	Status	Author	Description
v 0.01	18/09/2025	Draft	IK	First draft sent to project management and SEAB for review purposes
v 0.02	30/10/2025	Final version	IK	Amended version following internal review
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1. AI4Deliberation project description

The AI4Deliberation project aims to develop and pilot an innovative framework for AI-enabled, multimodal, gamified public deliberations that are scalable, inclusive, and ethically grounded. Its vision is to support governments across Europe in institutionalising deliberative processes enhanced by emerging AI technologies capable of processing text, audio, and video data, while incorporating privacy-by-design principles and maintaining high standards of data protection, ethical integrity, and societal trust.

At the core of the project is the integration of AI functionalities such as automated summarisation, content moderation, fact-checking, and detection of hate speech and toxicity, all of which necessarily involve the collection, analysis, and processing of personal data generated during citizens' participation in deliberation activities. These may include speech recordings, video submissions, written contributions, and user interaction data related to gamification mechanisms (e.g., avatars, scoreboards, missions, participation metrics).

Additionally, the project aims to enhance accessibility, including scenarios where AI-based facilitators assist vulnerable users, such as the elderly or persons with disabilities. Alongside gathering data directly from COVID-19 patients (subject of one of the four pilots), the project will potentially encompass processing special categories of personal data (e.g., related to health, cognitive abilities, as well as political opinion).

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2. Pilot partners

The AI tools, platforms, applications and other software solutions developed within the project are intended to be applied, and thus tested, within deliberative processes facilitated by the pilot partners of the consortium – four entities which, in various contexts and settings, organize or enable mass deliberation activities on an international, national or local level:

Pilot 1 – ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA (GFOSS): In Greece, every draft law is published by the relevant Ministry in opengov.gr, providing citizens the opportunity to participate in national-level deliberations on draft legislation. For the AI4Deliberation project, several AI features will be tested (for example, the summarisation feature, opinion and argument extraction, and fact-checking). The participants in the testing phases will be initially internal technicians and administrators, and later also the general public.

Pilot 2 – THOUGHTGRAPH LTD (TG): TG is the provider of DebateGraph (debategraph.org) – a collaborative cloud-based platform, which enables participants to contribute various forms of content (text, images, video, links, citations etc.) on complex cultural and political issues, in the form of structured interactive policy graphs. Within the AI4Deliberation project TG aims to develop, as a shared public good, an open, comprehensive, collaborative and continuously evolving international graph of the societal impacts of Long Covid and the policy options arising, which can be used to support – and/or act as an external, transparent check and balance on – ongoing national policy deliberations on this topic. The pilot will explore the potential for AI features to augment and speed aspects of this process, which, if successful, will help different communities of stakeholders to apply these policy graphs as shared public goods in other deliberative contexts and inform the development of the wider AI4Deliberation Toolkit. While the graph will be open to general public participation (including people who are experiencing long covid), the structured nature of the graph building process means that the pattern of interaction is most likely to take the form of (i) a core group of individuals committed to representing the structure of the global policy conversation fairly and comprehensively, and (ii) a wider public community acting as a check and balance on the open, continuing work of the core group.

Pilot 3 – ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS (AAIT) and DEMBRANE B.V. (BRANE): The pilot is, in terms of content, based on the implementation of a national-scale deliberative process regarding the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC), which has been approved by the Italian Government. The participants will provide their opinion in audio form, which will be transcribed with the existing AI tool - the ECHO platform owned by BRANE. Within AI4Deliberation, the deliberative digital platform developers BRANE will technically explore the potential of integrating additional AI tools, not only providing the possibility of displaying and disseminating text content, but also video discussions. The participants will be recruited from various social strata, e.g. in terms of gender, age, rural-urban settings, which still needs to be decided by AAIT.

Pilot 4 – STADT BAMBERG (CBAM): The Municipality of Bamberg regularly opens discussions on their online platform to solicit input from local residents on various topics of local significance, such as the redesign and change of use of public spaces or the drafting of a self-imposed municipal data policy. Within AI4Deliberation, the use of AI features may be introduced to this platform, e.g., fact-checking and testing whether AI can mitigate misinformation and disinformation in municipal dialogue. The participants of this pilot will only be citizens of Bamberg.

Software developer – KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED (KT): KT is a company with long expertise in designing data-driven IT (incl. AI) solutions for the public sector. Their objective within the AI4Deliberation project is to develop the AI toolkit and architecture to support deliberative processes, possibly enhancing the platforms operated by TG and the Greek Government (opengov.gr) with AI features. KT will set up a sandbox that will enable the experimentation of AI-enhanced deliberation-specific tasks (e.g., argument extraction) and gamification (avatars, skill points, scores), assist pilots in determining their infrastructure needs and evaluate the AI models based on a prompt engineering test suite to determine which models are suitable.

A more detailed description of the project's objectives and activities to reach them, and the composition of the consortium, can be found in the Proposal template Part B: technical description, for more insights on the processing of personal data.

3. Why is a DPIA necessary?

Given the context outlined above, the AI4Deliberation project recognises that the risks to fundamental rights and freedoms — particularly with regard to privacy, personal data protection, and informed consent — must be systematically identified and addressed from the outset. The Data Protection Impact Assessment (hereafter: DPIA) should hence be conducted according to Art. 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (hereafter: GDPR) to assess, identify, and mitigate the ethical risks related to the data processing activities of the AI4Deliberation project.

Key personal data considerations include:

- **Multimodal personal data collection** (text, video, audio), including biometric data (e.g. voice) and interaction patterns.
- **Profiling and possible automated decision-making**, especially in gamified engagement systems and AI facilitation.
- **Data accuracy and fairness**, particularly in summarisation and moderation tools.
- **Security of large-scale deliberation datasets** and long-term storage of deliberation knowledge graphs.
- **Cross-border data sharing and transfers** during multi-country pilots.
- **Transparency and contestability** of AI outputs and institutional decision-making supported by AI based on personal data.

This DPIA is therefore initiated to ensure that all personal data processed within the AI4Deliberation framework is handled in compliance with GDPR and relevant national personal data protection laws, as well as internal rules that apply to individual members of the AI4Deliberation consortium. Its aim is to identify potential risk factors to personal data as well as to ensure that appropriate technical and organisational safeguards to mitigate these risks are put in place.

The DPIA is envisioned as a “living” document, a “work in progress” to be updated during the project timeline: an initial assessment of the AS-IS state is attempted first to identify the way personal data has been processed by the pilot partners in the past (i.e. before the start of the AI4Deliberation project) and whether any of this previously collected personal data aims to be repurposed for the AI4Deliberation project (hereafter: “secondary use”). In this initial stage, the pilot partners and other key consortium members have also provided their estimation on the expected collection/processing of personal data after AI features are introduced to their deliberation tools and

methods. It must be noted that at present, the majority of pilot partners had not yet carved out the details of how their deliberation processes will be enhanced with AI tools. The only AI tool which has been definitively chosen to be applied in pilot trials was Dembrane's ECHO tool, which will be used in the Italian pilot (AAIT), but it remains to be determined in what manner and scope the tool will be applied.

Consequently, after the design phase of the AI tools is completed and the AI solutions are ready to be tested in the pilots, the DPIA will be updated with accurate information on the processing of personal data during the four pilot trials for all pilot partners. The updated DPIA will cover all aspects of personal data processing in the pilot trials as well as risks to participant's privacy, associated specifically with AI use (for example AI content moderation). The risk assessment will be conducted in multiple stages – risks will be identified and mitigated gradually, following the progress of project activities. Initially, only present risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. At a later stage, risks relating to the application of AI tools and add-ons to existing pilot platforms/services will be identified and added to the DPIA, together with possible mitigation measures, i.e. as/if these concern processing of personal data.

In this version of the DPIA, the following questions are analysed, according to the Article 35 GDPR:

- Description of the types of data (primary, secondary use of data, data sources, personal data, special categories of data – Article 9 GDPR) that will be processed within the research project)
- Clarification on how all the personal data that will be processed are relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project (in accordance with the “data minimisation” principle)
- Description of the organisational, technical and security measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants
- Description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques, and in case personal data are not to be anonymized/pseudonymized, a justification for not anonymizing/pseudonymizing the relevant data
- For personal data to be transferred from the EU to a non-EU country or international organisation, a justification that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the GDPR

- For personal data to be transferred from a non-EU country to the EU (or another third country), a justification that such transfers comply with the laws of the country in which the data was collected
- Detailed information on the informed consent procedures related to the processing of personal data

Through this DPIA, the consortium reaffirms its commitment to personal data processing and to developing ethical, transparent, and trustworthy AI systems to aid in democratic deliberation processes without compromising the fundamental right to personal data protection, in compliance with the relevant national, international, and EU regulations and ethical standards.

The consortium's commitment to ethics is exemplified by the presence of an **Ethics Manager** (Inštitut za kriminologijo - IK), ensuring that all project activities adhere to the highest ethical standards. Furthermore, the **Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board** (SEAB), comprising experts with extensive experience in AI ethics and data protection, provides an additional layer of oversight and guidance. The Board includes a balanced, multidisciplinary set of experts in areas essential to the project.

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4. DPIA Methodology

To assess the risks to privacy and personal data protection of project participants, IK structured a questionnaire designed to identify what activities related to personal data processing will be carried out during the pilot trials (sprint rounds), as well as what (if any) personal data processing activities have already been performed by pilot partners prior to the start of the sprints, focusing specifically on the reuse of personal data, collected before the AI4Deliberation project, possible for other purposes (other projects or actual democratic deliberation processes). The questions pertained to all relevant aspects of personal data processing - how personal data is being or will be collected, analysed and transferred, on what grounds, for which purposes, and how the principles of personal data protection, codified in the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (hereinafter: GDPR) and national data protection legislation, will be implemented. After pilot partners filled out the questionnaire in writing, we also conducted 1-on-1 calls with each pilot to review their answers and address possible outstanding issues.

Based on the questionnaire and the calls with the pilot partners, IK categorised and recorded all relevant aspects of personal data processing for each individual pilot, as well as identified all foreseeable situations and scenarios, which could pose a risk to participants privacy and personal data protection. The risks were subsequently evaluated via a dedicated risk matrix and accompanied by possible mitigation measures, aimed at neutralizing or minimizing identified risks.

It must be noted at this point, that at the time of drafting the first version of this DPIA, the pilot trials (sprints) were not yet underway, and most of the pilot partners were in the initial (preliminary) stages of planning their pilot trial activities. Most aspects of integrating AI into their deliberation processes, platforms and tools were undetermined. Subsequently, several highly relevant questions about personal data processing during pilot trials and especially the effect of AI on personal data protection were left to be identified, determined and evaluated at a later stage. This resulted in the joint decision of IK and project management, to design the DPIA as an evolving, “living” document which will be updated as the project progresses. For this purpose, at least one more round of questionnaires and meetings with pilot partners will be carried out, following which the DPIA document will be accordingly supplemented with newly identified personal data protection aspects, risks and mitigation measures.

At the preparation of this DPIA, the IK ethics and legal team was supported by internal reviewer Sam Nouws (TUD) and external reviewers from the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) composed of experts: Heidi Beate Bentzen, Alice Siu and Alexei Grinbaum.

5. Risk Matrix

		Severity of Impact		
		Minimal	Significant	Severe
Likelihood of Harm	Remote	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
	Possible	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
	Probable	MEDIUM	HIGH	HIGH

The risks to personal data protection are evaluated based on a matrix which combines the relative likelihood of harm with the severity of the impact on the rights of participants. Both criteria are evaluated to create pairings between the probability of harm resulting from a specific risk situation with the extent of negative consequences incurred. Examples: If the likelihood of an act of personal data processing causing harm is remote, and the impact on individuals rights is minimal, the risk is considered low. Adversely, if the likelihood of harm is probable and the impact significant or severe, the risk is graded as high.

There have been no high-risk situations identified with this first version of the DPIA, mainly because the processing of personal data by the pilot partners at this stage of the project was limited and due to a lack of definitive knowledge about how personal data might be impacted once AI tools are tested in pilot trials. As the DPIA will be updated during later stages of the AI4Deliberation project, all risk situations will be evaluated anew, through the lens of using AI technology to moderate debates, summarize content or carry out other tasks within deliberation processes.

6. Data Processing Impact Assessment for Pilot Partners

6.1 ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA (GFOSS) - Greek Pilot

1. Stakeholders involved in personal data processing	
Who are the stakeholders involved in personal data processing?	<p>Participants – data subjects: Individuals who submitted comments on legislative proposals via the platform opengov.gr, provided by the Greek government (Ministry of Administrative Reform and E-Governance)</p> <p>Researchers: Primarily the staff/dedicated employees of the pilot partner. The results and (only if necessary) raw personal data collected during the pilot trials will be shared with consortium members of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>Third parties: To be determined</p>
Who are data controllers?	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
Who are data processors?	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
What rules on personal data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GDPR

protection (internal, national, supranational) are data controllers subject to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Greek Law 4624/2019 “on the Hellenic Data Protection Authority, the implementation of Regulation 2016/679 and the transposition of Directive 2016/680” (“Greek Data Protection Law”) • Privacy Policy of the Ministry of Administrative Reform and E-Governance available at https://www.opengov.gr/home
2. Scope of data collection and processing	
Who will personal data be collected from?	Data will be collected from Greek citizens, posting comments on Greek draft laws via the government-hosted platform opengov.gr . Only publicly available comments will be scraped, with any personal identifiers such as names or emails being anonymised before further processing of comments. Subsequently, the scraped anonymized data will be aggregated.
How many individuals will data be collected from?	To be determined, but expectedly, several hundred or thousands of individual comments will be scraped. During Sprint 1, the dataset is comprised of comments from historical consultations on the opengov.gr platform, as these are publicly available for all previous consultations. Additionally, a subset of 42 synthetically generated comments was annotated for moderation pipeline evaluation.
Geographical area of the participants	Greece mostly but Greeks abroad may also take part.

Will personal data of children and/or other vulnerable individuals be processed?	The opengov.gr platform does not collect demographic or personal profile data from commentators, which means there is no mechanism to identify whether vulnerable individuals are among the participants. Determining vulnerability status would require analysing the substance of individual comments for this specific purpose, which falls outside the scope and objectives of the AI4Deliberation project. During Sprint 1, no live participants were involved. For Sprint 2, the platform's open-access design means that any citizen may participate, but no vulnerability-specific recruitment, screening, or targeted safeguards are in place, as the platform functions as a general-purpose legislative consultation tool under the Greek government's framework.
How will the data be collected (e. g. via online tools and platforms, interviews and questionnaires , polls, etc)	Data will be collected from online citizens' comments on draft legislation, which are publicly available from an openly available platform.
What personal data will be collected?	In principle, users can comment on Greek draft legislation by selecting as their user name their actual name or a pseudonym. Participants must also provide an email address, which may or may not contain personal data (use of non-descriptive email address is also allowed). Expectedly, all personal identifiers (such as names/usernames/emails) will be removed before further processing of comments. It is possible that the content of the comments themselves could contain enough personal data that a specific individual could be identified from the content of the comment. This possibility is remote and risk to individual's data privacy is low. Nonetheless, the collected data (comments) will be anonymized with an anonymization technique which not only removes identifiers like personal names, user names and emails, but also (to an extent) contextual data which could be compiled to identify a specific individual.

	<p>For Sprint 2, participants can share their personal data (full name and/or email address) for the purpose of possible further communication regarding the deliberation process or its outcomes. Participants are informed of the voluntary nature of this data provision. Before the transmission of the pilot data to the shared project infrastructure a more comprehensive anonymisation technique based on Named Entity Recognition (NER) will be applied to detect and remove additional personal identifiers (such as names, locations, and organisational affiliations) that may appear within the text of comments themselves.</p>
<p>Will special categories of data be collected? If so, which categories?</p>	<p>No special categories of personal data will expectedly be collected.</p>
<p>How often will data be collected?</p>	<p>Data will most probably be collected once per sprint during the project life cycle.</p>
<p>How will the collected data be used?</p>	<p>The collected data will be used for summarization, translation, argumentation mining, sentiment analysis and AI training for democratic deliberation tools.</p>
<p>Would data subjects expect their</p>	<p>No, data subjects commenting on past Greek draft laws via the government-hosted platform were not explicitly informed that their data would be reused for the AI4Deliberation project, as their comments were submitted for the purpose of participating in the public debate on national legislation proposals. It must be pointed out, that until recently, the opengov.gr platforms' Privacy Policy and Terms of use were not aligned with GDPR and did not contain</p>

<p>data to be used in this way?</p>	<p>necessary privacy and data processing information for users. The Privacy Policy has since been updated with the necessary information under GDPR, but does not contain a mention that user data and comments can be used for research purposes.</p> <p>In the context of Sprint 2 onwards the terms and conditions of the pilot platform will contain information about the use of user comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project.</p>
<p>3. Purpose of processing and lawful basis</p>	
<p>What is the purpose of data processing?</p>	<p>The purpose of collecting citizens' comments is to assess the quality, intensity and other dimensions of public deliberation and support the development of AI tools promoting democratic engagement.</p>
<p>What are the benefits of data processing for the controllers, data subjects and the wider public?</p>	<p>Improvements in public policy participation, e.g. qualitative improvement of citizens engagement, AI-supported analysis of citizen input, and academic/policy research.</p>

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<p>What is the lawful basis for data processing (for all categories of personal data)?</p>	<p>The lawful basis for the processing of personal data on the opengov.gr is stated as Article 6(1)(c) of the GDPR (“compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject”) and Article 6(1)(e) (“performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller”).</p> <p>However, for collection and processing of personal data for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project (as of Sprint 2) the lawful basis for the processing of personal data (including special categories of personal data) will be consent under Article 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR.</p>
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4. Principles of data processing

<p>Transparency: Which information will be given to data subjects prior to the collection of their data? In what manner will data subjects be informed about the nature of</p>	<p>During and after the second pilot testing the terms and conditions will contain information about the use of user comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project.</p>
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data processing and their respective rights?	
Accuracy: Are data subjects able to update their personal data in case of changes?	No, the opengov.gr website does not allow subsequent changes or updates to comments.
Data minimization: Is the personal data collected the minimum necessary to achieve the purpose?	Yes. Expectedly, all personal identifiers (user name and emails) will be deleted from the research data set before any further processing. The only remaining personal data might be contextual – in rare cases contained in the content of the comments themselves.
5. Data access and sharing	
Who will have access to the personal data	Access to the datasets collected and stored by GFOSS is available to GFOSS project staff.

<p>of data subjects?</p>	<p>Text contributions (deliberation posts and comments), reactions/votes, and timestamps are transmitted to the shared project infrastructure, which can be accessed by consortium members. No personal identifiers (name, email) are included in this transmission.</p> <p>In addition, anonymised and AI-ready datasets derived from opengov.gr consultations are published as open data on the Hugging Face platform through GFOSS's glossAPI.gr initiative, as part of GFOSS's broader strategy for fully open-source AI and open data in the public sector.</p>
<p>Will access be restricted to those with a strict need to know?</p>	<p>Access to any intermediary data (prior to anonymisation) is restricted to GFOSS project staff and stored on GFOSS's self-hosted servers. The GFOSS system administrator and GFOSS employees directly involved and assigned to the project have access to locally stored pilot data. Access is limited to those with a clear operational need.</p> <p>The final anonymised datasets are published openly, consistent with the FAIR data principles and GFOSS's open-source AI strategy.</p>
<p>How will access be controlled?</p>	<p>Intermediary data access is controlled internally by GFOSS. Published open datasets on Hugging Face are accessible under open licences.</p>
<p>Who will the data be shared with?</p>	<p>Datasets are shared with the AI4Deliberation consortium and also published as open data on Hugging Face via glossAPI.gr for use by the broader research and AI development community.</p>
<p>Is there any scope to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?</p>	<p>Data is anonymised at the point of collection by excluding usernames, email addresses, and other personal identifiers from the scraped datasets. During Sprint 1, this was achieved through direct removal of username and email fields during the data extraction process, through hashing names (converting names into a code) and adding a random string („salt“) to further prevent reidentification. For Sprint 2, a more comprehensive anonymisation technique based on Named Entity Recognition (NER) will be applied to detect and remove additional personal</p>

	identifiers (such as names, locations, and organisational affiliations) that may appear within the text of comments themselves.
6. Data retention and cybersecurity	
How long will data be retained?	Raw pilot data will be retained by GFOSS for a maximum of 6 months following the conclusion of the project, after which it will be deleted. Data from formal government deliberation rounds that is permanently available via the opengov.gr website, will expectedly be retained permanently. All comments from all previous government deliberation rounds are and will remain available for download. Expectedly for future deliberations, the same will apply.
Is there a clear reason for the retention period?	The advancement of open science.
Are there procedures in place for monitoring data retention?	No.
Will data be stored securely, and what are the	The opengov.gr platform is hosted on-premise at the Greek Ministry of Education server, located in Greece, operated and managed by GFOSS.

information security protection measures employed?	Data used for AI4Deliberation purposes is securely stored on GFOSS's servers, located within the European Union and in Hugging face website servers. Any transmission to the shared project infrastructure are TLS 1.2+ and HTTPS encrypted.
Is the level of security appropriate to the risks of data loss or breach?	Yes. The servers are self-hosted and access to data is limited to research staff.
Will procedures be put in place for the deletion of data when retention is no longer required?	Data will be stored permanently.
7. Data transfers	
Will there be any transfers of	No transfers of data outside the EU/EEA are planned.

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personal data to countries outside the EU? How will personal data protection be ensured in these cases?	
Is this data transfer necessary or could it be avoided by the use of other methods and service providers?	N/A
8. Rights of data subjects	
How much control will the data subjects have over the	Principally, data subjects will not have any control over the use of their comments, as the comments are public. With regard to user names and emails, those will be removed before any further processing of comments.

use of their data?	
What effects will data processing have on data subjects?	No adverse effects on data subjects are anticipated in the context of the project.
How are the rights of data subjects relating to the processing of their personal data ensured?	Data subjects rights should not be adversely affected by the processing of their public comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project.

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RISK IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

NOTE: Initially, only present risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. Risks and possible mitigation measures will be identified and addressed gradually, following the progress of project activities.

Risk situation	Likelihood of Harm	Severity of Impact	Overall assessment	Reasoning	Possible mitigation measures
1. Inadequate/misguiding information given to data subjects	Probable	Minimal	MEDIUM	Participants contributing comments to the opengov.gr platform will most likely not be aware that their comments (without their personal identifiers) will be used for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project. However, the comments are posted publicly, of which participants are aware.	When this pilot focuses on the analysis of users' comments on current/existing Greek draft legislation (Sprint 2 and onwards), the participants will need to be adequately informed about the use of their comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project with a public notice and required to consent to the processing of their personal data.

2. Disabled or impeded access to personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	For data collection during pilot trials, participants will be made aware if the processing of their comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project with appropriate notices, but as the comments will be anonymized before further processing, no access of users to their personal data is envisioned or made possible.	
3. Inability of data subjects to correct/update data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing, therefore possible updates of personal data are not possible or necessary.	
4. Inability of data subjects to request the deletion of their personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing.	
5. Inability of data subjects to restrict processing as an	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing.	

alternative to data deletion					
6. Inability of data subjects to access services	Remote	Minimal	LOW	The accessibility of the opengov.gr website depends upon the administrator of the platform (Greek government) and is outside the scope of pilot influence. However, the governmental platform is sufficiently robust and has been consistently available from the start of its operation.	
7. Discrimination	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing, making it effectively impossible to distinguish among users and thus discriminate between them.	
8. Identity theft	Remote	Minimal	LOW	On the opengov.gr platform users are free to choose their user name, which can be their actual name or a pseudonym. There is the theoretical chance of users using other individuals' names (for example names of politicians or	

				celebrities), but there are no apparent benefits for users doing so. The Greek public is aware, that the pseudonyms can be freely chosen. No adverse effects of users posing as somebody else are expected, especially as user names will be deleted before further comment processing.	
9. Fraud	Remote	Minimal	LOW	No possibility of fraud or adverse effects in this regard are identified.	
10. Financial loss	Remote	Minimal	LOW	No possibility of financial loss or adverse effects in this regard are identified.	
11. Reputational damage	Remote	Minimal	LOW	It is possible that user comments could have negative effects on the reputation of a specific individual, but this is not in the domain of the pilot. User comments will be aggregated after collection and no individual comments will be reposted or specifically exposed, minimising the risk of reputational damage.	

12. Physical harm	Remote	Minimal	LOW	No possibility of physical harm or adverse effects in this regard are identified.	
13. Emotional harm	Remote	Minimal	LOW	No possibility of emotional harm or adverse effects in this regard are identified. While it is possible that individuals might sustain emotional harm as a consequence of users' public comments, but the risk of this is low and outside the sphere of influence of the pilot. User comments will be aggregated after collection and no individual comments will be reposted or specifically exposed, minimising the risk of harm.	
14. Loss of confidentiality	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing.	
15. Reidentification after anonymisation	Remote	Significant	LOW	In exceptional cases, participants' comments may contain enough data (like name, profession, ethnicity, geographical location, age, etc.) for a specific individual to	While names and emails can easily be filtered and deleted before any processing of data takes place, erasing personal circumstances from comment

				<p>be identifiable solely from the content of the comments. The possibility of this is remote, given that the opengov.gr platform is available to all adult Greek citizens. For data collection during pilot trials, participants will be made aware if the processing of their comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project with appropriate notices.</p>	<p>text requires the use of specialized technology and/or human oversight. For Sprint 2, a more comprehensive anonymisation technique based on Named Entity Recognition (NER) will be applied to detect and remove additional personal identifiers (such as names, locations, and organisational affiliations) that may appear within the text of comments themselves.</p>
<p>16. Loss, tampering or unauthorised disclosure of personal data due to poor physical security measures and cybersecurity breaches</p>	<p>Remote</p>	<p>Minimal</p>	<p>LOW</p>	<p>Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing. Self-hosted servers and limited access of pilot staff to research data further minimize this risk.</p>	
<p>17. Unclear purpose of processing</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Minimal</p>	<p>LOW</p>	<p>Participants on the opengov.gr platform from previous</p>	

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				<p>deliberations have indeed not been made aware that their comments will be used for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>However, since personal data will be deleted before processing and the comments are published on the platform publicly with the participants' consent, the harmful impact on individuals through the processing of their public comments is minimal. For data collection during upcoming pilot trials, participants will be made aware if the processing of their comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project with appropriate notices.</p>	
18. Processing for new purposes	Possible	Minimal	LOW	<p>Participants on the opengov.gr platform from previous deliberations have indeed not been made aware that their comments will be used for the</p>	

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				<p>purposes of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>However, since personal data will be deleted before processing and the comments are published on the platform publicly with the participants' consent, the harmful impact on individuals through the processing of their public comments is minimal. For data collection during upcoming pilot trials, participants will be made aware if the processing of their comments for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project with appropriate notices.</p> <p>Data collected for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project will not be used for any other purpose or shared with third parties outside the consortium.</p>	
19. Unlawful processing of special	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Pilot participants may reveal special categories of personal data	

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categories of personal data				through the content of their comments, especially their political opinion and religious beliefs. However, as all personal identifies will be deleted prior to further processing, the possibility of identification of the specific individual based on this data, and resulting negative consequences for participants, are remote.	
20. Redundant or excessive personal data collection (contrary to the principle of data minimisation)	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing, effectively minimizing the use of any personal data.	
21. Inaccuracy of personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Personal data will be deleted from comments before further processing.	

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6.2 THOUGHTGRAPH LTD (TG) – International pilot

1. Stakeholders involved in personal data processing	
Who are the stakeholders involved in personal data processing?	<p>Participants – data subjects: The participants of the pilot trial will be individuals who have created a user account (profile) on the DebateGraph platform. Afterwards, they can add nodes and contribute content (text, documents, images, videos, links, citations, etc.) to the Long Covid policy graph – the pilot case study. Some personal data may be collected temporarily (as part of the essential technical functionality of the site) for non-logged in visitors to DebateGraph who are able view the publicly available content but not able contribute to the graph (without first registering and/or logging-in).</p> <p>Researchers: primarily the staff of Thoughtgraph (TG) which consists of two founders who are also administrators and have access to all data of users and non-users, as well as content contributed to the graph. The results of the pilot trial (but not raw personal data of participants) may be shared with consortium members of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>Third parties: DebateGraph is hosted on the servers of cloud service provider IBM in the USA.</p>
Who are data controllers?	Thoughtgraph Ltd. (TG) – pilot partner
Who are data processors?	Thoughtgraph Ltd. (TG) – pilot partner
What rules on personal data protection (internal, national, supranational)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR • Data Protection Act 2018; UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR), proposal of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 (TBU) • Internal Privacy Policy of DebateGraph available at https://debategraph.org/Details.aspx?nid=65028

are data controllers subject to?	
2. Scope of data collection and processing	
Who will personal data be collected from?	Personal data will be collected from members of the public who create a user profile on DebateGraph, which is the platform being used to run and host the AI4Deliberation pilot. There is no limitation or conditions as to who may become a user, as the platform is open to all members of the public, globally. Information from the browser (such as IP address, device type, and approximate location/timezone) will also be collected and temporarily stored for the duration of the live browser session (to support the live site functionality) for visitors to the site who do not create a user profile but only view at the publicly available content on the webpage.
How many individuals will data be collected from?	Fewer than 100 users expected to actively contribute content to the graph, but several thousand visitors (non-registered users) plus are expected to visit the site.
Geographical area of the participants	Global
Will personal data of children and/or other vulnerable individuals be processed?	<p>The DebateGraph Privacy Policy prohibits children under the age of 13 to create user profiles and if a case would be discovered such a profile would be deleted. The Privacy Policy also features a statement to the effect that users affirm that they are either more than 18 years of age or possess legal parental or guardian consent and are fully able and competent to understand, enter into, and comply with the Terms & Conditions of DebateGraph.</p> <p>The international pilot will not actively seek the input from children; however, it also does not want to automatically exclude the voices of people who are younger than 18 (e.g. 16-18), and who are experiencing long covid and are already acting as public advocates for better public policy responses to long covid in children.</p>

	<p>Age based ID checks on registration would also require all users to share more significant personal data than is currently required and would run counter to the important privacy principles currently enacted on of requiring minimal personal data and using functionally cookies only.</p> <p>The registration process is open to all, and minimal data is required for registration (name and a valid/confirmed email address,) special considerations not given to other vulnerable groups of individuals. The data required for registration also supports pseudonymous participation (supported by a valid/confirmed email address). In the light of each of these factors, the risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons leading to physical, material or non-material damage, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, damage to the reputation, loss of confidentiality or any other significant economic or social disadvantage is unlikely.</p>
<p>How will the data be collected (e. g. via online tools and platforms, interviews and questionnaires, polls, etc.)</p>	<p>Personal data is entered by the user at the creation of their user profile on the online platform DebateGraph. Some personal data (like IP address, device type, and approximate location/time-zone) are also collected by the platform software for registered users and site visitors (non-users) as part of the essential functionality of the site.</p>
<p>What personal data will be collected?</p>	<p>For the creation of the user profile the data required on registration is: first name, last name, and a valid and confirmed email address. As the accuracy of the name data is not validated in any way, in theory, a user could create a profile (with a valid but non-descriptive email address) without revealing personal data. Optionally, users can also share: their approximate location (Country and/or Town), a short biography, a personal website, and a thumbnail picture or avatar. IP addresses, device types, and approximate location/time zone are also collected for users and non-users during the live browser session to support the essential functionality of the site. Because DebateGraph is a user-generated content platform, users can upload various types of content (text, documents, images and videos). Therefore, it is possible that this content would contain other types of personal data like their address, age, education, as well as ethnic origin, political beliefs, observations about personal health in the context of the long covid graph, voice recordings, and other personal data.</p>

<p>Will special categories of data be collected? If so, which categories?</p>	<p>At the creation of the user profile, no special categories of data are collected, but because users can upload content to the platform, it is possible that some participants might opt to share special categories of personal data, like political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or personal experiences of Long Covid as a form of health data. It is also possible for users to embed videos (showing themselves) that have been uploaded elsewhere (e.g. YouTube).</p>
<p>How often will data be collected?</p>	<p>The data entered at the creation of the user profile is only collected once, but can be edited at any time by the user. The background technical session data is collected as account holders and non-account holders use DebateGraph, and participant contributions to the graph are collected as users make the contributions to the graph.</p>
<p>How will the collected data be used?</p>	<p>The data is used in various ways to operate the online platform, including: creating a user account; enabling log in to DebateGraph; tracking how DebateGraph is performing and to help improve DebateGraph; to send (optionally) periodic digests of updates to maps, and (optionally) to share news about DebateGraph (including, for example, about new features and initiatives). Data collected as part of the International Pilot may also be used to support the wider research goals of the AI4Deliberation project (although at the time of writing the precise extent and form of the potential data use have not been determined as wider technical development on the project is just getting underway).</p>
<p>Would data subjects expect their data to be used in this way?</p>	<p>Yes. At registration data subjects are alerted and must consent to DebateGraph’s Privacy Policy, which contains a detailed explanation of the aim and nature of the processing of their personal data, and Long Covid graph will include a detailed background on the role of the graph, the potential uses of AI in the context of the graph, the role of data within the wider AI4Deliberation project, and the fact that the content shared into the graph will be publicly visible (and hence open to review and use by external actors, such as employers and insurance agencies). With regard to personal data that users share as content in the graph, it can reasonably be expected that because the Long Covid graph, which will be the pilot trial, specifically focuses on this topic, users will voluntarily mostly share content, connected with this topic (this could specifically relate to their health, as well as their political beliefs and opinions in connection with how the topic of Long Covid was handled by authorities and how the public debate around this issue has so far been managed).</p>

3. Purpose of processing and lawful basis	
What is the purpose of data processing?	The pilot aims to develop a dynamically updated policy graph for Long Covid to create an open knowledge graph of Long Covid as a shared public good that can inform public deliberations globally and to experiment with a positive feedback loop between human and AI curators and readers of the graph – and, through this, to inform the wider development of the AI4Deliberation toolkit. For this purpose, users will be invited to create user profiles and share their knowledge and, optionally where this applies, their experiences regarding Long Covid. Due to the nature of the DebateGraph platform, the collection of personal data, entered at registration, is a necessary prerogative.
What are the benefits of data processing for the controllers, data subjects and the wider public?	Processing of personal data in this way enables the normal use of DebateGraph as a freely available tool to support individual and collective deliberation on public policy topics, and, in the context of the AI4Deliberation project, also informs the development of the AI Toolkit and the project’s research goals.
What is the lawful basis for data processing (for all categories of personal data)?	The lawful basis for the processing of personal data (including special categories of personal data) is consent under Article 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR. With regard to the user-uploaded content, there is neither a requirement nor an incentive for users to disclose any personal data in order to be able to participate in co-creating the graph. Any personal data shared by the user as uploaded/contributed content, is strictly voluntary. With regard to the processing of special categories of personal data (for example health data and political opinions), Article 9(2)(e) might also provide a suitable lawful basis, when participants post their personal data manifestly on the publicly available platform.
4. Principles of data processing	
Transparency: Which information will be given to data	At registering to DebateGraph and creating a user profile, the user is alerted, and specifically acknowledges DebateGraph’s privacy policy, which contains information about the data controller, explains the process of collection and processing of their personal data, the aims of data processing, the cookies policy, data sharing and

<p>subjects prior to the collection of their data? In what manner will data subjects be informed about the nature of data processing and their respective rights?</p>	<p>export to third countries, data retention period, rights of data subjects and data security measures. Without consenting to the Privacy Policy, the registration and creation of a user profile are not possible.</p> <p>In the context of the International Pilot, the Long Covid graph will also include a detailed background on the role of the graph, the potential uses of AI in the context of the graph, the role of data within the wider AI4Deliberation project, and the fact that the content shared into the graph will be publicly visible.</p>
<p>Accuracy: Are data subjects able to update their personal data in case of changes?</p>	<p>Yes. Users can update their personal data in their user profile at any time, as well as modify/delete any data they have uploaded to the platform as user content.</p>
<p>Data minimization: Is the personal data collected the minimum necessary to achieve the purpose?</p>	<p>The only data required for the creation of a user profile are name, surname and a valid email address. Theoretically, the user would be able to use the graph fully by adopting a pseudonym and entering an email address that does not reveal personal data. The required data is necessary for the user to be able to be identified as the participant/uploader of content (name/surname), whereas the email address is used for log in, to inform the user about possible policy changes and other necessary notifications of the data controller, changes to the graph they are participating in (optional), sending of digests (optional). All other personal data are contributed by the user voluntarily as part of their user profile or uploaded content. The processing of IP addresses, device type, and approximate location/time zone is a necessary technical requirement for the live functioning of the DebateGraph platform and users are made aware of this through the Privacy Policy.</p>

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5. Data access and sharing	
Who will have access to the personal data of data subjects?	Access to personal data is restricted exclusively to the two directors – who are also the co-founders and sole staff members – of DebateGraph as joint site administrators.
Will access be restricted to those with a strict need to know?	Yes. As the two co-founders administer DebateGraph jointly, it is necessary for them both to have access to personal data. But, as no other persons are involved in the administration of the platform, the data will not be accessed by third parties, keeping the count of people with access to a minimum.
How will access be controlled?	As TG is a two-person organization, access to data can be controlled and managed personally by both administrators, based on their internal agreement and division of tasks. This approach eliminates the need for a complex access-logging system. Third parties have no access to the personal data of DebateGraph users and non-users.
Who will the data be shared with?	It is not currently envisaged that any data from the first and Sprint 2 will be sent to the shared project infrastructure for ingestion and post-processing prior to the end of Sprint 2. Some publicly shared data contributed by participants may be sent to the shared project infrastructure for ingestion and post-processing as part of Sprint 3 (depending on the developments and use cases emerging from WP4). It is not anticipated that any data flows would involve personal data beyond the publicly accessible data in the graph.
Is there any scope to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?	As personal data is not expected to be shared with either consortium members or third parties at any point of the project, it seems that initially there is no need to anonymise or pseudonymise the data. All data needed for the purposes of this project will be publicly accessible as part of the graph and will be contributed by the users of the platform on a voluntary/consensual basis.

6. Data retention and cybersecurity	
How long will data be retained?	<p>The user registration data is retained continuously as part of the day-to-day operations of the DebateGraph platform until a person opts to close their account. When an account is closed, the personal data is retained as part of the essential functionality of the rolling, site backups for a period of 7 days, at which point it is permanently deleted. The retention of the content of the graphs is open-ended in accordance with the essential functionality of the site. However, participants can remove the content they have contributed to the graph themselves or request to have the content removed by administrators. Where a user has contributed significant portions to a collaborative graph's structure, the nodes and information are not removed, but the name of the contributor of this content is removed, thus effectively the data is de-identified.</p> <p>IP addresses, device type, and the approximate location/timezone of users and non-users, which is collected at their visiting of the platform, is retained only temporarily as part of the essential functionality of the site – for the duration of the live browser session for non-logged in and non-registered users and for a period of 7 days for logged-in registered users – and then deleted immediately.</p>
Is there a clear reason for the retention period?	<p>The retention period of 7 days is an intrinsic part of the essential rolling back up functionality of the site – which serves to safeguard users from the loss of contributed data. The rolling back ups – and their deletion after seven days function automatically and, as access to the data in the rolling back ups requires special procedures, distinct from usual functionality of the site, such data is designed to be accessed only in the unexpected event of the loss of live data on the live site.</p>
Are there procedures in place for monitoring data retention?	<p>Monitoring of retention is part of the usual day-to-day operations of DebateGraph and is managed manually by the two administrators of the platform. In cases where users delete their accounts, the administrators also manually check that all of the content uploaded by the user has been deleted (or in the case of contributions to the collaborative graphs, that the name of the contributor has been removed).</p>
Will data be stored securely, and what are the information security	<p>TG's methods of data security include the use of a physically secured and dedicated bare metal server, supported by a combination of hardware security, encryption and access control, intrusion detection and prevention systems, logging and monitoring, multi-factor authentication, regular security audits and audits of user accounts and access permissions to ensure that only authorized personnel have access. DebateGraph's server is physically located at an IBM Data Center in Dallas, Texas, with IBM Cloud acting as a sub-processor for TG.</p>

<p>protection measures employed?</p>	<p>Additional layers of security measures are applied at the point to registration to counter bot registrations (including validation of the email address supplied, an invisible captcha, checking the IP address against lists of know Spam/Bot IP Addresses and mail servers, and pattern matching on form field entries).</p> <p>Moreover, the complex structure of the graph-based website has (to date, at least) made it less conducive to generic bot interactions.</p> <p>The existing data entry fields across the site are designed to reject injection attacks, and similarly rigorous security measures will be applied to any new AI data entry fields to anticipate and block Prompt injection attacks.</p> <p>Prompt injection attacks will also be anticipated, and the appropriate countermeasures designed to reject the entry of scripts, will be implemented in the event of the introduction of any AI functionality that is potentially vulnerable to these forms of attack.</p>
<p>Is the level of security appropriate to the risks of data loss or breach?</p>	<p>Yes, the level of security is sufficient when considering the type of personal data that is processed as well as the nature of the platform, where personal data is contributed by the users on an informed consent basis, with their full knowledge of how the data will be used and who it will be visible to. The structure of the website also makes for an non-favourable environment for bots to set up fake user accounts. TG has implemented, and continues to update, the security measures outlined above to minimise any risks of data breaches, and, thus far, in 19 years of operation, TG is not aware that any incidents of data breach have occurred. Constant vigilance is an integral part of maintaining the platform, particularly given the rapid growth and application of AI capabilities and other threat actors that target personal data.</p>
<p>Will procedures be put in place for the deletion of data when</p>	<p>Yes. There is already a robust and well-functioning procedure of data deletion in place. At the closure of the user account all user personal data is deleted on the live server automatically and immediately (and then removed automatically from the site backups after the expiration of the backup retention period of 7 days), as well as the content the user has contributed, which is manually checked by the administrators of the platform. DebateGraph also gives continuing users the ability to delete specific items and/or sets of items of content that they have</p>

retention is no longer required?	previously shared on DebateGraph and that they no longer wish to share and all users are able to access and download programmatic outputs of their data on request.
7. Data transfers	
Will there be any transfers of personal data to countries outside the EU? How will personal data protection be ensured in these cases?	Yes. Data is stored on DebateGraph's server, which is physically located at an IBM Data Center in Dallas, Texas. IBM is certified under the Data Privacy Framework Program (DPF), which replaces the previous EU-US Privacy Shield. The European Commission considered that transfers of personal data from the EEA to companies certified under the DPF enjoy an adequate level of protection. As a result, personal data can be transferred freely to U.S. certified companies, without the need to put in place additional safeguards or obtain an authorisation.
Is this data transfer necessary or could it be avoided by the use of other methods and service providers?	The transfer is a necessary part of DebateGraph's established day-to-day operations, and, given the global nature of the userbase, transfer between third countries is an essential part of the process.
8. Rights of data subjects	
How much control will the data subjects	All personal data is entered on the basis of users' – i.e., data subjects' – consent and can be edited or deleted at any point. The only hard requirement for the opening of the user profile is the entering of a name (can be a pseudonym) and operational email address (which does not need to contain personal data). All other personal data

<p>have over the use of their data?</p>	<p>within the user profile as well as contributed to users withing individual graphs is entered by users themselves. This allows users virtually complete control over the use and accuracy of their personal data. The only personal data collected automatically from users and non-users are IP addresses, device type, and approximate location/time zone (as indicated by the IP address) at the visiting of the DebateGraph site. This is a necessary technical requirement for the functioning of the DebateGraph platform and users are made aware of this through the Privacy and Cookie Policies displayed on the site.</p>
<p>What effects will data processing have on data subjects?</p>	<p>The required personal data (name and valid email) enables users to create their user profile and contribute to the graphs. The scope of this necessary data follows the data minimization principle, safeguarding the privacy of data subjects and ensuring no personal data is collected end processed (except for the additional data that the users choose to share voluntarily). There are no adverse effects of personal data processing foreseen, as the personal data is not used for any other purpose than for the functioning of DebateGraph. The data is not sold to third parties for marketing or advertising purposes, and users are not profiled or targeted by either the data processor or third parties in relation to other services/products outside DebateGraph.</p>
<p>How are the rights of data subjects relating to the processing of their personal data ensured?</p>	<p>It is easy for data subjects to exercise their rights with regard to the processing of their personal data, as the contact details for the data controller are readily available on DebateGraph, and requests from data subjects (e.g. to remove all personal data) are – and have been – processed promptly and manually by human administrators. Data subjects can access their own data, and copies of their data can be delivered to them via the DebateGraph interface. They can also edit/update/erase their data of their own accord or ask the administrators to do so on their behalf.</p>

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RISK IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

NOTE: Initially, only present risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. Risks and possible mitigation measures will be identified and addressed gradually, following the progress of project activities.

Risk situation	Likelihood of Harm	Severity of Impact	Overall assessment	Reasoning	Possible mitigation measures
1. Inadequate/misguiding information given to data subjects	Remote	Minimal	LOW	The Long Covid Graph, which is currently being curated as a private map ahead of the public launch, identifies the graph as part of the AI4Deliberation project. When the graph is made available for public contributions of content by users, an information sheet shall be added to the landing site, informing users about the purposes of the Long Covid graph and the processing of personal data in connection with this graph and related to the AI4Deliberation project.	
2. Disabled or impeded access to personal data	Remote	Significant	LOW	Users can freely access and update their personal data via their user profile. Users and non-users also have the option to ask the site administrators to provide them	

				<p>with information on which personal data (pertaining to them individually) was collected and how it is being processed. Administrator contact data is published on the DebateGraph site.</p> <p>Since the site is available to users globally, there is a possibility of an increased influx of users requesting access to their data, should the graph gain wider recognition and traction. In this case, there is potential risk that the 2-person administrator team, which responds to access requests on a manual case-by-case basis, could be overwhelmed by a high influx of access requests, which could result in operational difficulties and delays to data access. Although this risk in such a scenario is significant for data subjects, the possibility of this issue arising is remote, as it is expected that there should be less than one hundred persons actively</p>	
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				contributing their data to the Long Covid graph.	
3. Inability of data subjects to correct/update data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Most of the personal data is contributed by the users of the graph themselves, either as part of the registration process or while contributing content to the structure of the graph. As users have full control over this data and can update it at any time, the risk of adverse effects is minimal. Additionally, users can always request that administrators of the platform update their data accordingly, should they be unable to do this by themselves.	
4. Inability of data subjects to request the deletion of their personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	User data is deleted when the user profile is closed. Data in backups is deleted automatically after 7 days. Data deletion is explained in the Privacy Policy, which is available on the DebateGraph website.	
5. Inability of data subjects to restrict processing	Remote	Minimal	LOW	There is currently no possibility for data subjects to restrict data processing as an alternative to data deletion. Given the limited staff of TG, this measure would be unfeasible.	

<p>6. Inability of data subjects to access services</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Significant</p>	<p>MEDIUM</p>	<p>Data is hosted on a reliable server, but maintenance issues and temporary server unavailability issues cannot be completely excluded. A longer downtime period could also result in users' loss of trust and interest in the graph, which could negatively affect the pilot trial.</p> <p>There are currently no specific functionalities to ensure access to services for people with disabilities (for example, visual impairments),</p> <p>The DebateGraph site is only generally available in the English language, due to the users of the site residing globally.</p>	<p>This risk of downtime of services is countered by the fact, that in 19 years of operation, the service has been available almost uninterruptedly. We evaluate the implementation of any additional measures to mitigate this risk is not necessary.</p> <p>With relation to providing services to people with visual impairments, the contents of the graph can be displayed in a document view that is, in principle, accessible to Text Readers – and, in cases where visual impairment represents an impediment to direct contributions to the graph, contributions can be suggested via, for example, email and be added to the graph on that person's behalf.</p>
<p>7. Discrimination</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Significant</p>	<p>MEDIUM</p>	<p>Currently, personal data of DebateGraph users is collected only for the purposes of creating user profiles. Personal data is not</p>	<p>To Be Determined (TBD) - With regard to the planned addition of AI features, the possible risks of discrimination between</p>

				<p>aggregated, analysed, categorized or otherwise processed in any way or for any other purpose. The data on users is thus collected non-discriminately and without regard or preference for any personal circumstance. All persons above the age of 18 are eligible to create a user profile and contribute to publicly available graphs, regardless of their gender, location, ethnicity or any other personal circumstance.</p> <p>Equally, the Long Covid graph – part of this pilot - will be publicly available to all interested users, who can add content to the graph on equal terms.</p>	<p>users will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools are determined.</p>
8. Identity theft	Remote	Significant	LOW	<p>User contributions to the graph are accompanied by the name and surname chosen by users. As users are free in their choice, and user names are not verified, there is a possibility of users assuming a false identity. This could potentially mislead other users and the general public about the identity of</p>	

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				<p>the contributor of the content. Other adverse effects are not envisioned.</p> <p>With regard to the theft of other data (for instance, user email), only the site administrators or potentially other consortium members will have access to this data, which lowers the risk of identity theft.</p>	
9. Fraud	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data (for the Long Covid graph), we grade this risk as low.	
10. Financial loss	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
11. Reputational damage	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	

12. Physical harm	Remote	Significant	LOW	As anyone can contribute content to the Long Covid graph, it is possible that faulty or harmful health advice could be posted intentionally or unintentionally by users of the graph. We grade this risk as low, due to factual data on the effects and remedies for Covid being widely known and readily available (and due to the ability of other users to contextualise and challenge potentially faulty or harmful health advice by sharing additional evidence and reasoning and in situ on the graph). Moreover, the material introducing the graph will make clear that the purpose of the graph is to map the full range of topics shared and that no aspects of the graph constitute medical advice.	
13. Emotional harm	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	The topic of COVID-19 and especially Long might cause anxiety and discomfort to some users. However, the graph aims to capture a wide range of policy related issues and evidence, which, in turn, may also be	Participating users should be provided with information on the purpose of the graph and the selected topic. They should also be informed prior to accessing the graph that the content may be emotionally triggering or

				<p>experienced empowering for a community of vulnerable individuals who are experiencing long covid and who feel that their voices and interests have not yet been fully heard in the context of existing policy deliberations. The participants are not encouraged in any way to share sensitive data or their subjective experience with the condition.</p>	<p>overwhelming and be offered resources and exit recommendations.</p>
14. Loss of confidentiality	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>TG's methods of data security include the use of a physically secure and dedicated server, supported by a combination of hardware security, encryption and access control, intrusion detection and prevention systems, logging and monitoring, multi-factor authentication, regular security audits and audits of user accounts and access permissions to ensure that only authorized personnel have access. Despite these strict security measures, which lower the possibilities of a data breach significantly, a breach cannot be completely ruled out.</p>	<p>We estimate that the cybersecurity currently in place is sufficient, given the scope of personal data collected and the risk posed to participants in case of a data breach.</p>

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				Data is stored outside the EU/EEA in Texas, USA, but the server provider IBM is certified under the Data Privacy Framework Program (DPF), which replaces the previous EU-US Privacy Shield.	
15. Reidentification after pseudonymisation	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>Content contributed to the graph is displayed with the chosen name of the user, to whom users have previously given informed consent.</p> <p>At the time of writing, due to the form of the pilot, the graph data generated, and the fact that the wider technical development on the AI4Deliberation project is just getting underway, the precise extent and form of the wider potential data use within the AI4Deliberation project have not yet been determined.</p> <p>Once any request for, and potential use cases for the data have been clarified, the questions of anonymization / pseudonymization and the</p>	

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				<p>avoidance of re-identification in such cases, will be addressed directly and in full.</p> <p>It is expected that raw data (user emails and other optional personal data entered by the user at the creation of the user profile) will not be shared with other consortium members and is only accessible to site administrators.</p>	
<p>16. Loss, tampering or unauthorised disclosure of personal data due to poor physical security measures and cybersecurity breaches</p>	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>As TG is operated by only two employees/administrators, who both have full access to personal data of users and visitors to the site, the risk of internal breaches by unauthorized personnel is very low to non-existent. There is, however, an ever-present possibility of an external cyberattack in which data could be lost, altered or disclosed to third parties/the public. In case of the loss or alteration of the graph's content – for which the 7-day backups provide one layer of mitigation – this would represent a</p>	<p>Given that current cybersecurity measures seem sufficient, additional security measures for the mitigation of this risk are not necessary. However, administrators should remain vigilant, particularly given the rapid growth and application AI capabilities and other threat actors that target personal data.</p>

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				<p>severe risk for the research project but not for data subjects themselves.</p> <p>With regard to unauthorized disclosure of personal data, this would only relate to user email addresses, which are not publicly disclosed. Possible special categories of personal data (like health data and political beliefs) are shared as part of the graph content voluntarily by users and are publicly accessible.</p> <p>Personal data is stored on IBM servers – a trustworthy provider of cloud services, which minimizes the possibility of physical or cyberattacks.</p> <p>The structure of the website also makes for a non-favourable environment for bots to set up fake user accounts. TG has implemented, and continues to update, the security measures outlined above to minimise any risks of data breaches, and, thus</p>	
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				<p>far, in 19 years of operation, TG is not aware that any incidents of data breach have occurred.</p> <p>Additional layers of security measures are applied at the point to registration to counter bot registrations (including validation of the email address supplied, an invisible captcha, checking the IP address against lists of know Spam/Bot IP Addresses and mail servers, and pattern matching on form field entries).</p> <p>Moreover, the complex structure of the graph based website has (to date, at least) made it less conducive to generic bot interactions.</p>	
17. Unclear purpose of processing	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>Public trust and transparency are important, especially in relation to health issues. It is crucial that data subjects be given adequate information before they contribute any content to the graph, on the purpose of the Long Covid graph,</p>	<p>Ensuring transparent information for data subjects and visitors on the graph landing site, in relation to the content and purpose of the graph, as well as the AI4Deliberation project.</p>

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				the nature and aim of the AI4Deliberation project and the processing of their personal data within the scope of this project.	
18. Processing for new purposes	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>Users create profiles on the DebateGraph platform to participate in a variety of deliberative processes on different topics, not just in relation to the Long Covid graph, which is part of the AI4Deliberation project. In this sense, the data they contribute to their user profiles and to the graphs can and is used for purposes outside the project itself, as such use is covered by the consent of the users and clearly explained in the Privacy Policy.</p> <p>The purpose of data usage within the AI4Deliberation project is defined broadly in the project documentation and agreements to encompass all foreseeable uses of data within the project scope. Information provided in the introduction to the graph will make pilot participants aware of the</p>	Obtaining consent of the data subject for the reuse of their data for new purposes, not previously covered by their consent.

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				<p>nature and scope of their participation and the potential processing of their personal data in the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>Clear consent will be sought from data subjects if any reuse of their data for purposes outside of the AI4Deliberation project is to be attempted, which has not been covered by the consent given at the creation of the user profile and is not subject to information given to users before contributing to the Long Covid graph.</p>	
19. Unlawful processing of special categories of personal data	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>Users may contribute special categories of personal data to the Long Covid graph, especially in the form of health data, ethnic origin and political opinion.</p> <p>There is also a remote possibility that insurance agencies and employers of individual users might become aware of a specific user's health situation, which could have negative consequences for the user (higher</p>	<p>Prior to contributing content to the Long Covid graph the users should give explicit consent to the processing of special categories of personal data (as per Article 9(2)(a) of the GDPR). Users should also be made aware that all contributed content is available publicly, as in this case Article 9(2)(e) might provide an additional lawful bases for the processing of data made manifestly public.</p>

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				insurance costs, employment related consequences), which would require the employers/agencies to actively seek out this information via the graph.	To mitigate risk of negative consequences resulting from employers, insurance agencies and other entities which becoming aware of the user's health situation, it would be advisable to specifically instruct users (via the entry site notification), that all their posted data will be publicly available and that they should only post data which they are comfortable sharing.
20. Redundant or excessive personal data collection (contrary to the principle of data minimisation)	Remote	Minimal	LOW	The only data necessary for the creation of the user profile is name, surname and a valid email address (for the purposes of two-factor authentication and notification of the users). All other personal data is contributed voluntarily by users and is not necessary for users to be able to contribute to the graph and use the functionalities of the platform. IP addresses, device type, and approximate user location/ time-zone are stored temporarily to ensure technical	

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				functionality of the graph and in order to adapt the graph to the specific user experience (for instance, to adapt the time zone).	
21. Inaccuracy of personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Users can update their data at any time in their user profile, as well as ask site administrators to update their data for them.	

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6.3 ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS (AAIT) and DEMBRANE B.V. (BRANE) – Italian Pilot

1. Stakeholders involved in personal data processing	
Who are the stakeholders involved in personal data processing?	<p>Participants – data subjects: The participants of the pilot trial will be members of civil society, selected by AAIT to participate in an online deliberation platform, ECHO, hosted by BRANE. ECHO records the spoken discussion from participants on a selected topic, transcribes the audio data and offers several functions which support deliberative processes (like summarization of the discussion, analysis of the conversation, identification of key topics and ideas, etc.).</p> <p>Researchers: primarily the staff of AAIT, who acts as data controller, and BRANE, who acts as data processor. The results of the pilot trial and (if necessary) personal data will be shared with consortium members of the AI4Deliberation project. AAIT has a Data Protection Officer who guarantees that the organization complies with data protection laws, monitors how personal data is handled, and acts as the point of contact with data subjects even though him/her does not directly manage the data.</p> <p>Third parties: BRANE relies on third-party services offered by Microsoft Azure and DigitalOcean for cloud computing and data storage</p>
Who are data controllers?	Actionaid International Italia ETS (AAIT) – pilot partner
Who are data processors?	Dembrane B.V. (BRANE) – pilot partner
What rules on personal data protection (internal, national, supranational) are data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR • Italian Data Protection Law: Legislative decree of 30 June 2003, n.196 with “Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali” (“Personal Data Protection Code”) with subsequent amendments AAIT Code of Ethics • Dembrane Privacy Statement available at https://www.dembrane.com/en-US/notion/1439cd84270580748046cc589861d115 • Data Policy for Dembrane’s Products available at https://www.dembrane.com/en-US/notion/13c9cd8427058069b5a8d190c459c5f2

controllers subject to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Processing Agreement between AAIT and BRANE (not yet concluded at time of DPIA)
2. Scope of data collection and processing	
Who will personal data be collected from?	Personal data will be collected from members of civil society, selected by AAIT to participate in an online deliberation platform, ECHO, hosted by BRANE.
How many individuals will data be collected from?	Between 30 and 100 participants.
Geographical area of the participants	Italy
Will personal data of children and/or other vulnerable individuals be processed?	Only adult individuals (over the age of 18 years) will be able to take part in the pilot, but people belonging to vulnerable categories might also be able to take part. AAIT will not specifically encourage vulnerable individuals to participate but will not discourage their participation either. Participation in the pilot trials will be voluntary. If vulnerable individuals should participate, given the relatively small number of participants, their special requirements might be taken into account on a case-by-case basis.
How will the data be collected (e. g. via online tools and platforms, interviews and questionnaires, polls, etc)	Personal data will be collected via questionnaires distributed to participants by AAIT before the pilot trials, in online format. Audio recordings of participants will be collected during deliberation rounds via the ECHO online platform. The ECHO platform will also be linked to Frankly – an open-source online video-based discourse platform designed to facilitate dialogue and collaborative decision-making. Frankly is operated by Harvard’s Applied Social Media Lab at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society. Within the AI4Deliberation consortium, Dembrane and Frankly would integrate their platforms so that online video deliberation (Frankly) feeds into AI-powered sense-making (Dembrane’s ECHO).

What personal data will be collected?	Via the questionnaire, the following personal data will be collected: first name, last name, email address, or phone number (for authentication purposes), as well as socio-demographic data (age range, gender, profession, level of education and citizenship). Via the ECHO/Frankly platform, the only collected data will be participant names/pseudonyms/assigned number (depending on the option chosen by the data controller in the project interface of ECHO/Frankly) and audio/video recording of participants during the discussion.
Will special categories of data be collected? If so, which categories?	Yes – audio/video recordings of participants will be collected. Participants might also opt to share special categories of personal data like political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs and health data as part of the discussion. This data is shared by participants on a voluntary basis and can be erased from the transcripts of the discussions, should the individual participant request so. This data can only be erased from the original recording of the conversation if the entire recording is erased, which might not be possible/feasible when multiple participants are speaking simultaneously and their audio patterns are intertwined in one recording.
How often will data be collected?	Personal data will be collected once before the pilot trials via a questionnaire. Audio recordings will be made in multiple deliberation sessions – possibly in all 4 sprints. Video recordings will be made in the second and following sprints.
How will the collected data be used?	The audio/video data and transcripts of discussions will be used for analysis of the deliberative process and decision-making behaviour of the participants. The collection of socio-demographic data is important to ensure inclusiveness, fairness, and transparency, and can provide insights to improve future deliberative processes.
Would data subjects expect their data to be used in this way?	Yes. Data subjects will be made aware of the purpose of the project as well as the methods of collection and data processing before the start of the pilot trials via an information sheet and consent form.
3. Purpose of processing and lawful basis	
What is the purpose of data processing?	Climate change represents one of the most urgent and complex challenges of our time. Adaptation policies require not only solid scientific and technical foundations, but also broad citizen involvement, so that the solutions identified are effective, shared, and socially equitable. A pilot deliberative process allows experiments with

	<p>participatory methods that enable citizens to discuss, learn, and formulate recommendations on adaptation measures, while also testing which approaches may be most effective and inclusive in preparation for future large-scale processes.</p> <p>The National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC) covers numerous sectors affected by climate change. Some themes suitable for public deliberation: from Environment and Natural Resources to Production Systems and Food Security, Settlements, Infrastructure and Territory, Human Health, Governance and Adaptation. The final decision on the topic to be addressed in the pilot will be made by participants themselves. However, the pilot will probably focus on themes such as participation and accountability from an intersectional perspective that considers the needs and requirements of specific communities, particularly affected by climate change or vulnerable to it. The pilot serves to experiment with innovative forms of democratic engagement on a crucial issue, such as climate change adaptation.</p>
<p>What are the benefits of data processing for the controllers, data subjects and the wider public?</p>	<p>The evidence derived from the analysis will help achieve the project goals. Participants, depending on their experience, will be able to improve their trust in deliberative and AI processes and will collaborate to improve a public policy (National Climate Adaptation Plan). AAIT will benefit from the data analysis, giving continuity to its program, in the context of policy around the topic of participation and adaptation to climate change. In the future, following the possible institutionalization of the platforms developed by AI4D, the wider public will benefit from the evidence and results achieved by the project by using these platforms for participatory processes. It will also be able, if the deliberative process outcomes are incorporated by the proper institution, to benefit from better public policies for adaptation.</p>
<p>What is the lawful basis for data processing (for all categories of personal data)?</p>	<p>The lawful basis for the processing of personal data (including special categories of personal data) is consent under Article 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR. In the Data Policy for Dembrane's Products, participants in discussions are discouraged from disclosing any personal data during the debate, and any personal data shared as contributed content is strictly voluntary.</p>
<p>4. Principles of data processing</p>	

<p>Transparency: Which information will be given to data subjects prior to the collection of their data? In what manner will data subjects be informed about the nature of data processing and their respective rights?</p>	<p>Data subjects will be made aware of the purpose of the project as well as the methods of collection and data processing before the start of the pilot trials via an information sheet and consent form distributed by AAIT, in online format. Afterwards, AAIT will create one or multiple projects (deliberation topics) via their ECHO client interface. The interface then creates a QR code for the data controller, which they can distribute among the participants. The participants join the discussion on the platform by scanning the code. At entry to the platform, they are alerted to Dembrane’s Data Policies, which contain information on which personal data is collected when using the ECHO platform and how this data is used. Participants join the discussion after consenting to Dembrane’s Data Policies via a checkbox. The Policies also contain information about the data processor (Dembrane), legal basis for data processing, data sharing and transfers, retention periods and data subjects’ rights.</p>
<p>Accuracy: Are data subjects able to update their personal data in case of changes?</p>	<p>Yes. Users will be able to update their personal data, collected via the questionnaire, by contacting AAIT. While using the ECHO platform, no personal data, apart from voice recording, is collected; therefore, by nature not subject to updates.</p>

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<p>Data minimization: Is the personal data collected the minimum necessary to achieve the purpose?</p>	<p>Contact data (name, email and/or telephone number) is collected for the purposes of communication with the participants and the verification of their identity. The collection of basic socio-demographic information (gender, age group, level of education, profession, country of birth) serves several purposes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Representativeness and inclusiveness: Knowing the socio-demographic profile of participants makes it possible to verify that the sample reflects, as far as possible, the diversity of the population. This helps to ensure that different experiences, needs, and points of view are taken into account. 2. Analysis of process quality: The data allow us to understand whether and how different social individuals or groups participate and contribute to deliberation, evaluating any imbalances in representation or participation. 3. Evaluation of process impact: Analysing how various individuals or groups perceive the process and its outcomes helps improve engagement methodologies and strengthen the democratic legitimacy of the recommendations produced. 4. Transparency and reliability: Documenting the group composition ensures greater credibility of the process, demonstrating that the conclusions are not derived from a self-referential sample but from a diverse set of citizens.
<p>5. Data access and sharing</p>	
<p>Who will have access to the personal data of data subjects?</p>	<p>Access to personal data collected via the questionnaires will be restricted to AAIT project personnel only. BRANE, as well as AAIT, will have access to the audio recordings.</p>
<p>Will access be restricted to those with a strict need to know?</p>	<p>Yes. Only the necessary personnel of both AAIT and BRANE will have access to personal data.</p>

How will access be controlled?	Access to participant data collected via the questionnaire will be controlled manually by the research staff of AAIT. Access to audio recordings is only granted to the data controller, as well as dedicated personnel on the side of the data processor.
Who will the data be shared with?	If not strictly necessary, raw personal data will not be shared with other members of the consortium. For the purposes of explainability of pilot trial results, individual examples of audio recordings might be shared with other consortium members.
Is there any scope to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?	Personal data collected via the questionnaires will be pseudonymised by assigning an alphanumeric code to each participant. A file will match the individual participant with their code. As this data is not expected to be shared with either consortium members or third parties at any point of the project, there is no need to further anonymise the data. Audio recordings of participants' voices could, in theory, lead to the identification of participants (especially if using automated tools for voice recognition and matching), but as no other data will be gathered on participants while using the ECHO platform, the audio data is effectively pseudonymised. With regard to the personal data shared as part of the discussion, BRANE does not yet have an effective method to anonymise this information, as transcript data is difficult to anonymise. Participants are therefore advised to only share what they are comfortable with being transcribed and should present themselves to the group (if required) before the recording of the discussion starts.
6. Data retention and cybersecurity	
How long will data be retained?	AAIT will retain the data collected via the questionnaire foreseeably for the duration of the AI4Deliberation project. The ECHO audio recordings will be retained until the data controller deletes them or after 30 days of the specific project (topic) being inactive, whichever comes first. It is possible to customize ECHO data retention based on the specific requirements of each client (data controller). It is possible that, in the specific case of the AI4Deliberation project, original audio recordings and/or their transcripts might be retained for a longer period of time to ensure transparency and replication of project results.
Is there a clear reason for the retention period?	The retention periods seem sensible when considering the aim of the AI4Deliberation project and the possible need for the replication and verification of project results.

<p>Are there procedures in place for monitoring data retention?</p>	<p>Currently, both AAIT and BRANE monitor data retention manually, with BRANE conducting retention check-ups every week. BRANE is also in the process of researching possible automated methods of retention monitoring.</p>
<p>Will data be stored securely, and what are the information security protection measures employed?</p>	<p>AAIT has an IT security policy and procedures in place. The technical and organisational security measures to preserve the confidentiality and availability of data, and their integrity, can be summarised as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to permanently ensure the confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services; - Ability to promptly restore availability and access to data in the event of a physical or technical incident; - Procedure for regularly testing, verifying and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures to ensure security of processing; - Technical procedures for detecting cases of “data breach” (Art. 4(11) GDPR: “a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed”). <p>The IT system is subject to maintenance and control by ITC staff nationally and internationally. Lost data can be recovered. Through the history file, old versions can be recovered and traced back to those who altered the data.</p> <p>BRANE is ISO27001 certified with all controls included. They have implemented a wide range of data security measures, from physical controls to automatic data-leakage-prevention, and from periodic asset reviews to employee screening.</p>
<p>Is the level of security appropriate to the risks of data loss or breach?</p>	<p>Yes, the level of security seems sufficient, especially considering the high standard of cybersecurity required under the ISO 27001 standard. The type of personal data processed, as well as the nature of the ECHO platform, which collects only a minimum amount of personal data, does not require more stringent security measures.</p>

<p>Will procedures be put in place for the deletion of data when retention is no longer required?</p>	<p>AAIT will monitor data retention manually, which is manageable considering the number of participants (between 30 and 100). After the completion of the AI4Deliberation project, data will be permanently deleted. BRANE deletes data collected via the ECHO platform after 30 days of the specific project (topic) being inactive, if the data controller does not delete it before this. The data controller can delete only a specific project or all of the projects, together with all audio recordings, transcripts, reports and analyses.</p>
<p>7. Data transfers</p>	
<p>Will there be any transfers of personal data to countries outside the EU? How will personal data protection be ensured in these cases?</p>	<p>No. Dembrane stores its data within the EEA (Netherlands or Switzerland) on enterprise-grade secure cloud solutions - Microsoft Azure and DigitalOcean. Both the Microsoft Corporation and DigitalOcean are certified under the Data Privacy Framework Program. All data processing and storage occurs within the European Economic Area.</p> <p>AAIT stores their data locally.</p>
<p>Is this data transfer necessary, or could it be avoided by the use of other methods and service providers?</p>	<p>N/A</p>

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8. Rights of data subjects	
How much control will the data subjects have over the use of their data?	<p>With regard to data collected by AAIT via questionnaires, the data subjects may request to withdraw from the project, access, update or delete their data by contacting AAIT directly via contact information provided on information sheets and/or consent forms. Participants will have communication channels with the data controller, who can direct them to the appropriate steps to follow up on their requests.</p> <p>With regard to audio recordings and transcripts on the ECHO platform, participants may exit the discussion at any time. Access to personal data and deletion of a specific voice track of an individual participant, however, is difficult, as the discussion involves multiple individuals simultaneously, whereby the voice track of one individual becomes intertwined with the voices of other individuals, making singling out and deletion of only one voice track impossible. Data subjects' rights to access and deletion of their recording and/or transcripts after analysis are therefore limited.</p>
What effects will data processing have on data subjects?	No negative effects of personal data processing are foreseen for data subjects.
How are the rights of data subjects relating to the processing of their personal data ensured?	Data subjects' rights can be fully exercised with regard to the personal data collected via questionnaires: participants may withdraw consent to the processing of their data at any time, request access to, update and deletion of their data. With regard to the ECHO platform, participants are informed about the particularities of the functioning of the platform via Dembrane's data policies and comprehensive information on their website (https://dembrane.notion.site/compliance-trust-at-dembrane). Data subjects are, however, limited in their ability to request deletion of their audio recording and/or transcript, as this would negatively affect the rights of other participants, with whom their recordings are intertwined due to the nature of the ECHO tool.

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RISK IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

NOTE: Initially, only present risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. Risks and possible mitigation measures will be identified and addressed gradually, following the progress of project activities.

Risk situation	Likelihood of Harm	Severity of Impact	Overall assessment	Reasoning	Possible mitigation measures
1. Inadequate/misguiding information given to data subjects	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants will be adequately informed about the purpose of data processing via information sheets, consent forms and Dembrane's Data Policies.	We recommend additionally informing participants about their limited rights with regard to access and deletion of their audio recordings and transcripts.
2. Disabled or impeded access to personal data	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	Participants will be able to access personal data collected by AAIT via questionnaires, but will have limited access to their audio recordings and transcripts due to the inability of the ECHO platform to discern individual voice tracks from multiple-participant discussions.	We recommend additionally informing participants about their limited rights with regard to access to their audio recordings and transcripts.
3. Inability of data subjects to correct/update data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants can always request that AAIT update their data. No updates are applicable for audio	

				recordings and transcripts of the discussions on the ECHO platform.	
4. Inability of data subjects to request the deletion of their personal data	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	Participants will be able to request deletion of data collected by AAIT via questionnaires, but will have limited possibilities to request deletion of their audio recordings and transcripts due to the inability of the ECHO platform to discern individual voice tracks from multiple-participant discussions. Deleting the entire discussion would disproportionately negatively impact the rights of other participants as well as the results of the deliberation process.	We recommend additionally informing participants about their limited rights with regard to the deletion of their audio recordings and transcripts.
5. Inability of data subjects to restrict processing	Remote	Minimal	LOW	There is currently no possibility for data subjects to restrict data processing as an alternative to data deletion. Given the limited technical options of the ECHO platform in this regard, this measure would be unfeasible.	
6. Inability of data subjects to access services	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	The ECHO platform is hosted on a reliable server, but maintenance issues and temporary server unavailability issues cannot be completely excluded. There are	

				currently no foreseen measures to ensure access to services for people with disabilities (for example, auditory impairments).	
7. Discrimination	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>AAIT collects socio-demographic data with the intention of including a balanced variety of participant profiles (with regard to gender, age, education, profession and citizenship). All persons above the age of 18 are eligible to participate in the project, regardless of their gender, location, ethnicity or any other personal circumstance.</p> <p>Discrimination is possible with regard to persons with disabilities, such as auditory and visual impairments. Due to the technical functionalities of the ECHO platform, these cannot be effectively offset.</p>	
8. Identity theft	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Only participants who are provided with the QR code by AAIT can join the discussion on the ECHO platform.	
9. Fraud	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Only participants who are provided with the QR code by AAIT can join	

				the discussion on the ECHO platform.	
10. Financial loss	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the research staff of AAIT and BRANE will have access to users' personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
11. Reputational damage	Remote	Minimal	LOW	<p>As only the research staff of AAIT and BRANE will have access to users' personal data, we grade this risk as low. Participants are also discouraged from sharing any personal information and sensitive details during discussions.</p> <p>With regard to special categories of personal data (like political opinions, philosophical beliefs, health data, etc.), the collection and processing of this data will be covered by the explicit consent of the participants. Additionally, negative impacts on the rights of participants resulting from the processing of such data are mitigated by the fact that data is pseudonymized at collection, as no other data will be gathered on participants while using the ECHO</p>	

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				platform (apart from the audio recording of their voice and video recording of their image).	
12. Physical harm	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the research staff of AAIT and BRANE will have access to users' personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
13. Emotional harm	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	The topics relating to climate issues might cause anxiety and discomfort to some users, but discussions are aimed at facilitating a nuanced and varied debate, which in turn might be empowering for individuals who may have previously felt isolated in their views or lacked information on the topic. The participants are not encouraged in any way to share sensitive data or personal experiences.	Participants should be provided with information on the purpose of the discussion and the selected topics.
14. Loss of confidentiality	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	AAIT and BRANE's methods of data security include the use of secured and dedicated servers and access control, assignment of codes to participants to shield their personal data, regular security audits and contingency plans for security incidents (in case of	We estimate that the cybersecurity measures currently in place are sufficient, given the scope of personal data collected and the risk posed to participants in case of a data breach.

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				BRANE). Despite these security measures, which lower the possibilities of a data breach significantly, a breach cannot be completely ruled out.	
15. Reidentification after pseudonymisation	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Since no personal data is collected on the ECHO platform, which would enable the identification of the participating speakers, we grade this risk as low. It would be theoretically possible to identify participants via voice recognition technology; however, due to the relative scarcity of such technology in the wider public and no apparent gain (financial or otherwise) from reidentification, we estimate this risk as remote.	
16. Loss, tampering or unauthorised disclosure of personal data due to poor physical security measures and cybersecurity breaches	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	AAIT and BRANE’s methods of data security include the use of secured and dedicated servers and access control, assignment of codes to participants to shield their personal data, regular security audits and contingency plans for security incidents (in case of BRANE, which is ISO 27001 certified). Despite these security	We estimate that the cybersecurity measures currently in place are sufficient, given the scope of personal data collected and the risk posed to participants in case of a data breach.

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				measures, which lower the possibilities of a data breach significantly, a breach cannot be completely ruled out.	
17. Unclear purpose of processing	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants will be adequately informed about the purpose of data processing via information sheets, consent forms and Dembrane's Data Policies.	
18. Processing for new purposes	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants' personal data will not be used for other purposes or projects outside the scope of the AI4Deliberation project and will be deleted after the project's completion.	
19. Unlawful processing of special categories of personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Pilot participants may reveal special categories of personal data during the conversations, especially their political opinion and religious beliefs. However, as only a limited amount of personal data will be collected during the ECHO deliberation session (or none at all, if names will be omitted) and because participants will be actively discouraged to disclose personal data during the debate by the host (data	

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				processor), the possibility of identification of the specific individual based on this data, and resulting negative consequences for participants, are remote.	
20. Redundant or excessive personal data collection (contrary to the principle of data minimisation)	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	Contact data (name, email and/or telephone number) is collected for the purposes of communication with the participants and the verification of their identity. The collection of basic socio-demographic information (gender, age group, level of education, profession, country of birth) serves the purposes of representativeness and inclusiveness, analysis of deliberation process quality, evaluation of process impact and transparency.	Should it become apparent during the pilot trials that some data might be redundant with regard to the pilot objectives, we recommend deleting this data.
21. Inaccuracy of personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants will enter their data into AAIT questionnaires of their own accord and may ask the dedicated research staff to update their data at any time.	

6.4 STADT BAMBERG (CBAM) – German Pilot

1. Stakeholders involved in personal data processing	
Who are the stakeholders involved in personal data processing?	<p>Participants – data subjects: Citizens of Bamberg, registered on the https://bamberg-gestalten.de/ platform, operated by the Municipality of Bamberg.</p> <p>Researchers: Primarily the staff/dedicated employees of the pilot partner. The results and (if necessary) raw personal data collected during the pilot trials will be shared with consortium members of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>Third parties: To be determined</p>
Who are data controllers?	City of Bamberg (CBAM)
Who are data processors?	City of Bamberg
What rules on personal data protection (internal, national, supranational) are data controllers subject to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR • Bavarian Data Protection Law (Bayerisches Datenschutzgesetz – BayDSG, vom 15. Mai 2018 (GVBl. S. 230, BayRS 204-1-I) with subsequent amendments and German Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz - BDSG) • Privacy Policy of CBAM available at https://www.stadt.bamberg.de/datenschutzhinformatio
2. Scope of data collection and processing	

Who will personal data be collected from?	Personal data will be collected from adult citizens of the Municipality of Bamberg, who have created an online profile on the deliberation platform available at https://bamberg-gestalten.de/ . The platform is a Consul instance by the solution provider DemokratieToday.
How many individuals will data be collected from?	To be determined, but expectedly about 1.000 participants in total per pilot, depending on engagement rates. Sprint 1: Internal (5 Participants) Sprint 2: Small Group (20-50 Participants) Sprint 3: Massification (as much participants as possible)
Geographical area of the participants	Municipality of Bamberg, Germany
Will personal data of children and/or other vulnerable individuals be processed?	Persons under the age of 18 cannot participate in the deliberations, as they are unable to create a user profile (the age of the user is verified via entering the last 4 digits of their personal identification number, which is verified via comparison with a public registry). However, as all adult citizens are allowed to participate on the platform, it can reasonably be expected that members of vulnerable groups (such as minorities, the elderly, persons with disabilities, etc.) will be included in the pilot trials.
How will the data be collected (e. g. via online tools and platforms, interviews and questionnaires, polls, etc)	Data will be collected from online user interactions – extraction of data from the publicly available platform, as well as possibly some platform analytics (e.g., number of participants in an individual deliberation round, relative increase in number of participants between rounds, etc.). Questionnaires might also be distributed to participants.
What personal data will be collected?	The scope of collected data will depend on the selected collection method and pilot metric – it is possible that only publicly available comments with personal data of the citizens will be scraped from the deliberation platform. If, however, user profile data will also be collected, this may include: Name, E-Mail, Address, the last 4 digits of the

	<p>participant's ID-No., gender and birth date. The ID number is used only at the first creation of the user account, to verify the identity of the user. This data will only be collected if necessary for research purposes and the data minimization principle will be observed.</p> <p>For evaluating the tools tested in Sprint 1 and 2 there was/is no need to collect any of the named personal data points.</p> <p>The internal staff involved in Sprint 1 was voice recorded, which they consented to. In Sprint 2 voices of participants will also be recorded, following their explicit consent.</p> <p>In the upcoming sprints the possibilities of participants uploading video recordings might also be explored and evaluated.</p>
<p>Will special categories of data be collected? If so, which categories?</p>	<p>Possibly, the following special categories of personal data might be collected during the pilot trials, as part of the specific comments/content that participants leave on the deliberation platform, depending on the topic discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Racial or ethnic origin ■ Political opinions ■ Religious or philosophical beliefs ■ Health data ■ Sexual orientation
<p>How often will data be collected?</p>	<p>Data will most probably be collected once per pilot round (4 sprints in total).</p>

How will the collected data be used?	The collected data will be used for the evaluation of applied AI online tools.
Would data subjects expect their data to be used in this way?	Currently, the participants create a user profile and contribute content to the platform (comments) with the intention of participating in deliberation on local matters. They have not been informed that their data might be used for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project. Nothing in the Privacy Policy available at https://www.stadt.bamberg.de/datenschutzhinformati informs the participants of the possibility of their data being used for research purposes. For sprint 2 all involved participants will be briefed about the objectives of the research.
3. Purpose of processing and lawful basis	
What is the purpose of data processing?	The purpose of processing personal data is to measure the effects of the applied AI online tools. The data will potentially measure the increase in user participation, quality and content of the deliberation, civility of the conversation, or other metrics which will be determined during the 4 sprints.
What are the benefits of data processing for the controllers, data subjects and the wider public?	Based on the results of the pilot trials, the AI tools applied to the deliberation platform can be adjusted in such a way that they become more effective depending on their goals. This contributes to a better participation environment, which is a win/win/win for the municipality of Bamberg, the participants, as well as the wider public.
What is the lawful basis for data processing (for all categories of personal data)?	The lawful basis for the processing of personal data (including special categories of personal data) is consent under Article 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR. Participants will expectedly be informed about the use of their data at least through a public notice with information about the AI4Deliberation project or by giving explicit informed consent before the deliberation rounds. If participants post their personal data on the public platform (bamberg-gestalten.de) the lawful basis under Article 9(2)(e) of the GDPR might also be applicable.

4. Principles of data processing	
<p>Transparency: Which information will be given to data subjects prior to the collection of their data? In what manner will data subjects be informed about the nature of data processing and their respective rights?</p>	<p>Informed consent is obtained from the participants by agreeing to the Terms of Service and Data Protection policy when creating the user account. While these documents clearly and comprehensively explain the personal data collection and processing, cookie policy, rights of data subjects and functionalities of the deliberation platform, as well as provide individuals with sufficient contact data on the data controller and oversight bodies, these documents are not yet adapted to the possibility of collecting personal data for research purposes or informing the participants, that by participating in certain deliberation rounds, they are simultaneously participating in the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>For sprint 2 all involved participants will be adequately informed about the objectives of the research and their informed consent for personal data processing, voice and video recording (if applicable) will be obtained.</p>
<p>Accuracy: Are data subjects able to update their personal data in case of changes?</p>	<p>Yes. In cases where participants provide data that may change (e.g., demographic data), they can update it in their user profile. They cannot, however, change their name or their ID No., which is entered only at the first registration and compared to the public register, to verify the identity of the citizen.</p>
<p>Data minimization: Is the personal data collected</p>	<p>Yes. For the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project, only those categories of personal data will be collected which are essential to achieve the objectives of the project. Depending on the chosen metrics, there may be only a limited amount of personal data collected (names and public comments of participants), or a broader collection of personal data from the user profiles can be chosen (for instance, data like age and gender).</p>

the minimum necessary to achieve the purpose?	For sprint 2 only public comments of users will expectedly be collected, no names or any other personal demographics. The participants will only be able to participate if they consent to the voice recording. The recordings will be deleted, expectedly at the end of the project.
5. Data access and sharing	
Who will have access to the personal data of data subjects?	<p>Access to personal data collected and stored by CBAM is limited. Only one person (the application manager) has access to a specific dataset. Application managers are employed by the Municipality of Bamberg.</p> <p>Users also have access to their data in their user profile, to which they log in using a personal password.</p> <p>In the case of AI4Deliberation, only the research team of the CBAM will have access to user data, the scope of which depends on the chosen metric and research task.</p> <p>CBAM will share the input and output of the AI tools and if necessary to calculate indices (e.g. DRI), as well as the anonymized transcript of the whole conversation, but no personal data shall be transferred to shared project infrastructure.</p>
Will access be restricted to those with a strict need to know?	Yes. Data will be collected and analyzed by the pilot partner CBAM and only shared with other consortium members if strictly necessary to achieve the research objectives. Ideally, only anonymized results of the pilot trials will be shared with the consortium.
How will access be controlled?	To be determined, as this is largely dependent on the scope of personal data that will be used for the purposes of the project.
Who will the data be shared with?	At the initial stages of the project, it is yet to be determined if and what data will be shared with other consortium members. It depends on technical infrastructure decisions; do we want to use the API to get the data or do we want to scrape the contributions directly. In any case we do not need to include personal data, only the comments. For

	<p>the conducting of the pilot trials, CBAM intends to analyse the data independently and not share raw personal data with consortium members and/or third parties.</p> <p>Voice recordings made with the ECHO tool are stored on DEMB infrastructure and can be accessed by DEMB, but only if necessary.</p>
Is there any scope to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?	<p>The possibilities of anonymization/pseudonymization depend largely on the scope of personal data collected. If only the comments of Bamberg citizens were scraped from the publicly accessible platform (together with the names of the participants contributing the comments), it would be fairly easy to pseudonymize the data to the extent that the name of the participant is removed, leaving only the content of the comment itself. However, this alone can entail personal data (disclosing the name, profession, age, gender, or other personal circumstances, which enable the contributor of the comment to be identified – especially considering the localized scope of the participants and the possibility of their intimate knowledge of each other). Personal circumstances, described in text form (as part of the comment), are more difficult to detect and remove with either human oversight or automated moderation tools, making complete anonymization largely impossible. Anonymization methods which remove personal circumstances from the context of the comments are currently under evaluation and might be applied in Sprint 2.</p>
6. Data retention and cybersecurity	
How long will data be retained?	<p>If a database of personal data is created only for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project (separate from the database of CBAM deliberation platform users), the data retention period will have to be determined based on the requirements of the project. Expectedly, the exported datasets will be deleted 5 years after the final payment of the project.</p> <p>Since the database of Bamberg citizens who participate in the Bamberg deliberation platform exists independently of the AI4Deliberation project, personal data is retained by CBAM for the purposes of providing the deliberation platform as long as the users have an open user account. Users are free to delete their user account at any time, which deletes their personal data as well as their contribution to the platform (their comments). Personal data is</p>

	still retained in backups, but is deleted monthly as the backlogs are updated. Users can also independently delete one or several of their comments, whilst retaining their user profile.
Is there a clear reason for the retention period?	To be determined, based on the data collected and the requirements of the pilot trials. The 5-year retention period could be necessary due to contractual and taxation obligations.
Are there procedures in place for monitoring data retention?	Currently, there are no specific procedures in place for monitoring data retention.
Will data be stored securely, and what are the information security protection measures employed?	<p>Personal data collected and stored by CBAM for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project will be stored on secure servers operated by Amazon Web Services (AWS) located within the European Union.</p> <p>In relation to the personal data of Bamberg citizens collected for the purposes of the deliberation platform, data is stored on the servers of the Municipality of Bamberg.</p>
Is the level of security appropriate to the risks of data loss or breach?	<p>To be determined, based on the scope of data collected.</p> <p>Currently, the Municipality of Bamberg does not have a cybersecurity protocol.</p>
Will procedures be put in place for the deletion	Yes. Procedures for the deletion of data after the conclusion of the AI4Deliberation project will be determined once pilot trials have been carried out.

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of data when retention is no longer required?	
7. Data transfers	
Will there be any transfers of personal data to countries outside the EU? How will personal data protection be ensured in these cases?	No transfers of personal data outside the EU/EEA are planned. Data collected for research purposes during the pilot trials will be hosted by Amazon Web Services, whereby the provider Amazon.com is certified under the Data Privacy Framework Program.
Is this data transfer necessary, or could it be avoided by the use of other methods and service providers?	N/A
8. Rights of data subjects	
How much control will the	In the initial stages of the pilot trials, it is most likely that the collected dataset will feature participants' comments (with their names) from previous municipal deliberation rounds, scraped from the public deliberation platform and

<p>data subjects have over the use of their data?</p>	<p>subsequently pseudonymized to delete the names of the data subjects. In this case, the subjects might not be aware of their data being scraped for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project. In the subsequent pilot trials, if special deliberation rounds (mock or actual municipal deliberations) are used for the purposes of the project, the participants will be clearly informed of their participation in the project, giving them the chance to avoid participating in the deliberation process, should they not wish their personal data to be collected and processed. Data subjects will be provided with clear information by the data controller at the point of data collection.</p>
<p>What effects will data processing have on data subjects?</p>	<p>To be determined when the required scope of data processing is established.</p>
<p>How are the rights of data subjects relating to the processing of their personal data ensured?</p>	<p>Data subjects can exercise their rights with relation to information about the processing of their data for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project, access to their data, updating and deletion of their data directly with CBAM via established contact points.</p>

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RISK IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

NOTE: Initially, only present risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. Risks and possible mitigation measures will be identified and addressed gradually, following the progress of project activities.

Risk situation	Likelihood of Harm	Severity of Impact	Overall assessment	Reasoning	Possible mitigation measures
1. Inadequate/misguiding information given to data subjects	Probable	Significant	HIGH	Primarily, the responsibility of providing necessary information to pilot participants lies with the pilot partners. Collecting participants' personal data from previous deliberation rounds could pose a risk to the rights of data subjects, as participants were not yet aware of the possibility of their data being used for research purposes. This risk is low if no personal data is collected (in case only statistical data on public engagement in the deliberation would be analysed) or if comments with names of participants are scraped from the public website, since participants in the municipal deliberations are	It is recommended that the minimal necessary amount of personal data be collected from previous municipal deliberation rounds (before/outside of the AI4Deliberation project). If strictly necessary, publicly available data (like comments with names) should be scraped and pseudonymized, removing personal data from the collected dataset at the earliest convenience. For subsequent rounds of deliberations, held either solely for the purposes of AI4Deliberation (mock

				<p>aware that their comments together with their names are published publicly.</p> <p>However, should pilot trials require a collection of participants' personal data from their user profiles (for instance, to analyse deliberation processes from the perspective of different age groups or genders), participants would not have been previously informed that their personal data might be used for such purposes, nor would they have been asked to consent to their data being processed in this way.</p>	<p>deliberations) or actual municipal deliberation rounds which will be included in the AI4Deliberation project, it would be advisable to consider the need for privacy notices, information sheets and/or consent forms with possible checkboxes, to ensure that data subjects are sufficiently informed about the aims of the AI4Deliberation project, the ways in which their data will be used and their rights as data subjects.</p> <p>Especially with regard to participants sharing special categories of personal data (like their political opinion) in their comments, participants should be made clearly aware that the contents of their comments will be used in the AI4Deliberation project and advised not to share any information that they consider sensitive in public posts.</p>
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2. Disabled or impeded access to personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants are able to update their user profile data at all times on the municipal platform (except for their name). They can do so themselves or contact the platform administrators to request updates, corrections, or deletion.	
3. Inability of data subjects to correct/update data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants are able to update their user profile data at all times on the municipal platform (except for their name). They can do so themselves or contact the platform administrators to request updates, corrections, or deletion.	From the viewpoint of data accuracy, it would not be advisable to duplicate datasets (create a new participant database only for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project, parallel to the database of users of the municipal deliberation platform), as this can lead to an increased risk of inaccurate data if both datasets are not simultaneously updated.
4. Inability of data subjects to request the deletion of their personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	Participants are able to update their user profile data at all times on the municipal platform (except for their name). They can do so themselves or contact the platform administrators to request updates, corrections, or deletion.	In relation to data deletion, KT should ensure secure and irreversible deletion from its databases in cases where data controllers are required to comply with data subjects' deletion requests.

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				Participants can also delete their comments (one or multiple) from the public debate at any time.	
5. Inability of data subjects to restrict processing as an alternative to data deletion	Remote	Minimal	LOW	This option is currently not supported by the municipal platform, but may also be unnecessary as personal data is collected solely for the purpose of creating a user profile on the deliberation platform and not analysed, compiled or otherwise processed for other purposes.	
6. Inability of data subjects to access services	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>The deliberation platform hosted by CBAM has been in use for 5 years without major incidents of widespread unavailability.</p> <p>Despite this, the possibility of temporary system failures or inaccessibility of services cannot be completely ruled out.</p>	While a prolonged inaccessibility of the CBAM platform would present a significant setback for the AI4Deliberation project, this risk cannot be adequately addressed at the level of the consortium, as the platform is managed exclusively by CBAM.
7. Discrimination	Remote	Significant	LOW	Personal data of CBAM platform users is currently collected only for the purposes of creating user profiles. Personal data is not aggregated, analysed, categorized	

				<p>or otherwise processed in any way or for any other purpose. The data on users is thus collected indiscriminately and without regard or preference for any personal circumstance. All Bamberg citizens above the age of 18 are eligible to create a user profile and contribute their comments in municipal deliberation rounds, regardless of their gender, ethnicity or any other personal circumstance.</p> <p>With regard to vulnerable participant groups, CBAM concluded consultations with representatives of various social groups (visually impaired, migrants, students, women, elderly, etc.) at the setup of the municipal platform, but no technical measures had been implemented so far (no visual aids, no translation, etc.).</p>	
8. Identity theft	Remote	Minimal	LOW	When creating user profiles, citizens are required to enter the last 4 digits of their personal ID	

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				<p>Number. Their identity is then verified by comparison with the public citizens registry. The user logs onto the platform by entering their personal password.</p> <p>While it is theoretically possible for an unauthorized person (for instance, a non-Bamberg resident) to acquire the last ID digits of a Bamberg citizen, this risk seems remote, as there seems to be no apparent benefit to such theft.</p> <p>The verification method also prevents systemic abuse or attacks by bots in order to create fake user profiles.</p>	
9. Fraud	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators, CBAM researchers and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
10. Financial loss	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators, CBAM researchers and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access	

				to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
11. Reputational damage	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators, CBAM researchers and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
12. Physical harm	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators, CBAM researchers and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
13. Emotional harm	Remote	Minimal	LOW	As only the site administrators, CBAM researchers and potentially other consortium members (if strictly necessary) will have access to user personal data, we grade this risk as low.	
14. Loss of confidentiality	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>The deliberation platform hosted by CBAM has been in use for 5 years without major incidents of cyberattacks or data breaches.</p> <p>Despite this, the possibility of data breaches cannot be completely ruled out.</p>	A significant data breach cannot be completely averted; this risk cannot be adequately addressed at the level of the consortium, as the platform is managed exclusively by CBAM.

<p>15. Reidentification after pseudonymisation</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Significant</p>	<p>MEDIUM</p>	<p>It is likely that, despite names being removed from participants' comments, identification is still theoretically possible, especially if personal circumstances are included as part of the comments (for instance, family background, profession, ethnicity, etc.). Since the participants are solely Bamberg citizens, it can be assumed that they might recognise each other, even if names are deleted from the comments.</p>	<p>While names and emails can easily be filtered and deleted, erasing other personal circumstances from comment text requires advanced technology and/or intensive human oversight, which might exceed the harm incurred to individuals due to reidentification. We would recommend informing participants prior to taking part in the deliberative process, to avoid sharing personal circumstances which could reveal their identity, should they prefer to remain anonymous.</p>
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<p>16. Loss, tampering or unauthorised disclosure of personal data due to poor physical security measures and cybersecurity breaches</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Significant</p>	<p>MEDIUM</p>	<p>The deliberation platform hosted by CBAM has been in use for 5 years without major incidents of cyberattacks or data breaches.</p> <p>Despite this, the possibility of data breaches cannot be completely ruled out.</p>	<p>A significant data breach cannot be completely averted; this risk cannot be adequately addressed at the level of the consortium, as the platform is managed exclusively by CBAM.</p>
<p>17. Unclear purpose of processing</p>	<p>Possible</p>	<p>Significant</p>	<p>MEDIUM</p>	<p>As a rule, participants need to be informed about the purposes of processing their personal data before any data is collected. Collecting participants' personal data from previous deliberation rounds, could pose a risk to the rights of data subjects, This risk is low, if no personal data is collected (in case only statistical data on public engagement in the deliberation would be analysed) or if comments with names of participants are scraped from the public website, since participants in the municipal deliberations are aware that their comments</p>	<p>It is recommended that the minimal necessary amount of personal data be collected from previous municipal deliberation rounds (before/outside of the AI4Deliberation project). If strictly necessary, publicly available data (like comments with names) should be scraped and pseudonymized, removing personal data from the collected dataset at the earliest convenience.</p> <p>For subsequent rounds of deliberations, held either solely for the purposes of</p>

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				<p>together with their names are published publicly.</p> <p>However, should pilot trials require a collection of participants' personal data from their user profiles (for instance, to analyse deliberation processes from the perspective of different age groups or genders), participants would not have been previously informed that their personal data might be used for such purposes, nor would they have been asked to consent to their data being processed in this way.</p>	<p>AI4Deliberation (mock deliberations) or actual municipal deliberation rounds which will be included in the AI4Deliberation project, it would be advisable to consider the need for privacy notices, information sheets and/or consent forms with possible checkboxes, to ensure that data subjects are sufficiently informed about the aims of the AI4Deliberation project and purposes for which their data will be processed.</p>
18. Processing for new purposes	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>This risk relates especially to processing personal data from previous deliberation rounds, where participants would not have been in a position to foresee or consent to their data being processed for research purposes. The severity of this risk depends on the scope of processed data (processing participants' comments with names vs.</p>	<p>This risk can be mitigated by informing the participants at the earliest convenience of the research purpose for processing their personal data and seeking appropriate consent.</p>

				<p>processing personal data from their user profiles).</p> <p>Apart from the above, personal data processed for the purpose of the AI4Deliberation project will not be used for any other projects or purposes and will not be made available to third parties for any further use.</p>	
19. Unlawful processing of special categories of personal data	Remote	Minimal	LOW	<p>Pilot participants may reveal special categories of personal data in their comments, especially their political opinion and religious beliefs. However, as only a limited amount of personal data will be collected for the purposes of the pilot trials and because participants will be made explicitly aware through a public notice that their personal data (including special categories) which they voluntarily disclose might be collected for the purposes of the project, unlawful use and possible negative consequences for participants are remote.</p>	

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<p>19. Redundant or excessive personal data collection (contrary to the principle of data minimisation)</p>	<p>TBD</p>	<p>TBD</p>	<p>TBD</p>	<p>This risk can be evaluated when the exact scope of data categories is determined in the pilot trials.</p> <p>In the initial rounds, it seems likely that only limited personal data (if any) will be processed, namely names of participants and any personal data revealed as the content of their comments in municipal deliberations.</p>	
<p>20. Inaccuracy of personal data</p>	<p>Remote</p>	<p>Minimal</p>	<p>LOW</p>	<p>Participants enter their data directly into their user interface at the creation of their profile, and can correct or update their data at any time.</p> <p>Users are also required to enter the last 4 digits of their personal ID Number. Their identity is then verified by comparison with the public citizens registry.</p> <p>While it is theoretically possible for a user to enter false details about their address, gender or age, this risk seems remote, as there seems to apparent benefit to such action.</p>	

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6.5 KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED (KT) – Software developer

1. Stakeholders involved in personal data processing	
Who are the stakeholders involved in personal data processing?	<p>Participants – data subjects: The participants of the pilot trials.</p> <p>Researchers: Primarily the staff/dedicated employees of the pilot partners. The results and (if necessary) raw personal data collected during the pilot trials will be shared with consortium members of the AI4Deliberation project.</p> <p>Konnekt Able Technologies Ltd (KT) is a technical partner and proprietary software developer, whose role in the AI4Deliberation project is the development of AI solutions, which will be applied to the existing infrastructure of the pilot partners, adding new features or enhancing existing features of their deliberation tools and methods.</p> <p>Third parties: To be determined</p>
Who are data controllers?	<p>Pilot partners.</p> <p>KT may exceptionally act as a joint controller depending on the circumstances of the pilot trial. In specific cases, KT may be explicitly involved in co-determining both the purposes and essential means of processing personal data in collaboration with pilot partners.</p> <p>(NOTE: The relations between KT and pilot partners with regard to personal data processing still need to be defined in data processing agreements. The current first version DPIA has been drafted on the assumption that KT will serve in the capacity of a data processor.)</p>
Who are data processors?	KT (when not acting as a joint controller with pilot partners)
What rules on personal data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR • KT Information Security Policy and Privacy Policy

protection (internal, national, supranational) are data controllers subject to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Processing Agreements between KT and pilot partners (when concluded)
2. Scope of data collection and processing	
Who will personal data be collected from?	Personal data will be collected from adult individuals voluntarily participating in the AI4Deliberation pilots. These are typically EU-based (in case of ThoughtGraph (TG) global) citizens engaging in democratic deliberation activities, either online or in-person, via platforms supported by the project.
How many individuals will data be collected from?	To be determined; the exact number will vary by site and pilot design.
Geographical area of the participants	EU (in case of pilot partner Thoughtgraph (TG) global)
Will personal data of children and/or other vulnerable individuals be processed?	Foreseeably, no participants under the age of 18 will participate in the pilot trials. With regard to other vulnerable groups, their participation is dependent upon the participant selection made by the pilots, but it can be expected that vulnerable groups (such as minorities, the elderly, persons with disabilities, etc.) will be included in the pilot trials, possibly as a measure to ensure inclusivity and representability of the participants.

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<p>How will the data be collected (e. g. via online tools and platforms, interviews and questionnaires, polls, etc)</p>	<p>As a technical partner, KT does not collect personal data directly from individuals. However, KT provides and supports digital platforms (e.g., online deliberation interfaces) that facilitate the collection of data by pilot organisations.</p> <p>The following data collection methods may be supported through KT's systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Online user interactions (e.g., posting, voting, commenting within the platform) ■ Platform analytics (e.g., timestamped log data, IP anonymised for usage metrics) ■ Embedded questionnaires or polls (if configured by the pilot controllers)
<p>What personal data will be collected?</p>	<p>KT systems are configurable by pilot partners and may process the following basic categories of personal data, depending on use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Identifiers: username/pseudonym, hashed user ID, email ■ Demographic data (e.g., age range, gender, nationality) ■ Deliberation content: text inputs (e.g., arguments, comments, posts) ■ Metadata: time of access, browser language, activity timestamps, session duration
<p>Will special categories of data be collected? If so, which categories?</p>	<p>Possibly, the following special categories of personal data might be collected during the pilot trials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Racial or ethnic origin ■ Political opinions ■ Religious or philosophical beliefs ■ Health data ■ Sexual orientation

<p>How often will data be collected?</p>	<p>KT systems collect data during active pilot operation. This may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ User interaction data during platform use ■ Periodic responses to surveys or questionnaires ■ Logging of activity (e.g., timestamped actions) <p>No background or passive tracking is used beyond what is necessary for platform functionality and research as defined by the controllers. No persistent monitoring or profiling occurs.</p>
<p>How will the collected data be used?</p>	<p>KT's role is to support the secure processing and technical implementation of deliberative processes from the pilot partners.</p> <p>Based on the requirements of the pilot trials, the data will be used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Facilitate and record citizen participation in deliberative processes ■ Evaluate the quality and inclusiveness of deliberation (e.g., participation levels, argument diversity) ■ Test and improve AI-enabled moderation, summarisation, and analysis tools ■ Generate anonymised metrics for research and policy recommendations ■ Support feedback to participants or organisers, where applicable
<p>Would data subjects expect their data to be used in this way?</p>	<p>Yes. In principle, data subjects will be made aware of the purpose and methods of personal data collection and processing via information sheets and consent forms, provided by pilot partners.</p>

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3. Purpose of processing and lawful basis	
What is the purpose of data processing?	The purpose of processing personal data is to supply pilot partners with digital infrastructure that supports participatory democratic deliberation, a core activity of the AI4Deliberation project. The systems developed and maintained by KT allow for user participation, data-driven analysis, and evaluation of deliberative processes. KT develops and configures its systems to support purpose limitation by design (e.g., modular collection, purpose-specific data fields). Any reuse of data requires a proper legal basis. KT will not use personal data for commercial profiling, marketing, or unrelated analytics.
What are the benefits of data processing for the controllers, data subjects and the wider public?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ For participants: Empowered engagement in democratic processes, increased transparency, and access to inclusive deliberation tools ■ For the wider public: Improved democratic innovations, evidence-based policymaking, and AI systems designed with ethical safeguards ■ For KT: Advancement of responsible AI technologies, knowledge transfer on secure system design, and contribution to societal impact through democratic innovation
What is the lawful basis for data processing (for all categories of personal data)?	The lawful basis for the processing of personal data (including special categories of personal data) is consent under Article 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR. In cases where pilot participants post their personal data on public platforms (like opengov.gr, DebateGraph and bamberg-gestalten.de) the lawful basis under article 9(2)(e) might also be applicable.
4. Principles of data processing	
Transparency: Which information will	Informed consent should be obtained by the data controller (pilot partner) prior to any data collection. KT ensures that the platform is technically capable of supporting the presentation and logging of all necessary transparency information and consent documents for legally compliant data processing. The data controller must provide this

<p>be given to data subjects prior to the collection of their data? In what manner will data subjects be informed about the nature of data processing and their respective rights?</p>	<p>information and documents to enable data subjects to exercise their rights under GDPR, e.g., the right to access, rectification, erasure, objection, portability, and complaint. This information should be made available by pilots through privacy notices, informed consent forms and information sheets and/or instructions for use, depending on the data controller’s implementation design. KT supports the display and logging of these notices within its systems.</p>
<p>Accuracy: Are data subjects able to update their personal data in case of changes?</p>	<p>Yes. If participants provide data that may change (e.g., demographic or profile data), systems may allow them to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ View and edit their information via a user profile interface (if available) ■ Contact the data controller to request updates, corrections, or deletion ■ Exercise their rights under Articles 15–22 GDPR
<p>Data minimization: Is the personal data collected the minimum necessary to achieve the purpose?</p>	<p>Yes. Any personal data processed through KT’s systems is strictly limited to what is necessary for enabling secure, inclusive, and functional deliberative engagement as defined in the AI4Deliberation project objectives. KT does not design or decide what data to collect, but ensures that its platforms can be configured by data controllers to collect only the minimum required data for research, participation tracking (i.e. tracking of the deliberation progress), or analytical purposes.</p> <p>For this reason, KT:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Encourages pilot partners (data controllers) to use pseudonyms, anonymisation, or aggregated data where possible ■ Supports configurable data collection fields, allowing the controller to disable unnecessary inputs ■ Avoids use of persistent identifiers or background tracking unless explicitly justified
5. Data access and sharing	
Who will have access to personal data of data subjects?	<p>Access to personal data collected and stored by KT is strictly limited to authorized KT personnel directly involved in system operation or technical support. Access to data might be shared by pilot partners, according to provisions of data processing agreements.</p> <p>With regard to data stored on project infrastructure. Consortium members will have no direct infrastructure access; they will interact with data only via exposed API endpoints. Before reaching the shared infrastructure, each pilot applies local anonymisation and data. Expectedly, other consortium members will only have access to anonymised data, not pilot raw data.</p>
Will access be restricted to those with a strict need to know?	Yes. Data is collected by pilot partners (data controllers) via KT-supported platforms, and pilot partners should assign access rights to specific authorized personnel according to their internal policies. KT will act as data processor on behalf of these controllers. KT does not independently share personal data with any third parties.
How will access be controlled?	<p>The details of access to data will be determined on a case-by-case basis with the individual pilot partners.</p> <p>With regard to the shared infrastructure, only infrastructure administrators will have access to the shared infrastructure.</p>
Who will the data be shared with?	<p>At the initial stages of the project, it is yet to be determined if and what data will be shared with other consortium members.</p> <p>KT ensures secure data transmission through indicatively:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ End-to-end encryption when transmitting data between the client and the server

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Use of VPNs or secure tunnelling for administrative access ■ Digital certificates and secure API keys for internal system communication
Is there any scope to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?	<p>Based on the needs of the pilot partners, KT enables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Pseudonymisation techniques such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hashing user IDs (e.g., salted SHA-256) ○ Replacing direct identifiers with random unique tokens ■ Anonymisation techniques including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data masking ○ Generalisation (e.g., age brackets instead of exact age) ○ Salting
6. Data retention and cybersecurity	
How long will data be retained?	KT does not determine retention periods, as this responsibility lies with the data controller.
Is there a clear reason for the retention period?	N/A
Are there procedures in place for	These procedures will be established by the data controller (pilot partner).

monitoring data retention?	
Will data be stored securely, and what are the information security protection measures employed?	<p>Personal data processed by KT is stored on secure servers operated by Hetzner and located within the European Union. KT applies a comprehensive set of technical and organisational security measures aligned with ISO/IEC 27001 and GDPR Article 32. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Encryption of all personal data at rest (e.g., AES-256) and in transit (e.g., TLS 1.2+) ■ Firewalls and secure network segmentation ■ Multi-factor authentication (MFA) for admin and developer access ■ Role-based access controls (RBAC) with least-privilege principles <p>KT also maintains an incident response plan to address breaches promptly.</p>
Is the level of security appropriate to the risks of data loss or breach?	<p>Yes, the level of security is sufficient, especially as KT is aligned with the ISO 27001 standard. This criterion will be subject to re-evaluation once data processing agreements are reached with the pilot partners and the pilot trials are about to kick off.</p>
Will procedures be put in place for the deletion of data when retention is no longer required?	<p>When data is no longer needed, KT ensures secure and irreversible deletion, mainly using Logical deletion from databases with overwriting of indexes.</p>
7. Data transfers	
Will there be any transfers of personal data to	<p>KT's default policy is to store and process all data strictly within the EU/EEA, but possible transfer to third countries could be required by individual pilot partners (for example, TG, which stores its data on cloud servers in the USA).</p>

countries outside the EU? How will personal data protection be ensured in these cases?	
Is this data transfer necessary, or could it be avoided by the use of other methods and service providers?	From the perspective of personal data processing by KT, all project goals, platform functionality, and research objectives can be achieved using EU/EEA-based infrastructure and personnel, but due to the nature of the service provided by pilot partners like TG, offering their platforms outside the scope of the AI4Deliberation project, a limitation to store data exclusively in the EU/EEA might not be feasible. In such cases, however, the insurance of complying with GDPR lies with the specific pilot partner.
8. Rights of data subjects	
How much control will the data subjects have over the use of their data?	Data subjects should be provided with clear information by the data controller in the privacy notice and via informed consent forms or information sheets at the point of data collection. KT is able to create the necessary functionalities that facilitate user information and access to data.
What effects will data processing have on data subjects?	To be determined by data controllers – pilot partners.

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<p>How are the rights of data subjects relating to the processing of their personal data ensured?</p>	<p>KT is able to create the necessary functionalities of the software that enable deletion of data and thus the right to erasure (right to be forgotten) to be respected, following parameters set by data controllers. The controller decides whether to approve erasure requests based on legal grounds and project needs.</p> <p>With relation to requests for access to data by data subjects or possible objections to data processing, it is the responsibility of the data controller to assess and respond to such queries, and KT supports their implementation upon request.</p>
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RISK IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

NOTE: Initially, only existing risks that pilots experience with their services will be identified and addressed, as well as risks that can reasonably be foreseen before the start of the pilot trials. Risks and possible mitigation measures will be identified and addressed gradually, following the progress of project activities.

Risk situation	Likelihood of Harm	Severity of Impact	Overall assessment	Reasoning	Possible mitigation measures
1. Inadequate / misleading information given to data subjects	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	Primarily, the responsibility of providing necessary information to pilot participants will lie with the pilot partners – data controllers. KT ensures that their AI tools will be technically capable of supporting the presentation and logging of all necessary transparency information in accordance with Article 13 GDPR, relating to data subject rights (e.g. access, rectification, erasure, objection, portability, complaint), clarifications that participation is voluntary and that no automated decision-making is used. This information will be made available through privacy notices, informed	It is recommended to consider the need for privacy notices, information sheets and informed consent forms with possible checkboxes early in the development stages, to ensure that compatible software solutions which include these functionalities are chosen when enhancing existing pilot deliberation platforms.

				<p>consent forms and/or information sheets, terms and conditions or instructions for use, depending on the controller's implementation. KT supports the display and logging of these notices within its systems.</p> <p>Before the enhancement of pilot platforms with AI add-ons, it cannot be foreseen with certainty how the functionalities of notices and consent forms will be implemented.</p>	
2. Disabled or impeded access to personal data	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>To be determined once the possibilities of access to data are defined and the responsibilities are divided between pilot partners and KT.</p> <p>In principle, KT systems should allow participants to view and edit their information via a user profile interface (if available) and contact the data controller to request updates, corrections, or deletion.</p>	

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3. Inability of data subjects to correct/update data	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>To be determined once the possibilities of access to data are defined and the responsibilities are divided between pilot partners and KT.</p> <p>In principle, KT systems should allow participants to view and edit their information via a user profile interface (if available) and contact the data controller to request updates, corrections, or deletion.</p>	
4. Inability of data subjects to request the deletion of their personal data	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>To be determined once the possibilities of access to data are defined and the responsibilities are divided between pilot partners and KT.</p> <p>In principle, KT systems should allow participants to view and edit their information via a user profile interface (if available) and contact the data controller to request updates, corrections, or deletion.</p>	<p>In relation to data deletion, KT should ensure secure and irreversible deletion from its databases in cases where data controllers are required to comply with data subjects' deletion requests.</p>
5. Inability of data subjects to restrict	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>To be determined once the possibilities of access to data are</p>	

processing as an alternative to data deletion				defined and the responsibilities are divided between pilot partners and KT.	
6. Inability of data subjects to access services	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>KT applies a comprehensive set of technical and organisational security measures aligned with ISO/IEC 27001 and maintains an incident response plan to address breaches and system errors promptly.</p> <p>Despite these measures, the possibility of temporary system failures or inaccessibility of services cannot be completely ruled out, especially considering the interdependence between existing deliberation platforms/services offered by the pilot partners and subsequent KT AI add-ons.</p>	We recommend that KT considers possible systemic errors and inaccessibility of services due to incompatible AI solutions with existing pilot deliberation platforms in the early stages of development, to ensure sustained and stable access of users to services.
7. Discrimination	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks of discrimination among users will be assessed once the functionalities	

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				of the AI tools and their application are determined.	
8. Identity theft	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.</p> <p>Access to user profiles and possible security measures with regard to user authentication will be assessed when developed and applied.</p>	
9. Fraud	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.	
10. Financial loss	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.	

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11. Reputational damage	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.	
12. Physical harm	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.	
13. Emotional harm	TBD	TBD	TBD	With regard to the planned addition of AI features to pilot deliberation platforms, the possible risks will be assessed once the functionalities of the AI tools and their application are determined.	
14. Loss of confidentiality	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>KT applies a comprehensive set of technical and organisational security measures aligned with ISO/IEC 27001. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Encryption of all personal data at rest (e.g., AES-256) and in transit (e.g., TLS 1.2+) ▪ Firewalls and secure network segmentation 	We estimate that the cybersecurity measures currently in place are sufficient, given the scope of personal data collected and the risk posed to participants in case of a data breach, but a more detailed evaluation will be carried out during pilot trials.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multi-factor authentication (MFA) for admin and developer access ▪ Role-based access controls (RBAC) with least-privilege principles <p>Access to personal data is strictly limited to authorised KT personnel directly involved in system operation or technical support. KT also maintains an incident response plan to address breaches promptly.</p> <p>KT does not independently share personal data with any third parties, unless specifically instructed to do so by the data controllers.</p> <p>Despite these strict security measures, which lower the possibilities of a data breach significantly, a breach cannot be completely ruled out.</p>	
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				<p>Nonetheless, we assess this risk as low due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strong preventive measures ▪ Monitoring and alerts for abnormal behaviour or access patterns ▪ Frequent software and security controls ▪ Backups and redundancy plans to prevent accidental loss 	
15. Reidentification after pseudonymisation	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>KT's software solutions enable both pseudonymisation (hashing user IDs and replacing direct identifiers with random unique tokens) and anonymisation techniques (like data masking, generalization and salting). The application of a pseudonymization or anonymization technique will be determined on a case-by-case basis, considering each pilot's needs.</p>	
16. Loss, tampering or unauthorised disclosure of personal data due to poor	Possible	Significant	MEDIUM	<p>KT applies a comprehensive set of technical and organisational security measures aligned with ISO/IEC 27001. These include:</p>	<p>We estimate that the cybersecurity measures currently in place are sufficient, given the scope of</p>

<p>physical security measures and cybersecurity breaches</p>				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Encryption of all personal data at rest (e.g., AES-256) and in transit (e.g., TLS 1.2+) ▪ Firewalls and secure network segmentation ▪ Multi-factor authentication (MFA) for admin and developer access ▪ Role-based access controls (RBAC) with least-privilege principles <p>Access to personal data is strictly limited to authorised KT personnel directly involved in system operation or technical support. KT also maintains an incident response plan to address breaches promptly.</p> <p>KT does not independently share personal data with any third parties, unless specifically instructed to do so by the data controllers.</p> <p>Despite these strict security measures, which lower the</p>	<p>personal data collected and the risk posed to participants in case of a data breach, but a more detailed evaluation will be carried out during pilot trials.</p> <p>We would recommend not duplicating the data set, but having data stored by either the data controller or the processor, depending on technical availability. This minimizes the risk of cybersecurity breaches.</p>
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				<p>possibilities of a data breach significantly, a breach cannot be completely ruled out.</p> <p>Nonetheless, we assess this risk as low, due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strong preventive measures ▪ Monitoring and alerts for abnormal behaviour or access patterns ▪ Frequent software and security controls <p>Backups and redundancy plans to prevent accidental loss</p>	
17. Unclear purpose of processing	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>The purpose of data processing should be determined by the pilot partner, but TK's software solutions should enable transparent informing of data subjects with regard to the purpose of data processing, before any collection or processing of data occurs. It should also enable subsequent informing of data subjects on possible changes with relation to new or different purposes.</p>	
18. Processing for new purposes	TBD	TBD	TBD	<p>The purpose of data processing should be determined by the pilot</p>	

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				partner, but TK’s software solutions should enable transparent informing of data subjects with regard to the purpose of data processing, before any collection or processing of data occurs. It should also enable subsequent informing of data subjects on possible changes with relation to new or different purposes. Obtaining consent of the data subject for the reuse of their data for new purposes, not previously covered by their consent, must be enabled.	
19. Unlawful processing of special categories of personal data	TBD	TBD	TBD	The purpose and lawful basis for data processing should be determined by the pilot partner, but TK’s software solutions should enable transparent informing of data subjects and obtaining their explicit consent for data processing.	
19. Redundant or excessive personal data collection (contrary to the	TBD	TBD	TBD	The scope of personal data collected from participants in the pilot trials will be determined by the data controllers. The developed software solutions	

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principle of data minimisation)				should enable the collection and processing of all necessary personal data categories, whilst keeping the minimization principle at the forefront already during the development stage. This could result in developing solutions which limit the amount of personal data participants can share (for instance by online forms which require the entry of a minimal amount of personal data necessary for the creation of user profiles, choosing age in ranges, not specific numerals, avoiding options where users can share their biography or photographs, if this is not necessary for the pilot trial, etc.)	
20. Inaccuracy of personal data	TBD	TBD	TBD	Users should have the option to update their data at any time, either in their user profile or by sending a request for change directly to the data controller and/or data processor.	
21. Unclear division of responsibilities between data	TBD	TBD	TBD	The pilot cases are not yet sufficiently clear to enable the adoption of specific rules,	

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controller (pilot partner) and data processor (KT); either acting as joint controllers or not				including the stipulation of obligations of both parties.	
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Annex 14
AI tools shortlist

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AI Tools Shortlist

Tier 1 – Priority (Pilot/Test First)

These tools are highly relevant, compliant, technically strong, and cover all main needs:

LLMs (core engines)

- ChatGPT (GPT-4o mini) – versatile, strong reasoning, multimodal, widely supported.
 - **Use:** General reasoning, summarisation, drafting, multilingual assistance.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Covers all key functional areas in the evaluation, widely adopted, reliable, and directly applicable to pilot tasks such as summarisation and drafting.
- Claude AI (Claude 4 Sonnet) – strong ethics focus, long context handling.
 - **Use:** Long-context analysis, careful drafting; strong safety posture.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Chosen over smaller or less mature LLMs because of its extended context length and focus on responsible AI, critical for sensitive deliberation content.
- Gemini 2.5 Pro – advanced multimodal reasoning, good integration.
 - **Use:** Multimodal reasoning (text + tables + media).
 - **Why Tier 1:** Selected ahead of niche or less proven models because it directly powers Sensemaker and supports multimodal input, aligning with project pilots.
- Mistral Large – strong open-source option, multilingual, privacy-friendly.
 - **Use:** Strong general LLM with EU-friendly self-host options.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Preferred over proprietary-only models due to open-source licensing, multilingual support, and suitability for GDPR-compliant deployment.
- LLaMA 3.3 (70B) – open-source, EU-compliant deployment possible.
 - **Use:** High-quality open-source baseline for on-prem deployment.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Chosen over smaller open models for its stronger performance and EU-compliance potential, ensuring flexibility in pilot environments.

Deliberation / Argument Mining

- ArgMiner – strong argument mining.
 - **Use:** End-to-end argument extraction with transformer backbones.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Preferred over experimental or less maintained argument mining tools due to maturity, open-source support, and alignment with WP4 sandbox goals.
- Jigsaw Sensemaker – designed for civic dialogue/consensus.
 - **Use:** Topic clustering + “common ground vs differences” summaries for civic dialogue.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Selected over generic summarisation tools because it is purpose-built for deliberation and consensus-finding, a core project need.
- ConvoKit – conversation analysis, fits deliberation goals.
 - **Use:** Conversation analytics (turn-taking, stance, politeness, features for a deliberation knowledge graph).
 - **Why Tier 1:** Chosen over less flexible frameworks because it directly supports building the deliberation knowledge graph identified in project deliverables.

Moderation & Safety

- Detoxify – active toxic speech classifier.
 - **Use:** Open-source toxic speech classification (multi-label).
 - **Why Tier 1:** Prioritised over Perspective API and Mod-Guard due to open-source availability, active maintenance, and GDPR-friendly deployment.
- Content-Checker – moderation across formats.
 - **Use:** Text + image moderation (profanity, offensive patterns, NSFW).
 - **Why Tier 1:** Selected over narrower moderation tools as it covers both text and images, offering broader coverage in pilots.

Translation & Accessibility

- LibreTranslate – open-source, GDPR-friendly.
 - **Use:** Self-hosted MT via REST API.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Chosen over OpenNMT-py and LaMaTE because it is simple, reliable, and GDPR-compliant with minimal infrastructure overhead.

- Whisper – robust speech-to-text (99+ languages).
 - **Use:** Robust multilingual speech-to-text (99+ languages).
 - **Why Tier 1:** Prioritised over less mature accessibility tools (e.g., SignLanguageRecognition) because it is robust, multilingual, and widely adopted.

Gamification & Engagement

- Chamilo LMS – GDPR-compliant LMS with gamification.
 - **Use:** GDPR-aware LMS with certificates, scoring, and gamification hooks.
 - **Why Tier 1:** Selected over engine because it is a full-featured LMS with active support, making it more practical for immediate pilot deployment.

Tier 2 – Secondary (Backup / Niche Use Cases)

Useful, but either overlapping with stronger alternatives, less active, or more niche:

Deliberation / Argument Mining

- AMTM – less mainstream than ArgMiner.
 - **Use:** Argument mining pipeline for extracting claims and premises.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because ArgMiner is more mature, better documented, and already integrates with HF Transformers.
 - Better than Tier 3 tools (e.g., ARGAEI, oAMF) because it is functional, research-backed, and still viable for backup testing.
- MAMKit – similar overlap with ArgMiner.
 - **Use:** Multimodal argument mining kit (text + other inputs).
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because ArgMiner already covers the core needs more cleanly and with better support.
 - Stronger than Tier 3 research-only pipelines because it includes multimodal components and a maintained framework.
- DelibAnalysis – useful for quality assessment, but niche.

- **Use:** Analyses deliberative quality (argument balance, discourse patterns).
- **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it is narrow (only quality assessment, not extraction/structuring).
 - Not Tier 3 because it directly supports deliberation-specific metrics, which could be useful for WP4 evaluation phases.
- StanceAware-SBERT – interesting, but experimental.
 - **Use:** Sentence-BERT extension for stance detection in debates.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it's still experimental and not broadly validated.
 - Not Tier 3 because stance detection is a relevant deliberation task, and it offers unique functionality compared to simpler sentiment tools (e.g., VADER, TextBlob).

Summarisation / NLP

- BART – still useful, but can be replaced by modern LLMs.
 - **Use:** Abstractive summarisation and text generation.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because GPT-4o, Claude, and Gemini outperform BART in summarisation with fewer constraints.
 - Not Tier 3 because it is still a strong model in Hugging Face, stable, and lightweight for controlled summarisation tasks.
- Sumy – lightweight, limited vs newer models.
 - **Use:** Extractive summarisation with simple algorithms (e.g., LSA).
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it's too simplistic and limited compared to LLMs or Sensemaker.
 - Not Tier 3 because it is reliable, very lightweight, and can serve as a fallback summariser where resources are constrained.
- Stanza – solid NLP, but overlaps with LLM abilities.
 - **Use:** POS tagging, dependency parsing, named entity recognition.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because LLMs now handle these tasks better, reducing its necessity.
 - Not Tier 3 because Stanza is still maintained by Stanford NLP, robust, and could serve as a fallback for structured NLP.

Moderation

- Mod-Guard – older, less maintained, only keep as backup.
 - **Use:** Text moderation, detecting offensive language.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because Detoxify and Content-Checker are more accurate, modern, and maintained.
 - Not Tier 3 because it still functions, could be used as redundancy, and provides comparative baselines in evaluation.

Accessibility

- LaMaTE – strong translator, but LibreTranslate more GDPR-safe.
 - **Use:** Machine translation tool with multilingual support.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because LibreTranslate is open-source, lighter, and easier to self-host with GDPR compliance.
 - Not Tier 3 because LaMaTE still has strong multilingual accuracy and could serve as an additional translation engine for benchmarking.
- SignLanguageRecognition – valuable, but research-stage.
 - **Use:** Recognition of sign language gestures for accessibility.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it's research-stage, limited documentation, and not production-ready.
 - Not Tier 3 because accessibility is central to AI4Deliberation, and this could later be tested in inclusivity pilots.

Gamification

- Gamification-Engine (gengine) – useful if Chamilo insufficient.
 - **Use:** Gamification framework (points, leaderboards, achievements).
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because Chamilo is a full LMS with integrated gamification, making it more practical for pilots.
 - Not Tier 3 because gengine still offers modular gamification, useful if Chamilo needs reinforcement or extra gamification hooks.

Computer Vision / Multimodal

- Amazon Rekognition – powerful but proprietary/privacy issues.
 - **Use:** Image and video analysis (object detection, moderation, face recognition).
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it's proprietary, hosted in the US, and has GDPR/privacy concerns.
 - Not Tier 3 because it is powerful, well-documented, and could be tested for benchmarking multimedia moderation.

- OpenCV – useful library, but less central to deliberation.
 - **Use:** Computer vision library for image/video analysis.
 - **Why Tier 2:**
 - Didn't reach Tier 1 because it's not central to deliberation-specific needs.
 - Not Tier 3 because OpenCV is a core open-source library with wide adoption and could support accessibility or multimodal prototypes.

Tool	Relevance	Technical Capability	Usability	GDPR/Ethical Compliance	Integration Potential	Maturity & Support	Tier
ChatGPT (GPT-4o mini)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
Claude AI	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
Gemini 2.5 Pro	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
Mistral Large	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
LLaMA 3.3 (70B)	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	1
ArgMiner	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
AMTM	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	2

MAMKit	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	2
DelibAnalysis	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	2
Jigsaw Sensemaker	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	1
ConvoKit	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	1
StanceAware-SBERT	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	2
BART	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	2
Sumy	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	2
Stanza	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	2
Detoxify	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
Content-Checker	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	1
Mod-Guard	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	2
LibreTranslate	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
LaMaTE	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	2
Whisper	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
SignLanguageRecognition	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	2
Chamilo LMS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	1
Gamification-Engine (gengine)	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	2

Amazon Rekognition	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	2
OpenCV	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	2

Tier 3 – Evaluated but Not Prioritised

These tools were noted in the evaluation forms but not shortlisted, either due to overlap, low maturity, limited relevance, or because they are more general-purpose frameworks rather than project-specific solutions.

Commercial AI Tools (Webpages)

- **AWS Bedrock** – commercial AI platform, but limited flexibility for deliberation-specific needs.
 - **Use:** Access to commercial foundation models via API.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Too general-purpose and vendor-locked, with limited flexibility for deliberation pilots compared to Tier 1 LLMs.

- **Google AI Studio** – developer platform, not directly tailored to deliberation tasks.
 - **Use:** Platform for developers to build with Google AI models.
 - **Why Tier 3:** More of a developer toolset than an end-user deliberation resource, offering little direct benefit for pilots.

- **Perplexity AI** – strong Q&A engine, but not designed for structured deliberation.
 - **Use:** Conversational search and reasoning tool.
 - **Why Tier 3:** While strong for Q&A, it doesn't support structured multi-user deliberation, making it less relevant than chosen Tier 1 tools.

Other Commercial / Open-Source LLMs

- Llama 4 Scout – early-stage, less mature.
 - **Use:** Lightweight LLM prototype.

- **Why Tier 3:** Lacks maturity and adoption, with weaker evaluation results than Tier 1 and Tier 2 open-source LLMs.

- Llama-Krikri – limited adoption, niche.
 - **Use:** Specialised LLM variant.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Niche and minimally documented, without strong community or institutional support.

- DeepSeek R1 – research-focused, less EU-relevant.
 - **Use:** Research-oriented large language model.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Strong in experimental domains but less relevant for EU-focused deployment and compliance.

- Gemma 3 – newer, less proven in deliberation contexts.
 - **Use:** Smaller LLM from Google.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Not yet validated in deliberation use cases; overshadowed by Gemini and other stronger Tier 1 models.

- all-MiniLM-L6-v2 – efficient embedding model, but superseded.
 - **Use:** Sentence embeddings and similarity search.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Still useful for embeddings but largely superseded by newer, larger embedding-capable LLMs.

Non-LLM NLP / Argument Mining Tools

- ARGAE~~L~~ – niche argument mining toolkit.
 - **Use:** Argument mining.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Limited adoption and outdated compared to ArgMiner or MAMKit, which are better maintained and more functional.

- PredPatt – focuses on predicate-argument structures, not widely maintained.
 - **Use:** Predicate-argument parsing.

- **Why Tier 3:** Very narrow scope and no recent updates, offering little to deliberation pilots.

- Hugging Face Transformers – broad library, but not a standalone tool.
 - **Use:** Framework for training and running NLP models.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Powerful as infrastructure but not a self-contained tool for deliberation; requires significant setup.

- ParaSum – extractive summarisation, outdated vs modern LLMs.
 - **Use:** Extractive text summarisation.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Outdated compared to abstractive summarisation from modern LLMs and Sensemaker.

- VADER – sentiment analysis, limited for deliberation.
 - **Use:** Lexicon-based sentiment classification.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Too simplistic for nuanced deliberation analysis; overshadowed by stance detection tools in Tier 2.

- TextBlob – older sentiment/text library.
 - **Use:** Basic sentiment and NLP.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Superseded by modern NLP frameworks; lacks depth and relevance.

- Flair – NLP framework.
 - **Use:** Named entity recognition, sequence tagging.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Once strong, but now largely replaced by newer libraries and LLMs.

- OpenNMT-py – machine translation.
 - **Use:** Neural MT framework.
 - **Why Tier 3:** More complex to deploy and less GDPR-friendly than LibreTranslate, which fits pilots better.

- OpenDeyim – experimental, not widely adopted.
 - **Use:** Debate-related NLP in Turkish.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Very experimental, with narrow language/domain coverage and little broader relevance.

Additional Tools from Partner Evaluations

- bart-large-mnli – natural language inference model.
 - **Use:** NLI and classification.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Limited direct application to deliberation compared to more advanced LLMs.
- Perspective API – toxicity detection.
 - **Use:** Classifying toxic language.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Strong API but hosted in the US, raising GDPR/compliance risks; weaker option than open-source Detoxify.
- Echo – argumentation tool.
 - **Use:** Argument structure analysis.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Very niche, with limited documentation and low adoption.
- oAMF (open Argument Mining Framework) – research-stage framework.
 - **Use:** Argument mining.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Promising, but still research-stage, not production-ready.
- MAMKit (extended, multimodal version) – multimodal argument mining.
 - **Use:** Argument mining with multimodal inputs.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Redundant given ArgMiner and MAMKit already shortlisted in higher tiers.
- AM training pipeline (Morio et al., 2022) – experimental research pipeline.
 - **Use:** Cross-corpora multi-task training for argument mining.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Academic-focused and not production-ready for pilots.

- SUMMETIX PRO – commercial analytics tool.
 - **Use:** Argument and feedback analysis.
 - **Why Tier 3:** Proprietary and limited transparency; doesn't align with project's open science focus.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Annex 15
Evaluated but not utilized AI tools

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Evaluated but not utilized AI tools

Jigsaw Sensemaker

Jigsaw Sensemaker is a tool for detecting and understanding toxic or harmful online content, assisting in the moderation and analysis of discourse dynamics.

Note: The Jigsaw Sensemaker specifically runs on Google's Vertex AI Platform. Technical partners considered it inappropriate to rely on a deliberation tool which requires commitment to a specific commercial provider. For this reason, it was not utilized during pilot trials.

1) Human agency and oversight

Sensemaker is purposely developed to complement facilitators and decision-makers' agency instead of replacing it. Human surveillance is important, and authorised observers can look back and amend the reports before they are shared.¹ Available documentation also emphasises grounded citations for the summaries, allowing users to verify and challenge synthesised claims.² This is one of the immense possibilities for rejecting blackbox tools and instead reclaiming the analyst.³

Such effort is in the spirit of HLEG language. To increase compliance, Jigsaw should formalise workflows for oversight (approvals steps, engagement and capture of reviewer changes) and publish a user-facing explanation of oversight roles and responsibilities when deploying a tool.

2) Technical robustness and safety

The instructions report judgments for hallucinations (human and automated raters) and stability ($\approx 90\%$ topic/categorisation consistency across runs). They also utilise vote-count thresholds (e.g., exclude statements with < 20 votes) to avoid erroneous "common ground" signals, and they ground claims in source statements and votes in the library, which is open-source and described as a proof-of-concept.⁴

¹ Jigsaw (a): Making Sense of Large-Scale Online Conversations, Medium, published December 18, 2024, available on: <https://medium.com/jigsaw/making-sense-of-large-scale-online-conversations-b153340bda55> (accessed October 14, 2025).

² Jigsaw (b): Sensemaking Tools Documentation, available on: <https://jigsaw-code.github.io/sensemaking-tools/docs/> (accessed October 14, 2025).

³ Stasko, J. et al.: Jigsaw: supporting investigative analysis through interactive visualization. In Information Visualization (2008), volume 7, issue 2, p. 119.

⁴ Jigsaw (c): Sensemaker by Jigsaw - A Google AI Proof of Concept, GitHub, published August 20, 2024, available on: <https://github.com/Jigsaw-Code/sensemaking-tools> (accessed October 14, 2025).

Jigsaw has indicated in their documentation that this tool is still “beta” and that some evaluation code is “to be published”.

A work-in-progress maturity level, rather than a fully production-hardened system, is therefore mostly compliant for a beta library. To achieve greater compliance, it would be recommended to publish end-to-end evaluation protocols and datasets, documenting failure modes and fallback behaviours, enhancing security and performing regular post-deployment audits when embedded in civic platforms.

3) Privacy and data governance

Jigsaw aggregates votes and handles statements without gathering individual user accounts. There is a platform, Vertex, that processes final data in its own hosted and owned account and environment, and thus it is never seen by Jigsaw.⁵ In addition, the library can be run on one’s own infrastructure with one’s own models to ensure that data and content sovereignty is respected.⁶ This meets the HLEG requirement. Jigsaw authors should still conduct case-specific DPIAs, publish data flow diagrams, and research that platform's (Vertex) T&C and cross-border processing are legal in their jurisdiction.

4) Transparency

With the intended purpose to allow external scrutiny, Jigsaw is open-source. Jigsaw provides grounded citations in its reports as a method for traceability.⁷ The documentation indicates that the library is beta, describes limitations (what is and is not analysed, how "common ground" is selected) and cost/token considerations with model options.⁸ This is in line with the literature favouring exploratory methods in visual analytics with transparent methodologies rather than black-box automation.⁹ Therefore, Jigsaw is aligned with this HLEG requirement.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

To assess representation and proportionality, the Jigsaw team shares targeted evaluations on sensitive topics and considers viewpoint bias and over-reliance on AI.¹⁰ Moreover, the pipeline

⁵ See Jigsaw (a).

⁶ See Jigsaw (b).

⁷ See Jigsaw (a).

⁸ See Jigsaw (b).

⁹ See Stasko, J. et al., p. 119.

¹⁰ See Jigsaw (a).

surfaces areas of agreement and disagreement between groups, and when appropriately used, leads to inclusion.¹¹ Open-sourcing allows for further probing of external bias.

Nonetheless, the HLEG requirement calls for systematic bias auditing and mitigation (including demographic fairness when applicable). Because Jigsaw relies on LLMs (often trained on broad, opaque corpora) and because vote distributions may reflect imbalances in participation, more fairness checks would be warranted, such as reporting confidence bands, testing for systematic under- or over-representation of marginalized statements, and reporting how biases are mitigated if weighing the votes could disadvantage specific groups.

Jigsaw is thus only partially compliant with the requirement of HLEG. Jigsaw would require additional development to improve compliance with standards related to fair-developing processes by documenting fairness metrics, conducting bias tests across subpopulations, and implementing plans to mitigate imbalances in participatory deliberations.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

Jigsaw is designed for public-interested use cases (civil deliberation, accelerating feedback loops, producing actionable summaries while keeping nuance). It seeks to let “more communities engage in meaningful, large-scale conversations and get to informed decisions in minutes”, which potentially enhances democratic responsiveness.¹² Environmental sustainability is not discussed in any explicit way. The documents do report costs and token usage (an indirect proxy for model load), but there is no energy accounting at all.¹³

The societal impact of Jigsaw is therefore positive and important, whilst the environmental dimension remains quite incomplete. Developers should be encouraged to provide resource-use footprints for each run (or per N statements), have model-size controls, and guide adopters on their green-compute options, in line with the requirements of the HLEG.

7) Accountability

The open code, citations, and community feedback options all provide for auditability and community accountability. The library’s proof of concept framing suitably locates governance of deployment responsibility onto the host platform where the data is stored, and the outputs can impact people.¹⁴

¹¹ See Jigsaw (b).

¹² See Jigsaw (a).

¹³ See Jigsaw (b).

¹⁴ See Jigsaw (c).

The literature emphasizes the significance of provenance in analytic workflows (for instance, timelines and links to the evidence base);¹⁵ this can motivate specific and tangible accountability constructs in a production environment.

Thus, Jigsaw is somewhat compliant with the HLEG requirement at the library level. To be fully compliant, it should also include (i) matrices of roles and responsibilities (who signs off on summaries; who manages challenges); (ii) records of prompts, models, and outputs, along with versioning; and (iii) accident protocols.

8) Overall assessment

In general, the Jigsaw design choices (human-in-the-loop control, grounding with citations, open-source transparency, privacy-preserving data posture, and explicit evaluation for hallucination/stability) align well with the HLEG framework for a beta-stage toolkit.

ConvoKit

ConvoKit is an open-source toolkit for analysing and modelling conversations. It provides tools for studying dialogue patterns, politeness, power dynamics, and conversational outcomes.

Note: ConvoKit's transformation to conversational-style data was not considered useful for the international pilot, which focuses on pre-prepared informative materials rather than interactions. The analysis tools also focus on aspects of interactive conversation, such as how time is shared between participants, rather than being applicable to the analysis of static documents. For both of these reasons, technical partners have not proceeded with ConvoKit for the international pilot.

1) Human agency and oversight

ConvoKit is a Python toolkit for interactive analyses instead of a self-sufficient decision system. Its architecture is focused on user-intuitive artefacts for human purpose and exploration: a “user-friendly interface for the exploration and interaction of conversational data” that “reduces the technical hurdles” essentially for adoption.¹⁶

ConvoKit maintains its foundational constructs for research as (Corpora and Transformations). Conversational data analyses are made explicit and composable, with researchers at the centre of pre-processing, feature extraction and modelling, e.g. TextParser, FightingWords and Forecaster. Each of the documentation of the constructs promotes explicit data structures (e.g.,

¹⁵ Görg, C. et al.: Reflections on the evolution of the Jigsaw visual analytics system. In Information Visualization (2014), volume 13, Issue 4, p. 342.

¹⁶ Chang, J. et al.: ConvoKit: A Toolkit for the Analysis of Conversations. In Proceedings of the 21th Annual Meeting of the Special Interest Group on Discourse and Dialogue (2020), p. 57.

Conversations, Utterances, Speakers with primary data field variables, timestamp and reply_to) where the user interacts directly.¹⁷

ConvoKit, as a researcher-controlled tool, quite naturally supports oversight by a human in the loop; the researcher makes decisions with the corpora they select, the transformers they configure, and the outputs they interpret. A pragmatic safeguard, for instance, would be for researchers to keep review checklists for reviewing each pipeline (e.g., data selection, data preprocessing, model fitting), which is aligned with HLEG's recommendation for human oversight. There is no automation that would simply eliminate human agency and decision-making.

2) Technical robustness and safety

Active maintenance and bug-fixing are ongoing processes in the usage of ConvoKit.¹⁸ ConvoKit also expands infrastructure for sustainable data storage, with a MongoDB back-end so that "all data is automatically saved to persistent storage over the long run."¹⁹ Methodologically, the framework enforces explicit, immutable deployable metadata fields and standardised representations that reduce silent state changes and allow for reproducible analysis pipelines (note the emphasis on explicit primary fields and metadata).²⁰

ConvoKit, as a research library, does not directly address adversarial safety or security in deployment settings. Nevertheless, the design choices (robust object model, explicit metadata on methods, careful maintenance, clear version history) facilitate reproducibility and resilience. Therefore, we would recommend that (i) when possible, maintain unit tests and dataset checksums to preserve integrity; (ii) document known failure modes with each transformer (for example, parsing noise from body text); and (iii) continue to release notes that describe breaking changes and mitigation instructions.

3) Privacy and data governance

ConvoKit includes various datasets, including Wikipedia talk pages, "the complete dump of Reddit," and another dataset that the tutorial mentions called Switchboard (it is a collection of anonymized five-minute telephone conversations).^{21,22} The object model structuring for ConvoKit

¹⁷ ConvoKit Developers: ConvoKit: Cornell Conversational Analysis Toolkit, published July 2020, available on: <https://convokit.cornell.edu/> (accessed October 15, 2025).

¹⁸ CornellNLP: ConvoKit, GitHub, published April 20, 2019, available on: <https://github.com/CornellNLP/ConvoKit> (accessed October 14, 2025).

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ See ConvoKit Developers: ConvoKit.

²¹ See Chang, J. et al., p. 60.

²² See ConvoKit Developers: ConvoKit.

keeps primary fields explicit (text, timestamps, reply relationships, speaker identifiers) and tracks metadata separately from salient attributes, allowing for traceability and governance within a project.²³ The new databases backend (MongoDB) facilitates durable and auditable storage.²⁴

Some demo corpora (for example, Reddit, Wikipedia talk pages) are large-scale user-generated corpora. While these are widely used in research, they have the potential to include personally identifiable information or sensitive information. ConvoKit's documentation notes an anonymised corpus (Switchboard), and can facilitate standardised ingestion, but does not provide de-identification on custom data.

While the interface and functions of ConvoKit can facilitate sound data governance if the user follows the licensing and privacy conventions of each corpus, for a higher compliance standard it would be suggested to: (i) provide prominent licensing and privacy notes at dataset download points; (ii) provide utility transformers for pseudonymization (e.g., redacting emails/URLs/IPs) prior to analysis; and (iii) offer project templates that both provide for data inventories and data retention policies. These anonymized datasets and particularly data structures do provide a decent starting point.

4) *Transparency*

ConvoKit is an open-source project that "welcomes contributions" and provides public documentation and tutorials.²⁵ The system is intentionally simple: "two key concepts: Corpora and Transformations" that make the analytic pipeline understandable and auditable.²⁶ The public documentation also refers to a "unified framework" that promotes reproducible manipulation of conversational data. By "lowering the technical barriers" to broader use, ConvoKit represents a type of transparency too.²⁷

The explicit object model used by ConvoKit (Conversation–Utterance–Speaker) and its transformer design lend transparency to the object model for conversation analytics. Compliance improvements could include (i) provenance logging transformers (for capturing versions, parameters, and dataset hashes) and (ii) standard model cards for baked-in models that summarize training data and known limitations.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ See CornellNLP: ConvoKit.

²⁵ See Chang, J. et al., p. 60.

²⁶ See ConvoKit Developers: ConvoKit.

²⁷ See Chang, J. et al., p. 57–58.

5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

ConvoKit features archives of datasets from sources that span online forums, institutional transcripts, and fiction, providing both cross-domain comparisons and facilities for experimental controls.²⁸ A number of analyses are off-the-shelf, such as politeness strategies, and constructs of linguistic coordination are common analyses to study differences in group behavior.²⁹ At the same time, however, there are a number of large, community-specific corpora (e.g., "900K subreddits") that indicate strong opportunities for either sampling bias due to unequal coverage or affordances of stratifying or weighing your data for research.³⁰

ConvoKit itself is a neutral analytical substrate and fairness depends entirely on the choice of dataset and the sampling and labelling decisions as users/researchers engage. At the same time, the flexibility within the framework is a virtue as it is very simple to run bias diagnostics (e.g., group comparisons using FightingWords or coordination differentials), as well as to document sampling decisions within the metadata. It is also advisable for ideas related to Fairness & Representativeness to be added to the docs (e.g., things for users to look at regarding group coverage, language varieties, and topic skew). It might also be advantageous to include examples for re-weighting or stratified sampling.

6) Societal and environmental well-being

The ConvoKit's mission is scholarly investigation into "conversations, and the social interactions embedded within," across settings "from dyadic face-to-face... to large-scale threaded discussions on social media". The documentation that accompanies ConvoKit states that the project "makes... cutting-edge techniques accessible" to users of differing skill levels, thereby removing some barriers to research capacity.³¹ The NYU DSR tutorial shows how ConvoKit could be used to study polarisation in a transparent manner.³²

ConvoKit reduces entry barriers for social-good research (e.g., civil discourse, institutional transparency), but there are some risks; powerful analytics applied to user-generated text could be repurposed for intrusive surveillance or manipulation if used for nefarious purposes. To

²⁸ See Chang, J. et al., p. 60.

²⁹ Kyrchechnko, Y.: Natural Language Processing of Conversations in Python with ConvoKit, Medium, published November 29, 2022, available on: <https://medium.com/nyu-ds-review/how-to-do-natural-language-processing-of-conversations-in-python-with-convokit-b95b700b8256> (accessed October 15, 2025).

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Fadelli, I.: ConvoKit: An open-source toolkit to aid the analysis of conversations, TechExplore, published June 1, 2020, available on: <https://techxplore.com/news/2020-06-convokit-open-source-toolkit-aid-analysis.html> (accessed October 15, 2025).

³² See Kyrchechnko, Y.

improve HLEG compliance, project documentation could include an Ethical Use note. On environmental aspects, ConvoKit's classical NLP architecture generally has low compute cost, but newer LLM-enabled transformer family of architectures (e.g., forecasting) may have greater compute cost and should be provided with compute/CO₂ cost flags and configurable limits of resource use.³³

7) Accountability

ConvoKit is an open-source project, which means it has released versions and issues available for the public to scrutinize and cite. Because these release artifacts are versioned, they also provide artifacts for external accountability. For example, the release notes³⁴ describe the specific changes and bug fixes (i.e., fixing installation issues, addressing corpus download issues) that can serve the purpose of traceability. At the data level, the primary fields (id, timestamp, reply_to) and consistent structure of the corpus serve the purpose of providing an internal audit trail for projects.³⁵

ConvoKit is not an autonomous service of AI; it is a code researchers run in their own environments. Hence, accountability is two-fold: the project is accountable for the quality of the software and documentation (shown by active releases and clear architecture), while the user organisation is accountable for data governance and use. To enhance accountability, ConvoKit might consider adding (i) security advisories when dependencies pose risk; (ii) a responsible disclosure channel; and (iii) dataset datasheets/model cards for hosted corpora and built-in transformers.

8) Overall assessment

ConvoKit, as an open-source toolkit with a unified framework and an emphasis on lowering technical barriers, maps well to the requirements of HLEG's Trustworthy AI guidelines for research infrastructures.

³³ See CornellNLP: ConvoKit.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ See ConvoKit Developers: ConvoKit.

Annex 16

AI4Deliberation Architecture

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Option 2 (centralized / data lake)

